

**IT Governance:
Current State of and Future Perspectives on
the Concept of Agility in IT Governance**

Sulejman Vejseli

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

In collaboration with Reutlingen University

April 2020

Abstract

Digital transformation has changed corporate reality and, with that, corporates' IT environments and IT governance (ITG). As such, the perspective of ITG has shifted from the design of a relatively stable, closed and controllable system of a self-sufficient enterprise to a relatively fluid, open, agile and transformational system of networked co-adaptive entities. Related to the paradigm shift in ITG, this thesis aims to conceptualize a framework to integrate the concept of agility into the traditional ITG framework and to test the effects of such an extended ITG framework on corporate performance.

To do so, the thesis uses literature research and a mixed method design by blending both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Given the poorly understood situation of the agile mechanisms within the ITG framework, the building process of this thesis' research model requires an adaptive and flexible approach which involves four different research phases. The initial a priori research model based on a comprehensive review of the extant literature is critically examined and refined at the end of each research phase, which later forms the basis of a subsequent research phase. As a result, the final research model provides guidance on how the conceptualized framework leads to better business/IT alignment as well as how business/IT alignment can mediate the effectiveness of such an extended ITG framework on corporate performance.

The first research phase explores the current state of literature with a focus on the ITG-corporate performance association. This analysis identifies five perspectives with respect to the relationship between ITG and corporate performance. The main variables lead to the perspectives of business/IT alignment, IT leadership, IT capability and process performance, resource relatedness and culture. Furthermore, the analysis presents core aspects explored within the identified perspectives that could act as potential mediators or moderators in the relationship between ITG and corporate performance.

The second research phase investigates the agile aspect of an effective ITG framework in the dynamic contemporary world through a qualitative study. Gleaned from 46 semi-structured interviews across various industries with governance experts, the study identifies 25 agile ITG mechanisms and 22 traditional ITG mechanisms that corporations use to master digital transformation projects. Moreover, the research offers two key patterns indicating to

a call for ambidextrous ITG, with corporations alternating between stability and agility in their ITG mechanisms.

In research phase three, a scale development process is conducted in order to develop the agile items explored in research phase two. Through 56 qualitative interviews with professionals the evaluation uncovers 46 agile governance mechanisms. Moreover, these dimensions are rated by 29 experts to identify the most effective ones. This leads to the identification of six structure elements, eight processes, and eight relational mechanisms.

Finally, in research phase four a quantitative research approach through a survey of 400 respondents is established to test and predict the formulated relationships by using the partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) method. The results provide evidence for a strong causal relationship among an expanded ITG concept, business/IT alignment, and corporate performance. These findings reveal that the agile ITG mechanisms within an effective ITG framework seem critical in today's digital age.

This research is unique in exploring the combination of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms. It contributes to the theoretical base by integrating and extending the literature on ITG, business/IT alignment, ambidexterity and agility, all of which have long been recognized as critical for achieving organizational goals. In summary, this work presents an original analysis of an effective ITG framework for digital transformation by including the agile aspect within the ITG construct. It highlights that is not enough to apply only traditional mechanisms to achieve effective business/IT alignment in today's digital age; agile ITG mechanisms are also needed. Therefore, a novel ITG framework following an ambidextrous approach is provided consisting of traditional ITG mechanisms as well as newly developed agile ITG practices. This thesis also demonstrates that agile ITG mechanisms can be measured independently of traditional ITG mechanisms within one causal model. This is an important theoretical outcome that allows the current state of ITG to be assessed in two distinct dimensions, offering various pathways for further research on the different antecedents and effects of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms. Furthermore, this thesis makes practical contributions by highlighting the need to develop a basic governance framework powered by traditional ITG mechanisms and simultaneously increase agility in ITG mechanisms. The results imply that corporations might be even more successful if they include both traditional and agile mechanisms in their ITG framework. In this way, the uncovered agile ITG practices may provide a template for CIOs to derive their own mechanisms in following an ambidextrous approach that is suitable for their corporation.

Declaration

The research presented in this thesis was carried out by the undersigned. No part of the research has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification at this or any other university.

Solothurn, April 28, 2020

Acknowledgments

For the past three years, I have been delighted to write these paragraphs and I thank everyone who contributed to this thesis by advising me, referring me to experts, questioning my ideas, reviewing my work, and above all providing the mental support I needed to arrive at this point.

First and foremost, my greatest thanks belong to Almighty God, who gave me the spiritual power, opportunity, determination and strength to carry out my research. His uninterrupted grace and mercy accompanied me throughout my research.

Now, I would like to express my deep and sincere gratitude to my advisor of this thesis, Professor Dr. Alexander Rossmann, who has shown the attitude and substance of a true mentor. I have come to appreciate him greatly for his guidance as well as his trust in my abilities, which gave me great motivation in approaching this work. He continually and influentially conveyed a spirit of perseverance regarding research and extreme compassion in regard to coaching. Without his supervision and constant support on all levels, this thesis would not have been possible.

Further, I would like to thank the academic director of this thesis, Professor Thomas Connolly, who gave me much freedom in approaching this work and provided help whenever requested while offering me the flexibility I needed to accomplish this thesis. His valuable input, time and direction throughout this thesis project significantly contributed to my completing the thesis.

To my colleagues at Herman Hollerith Zentrum (HHZ), Gerald Stei, Stephanie Göring and Konstantin Garidis, who have provided advice and support throughout my time at Reutlingen University, I would like to extend my thanks for the time and effort.

I would like to acknowledge the support and love of my father, Nedzat, my mother, Nazime, and my two brothers, Prparim and Ramazan, whose kind words and eager encouragement kept me going.

I would not have made it to the finish line without the great support of my family. I wish to explicitly mention my wife, Selviye, my son, Rayan, and my daughter, Amelia, for always being there for me and giving me the mental power to keep going. You have been endlessly patient with me during what must at times have felt like a never-ending story.

Table of Contents

Abstract.....	i
Declaration.....	iii
Acknowledgments	iv
List of Figures.....	x
List of Tables.....	xii
List of Abbreviations	xiv
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation.....	1
1.2 Research gap	4
1.3 Research questions.....	6
1.4 List of publications	7
1.5 Structure of the thesis	8
2 Related Research.....	10
2.1 ITG background.....	10
2.1.1 ITG definitions	10
2.1.2 Traditional ITG framework	11
2.2 ITG and corporate performance – a literature review.....	17
2.2.1 Introduction	17
2.2.2 ITG and corporate performance	18
2.2.3 Method.....	19
2.2.4 Synthesis.....	21
2.2.5 Summary.....	28
2.3 Mediation of business/IT alignment	30
2.3.1 Background.....	30
2.3.2 ITG enabling of business/IT alignment.....	32
2.3.3 Building block one – Business/IT alignment as mediator.....	35
2.4 The agile aspect within ITG.....	37
2.4.1 Agility definitions.....	37
2.4.2 Towards agile ITG mechanisms	39

2.4.3	The notion of an ambidextrous ITG	41
3	Research Methodology.....	44
3.1	Methodology rationale and research design	44
3.1.1	Mixed-methods approach	44
3.1.2	An exploratory sequential research design.....	45
3.2	Research phase 2 – Qualitative research design	48
3.2.1	Overview	48
3.2.2	Qualitative data collection.....	48
3.2.3	Qualitative data analysis.....	53
3.2.4	Qualitative results	56
3.3	Research phase 3 – Development of the research model.....	57
3.3.1	Overview	57
3.3.2	Conceptualization and hypotheses development.....	57
3.3.3	Specifying the measurement models	58
3.3.4	Scale development and analysis – Delphi method	58
3.4	Research phase 4 – Quantitative research design	61
3.4.1	Overview	61
3.4.2	Quantitative data collection.....	61
3.4.3	Quantitative data analysis.....	64
3.5	Ethical considerations	66
4	Qualitative Research	68
4.1	Introduction.....	68
4.2	Qualitative data collection	69
4.2.1	Definition of the target population	69
4.2.2	Conducting a pilot study.....	70
4.2.3	Identification of the sample	70
4.2.4	Development of an interview guideline and pre-test.....	72
4.2.5	Preparing and conducting the interviews	72
4.2.6	Recording and transcribing the interviews	73

4.3	Qualitative data analysis	74
4.3.1	Preparation.....	74
4.3.2	Case-by-case evaluation and initial coding	74
4.3.3	Development of a system of categories and a coding scheme	74
4.3.4	Testing and extending the coding scheme.....	75
4.3.5	Coding the data and checking consistency	77
4.4	Qualitative results	79
4.4.1	Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms	80
4.4.2	Traditional ITG mechanisms	82
4.4.3	Agile ITG mechanisms.....	90
4.5	Transferability check	99
4.5.1	Background information.....	99
4.5.2	Qualitative results of the cross-industry study	100
4.5.3	Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms	100
4.6	ITG Patterns	104
4.6.1	Key patterns.....	104
4.6.2	Building block two – Ambidextrous ITG.....	106
4.7	Summary of the key findings.....	108
4.7.1	ITG structures	109
4.7.2	ITG processes	110
4.7.3	ITG relational mechanisms.....	111
4.7.4	Transferability check	112
4.7.5	ITG patterns.....	112
4.8	Preliminary discussions	113
5	Development of the Research Model.....	115
5.1	Conceptualizing	115
5.1.1	Specification of the structural model.....	115
5.1.2	Hypotheses formulation.....	117
5.1.3	Specification of the measurement model	118

5.2	Scale development of agile ITG mechanisms.....	130
5.2.1	Evaluation part.....	130
5.2.2	Rating part	132
5.2.3	Data analysis.....	133
5.2.4	Specification of the measurement model of agile ITG mechanisms	137
5.3	Final research model in detail	141
6	Quantitative Research	142
6.1	Introduction.....	142
6.2	Quantitative data collection	143
6.2.1	Development of the online questionnaire.....	143
6.2.2	Pre-testing and optimization.....	144
6.2.3	Identification of the sample	144
6.2.4	Survey launch and data collection	144
6.3	Quantitative data analysis	146
6.4	Quantitative results	148
6.4.1	Sample demographics and descriptive statistics.....	148
6.4.2	Evaluation of the measurement models.....	151
6.4.3	Evaluation of the hierarchical component models (HCMs)	156
6.4.4	Evaluation of the structural model.....	157
6.4.5	Evaluation of mediating effect	158
6.4.6	Out-of-sample prediction.....	159
6.5	Summary.....	163
7	Discussion	165
7.1	Introduction.....	165
7.2	Research phase 1 – Related research	165
7.2.1	Key findings	166
7.2.2	Discussion – Perspectives.....	166
7.3	Research phase 2 – Qualitative research.....	167
7.3.1	Key findings	168

7.3.2	Discussion – Towards ambidextrous ITG	168
7.4	Research phase 3 – Scale development of the agile items.....	170
7.4.1	Key findings	171
7.4.2	Discussion – Agile ITG mechanisms	171
7.5	Research phase 4 – Quantitative research.....	172
7.5.1	Results of the PLS-SEM evaluation	172
7.5.2	Discussion – Effective ITG framework for digital transformation	173
8	Conclusions	177
8.1	Revisiting aim, objectives and research questions.....	177
8.2	Originality	178
8.3	Theoretical contribution.....	179
8.4	Practical contribution	181
8.5	Limitations	183
8.6	Future research.....	184
	References	186
	Appendices	203
	Appendix A: Interview guideline of the pilot study	203
	Appendix B: Letter of solicitation	208
	Appendix C: Interview guideline of the main qualitative study	209
	Appendix D: Interview guideline for refining the agile ITG items	216
	Appendix E: Questionnaire – Quantitative screening	222
	Appendix F: Questionnaire of the quantitative study.....	227
	Appendix G: Ethical approval.....	234
	Appendix H: Ethical evaluation.....	235
	Appendix I: Interview transcript of bank 1	236
	Appendix J: Interview transcript of Bank 7.....	243
	Appendix K: Interview transcript of Bank 13.....	255
	Appendix L: Interview transcript of Bank 15.....	266
	Appendix M: Interview transcript of Bank 33.....	275

List of Figures

Figure 2.1: Structures, processes and relational mechanisms adapted from	12
Figure 2.2: Literature review search strategy	20
Figure 2.3: Basic research model	29
Figure 2.4: Initial research model.....	37
Figure 3.1: Exploratory sequential design: Instrument development model.....	45
Figure 3.2: Research design process.....	47
Figure 3.3: Qualitative research strategy	48
Figure 3.4: Research model development strategy.....	57
Figure 3.5: Quantitative research strategy	61
Figure 4.1: Initial coding scheme	75
Figure 4.2: Coding process for identifying ITG mechanisms	76
Figure 4.3: Extended coding scheme.....	77
Figure 4.4: Final coding scheme	78
Figure 4.5: Traditional and agile structures, processes and relational mechanisms used .	104
Figure 4.6:Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms used.....	105
Figure 4.7: Ambidexterity of ITG	108
Figure 5.1: Final research model (extended by the building blocks)	116
Figure 5.2: Measurement model and HCM of traditional ITG mechanisms.....	120
Figure 5.3: Measurement model and HCM of business/IT alignment	123
Figure 5.4: Measurement model and HCM of corporate performance	127
Figure 5.5: Measurement model and HCM of agile ITG mechanisms	138
Figure 5.6: Final research model in detail.....	141
Figure 6.1: Response rates in detail.....	146
Figure 6.2: Redundancy analysis of the agile ITG items	152
Figure 6.3: Structural model evaluation	157

Figure 6.4: Direct and indirect paths in the structural model	158
Figure 6.5: Residual plots for the business/IT alignment manifest variables.....	160
Figure 6.6: Residual plots for corporate performance manifest variables.....	161
Figure 7.1: Summary of key findings for research question 1	166
Figure 7.2: Summary of key findings for research question 2	168
Figure 7.3: Summary of key findings of the scale development process	171
Figure 7.4: Summary of the PLS-SEM evaluation.....	173

List of Tables

Table 1.1: Outcomes of research papers in relation to the RQs and chapters	8
Table 2.1: ITG definitions	10
Table 2.2: ITG structures, processes and relational mechanisms.....	15
Table 2.3: Results search databases.....	21
Table 2.4: Perspectives and key concepts	22
Table 3.1: Overview of research methods used.....	46
Table 3.2: Item development process	59
Table 4.1: Overview of the sample selected.....	71
Table 4.2: Interview schedule.....	73
Table 4.3: Bank characteristics and control variables	79
Table 4.4: Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms	81
Table 4.5: Background information of the corporations and interviewees	99
Table 4.6: Corporate characteristics and control variables.....	100
Table 4.7: Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms in the cross-industry study.....	101
Table 5.1: Overview of the HCMs	118
Table 5.2: Construct definitions for the traditional ITG framework.....	121
Table 5.3: Item definitions for traditional ITG mechanisms.....	121
Table 5.4: Construct definitions of business/IT alignment	124
Table 5.5: Item definitions of business/IT alignment.....	125
Table 5.6: Construct definitions of corporate performance.....	128
Table 5.7: Item definitions of corporate performance.....	128
Table 5.8: Overview of the respondents.....	132
Table 5.9: Agile ITG mechanisms and their perceived effectiveness	134
Table 5.10: Construct definitions for the agile ITG framework.....	139
Table 5.11: Item definitions of the agile ITG mechanisms	139

Table 6.1: Overview evaluation criteria and thresholds in PLS-SEM	146
Table 6.2: Sample demographics	148
Table 6.3: Descriptive statistics for ITG mechanisms.....	149
Table 6.4: Descriptive statistics for business/IT alignment.....	150
Table 6.5: Descriptive statistics for corporate performance.....	150
Table 6.6: Variance inflation factors of formative items	153
Table 6.7: Evaluation of the significance and relevance of the items	154
Table 6.8: Evaluation of collinearity and significance of HCM relations.....	156
Table 6.9: Direct and indirect effects of the paths.....	159
Table 6.10: PLS-SEM Q^2_{predict} values of the endogenous construct items	159
Table 6.11: PLS Predict business/IT alignment and corporate performance – RMSE	162
Table 6.12: PLS Predict business/IT alignment and corporate performance – MAE	162
Table 7.1: Overview of hypotheses results.....	174

List of Abbreviations

AM	Application Management
AMCIS	Americas Conference on Information Systems
BIS	International Conference on Business Information Systems
CB-SEM	Covariance-based structural equation modelling
CDO	Chief Digital Officer
CEO	Chief Executive Officers
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
CIO	Chief Information Officers
CMO	Chief Marketing Officer
Conf-IRM	International Conference on Information Resources Management
COO	Chief Operating Officers
COSO	Committee of Sponsoring Organizations (internal control framework)
e.g.	exempli gratia (for example)
ECIS	European Conference on Information Systems
ERM	Enterprise Risk Management framework
et al.	et al. (and others)
FINMA	Swiss Financial Market Supervisory Authority
FinTech	Financial technology start-up
HCM	Hierarchical component model
HICSS	Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences
HOC	Higher-order component
i.e.	id est (that is)
ICIS	International Conference on Information Systems
ICS	Internal control system
IS	Information systems
IT	Information technology
ITG	Information technology governance
ITGI	The IT Governance Institute
ITIL	IT Infrastructure Library
KPI	Key performance indicators
LM	Linear regression model
LOC	Lower-order component
MAE	Mean absolute error

MV	Manifest variables
NACE	Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community
NS	non-significant
PACIS	Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems
PAI	Product and Application Innovation
PLS-SEM	Partial least squares structural equation modelling
PM	Product Management
qual	qualitative
QUAN	quantitative
RBV	Resource-based view
RMSE	Root mean squared error
ROA	Return on assets
ROE	Return on equity
ROI	Return on investment
RP	Research paper
RQ	Research question
SD	Standard deviation
SEM	Structural equation modelling
SISP	information systems planning
SLA	Service-level agreement
STP	Straight-through processing
TMT	Top management team
VIF	Variance inflation factor

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Nowadays, information technology (IT) plays an essential role in organizational innovation adoption (Acemoglu, 2012). Very few products, services or process innovations can succeed without being supported, if not enabled, by IT (Davenport, 1993; Nambisan, 2013). Therefore, in the last decade, the deployment of IT has become crucial in enabling enterprises to continue to use digital innovations developed by start-ups and large players. Since new digital technologies surrounded by innovative thinking are driving new business models, flexible organizational structures, optimized processes and novel ways of communication that open a successful path into the future, it is essential for corporations to prepare for the future by adapting to the digital age.

To frame a specific digital strategy, corporations need to develop a management approach due to the necessary assessment and alignment of initiatives and projects. However, a corporate journey is not just about new channels and innovative IT strategies; corporations also struggle with changing business models and achieving a better alignment between IT and business. Consequently, corporations face the challenge of defining and implementing a digital strategy and mastering the digital transformation. What organisations need is a systematic approach to continuously developing and improving their business models with digital assets. Reorganization efforts through the deployment of new digital technologies reflect significant changes in the organizational architecture. As a result, business models must be changed at the core or even completely revised.

Mastering such fundamental changes in a corporate organization requires appropriate leadership and effective IT governance (ITG). However, the traditional concept of ITG as controlling the formulation and implementation of IT strategy and thus ensuring the fusion of business and IT is not fully equipped to deal with the current changes occurring in the digital age (Borgman *et al.*, 2016). Traditional governance methods and tools are considered too cumbersome and inflexible (Ambler and Lines, 2012). Recent rapid developments in technology require new agile or adaptive ways of working (Clark *et al.*, 2016; Gill *et al.*, 2018). The new emerging digital trends are significantly changing the IT landscape and therefore challenging the boundaries of traditional ITG. Consequently, the governance concept should shift from its traditional focus on control and compliance to an outcome-

oriented and agile approach that can respond to changing dynamics (Horlach *et al.*, 2016; Sommer *et al.*, 2014). As a result, corporations are heavily relying on agile ITG to secure better corporate performance.

In the literature, several definitions for ITG have been proposed. The IT Governance Institute (ITGI) and Van Grembergen define ITG as the responsibility of the board of directors and executive management to control the formulation and implementation of IT strategy through a framework consisting of leadership, organizational structures and processes and reflecting the importance of achieving a strategic alignment of IT and business (IT Governance Institute, 2003; van Grembergen, 2013). Weill and Ross's definition, on the other hand, equates ITG with the IT-related decision-making framework. Although ITG definitions differ in some aspects, they focus on the same issues of linking business and IT (Weill and Ross, 2004). Therefore, in existing studies, business/IT alignment has consistently been highlighted as one of the top three key issues for IT executives for almost three decades (Luftman and Ben-Zvi, 2010). The purpose of alignment is to merge business and IT objectives and forge a partnership for developing and achieving organizational strategies and goals. In the current dynamic business environment, an effective and efficient IT presence is vital to enhance business strategy and support the evolution of the corporate architecture if a corporation is to deliver consistent and scalable business value. Effectively aligning business and IT improves business performance, enhances efficiency and allows organizations to compete better inside their industry (Chen, 2010). This makes business/IT alignment the most important critical success factor discussed in the ITG literature (Alreemy *et al.*, 2016). As long-term success requires a strong connection between business and IT in corporations to maximize benefits and reduce the uncertainties of IT projects, a focus on ITG has become imperative for business organizations to meet the challenges presented by the business environment (Alreemy *et al.*, 2016). The importance of implementing an effective ITG framework in an organization is also illustrated by Weill and Ross's research, which showed that up to 40% higher returns can be generated by using effective ITG processes (Weill and Ross, 2004). However, although ITG frameworks are being increasingly adopted in today's world, IT projects continue to fail and therefore do not generate higher corporate performance (Brown, 2015). Because of sweeping changes in a fast-moving economy, leading to new requirements and expectations being vested in IT, the task of aligning business and IT remains a key challenge. In other words, the problems centre not necessarily around IT capabilities in general but rather around their exploitation and availability in distinct and changing business contexts (Schlosser, 2012). Hence, the agile

aspect of ITG frameworks has become a crucial factor in better aligning IT and business and therefore accommodating a changing corporate business model. However, to date, the agile aspect within ITG has not been analysed by a broad scientific community. The term “agility” is somewhat hyped in industry and a buzzword in literature (Chatwani, 2019). Furthermore, there is no formal definition of “agility” and is often used as a synonym for a corporation that is flexible, fast, lean, customer oriented, innovative and adaptable (Chatwani, 2019). Therefore, large uncertainty exists of how to create an agile ITG.

Agility is a complex multidimensional concept and has been analysed across strategic management, operations management disciplines (both referred to business agility), and IT systems discipline referred to IT agility (Seethamraju, 2006). While strategic agility deals with the agility of the corporation to respond flexible, nimble and innovative to the dynamic competitive landscape (Lewis *et al.*, 2014), operational agility is defined as the ability of the corporation to redesign existing processes rapidly and to create new processes in a timely fashion in order to be able to take advantage of dynamic market conditions (Ramasesh *et al.*, 2001; Sambamurthy *et al.*, 2003). Nevertheless, to support both dimensions of business agility an increased demand for IT departments to be agile in their internal delivery is required (Yousif *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, IT agility is considered to be a main driver of the IT function’s ability to support digitization (Haffke *et al.*, 2017b). In order for the IT organization to meet the new demands for increased agility, there is a need to adapt existing ITG (Tiwana and Kim, 2015). As noted by Gregory *et al.* (2015) this involves a turn towards an ambidextrous approach within ITG, i.e. an increased ability of supporting both exploration and exploitation (Raisch and Birkinshaw, 2008; March, 1991). Accordingly, the general concept of agility within ITG needs to ensure the IT function “*to respond operationally and strategically to changes in the external environment. The response has to be quick and effective for the corporation to be considered agile*” (Fink and Neumann, 2007, p. 444). Consequently, new ITG and alignment mechanisms need to be developed and established to align a corporations’ strategic as well as operational activities with the digital and the traditional IT in a faster and more agile manner (Horlach *et al.*, 2016). To do so, Luna *et al.* (2010) suggest enhancing existing traditional ITG mechanisms using the principles of the agile manifesto of software engineering introduced by Beck *et al.* (2001). This list is based on the foundation of agile practices and contains the following values: 1) Collaboration, 2) Communication, 3) Working software, 4) Flexibility, 5) Customer-centric, 6) Incremental, 7) Iterative, 8) Motivation, 9) Respect, 10) Trust, 11) Feedback, 12) Speed, 13) Technical excellence, 14) Simplicity, 15) Self-organizing, and 16) Learning (Madi *et al.*,

2011). The manifesto and its principles represent the philosophy behind agile mechanisms that ideally should be present in all practices (Fernandes and Almeida, 2010). With regard to the concept of Luna *et al.* (2010), implementing agile ITG mechanisms derived from agile practices can complement the agile principles within the traditional ITG framework and therefore resulting in a more agile ITG.

Given the strategic importance of digitalization, it is evident that resources for agile ITG need to be institutionalized. Agile ITG encompasses the management activities that determine the organizational structures, decision-making processes, information flows and communication efforts related to digitalization projects. Specific management actions include establishing cross-boundary committees to integrate all stakeholders, designing a steering system to break down actions ranging from the program level to the project and team level and vice versa, initiating and fostering communication, benchmarking programs and projects, and sharing information and success. Therefore, the agile aspect of ITG is important due to its significant impact on empowering innovation, enabling better business/IT alignment and enhancing corporate performance.

1.2 Research gap

Digitalization has fundamentally changed corporate reality so that the role of IT in business is now pervasive. While the dominant logic of the industrial age was linear and product-oriented, the digital age is non-linear and service-oriented (Collin *et al.*, 2014). This broad paradigm shift in the logic is also reflected in the changes in IT and consequently in a corporate ITG and enterprise architecture. The perspective has shifted from the relatively stable, closed and controllable system of a self-sufficient enterprise to the relatively fluid, open, agile and transformational system of co-adaptive networked entities (Collin *et al.*, 2015). Hence, agile approaches call for a revised governance approach. Consequently, agile ITG is becoming increasingly important for managers of enterprises in terms of enabling higher performance.

Existing studies have recognized efficiency and stability as core concepts in ITG design (Haffke *et al.*, 2016). This makes sense as the “old” world was characterized by a stable, placid environment in which neither the core technology nor the markets in which corporations were operating changed drastically over time. Organizations could afford to use “command-and-control” mechanisms to govern IT (Peterson, 2004b). In this context, many proposed methodologies, reference guides, sets of best practices (e.g., COBIT) and

frameworks such as the IT Infrastructure Library (ITIL) have emerged and developed in recent years. However, the adoption of such ITG frameworks, or so-called conventional or traditional frameworks, does not necessarily yield the desired return in the context of digital transformation (Luna *et al.*, 2010). In general, conventional frameworks are based on slow processes that require high investments for implementation in a corporation (Luna *et al.*, 2010). Furthermore, the ITG methods and tools in such frameworks are too inflexible (Awais and Gill, 2016). With the business imperatives and new enterprise logic of strategic flexibility and dynamic stability, the traditional ITG mechanisms no longer seem viable or prudent (Luna *et al.*, 2014; Horlach *et al.*, 2016).

By contrast, agile mechanisms have evolved in recent years, especially in the area of software development (Awais and Gill, 2016; Cheng *et al.*, 2009; Qumer, 2007). Independent of the business area, these agile mechanisms can “add value” to business organizations through a process in which the principles of communication and collaboration are essential (Fruhling *et al.*, 2008). Thus, adopting agile principles, values and best practices in the context of ITG can bring even more meaningful results to organizational management and improve business/IT alignment. The benefits can lead to an increase in the speed of decision making and can improve business processes and organizational competitiveness (Luna *et al.*, 2010). Thus, agile ITG has become highly relevant in keeping up with competitors in the dynamic contemporary world.

To date, the agile aspect within the ITG concept has not been analysed by a broad scientific community. Among the first researchers to integrate the agile aspect into ITG were Qumer (2007), Cheng *et al.* (2009), Dubinsky *et al.* (2010) and Luna *et al.* (2010; 2013). However, empirical evidence on what agile really means and how agile ITG can lead to better business/IT alignment and enhance corporate performance is lacking in the literature. Nonetheless, interest in the scientific analysis of this topic is growing. The current research offers only scant insights into proper governance frameworks for digital transformation at a holistic level. Specific governance frameworks are often related to single functional units, e.g., IT, marketing or management. This leads to the question of what organizational structures and processes are required to allow agility in digital transformation strategies at the corporate level. Tracing the implications might result in several conceptual typologies for linkages between business and IT in transformation initiatives. In summary, despite more than three decades of ITG research, little is known about the mutual relationship between effective ITG frameworks for digital transformation, business/IT alignment and corporate performance in the digital age.

1.3 Research questions

To address the research problems mentioned above, this doctoral thesis is concerned with management strategies for digital transformation in large and complex organizations, focusing on the issue of ITG agility in mastering digital transformation. Therefore, the central aim of this research is *to develop an effective agile ITG framework for digital transformation*. To do so, the core objectives of this thesis are (i) *to conceptualize a framework to integrate the concept of agility into the traditional ITG framework* and (ii) *to test the effects of such an extended ITG framework on corporate performance*. To achieve these two main objectives, the following research questions (RQs) are defined:

RQ1: *How is the current research structured with respect to the link between ITG and corporate performance? What concepts impact the ITG-corporate performance relationship?*

RQ2: *How is the concept of an effective ITG framework changing with respect to the demand for agility in corporations?*

RQ3: *How does the concept of agility affect the ITG-corporate performance relationship?*

RQ1 sets the scene and provides an overview of the relevant perspectives in the link between ITG and corporate performance to clarify the relations between organizational strategies, the governance concept and corporate outcome. In examining specific associations between single facets of ITG, mediating and moderating effects and different performance dimensions, RQ1 aims to clarify the relationship between ITG and corporate performance.

After conventional ITG and its links to performance are examined, the concept of ITG allowing agility for the digital age is discussed. Hence, RQ2 aims to investigate the agile aspects of an effective ITG framework in the dynamic contemporary world and to reveal agile ITG mechanisms that complement the traditional elements of ITG.

Finally, the third research question (RQ3) explores the benefits of such an extended framework. Based on a causal model, the relationship between an effective ITG framework for the digital world and corporate performance is formulated, empirically validated and predicted.

1.4 List of publications

This section outlines several research papers (RP) that were published between 2017 and 2019 in international scientific conference proceedings to demonstrate the contribution of this thesis to the body of knowledge. They were produced during the course of the researcher's PhD studies and are part of the thesis.

- RP 1: Vejseli, S. and Rossmann, A. (2017), "The Impact of IT Governance on Firm Performance A Literature Review", in *Proceedings of the 21st Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems (PACIS 2017)*, Langkawi, Malaysia, 2017.
- RP 2: Vejseli, S., Proba, D., Rossmann, A. and Jung, R. (2018). "The agile Strategies in IT Governance: Towards a framework of agile IT Governance in the banking industry", in *Proceedings of the 26th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2018)*, Portsmouth, UK, 2018.
- RP 3: Vejseli, S. and Rossmann, A. (2018). "Towards Agility in IT Governance Frameworks", in *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Business Information Systems (BIS 2018)*, Springer, Cham, (pp. 71-85).
- RP 4: Vejseli, S., Rossmann, A., Connolly (2019). "IT Governance and its Agile Dimensions", in *Proceedings of the 52nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2019)*, Maui, Hawaii, 2019.
- RP 5: Vejseli, S., Rossmann, A., Connolly (2020). "Agility matters! Agile Mechanisms in IT Governance and their Impact on Firm Performance", in *Proceedings of the 53rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2020)*, Maui, Hawaii, 2020.

Sulejman Vejseli is the main author of these five research papers. In these publications, the researcher developed the general research strategy and conceptual framework; made contact with the executives of the participating corporations in different countries; conducted the vast majority of the interviews; collected, structured and analysed the data; interpreted the outcomes; and wrote the body of these papers. Table 1.1 presents the outcomes of the included research papers in relation to the RQs and the chapters of this thesis.

Table 1.1: Outcomes of research papers in relation to the RQs and chapters

RQs	Research paper	Outcome	Chapters
RQ1	RP 1 <i>Literature review</i> (Vejseli and Rossmann, 2017)	The literature review identified five perspectives on the link between ITG and corporate performance.	Chapter 2
RQ2	RP 2, RP 3 <i>Qualitative analysis</i> (Vejseli <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Vejseli and Rossmann, 2018)	The studies identified 22 traditional and 25 agile mechanisms in terms of agile ITG. Moreover, agile mechanisms within the agile ITG concept and ten ITG patterns were revealed by the interview data. The analysis also highlights ambidextrous aspects of ITG.	Chapter 4
Pre-requisite for RQ3	RP 4 <i>Item development</i> (Vejseli <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	The item development process revealed 46 agile governance elements. These mechanisms were rated by 29 experts to identify the most effective ones. This led to the identification of six structural elements, seven processes and seven relational mechanisms.	Chapter 5
RQ3	RP 5 <i>Quantitative analysis</i> (Vejseli <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	The impact of a conceptual model containing traditional as well as agile ITG mechanisms on corporate performance was empirically tested by using partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). The results provide support for the integration of the agility concept into existing ITG frameworks leading to meaningful results for the ITG-corporate performance relationship.	Chapter 6

1.5 Structure of the thesis

This thesis consists of eight chapters:

Chapter 2 outlines the background for this research. It briefly presents concepts from previous studies, such as ITG definitions, ITG frameworks and the rationale for investigating the governance-performance link. Then, it conducts a literature review that explores the links between ITG and corporate performance. Therefore, this chapter addresses RQ1. After the first building block and the research hypotheses from the results are outlined, this chapter concludes with the presentation of the theoretical background of the agile concept and the idea to integrate it within today's ITG.

Chapter 3 describes the research process and methodological approach. It introduces the qualitative methods, the research model development process, and quantitative methods used

for this thesis. Additionally, the justification for selecting the research methods and data collection techniques is presented.

Chapter 4 contains an exploratory primary study through qualitative research. It outlines the sampling approach and develops the interview guideline. It also presents how the interviews were prepared, conducted and documented. Furthermore, this section applies qualitative content analysis to interpret the interviews and discusses the findings. Moreover, the transferability of the outcomes to other industries is checked through an additional qualitative study (secondary study) by replicating the primary study with other participants. The chapter concludes with the development of the second building block. In particular, the analysis of the qualitative examination leads to answering RQ2. The findings from this chapter are subsequently applied to developing the governance constructs in the causal model and to refine the hypotheses of the research model before it is quantitatively tested.

Chapter 5 deals with the development of the research model. Here, the outcomes of the previous chapters are used to conceptualize the final research model and to refine the research hypotheses. It further introduces a scale development process to establish and refine items for the governance constructs as examined in the qualitative investigation (see Chapter 4). After this approach is detailed, the structural models and their respective measurement models are operationalized and a set of hypotheses are introduced. This ultimately leads to a causal model that sets the base for the next chapter.

Chapter 6 represents an exploration of the present thesis through quantitative research. It begins with operationalizing the online survey and characterizing the samples. Then, an online survey with 400 usable results is used to estimate the impact of the effective ITG framework extended through the agile aspect on corporate performance (RQ3). The partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) approach is used to test the conceptual models (measurement models and structural models). Hence, the overall approach in this chapter leads to a validation of the developed research model through quantitative empirical data.

Chapter 7 summarizes the answers to the RQs by providing an overview of the key findings. Furthermore, this chapter discusses the results for each research phase.

Chapter 8 concludes with a description of original content of this thesis and expresses how this study contributes to research and practice in the field of ITG. Moreover, this section discusses the limitations of the study and proposes potential future research steps.

2 Related Research

This chapter presents the results of the related research that refers to the first research phase of this thesis. It intends to establish the foundation for the links between ITG and corporate performance and will therefore provide the first building block and its theoretical background for the development of the research model that will be implemented in Chapter 5. Furthermore, this chapter provides the theoretical background for the concept of agility within ITG. First, a brief introduction is provided and the ITG background is presented. This is followed by a short description of the method used for the literature search. The synthesis section introduces the key findings after which the first building block of the research model is offered. Lastly, the idea to integrate the concept of agility within today's ITG is outlined.

2.1 ITG background

2.1.1 ITG definitions

ITG as a research topic has been evolving rapidly in the last few years since for many corporations, it has become a crucial element to support, sustain and increase organizational growth for success in the modern business world (Posthumus *et al.*, 2010). Although many researchers have investigated ITG and several definitions have been proposed, practitioners and researchers continue to struggle with exact definitions of ITG, the question of who has responsibility for ITG and how ITG can be recognized, implemented and continuously managed (Jacobson, 2009). Consequently, debate persists surrounding the very definition of ITG (Webb *et al.*, 2006). Various definitions of ITG from different perspectives have been introduced and some of the most common definitions of ITG are presented in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: ITG definitions

ITG Definition	Reference
<i>ITG is the enterprise management system through which an organization's portfolio of IT systems is directed and controlled. ITG describes the distribution of IT decision-making rights and responsibilities among different stakeholders in the enterprise and defines the procedures and mechanisms for making and monitoring strategic IT decisions.</i>	(Peterson, 2004a)
<i>ITG represents the framework for decision rights and accountabilities to encourage desirable behaviour in the use of IT.</i>	(Weill and Ross, 2004)

<p><i>ITG is the organizational capacity exercised by the board, executive management and IT management to control the formulation and implementation of IT strategy and ensure the fusion of business and IT.</i></p>	<p>(van Grembergen and de Haes, 2005)</p>
<p><i>ITG is the responsibility of executives and the board of directors and consists of the leadership, organizational structures and processes that ensure that the organization's IT sustains and extends the organization's strategies and objectives.</i></p>	<p>(IT Governance Institute, 2007)</p>

A comparison of these definitions shows that they diverge in their characteristics. While some researchers focus on the roles performed by organizational executives, others emphasize a definition of ITG in terms of certain decisions and processes, irrespective of who is involved. Whereas the definitions by Peterson (2004a) and Weill and Ross (2004) focus on the decision-making process within the ITG framework, the definitions by van Grembergen and de Haes (2005) and the IT Governance Institute (2007) emphasize the structure of an ITG framework and highlight the importance of strategic alignment of IT with business. In the literature, the structure-versus-process debate is evident (Jacobson, 2009). Although these definitions differ in some aspects, they all tend to link business and IT. According to the presented definitions, ITG can be seen as a framework of structures, relational mechanisms and a set of processes that will lead corporations to use IT to support and enhance their business objectives. This thesis starts from the basic assumption that the ITG definition should include both structure and process aspects. Therefore, merging the definition of the IT Governance Institute with Weill and Ross's characterization should cover the most relevant dimensional concepts of current ITG research, leading to the following definition:

“ITG is the responsibility of executives and the board of directors and consists of the leadership, organizational structures and processes that ensure that the organization's IT sustains and extends the organization's strategies and objectives. It represents the framework for decision rights and accountabilities to encourage desirable behaviour in the use of IT.”

This thesis uses this definition as a proxy, representing most coherently the established definitions for ITG in current research. Therefore, this covers the most relevant dimensional concepts of current ITG research.

2.1.2 Traditional ITG framework

Implementing effective ITG within a corporation can ensure alignment between IT and business goals and is intended to improve IT performance in corporations (Ali and Green,

2012). By improving the alignment of business and IT and thus IT performance, corporations expect to obtain benefits from IT, such as reliable, fast and secure solutions; to acquire a related return on investment; and to improve efficiency and productivity (IT Governance Institute, 2003). Previous studies illustrate that effective ITG enables corporations to obtain a higher return on assets (Weill and Ross, 2004) and provides corporations with new business opportunities (Ali and Green, 2012). With the definition from the previous sub-section in mind, to implement ITG effectively, a corporation should employ well-designed, well-understood, and transparent ITG mechanisms (Ali and Green, 2012; de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009) to reach the ultimate goal of effective alignment between business and IT (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009). However, determining the right ITG mechanisms is complex, and managers must recognize that what works strategically for one corporation may not necessarily work for another (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2004). That is, effective ITG does not happen by accident; consequently, top-performing corporations should carefully design their ITG processes. Specifically, corporations can assess the effectiveness of their ITG by evaluating how well it enables IT to deliver on four objectives: cost-effectiveness, asset utilization, business growth, and business flexibility (Weill and Ross, 2005). Consequently, several studies have argued that effective ITG requires a framework based on a mixture of the three major dimensions, structures, processes and relational mechanisms, which is considered to be the traditional view in this thesis, as shown in Figure 2.1 (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2004; Peterson, 2004b; Weill and Ross, 2004):

Figure 2.1: Structures, processes and relational mechanisms adapted from de Haes and van Grembergen (2005)

Structures: In general, ITG structures represent formal integration structures that refer to defined IT executives, accounts and implemented committees and councils and consist of formal positions, roles, and responsibilities for IT-related decision making (Lunardi *et al.*,

2017; Peterson, 2004b). In particular, the framework of ITG structures should answer the following questions (Burtscher *et al.*, 2009):

- Who makes the decisions?
- What organizational units will be created?
- Who will take part in these organizational units?
- What responsibilities will they assume?

Examples of traditional structures are the institutionalization of IT steering committees, IT project steering committees and IT strategy committees and structures that enable CIOs (Chief Information Officers) and COOs (Chief Operating Officers) to report to CEOs (Chief Executive Officers) (van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004). In summary, ITG structural mechanisms include the creation of “meeting points” for business and IT managers that facilitate the formal relational integration of stakeholders in order to foster collaboration. This, in turn, can improve strategic planning, leading to a more effective IT landscape and finally to higher business value through IT (Schlosser, 2012).

Processes: Processes within an ITG framework refer to “*the formalization and institutionalization of strategic IT decision-making and IT monitoring procedures, to ensure that daily behaviours are consistent with policies and provide input back to decisions*” (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2015b, p. 11). The process aspect targets the following questions (Symons, 2005):

- How are IT investment decisions made?
- What are the decision-making processes for proposing, reviewing, approving, and prioritizing investments?

Conventional processes, for example, are portfolio management, IT budget control and reporting, project governance methodologies or information systems planning. In general, ITG processes can be used to assist corporate plans and to organize and control strategic IT decisions (Lunardi *et al.*, 2017). Metric and compliance processes furthermore aim to estimate and measure the value of IT-enabled business processes (Weill and Ross, 2004), including the monitoring of performance indicators, such as service-level agreements (SLAs), IT balanced scorecards, project tracking systems, and IT charge-back systems (Lunardi *et al.*, 2017).

Relational mechanisms: The aspects of communication and relational mechanisms raise the following questions (Symons, 2005):

- How will the results of ITG processes and decisions be monitored, measured, and communicated?
- What mechanisms will be used to communicate IT investment decisions to the board of directors, executive management, business management, IT management, employees, and shareholders?

Examples of relational mechanisms are a shared understanding of business/IT objectives, cross-functional business/IT training and collaboration among principal stakeholders. The objective of such relational mechanisms is to improve the understanding of business needs by IT managers and to be able to act proactively (Burtscher *et al.*, 2009; Peterson, 2004b). Central to such mechanisms is their relational integration character and the participative behaviour of different stakeholders to clarify differences and solve problems in order to find integrative solutions (Peterson, 2004b). This allows a corporation to discuss and identify broader solutions and unleashes the creativity of a collaborative exploration of solutions that exceed functional boundaries and define future possibilities (Peterson, 2004b).

Thus, deploying ITG in a corporation means using a mixture of various structures, processes and relational mechanisms. Therefore, in recent decades, several frameworks that support the implementation of ITG have been created. Some of the most familiar frameworks are COBIT and ITIL. However, no comprehensive framework covers all structures, processes and relational mechanisms for a comprehensive ITG approach. In addition, implementing too many layers of ITG mechanisms that are designed to fuse business and IT can significantly increase complexity and thus impose a counter-effect (Schlosser, 2012). The key challenge is not only to have the right structures, processes and relational mechanisms in place but also to ensure that they enable business/IT alignment (Schlosser, 2012). Depending on the corporate structure, a combination of different elements is required (van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004). Table 2.2 provides a detailed list of ITG structures, processes and relational mechanisms based on the studies of de Haes and van Grembergen (2009), who validated the elements through a set of multiple research methods and Almeida *et al.* (2013), who extended the list through an extensive literature review. Many recent studies, such as those of Ajayi and Hussin (2016), Bianchi and Sousa (2016), Dahlberg and Helin (2017) and Silva *et al.* (2018), use this list to define existing ITG mechanisms. According to Almeida *et al.* (2013) and Silva *et al.* (2018), the overarching list outlined in Table 2.2 represent all the relevant ITG mechanisms provided in the existing literature. However, in this thesis these elements refer to the traditional ITG mechanisms.

Table 2.2: ITG structures, processes and relational mechanisms based on Almeida et al. (2013) and de Haes and van Grembergen (2009)

No.	ITG mechanisms	Definition
Structures		
S1	IT strategy committee at level of board of directors	Committee at level of board of directors to ensure that IT is a regular agenda item and reporting issue for the board of directors
S2	IT expertise at level of board of directors	Members of the board of directors have expertise and experience regarding the value and risk of IT
S3	(IT) audit committee at level of board of directors	Independent committee at level of board of directors overseeing (IT) assurance activities
S4	CIO on executive committee	CIO is a full member of the executive committee
S5	CIO reporting to CEO and/or COO	CIO has a direct reporting line to the CEO and/or COO
S6	IT steering committee (IT investment evaluation/prioritization at executive/senior management level)	Steering committee at executive or senior management level responsible for determining business priorities in IT investments
S7	ITG function/officer	Function in the organization responsible for promoting, driving and managing ITG processes
S8	Security/compliance/risk officer	Function responsible for security, compliance and/or risk, which possibly impacts IT
S9	IT project steering committee	Steering committee composed of business and IT people focusing on prioritizing and managing IT projects
S10	IT security steering committee	Steering committee composed of business and IT personnel focusing on IT-related risks and security issues
S11	Architecture steering committee	Committee composed of business and IT personnel providing architecture guidelines and advice on their applications
S12	Integration of governance/alignment tasks in roles and responsibilities	Documented roles and responsibilities include governance/alignment tasks for business and IT personnel
S13	CIO on board	CIO is a full member of the board to ensure that IT will be a regular item on the board's agenda and that it will be addressed in a structured manner
S14	IT councils / IT leadership councils	IT councils, made up of CIOs and COOs, make enterprise-wide principles, architecture, infrastructure and investment decisions (Weill and Ross, 2005)
S15	IT organizational structure (centralized, federal, decentralized)	How the IT function is organized and where the IT decision-making authority is located in the corporation
S16	Business/IT relationship managers	Act as the intermediary between the business and IT, playing a critical daily two-way role by helping IT understand how business operates and giving the business units an entry point to IT

S17	IT investment committee or capital improvement	Committee responsible for evaluating and approving major capital expenditures (Weill and Ross, 2004)
S18	E-business advisory board	Should help the senior managers in optimizing and managing the e-business(Peterson, 2004b)
S19	E-business task force	Is a unit or formation established to work on a single defined task or activity. In that case is created a team to deal specifically with E-business(Almeida, 2013).
Processes		
P1	Strategic information systems planning	Formal process to define and update the IT strategy
P2	IT performance measurement (e.g., IT balanced scorecard)	IT performance measurement in domains of corporate contribution, user orientation, operational excellence and future orientation
P3	Portfolio management (incl. business cases, information economics, ROI, payback, VALIT)	Prioritization process for IT investments and projects in which business and IT are involved (incl. business cases)
P4	Charge-back arrangements – total cost of ownership (e.g., activity-based costing)	Methodology to charge IT costs back to business units to enable an understanding of the total cost of ownership
P5	Service-level agreements	Formal agreements between business and IT about IT development projects or IT operation
P6	ITG framework (e.g., COBIT, ITIL)	Process-based ITG and control framework
P7	ITG assurance and self-assessment	Regular self-assessments or independent assurance activities on the governance and control of IT
P8	Project governance/management methodologies	Processes and methodologies to govern and manage IT projects
P9	Project tracking	Processes to monitor IT projects
P10	IT budget control and reporting	Processes to control and report upon budgets of IT investments and projects
P11	Benefits management and reporting	Processes to monitor the planned business benefits during and after implementation of the IT investments/projects
P12	COSO/ERM	Framework for internal control
P13	Demand management	Forces all IT demands through a single point, where the demands can be consolidated, prioritized and fulfilled
P14	ITG maturity models	A self-diagnosing tool to evaluate ITG effectiveness and identify opportunities for improvement (van Grembergen <i>et al.</i> , 2004)
P15	Architectural exception process	Process to meet unique business needs and to gauge when existing standards are becoming obsolete(Weill and Ross, 2004).
Relational Mechanisms		
R1	Cross-functional business/IT job rotation	IT staff working in the business unit and business staff working in IT

R2	Business/IT collocation	Physically locating business and IT people near each other
R3	Cross-functional business/IT training	Training business staff about IT and/or training IT staff about business
R4	Knowledge management (in ITG)	Systems (e.g., intranet) to share and distribute knowledge about ITG framework, responsibilities, tasks, etc.
R5	Business/IT account management	Bridging the gap between business and IT by means of account managers who act as go-betweens
R6	Executive/senior management sets a good example	Senior business and IT management acting as “partners”
R7	Informal meetings between business and IT executive/senior management	Informal meetings with no agenda where business and IT senior managers talk about general activities, directions, etc. (e.g., during informal lunches)
R8	IT leadership	Ability of CIO or similar role to articulate a vision for IT role in the corporation and ensure that this vision is clearly understood by managers throughout the organization
R9	Corporate internal communication addressing IT on a regular basis	Internal corporate communication regularly addresses general IT issues
R10	ITG awareness campaigns	Campaigns to explain to business and IT staff the need for ITG
R11	Senior management announcements	A mechanism for communicating IT decisions and processes that prioritizes and commits to IT initiatives and to attracting attention in the corporation
R12	Office of CIO or ITG	An organizational structure for the CIO, IT and business in which CIOs define the scope and roles of the office to fit their needs and to strengthen IT
R13	Shared understanding of business/IT objectives	Involving key stakeholders in ITG to recognize the multiplexity of value drivers and develop a shared understanding of the value of IT (Peterson, 2004b)

2.2 ITG and corporate performance – a literature review

2.2.1 Introduction

To understand the future development of the governance concept in the digital age, it is important to examine related research on the antecedents of ITG. Since ITG is crucial due to its significant impact on enabling innovation and enhancing corporate performance, the relationship between ITG and corporate performance must be understood. Therefore, as

shown at the beginning of this thesis, the first research question (RQ1) is concerned with examining the determinants of ITG with respect to corporate performance as follows:

RQ1: *How is the current research structured with respect to the link between ITG and corporate performance? What concepts impact the ITG-corporate performance relationship?*

Hence, RQ1 aims to examine the association between ITG and corporate performance. First, the this chapter provides a consolidated overview of the body of knowledge of how current research views the link between ITG mechanisms and corporate performance. Second, the research reduces the blurring of the ITG-corporate performance links by uncovering key concepts as potential moderators or mediators of the general link between ITG and performance. In this context, a moderator refers to a third construct that may affect the strength and/or direction of the relation between the predictor (the independent variable), here ITG, and the outcome (the dependent variable), such as corporate performance (Fairchild and MacKinnon, 2009). In contrast, a mediator (a third construct) is included between the independent and dependent variables and explains why and how these variables are related (Nyello *et al.*, 2017).¹ Therefore, the related research offers the basis for further examination in this thesis based on the current state of ITG research. Moreover, the literature review seeks to explain multiple aspects of the ITG-performance relationship black box.

2.2.2 ITG and corporate performance

Various publications suggest that ITG is an integral part of corporate governance (IT Governance Institute, 2003; Lainhart IV, 2000; van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004). Corporate governance is defined as “*the system by which corporations are directed and managed. It influences how the objectives of the corporation are set and achieved, how risk is monitored and assessed, and how performance is optimized*” (Webb *et al.*, 2006, p. 2). Hence, a linkage between ITG and corporate performance can be expected since corporations with stronger ITG may carve out competitive advantage in driving technology decisions and keeping costs under control (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, many researchers analysing ITG and its mechanisms point out that there is a research gap with respect to the relationship between ITG and corporate performance. For instance, Dahlberg and Kivijarvi (2006) argue that effective governance is a vital way to ensure returns on IT investments and improved corporate performance. Tsai *et al.* (2015) propose paying more attention to value delivery

¹ For a more detailed description about moderator and mediator variables please refer to Hair *et al.* (2016, pp. 227–274).

within an ITG framework to improve performance. Jacobson (2009) argues that a more detailed emphasis on the ITG-corporate performance relationship is required. He states that achieving ITG fit in a corporation may lead to improved corporate performance, but a deeper examination to uncover and understand the links to performance is also needed. Indeed, an empirical study by Kaur *et al.* (2012) examines the direct impact of ITG effectiveness on corporate performance. Although ITG factors such as structures, processes and relational mechanisms were found to be significantly related to corporate performance, such ITG factors explained only approximately 6% of the variation in corporate performance. Therefore, they suggest that other contributing factors may be worth investigating with respect to the relationship between ITG effectiveness and corporate performance. Another perspective in exploring the direct link between ITG and corporate performance is presented by Wraikat (2010). Their findings indicate that there is a strong relationship between ITG and its pillars, including accountability, transparency, participation and predictability, which have a significant direct impact on corporate performance. Their ITG model explains approximately 50% of the variation in corporate performance. Therefore, they propose that corporations should consider the importance of ITG and its pillars – accountability, transparency, participation and predictability – in enhancing performance, especially in today’s rapidly changing world. As the digital era demands a culture of speed and collaboration, the links between ITG and performance should also consider dynamic aspects (Jacobson, 2009). Hence, a deeper examination of the links between ITG and performance is needed.

2.2.3 Method

The purpose of the study was to systematically trace the existing literature on the ITG-corporate performance link to discover the first building block for this thesis and to formulate the research hypotheses. However, many types of literature review are provided in previous studies. Grant and Booth (2009), for example, list 14 review types and the associated methodologies. Paré *et al.* (2015) introduce nine literature review types that help a researcher to analyse the literature about a specific topic. Among the various classes of literature analysis, a systematic literature review best fits addressing RQ1. This kind of analysis aims to identify, evaluate and interpret available research that is relevant to a particular research question, topic area or phenomenon of interest (Kitchenham, 2004). It has the following advantages that differentiate a systematic review from a conventional literature review (Kitchenham, 2004):

- It employs a defined search strategy to identify as much as possible of the relevant literature.
- It specifies explicit inclusion and exclusion criteria to determine whether each potential study should be included.
- It ensures reproducibility so that readers can assess its rigour and completeness.
- It is a prerequisite for quantitative meta-analysis.

A systematic literature review was therefore appropriate for investigating RQ1. However, in order to explore the current state of literature with a focus on the relationship between ITG and corporate performance, the review methodology described by Webster and Watson (2002) was adopted. According to them, the major contributions are likely to have been published in leading outlets. They also propose examining selected conference proceedings, especially those with a reputation for quality. However, as it is not possible to look through each journal and conference database for the relevant papers, as proposed by Webster and Watson this thesis research strategy was extended with the steps of Creswell (2012). As a result, the search process was follows:

1. Identify the key terms to use in the research.
2. Locate the literature by consulting several types of material and databases.
3. Critically evaluate and select the literature for review and exclude papers from non-leading journals and conferences.
4. Organize the selected literature; conduct a backward review and structure the papers.
5. Write a literature review that summarizes the literature.

Based on the points mentioned, the following three systematic stages and search activity steps were introduced, setting the basis for the systematic literature review before providing a synthesis of the related research (see Figure 2.2)

Figure 2.2: Literature review search strategy

Stage 1: Search Strategy: In this stage, the following keywords in various combinations such as “IT Governance” and “Performance” were used when conducting the search. To obtain high-quality data for this study, the search was performed on four databases: ACM Digital Library, Science Direct, IEEE and AISel. The first findings in Google Scholar with the precise key phrase “IT +Governance +Performance” returned 534 results. Hence, the search on the ITG-performance link indicated that there had been only a few investigations of this relationship. The results using the key phrase “IT +Governance +Performance” after setting in-/exclusion criteria (only English papers; published from January 2006 to May 2019; only title, authors, keywords and abstract considered) in the aforementioned databases are presented in Table 2.3. Finally, 207 relevant papers were identified in this stage.

Table 2.3: Results search databases

ACM Digital Library	Science Direct	IEEE	AISel	Google Scholar
363	50	219	199	534

Stage 2: Evaluation: In this stage, first, duplicates were removed. Then, only scientific papers were included that had been published either in leading IS (information systems) journals (such as MISQ, JAIS, EJIS, JIT, ISR, JMIS, Decision Science and DSS) or in the proceedings of top IS conferences (such as ICIS, HICSS, ECIS, ACIS, AMCIS, PACIS and Conf-IRM). If a paper did not explicitly state that ITG impacts corporate performance, it was excluded from the study. At this stage, 63 relevant papers were chosen.

Stage 3: Reading: This stage considered papers only by means of full text reading. In doing so, irrelevant articles were identified and excluded from the database. Furthermore, some papers were included from a backward review, leaving 37 papers. By reviewing the scope, key variables, methodologies and research settings of each article, the studies were structured by the perspectives and the possible mediating or moderating role of the variables in the ITG-corporate performance link.

2.2.4 Synthesis

In this section, the findings from the literature review are provided. The aim is to determine which key variables may impact the ITG-corporate performance relationship. Overall, 37 relevant studies were identified: 11 journal articles and 26 conference articles. It should be noted at this stage that the shortlisted papers were identified by following the search process described in the previous section. A different search strategy, i.e., including papers from other journals and conferences could have led to a much larger list of studies. However, in

this literature review, the range of publications found refers to leading academic IS journals and top IS research conferences worldwide. The results show that ITG has been under discussion for a long time in the academic world and that journal publications are currently being developed. The relevance of the topic can be further highlighted by the fact that there are ITG tracks at all relevant world IS conferences, such as ICIS, HICSS, ECIS and PACIS. Based on the literature considering the relationship between ITG and corporate performance, five relevant types of perspective were revealed for further research: the strategic alignment perspective, IT leadership perspective, IT capability and process performance perspective, resource relatedness perspective and culture perspective. These results are presented in Table 2.4. Furthermore, key concepts in these perspectives were highlighted. Additionally, the perspectives that potentially act as mediators or moderators of the relationship between ITG and corporate performance were recognized. The following descriptions will highlight some vital elements from the literature review in the context of the discovered perspectives.

It should be noted at this point that the concept of agility in the analysis did not arise on the basis of the defined search strategy and therefore does not appear in the following Table 2.4. This may be due to the fact that the literature on agility related to ITG and corporate performance is still in its infancy. Although aspects of agility in the individual perspectives are discussed in the literature, they have not yet been explored explicitly in the ITG-corporate performance context. By contrast, the perspectives on the ITG-corporate performance ratio revealed in this systematic literature research have been debated in the IS literature for more than 10 years and have thus reached a high degree of maturity in academic research.

Table 2.4: Perspectives and key concepts

Perspectives	Key concepts	Studies	Mediators/ moderators
Strategic alignment perspective	Business/IT alignment in general	(Banker <i>et al.</i> , 2011) (Buchwald <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	Mediators
	Intellectual dimension alignment	(Connolly <i>et al.</i> , 2017) (Fink and Ploder, 2008)	
	Social dimension alignment	(Gu <i>et al.</i> , 2008)	
	CIO-top management team alignment	(Haghjoo, 2012) (Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2008)	
	Inhibitors/enablers of ITG in relation to corporate performance	(Liang <i>et al.</i> , 2011) (Nfuka and Rusu, 2010) (Schlosser <i>et al.</i> , 2010)	
	Critical success factors of ITG in relation to corporate performance	(Schlosser <i>et al.</i> , 2015) (Urbach <i>et al.</i> , 2013) (Wu <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	

<i>IT leadership perspective</i>	Technology leader on board	(Banker <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	Mediators or moderators
	CIO reporting structure	(Bergeron <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	
	CIO structural power	(Bradley <i>et al.</i> , 2012)	
	CIO role and characteristics	(Jewer and McKay, 2012)	
	CIO strategic effectiveness	(Liang <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	
	CIO strategic decision making	(Pang, 2014)	
	Business process relatedness	(Preston <i>et al.</i> , 2008)	
<i>IT capability and process performance perspective</i>	IT strategy committee	(Smith <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	Mediators
	IT steering committee	(Buchwald <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	
	Operational committee	(Bradley <i>et al.</i> , 2012)	
	Communication committee	(Heier <i>et al.</i> , 2009)	
	CIO reporting structure	(Prasad <i>et al.</i> , 2009)	
	Process-level performance	(Prasad <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	
	Dynamic capabilities	(Samuwai and Prasad, 2014)	
	Operational capabilities	(Smith <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	
<i>Resource relatedness perspective</i>	IT relatedness	(Smits and van Hillegersberg, 2015)	Mediators
	Business process relatedness	(Turel and Bart, 2014)	
<i>Culture perspective</i>	Organizational culture dimensions	(Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	Moderators
	Organizational culture type	(Mikalef <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	
	National culture	(Lazic <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	

2.2.4.1 Strategic alignment perspective

One of the most investigated factors impacting the ITG-corporate performance relationship is the strategic alignment perspective between IT and business. The focus of strategic alignment is assuring the congruence of IT and business plans and goals over time and making them support and enhance each other (Fink and Ploder, 2008; Schlosser *et al.*, 2010). Several viewpoints have been proposed within strategic alignment and ITG-performance links. In the literature, the strategic alignment between IT and business is usually indicated as business/IT alignment (or sometimes as IT/business alignment). Some studies examine

business/IT alignment in general as one of the most important outcomes of ITG, which leads to higher corporate performance. Liang *et al.* (2011) show that business/IT alignment is a major factor that mediates the effect of ITG on corporate performance. Their model explains 53% of the variance in corporate performance. Based on a literature review by Haghjoo (2012), which examined how ITG leads to business value, business/IT alignment is the most common benefit of effective ITG, which leads to higher business value. According to Buchwald *et al.* (2014), ITG fosters the alignment of business and IT goals, which positively impacts business performance. Liang *et al.* (2011) further note that many alignment definitions in the literature focus only on how IT is aligned with business. What also matters is how business is aligned with IT. Therefore, in addition to the general business/IT alignment approach for the ITG-corporate performance conceptualization, some researchers provide more detailed insight into such concepts. Wu *et al.* (2015) examine how strategic alignment is realized through ITG mechanisms and which components of strategic alignment contribute to organizational competitiveness. Therefore, they propose a study in which strategic alignment is divided into two dimensions: the intellectual and the social. Based on their research, ITG mechanisms embody the social setting for strategic alignment, which, in turn, impacts the intellectual dimension of strategic alignment and ultimately leads to higher corporate performance. While the intellectual dimension includes alignment of strategy, alignment of plans and alignment of infrastructures and processes, the social dimension contains factors such as shared understanding; business-IT partnership; and CIO characteristics, attributes, abilities and leadership (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Likewise, Schlosser (2012; 2015) highlight the importance of the social dimension alignment within the ITG alignment-performance construct. Extending the alignment view, several studies also focus on the alignment between CIO reporting structures and corporate strategic positioning, which enhances corporate performance (Banker *et al.*, 2011; Urbach *et al.*, 2013; Buchwald *et al.*, 2014; Wu *et al.*, 2015). Other researchers investigate the critical success factors as well as the inhibitors/enablers of ITG and corporate performance (Gu *et al.*, 2008; Lee *et al.*, 2008; Nfuka and Rusu, 2010). In these studies, strategic alignment plays a major role. Based on the research presented, the strategic alignment perspective can be seen as an important factor in the ITG-performance black box, which may mediate the effect of ITG on corporate outcome. This is also highlighted by Connolly *et al.* (2017).

2.2.4.2 IT leadership perspective

Another important dimension with an impact on the relationship of ITG and corporate performance is IT leadership perspective. As stated by the IT Governance Institute (2003),

ITG requires leadership to ensure that IT activities are sustained and extended to achieve the organization's goals. This emphasis on leadership is confirmed by Weill and Ross, who find that the most important factor that separates top-performing from standard-performing organizations is the quality of senior leadership in making IT decisions (Weill and Ross, 2004). Liang *et al.* (2011) focus on IT leadership and suggest that this is the most critical element of ITG maturity. It plays a major role in the more mature implementation of ITG practices, which can generate a positive impact on strategic alignment and corporate performance (Liang *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, many investigations have been conducted on the impact of IT leadership on the ITG-corporate performance link. In the literature, IT leadership is typically associated with the role of technical leaders such as CIOs (Smith *et al.*, 2013; Taylor *et al.*, 2015). The importance of a CIO seems plausible as he or she can ensure that IT strategies support and complement business strategies (Pang, 2014; Smith *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, several studies focus on CIO roles, characteristics, attributes and abilities. Consequently, one main research topic is the involvement of CIOs on boards of directors to ensure IT competency in upper echelons. Including the CIO in the top management team may lead to significantly higher corporate performance (Jewer and McKay, 2012; Taylor *et al.*, 2015). As the inclusion of a technology leader within the corporate top management team represents one aspect of ITG, this conceptualization significantly affects the ITG-corporate performance relationship (Turel and Bart, 2014). Another topic investigated by several researchers is the CIO reporting structure. Having the CIO report to another C-level position, such as the CFO (Chief Financial Officer), COO or CMO (Chief Marketing Officer), is important because it provides the best opportunity for the CIO to pursue appropriate IT initiatives that align with the corporate strategic position, thereby achieving business/IT alignment and facilitating corporate performance. Banker *et al.* (2011) and Bradley *et al.* (2012) find a significant effect of the CIO reporting structure on corporate performance. Connected with the importance of the CIO reporting structure, the role of a CIO and its characteristics receive major attention. Zimmermann *et al.* (2016) present a CIO leadership mosaic structure that includes perspectives of the personal characteristics of an IT leader. These characteristics are also highlighted in a study by Preston *et al.* (2008). The leadership skills of a CIO are important for effectiveness in strategic decision making. The CIO's level of strategic effectiveness influences the relationship between the strategic decision-making authorities and the IT contribution to corporate performance (Jewer and McKay, 2012; Preston *et al.*, 2008; Smith *et al.*, 2013).

These few studies show that IT leadership, especially when executed by the CIO, plays a crucial role in the governance of IT by assuring the strategic value of IT, driving and supporting new business models, and improving corporate performance. Therefore, it can be stated that the IT leadership perspective is an important variable in the ITG-corporate performance relationship that can have mediating as well as moderating effects on the link between ITG effectiveness and corporate outcome.

2.2.4.3 IT capabilities and process performance perspective

When the CIO is part of the top management team, he or she is involved in the strategic decision making on IT capabilities in the organization (Bradley *et al.*, 2012; Turel and Bart, 2014). Therefore, several studies focus on the IT capability perspective. According to Zhang *et al.* (2014) IT capabilities can be defined as the corporate ability to innovatively implement and deploy IT resources in the process of business to obtain business/IT strategies and create a distinctive advantage. In their study, they propose coupling ITG with IT capability to evaluate their impact on corporate performance. Implementing several committees (e.g., an IT strategy committee, IT steering committee, or operational committee) as part of ITG in an organization may optimize the deployment of IT capabilities and therefore lead to higher performance (Prasad *et al.*, 2011). A study by Samuwai and Prasad (2014) shows that implementing such committees in an organization leads to effective ITG and therefore higher corporate performance. This is confirmed by Prasad *et al.* (2009), who examine the relationship between the effectiveness of IT steering committee-driven ITG initiatives, corporate IT management, and IT infrastructure-related capabilities. Their model explains 67.8% of the variance in corporate performance. The findings of Smith *et al.* (2013) highlight the role of ITG in IT value creation. They demonstrate the impact of sophisticated IT capabilities on organizational performance as a function of ITG dynamics, including CIO reporting structure, CIO turnover, and IT steering committee abandonment. Therefore, one of the main objectives of ITG is IT capability management. In a recent study, Mikalef *et al.* (2018) examine the impact of information governance in contemporary organizations. They regard information technology as a sub-set of ITG. Based on the resource-based view and dynamic capability view, they argue that ITG helps strengthen corporate operational and dynamic capabilities, which ultimately leads to competitive corporate performance. Indeed, they empirically show that the impact of information technology on competitive corporate performance is fully mediated through dynamic and operational capabilities, which can be considered sub-sets of corporate IT capabilities and process performance, respectively. The rapidly growing level of investment in IT resources in the current digital age and the impact

of such resources on corporate performance necessitate an active ITG stance, as already deployed for other critical organizational resources, such as capital or labour (Bradley *et al.*, 2012). However, the optimal use of IT capabilities does not directly impact corporate performance but rather reflects the extent to which IT assets and capabilities are used to support work processes across the organization (Buchwald *et al.*, 2014). Thus, the aforementioned studies propose models explaining how ITG mechanisms impact IT capabilities, leading to better corporate internal processes and consequently higher corporate performance (Bradley *et al.*, 2012; Prasad *et al.*, 2009; Samuwai and Prasad, 2014). The process performance perspective is also emphasized by Heier *et al.* (2009) and Prasad *et al.* (2011). Accordingly, the IT capability and process performance perspective have been identified as important variable affecting the relationship between ITG and corporate performance. The relevant studies mostly use the concepts of this perspective as mediators for the impact of ITG on corporate outcome.

2.2.4.4 Resource relatedness perspective

The category of resource relatedness perspective covers research papers that deal with the various impacts of relatedness variables on the ITG-corporate performance relationship. The studies reveal that two key concepts affect the ITG-corporate performance black box: first, IT relatedness, which can be defined as “*the usage of common IT resources and IT management processes across business units*” (Lazic *et al.*, 2011, p. 5); second, business process relatedness, which deals with the “*usage of common business processes across business units*” (Neff *et al.*, 2013, p. 4469). Tanriverdi (2006) examines how ITG moderates the influence of IT relatedness on corporate performance. He identifies IT resources and management processes as an important source of cross-unit synergy in multi-business corporations. Based on the resource-based view (RBV), he articulates the distinctive characteristics of IT resources and management processes that extend their range of applicability across diverse business segments. He distinguishes between cross-unit IT synergies and cross-unit business synergies and explains why the exploitation of a complementary set of related IT resources across multiple business units creates IT synergies even across a set of diverse businesses that has limited opportunity to exploit business synergies. The results of Lazic *et al.* (2011) suggest that ITG is positively related to business performance through the mediators IT relatedness and business process relatedness, and this relation consequently impacts corporate performance. Additionally, Neff *et al.* (2013) find that ITG is positively related to business process performance through the mediators IT relatedness and business process relatedness and identify levers that might significantly

improve business outcomes. In this context, it can be stated that approaches of the resource relatedness perspective mediate the influence of ITG mechanisms on corporate performance.

2.2.4.5 Cultural perspective

This section contains different perspectives on the influence of organizational culture on corporate performance. The key concepts around organizational cultures are the culture dimension, culture types and national culture viewpoints. There is a consensus that the concept of organizational culture is difficult to define, measure, and analyse since several definitions exist in the literature (Janssen *et al.*, 2013). However, because organizational culture is one of the various factors influencing ITG performance (Aasi *et al.*, 2016), it is a substantial variable in the ITG-corporate performance relationship. In terms of cultural dimensions, Janssen *et al.* (2013) provide a qualitative study in which they explore how organizational culture influences the pillars of ITG based on five culture dimension elements: results orientation, orientation towards individualism, long-term orientation, orientation by gender and orientation by rules and patterns. They conclude that organizational culture may impede the progress of ITG toward obtaining favourable results and, consequently, may impede the organizational implementation of ITG. This is confirmed by Wiedenhöft *et al.* (2015), who identify important moderating effects on these relationships through the dimensions of organizational culture. Aasi *et al.* (2016) consider other aspects of organizational culture, such as dominant characteristics, leadership style, management of employees, organizational glue, strategic emphases and criteria of success. These are grouped into four cultural types: clan, adhocracy, hierarchy and market. Their case study analysis provides evidence that all these cultural characteristics influence ITG performance and, consequently, corporate outcome. Hence, these few studies show that the culture perspective is important and its concepts may have a moderating effect on the ITG-corporate performance link.

2.2.5 Summary

The main objectives of the systematic literature review were to trace the existing research on the relationship between ITG and corporate performance and to identify key concepts with respect to this relationship. As shown in the synthesis section, the main concepts are associated with the perspectives of strategic alignment, IT leadership, IT capability and process performance, resource relatedness and culture. Furthermore, the literature review also presents the core aspects explored within these perspectives that could act as potential mediators or moderators in the relationship between ITG and corporate performance. The

focus in the chosen literature refers to strategic alignment perspective, IT leadership perspective and IT capability perspective. This is not surprising since these aspects have reached a high level of maturity in the literature. However, as these perspectives are the main objectives of ITG, it is necessary to develop a better understanding of how they impact the ITG-corporate performance relationship in the digital age. Nevertheless, because of extensive changes in the new and rapidly changing economy, leading to new requirements and expectations being vested in IT, the task of aligning business and IT remains a prime challenge (Schlosser, 2012). As pointed out previously, the ultimate goal of ITG is to achieve effective alignment between business and IT. Furthermore, according to Weill and Ross, ITG is seen as “*the single most important predictor of the value an organization generates from IT*” (Weill and Ross, 2004, p. 4). Hence, business/IT alignment is one of the mediating factors that is considered an important and necessary condition in the chain of IT value creation (Kohli and Grover, 2008). However, because corporations have increasingly pursued digital strategies that make them dependent on their IT, the ability to achieve alignment has become a dynamic capability (Teece *et al.*, 1997). As will be highlighted in Section 2.4.2, this thesis argues that new established agile ITG mechanisms complementing the traditional ITG mechanisms help build such a dynamic capability in aligning business with IT. For that reason, the perspective of strategic alignment (referred to hereafter as business/IT alignment), identified in the literature review, will be considered the first building block in this thesis’s exploration of the ITG-corporate performance link. Consequently, the basic research model can be developed with the business/IT alignment construct acting as a mediator between the governance-performance link and can be modelled as presented in Figure 2.3. Therefore, the theoretical foundation of business/IT alignment is presented in the following section to further justify this relationship. The examination of the interrelationships of the other four perspectives in the ITG-corporation performance link extends the scope of this thesis but opens a pathway for further research.

Figure 2.3: Basic research model

2.3 Mediation of business/IT alignment

2.3.1 Background

Business/IT alignment has been continuously ranked among the top three challenges of CIOs since 1994 and is therefore a key concern in many corporations (Kappelman *et al.*, 2013; Luftman and Ben-Zvi, 2011). Thus, a broad body of work has emerged that explores both theory and practice in this domain. There is a consensus that at its core, alignment is about bringing business and IT together in the sense that IT effectively supports or even drives business (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009; Schlosser, 2012; Weill and Ross, 2004). Therefore, in the strategy literature, business/IT alignment has been considered both a state at a single point in time (e.g., in a cross-sectional study using a variance or factor model) and a process to be understood over time (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Although many researchers focus on the process aspect of business/IT alignment (Chan *et al.*, 1997; Sabherwal and Chan, 2001; Tallon, 2008), this thesis concentrates on the content of alignment because this thesis' focus lies on how well the content of business strategy matches the content of the realized IT strategy enabled through appropriate ITG mechanisms. In this sense, business/IT alignment is seen as the fit between business and IT strategic orientation and is concerned with integrating IT and the business plan to achieve solutions and strategies that are aligned with IT strategies and the business enterprise (Lunardi *et al.*, 2017; Chan *et al.*, 1997). For that reason, business/IT alignment is conceptualized as a state or an outcome that is dependent on its antecedents (Chan *et al.*, 1997; Reich and Benbasat, 1996; Wu *et al.*, 2015). As such, the determinants of alignment are likely to be ITG mechanisms that drive alignment, for example, ITG processes, communication and planning and the establishment of appropriate structures (Wu *et al.*, 2015). This perspective allows us to describe how business/IT alignment is realized through governance mechanisms and which components of alignment contribute more to corporate competitiveness (Wu *et al.*, 2015).

In general, the literature divides business/IT alignment into two dimensions: (1) the *intellectual* and (2) the *social* dimension (Reich and Benbasat, 1996; Schlosser, 2012). *Intellectual business/IT alignment*, on the one hand, refers to “*the state in which a high-quality set of interrelated IT and business plans exist*” (Reich and Benbasat, 2000, p. 82). Previous research on intellectual business/IT alignment mainly includes studies on (1) *the alignment of business and IT strategy* (Kearns and Sabherwal, 2006), (2) *the alignment of plans* (Hirschheim and Sabherwal, 2001) and (3) *the alignment of infrastructure and processes* (Henderson and Venkatraman, 1992). A well-known model for business/IT

alignment that represents these alignment dimensions is the strategic alignment model (SAM) of Venkatraman *et al.* (1993), which addresses the required balance between business strategies, IT strategies, business processes, and IT processes (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009). Other studies provide additional insights into the model and propose that corporations should consider the degree to which technology aligns with their strategies, goals, and business needs prior to investing in an IT solution (Luftman, 2000; Sabherwal and Chan, 2001). For that reason, several researchers investigate the antecedents of the intellectual dimension of strategic alignment to better understand the alignment phenomenon. Such antecedents include, e.g., shared domain knowledge, IT/business planning sophistication, prior IT success, environmental uncertainty, and corporate size (Chan *et al.*, 2006; Luftman and Brier, 1999). Other recognized factors include senior executive support for IT; well-prioritized IT projects; business-IT partnerships; CIO characteristics, attributes, abilities, and leadership (Baker, 2004; Luftman and Brier, 1999); communication links between business and IT executives as well as shared participation and planning (Luftman and Brier, 1999; Reich and Benbasat, 2000); IT sophistication and external IT expertise (Chan *et al.*, 2006; Hussin *et al.*, 2002); the information intensity of the value chain (Kearns and Lederer, 2003); a track record for the IT department/CIO (Luftman and Brier, 1999; Chan *et al.*, 2006); and shared CIO-top management team (TMT) understanding (Tan and Gallupe, 2006; Preston and Karahanna, 2009).

Social business/IT alignment, on the other hand, is defined as “*the state in which business and IT executives understand each other and are committed to the business and IT mission, objectives and plans*” (Reich and Benbasat, 2000, p. 82) and is also highlighted in several studies, such as Chan (2002), Tiwana *et al.* (2003), Schlosser (2012) and Schlosser *et al.* (2015). The social alignment dimension focuses mainly on the *relationships and cognitive linkages* between business and IT-like relationships, such as communication, mutual understanding among the actors in the corporation, trust and respect, cultural issues and informal structures (Schlosser *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, it relates to the human behaviour that is socially organized among different actors (Alaceva and Rusu, 2015; Schlosser *et al.*, 2012). Based on prior empirical research on alignment, the factors making up the social dimension are highlighted as antecedents of the intellectual dimension, which positively influences intellectual alignment (Preston and Karahanna, 2009). In particular, shared understanding has been identified as an important antecedent of intellectual business/IT alignment (Armstrong and Sambamurthy, 1999; Chan, 2002; Preston and Karahanna, 2009; Tan and Gallupe, 2006) since it can foster shared domain knowledge in both business and

IT departments. In the literature, knowledge integration (referring to shared domain knowledge) is divided into two key components (Armstrong and Sambamurthy, 1999): the *objective knowledge* and *systemic knowledge*. According to Armstrong and Sambamurthy (1999), objective knowledge is concerned mainly with the visible domain knowledge of the CIO and TMT. Thus, it includes social alignment among CIOs and other board members at the strategic level (Reich and Benbasat, 2000). The systemic knowledge, on the other hand, refers to “*organizational arrangements that enable interaction among team members for sharing their perspectives, pooling knowledge, and developing shared understanding*” (Preston and Karahanna, 2009, p. 164). Hence, it is concerned with business-IT relationships at the operational level where strategies are implemented and coordinated business-IT activities have direct effects on corporate performance (Schlosser *et al.*, 2015). In summary, while the intellectual dimension focuses on alignment of strategy, plans, operations or processes, the social dimension addresses aspects such as shared understanding, common language, shared domain knowledge, and interaction quality between business and IT (Schlosser, 2012).

2.3.2 ITG enabling of business/IT alignment

Following the ITG definition stated in Section 2.1.1, ITG relates to the allocation of decision-making rights and responsibilities across business and IT functions (Peterson, 2004b; Weill and Ross, 2004) and proposes the integration of specific mechanisms that forge a joint approach of IT and business to ensure that IT strategies and projects are effectively put into action (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009; Peterson, 2004b). Thus, ITG mechanisms directly tap into the alignment concept that corporate performance “*is the consequence of fit between two or more factors such as strategy, structure, technology, culture, and environment*” (Bergeron *et al.*, 2004, p. 1004) and foster cross-domain interconnectedness between business and IT departments (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009; Schlosser *et al.*, 2015; Wu *et al.*, 2015). Consequently, ITG mechanisms can be considered organizational arrangements (Wu *et al.*, 2015) that can serve as mechanisms of coordination in the sense that they permit “*the timely and purposeful adjustment of decisions pertaining to values of different aspects, between stakeholders involved in decision making*” (Peterson *et al.*, 2000, p. 436). Thus, it can be stated that ITG mechanisms enable shared understanding between CIOs and TMTs on a strategic level as well as among team members on an operational level (Schlosser *et al.*, 2015; Wu *et al.*, 2015).

ITG structural mechanisms, such as boards, steering and strategy committees and councils, executive teams (e.g., CIO on the board), the CIO reporting to the CEO or COO, and business/IT relationship managers, are important formal structures for connecting and enabling horizontal, or liaison, contracts between business and IT management (decision-making) functions (Almeida *et al.*, 2013; Peterson, 2004b). In general, such structural mechanisms are situated at the executive level (van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004) and are responsible for determining business priorities and assisting executives in the delivery of business and IT strategies. Hence, they are “*comprised of high-level representatives who are ensured with the task of linking IT strategy with business strategy by matching corporate concerns with IT support*” (Wu *et al.*, 2015, p. 504). For example, *IT steering committees* have been recognized as one of the most effective ITG mechanisms for aligning IT-related decisions and actions with an organization’s strategic and operational priorities (Huang *et al.*, 2010). An IT steering committee is a formal body that meets regularly (Huang *et al.*, 2010) to discuss implementation issues (van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004), track IT investments, set priorities, and allocate scarce resources (IT Governance Institute, 2003). As such, steering committees are invaluable in establishing the tone of business-IT relationships (Ross *et al.*, 1996) and making IT initiatives visible, which is essential for top management to appreciate IT in the corporation (Prasad *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, ensuring that steering committees include both business unit managers and CIOs can enable the close coordination of business and IT in the corporation, which may result in better business/IT alignment (Bowen *et al.*, 2007; Wu *et al.*, 2015). As another example, when the CIO is on the board, or he or she reports directly to the CEO or COO (or even to other C-level executives), his or her position will ensure that IT is a regular item on the board and executive agendas and that it is addressed in a structured manner (Almeida *et al.*, 2013). Conversely, it allows the CIO to interpret the business strategy in terms of IT requirements and to seek ways to increase the IT value contribution to fully harmonize IT and business strategy (van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, it enhances shared domain knowledge and shared understanding in both directions: (1) the CIO’s business knowledge is enhanced by obtaining a global and holistic perspective on the corporation, its goals and strategies, and the understanding of the TMT’s vision (Wu *et al.*, 2015), and (2) the TMT’s IT knowledge is enhanced by keeping him or her up-to-date regarding current business models, innovations, and technologies and the potential risks and benefits associated with each of them. In summary, ITG structural mechanisms impact business/IT alignment by enabling access to both IT and business units for knowledge exchange and active participation (Wu *et al.*, 2015).

ITG process mechanisms ensure that the CIO and other participants better understand the business needs that prompt the CIO and TMT as well as the stakeholders to reach common organizational goals and objectives through organizational planning (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Thus, they facilitate the alignment of the corporate IT strategy with the corporate business strategy. For instance, portfolio management is considered one of the most effective formal processes that is crucial within a corporation in order to prioritize IT investments and projects (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009). In such a prioritizing process, both business and IT are involved; therefore, ITG acts as a liaison unit that spans the business-IT boundary and encourages interaction and collaboration. Another example of an effective ITG process mechanism is strategic information systems planning (SISP), which is a formal process to define and update the IT strategy (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009). According to Earl (1993), the main purposes of such a process are to align IT with business goals, exploit IT for competitive advantage, direct the efficient and effective management of IT resources, and develop technology policies and architectures. In short, SISP brings business and IT professionals together and establishes a mutual understanding of the value of IT and the problems associated with it and assists corporations in reaching their business objectives through IT investment (Altameem *et al.*, 2014). Overall, ITG process mechanisms ensure that the TMT, the CIO and stakeholders understand the importance of IT and its capabilities, which in turn facilitates intellectual business/IT alignment.

Finally, communication approaches in terms of *ITG relational mechanisms* “allow the IT and business executive management to communicate and make sure that their roles and responsibilities are clearly understood by each other” (Wu *et al.*, 2015, p. 504). ITG relation mechanisms are important for business/IT alignment since they enable effective two-way communication and a good participation/collaboration relationship between business and IT (van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004). They ensure ongoing knowledge sharing across departments, which is paramount for attaining and sustaining business/IT alignment (Callahan *et al.*, 2004; Luftman, 2000; van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004; Venkatraman *et al.*, 1993; Weill and Broadbent, 1998). For example, when senior business and IT managers act as “partners” in achieving corporate goals, it facilitates the sharing and management of knowledge. As a first example of an effective relational mechanism, executive/senior management provides a good example of collaboration within a corporation (van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004) and enables the CIO to interact with the TMT regarding how IT can add value and support business strategy. This effective communication mechanism allows a CIO’s business knowledge to be improved, and this knowledge can in turn be transferred back to the IT

department. At the same time, (as a second effective relational mechanism), the CIO is able to articulate a vision of the IT role, which helps the TMT understand the role of IT within the corporation, in turn enabling the transfer of IT knowledge to business executives (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Accordingly, it enables the “*IT and business executives, at a deep level, to understand and be able to participate in the others’ key processes and to respect each other’s unique contribution and challenges*” (Reich and Benbasat, 2000, p. 86). As highlighted in Table 2.2, ITG proposes additional effective relational mechanisms, such as informal meetings with no agenda in which business and IT senior managers talk about general activities and directions, to promote shared understanding and shared domain knowledge (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009). Furthermore, relational mechanisms such as cross-functional business/IT job rotation, continuous education, and cross-functional business/IT training (Luftman, 2000) facilitate the sharing and management of knowledge (van Grembergen *et al.*, 2004). In summary, ITG relational mechanisms usually improve shared knowledge that enables business and IT to create a shared understanding of how IT can be applied to enhance corporate performance, which is a critical and indispensable antecedent of intellectual business/IT alignment.

In line with the aforementioned theoretical considerations in this section, the first research hypothesis (H1) is introduced at this stage:

H1: *ITG mechanisms have a positive impact on intellectual business/IT alignment.*

2.3.3 Building block one – Business/IT alignment as mediator

As noted in Section 2.2.4.1, in the literature, business/IT alignment is the most investigated dimension in the ITG-corporate performance relationship and is considered one of the important necessary mediating factors in the chain of value creation (Kohli and Grover, 2008). As further explained in the previous sub-section, the goal of increased business/IT alignment and therefore their contribution to business value can be achieved by establishing an ITG framework with the well-designed implementation of the three types of mechanism – structural, process and relational mechanisms (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009; Weill and Ross, 2004). These mechanisms enable corporations to maximize IT investments by achieving fusion between IT and business strategies and plans, leading to a better *alignment outcome* and hence to greater profitability (Papp, 1999). Thus, intellectual business/IT alignment is an outcome of the mutual understanding between business and IT executives in which ITG provides the framework for such a shared understanding to occur (Wu *et al.*, 2015). In other words, intellectual business/IT alignment can be seen as a “*knowledge*

integration outcome” (Karahanna and Preston, 2013; Kearns and Sabherwal, 2006) of the social linkage between human actors in business and IT that is ensured through ITG mechanisms. First, the existence of committees consisting of both business and IT personnel can improve strategic planning and foster intellectual alignment through joint IT planning and decision making. Second, well-defined and effective processes that appropriately involve both IT and business departments will facilitate business and IT professionals’ collaboration on business-oriented IT decisions (Schlosser, 2012; Wu *et al.*, 2015). Third, relational mechanisms are important for leveraging social alignment, as they directly promote the relationship between business and IT and therefore foster shared knowledge. As such, social business/IT alignment is part of ITG where ITG mechanisms embody the social setting and are considered *alignment antecedents* for intellectual business/IT alignment (*alignment state*) (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, in this thesis, ITG mechanisms provide the contextual framework for business and IT personnel to be involved in IT decision making and share knowledge to enhance IT support of business objectives and hence to improve the intellectual alignment dimension. Once such ITG mechanisms have been implemented within a corporation, critical business strategies and IT strategies must be aligned for subsequent improved corporate performance (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, the second research hypothesis (H2) is stated as follows:

H2: *Intellectual business/IT alignment mediates the positive impact of ITG mechanisms on corporate performance.*

The resource-based view can help illustrate the relationship between an effective ITG framework containing ITG mechanisms and its impact on corporate performance through the mediating factor of (intellectual) business/IT alignment. ITG mechanisms are understood as human IT resources reflecting “*combinations of investment allocations and a mutually reinforcing system of competencies and practices*” (Aral and Weill, 2007, p. 765) that complement IT in delivering value to corporations. According to the resource-based view, corporate resources are the main predictors of corporate performance (Barney, 1991; Grant, 1991; Hall, 1992; Wernerfelt, 1984), and IT resources can bring about differentiation in corporate strategies (Bharadwaj, 2000; Wu *et al.*, 2015). If a corporation possesses heterogeneous resources that are difficult to replicate and are not perfectly mobile, it has the potential to gain a sustainable competitive advantage in the marketplace (Kearns and Lederer, 2003). Thus, in terms of ITG mechanisms, corporations should foster a mixture of inimitable structures, processes, and relational mechanisms and leverage core resources to combine business and IT knowledge and support business objectives. Consequently, IT

strategic alignment will result in outcomes that are the product of the alignment process through ITG mechanisms, that is, the strategies contained in the business plan and the IT plan. This, in turn, may result in better corporate performance through IT-based value creation. Kohli and Grover (2008) also illustrate the schematic relationship among IT resources, IT strategic alignment (as a mediator), and IT-based value creation. Wu *et al.* (2015) adopt this concept and show that the intellectual dimension of business/IT alignment fully mediates the impact of ITG mechanisms on corporate performance. Their model furthermore explains 30% of the variance in corporate performance. This thesis uses their research model as an initial point in the literature to further investigate the link among ITG, business/IT alignment, and corporate performance. Hence, Figure 2.4 presents the initial research model, providing more details than the previously derived model presented in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.4: Initial research model adapted from Wu *et al.* (2015)

However, before testing the formulated relationships, the thesis aims to extend this conceptual model through the agile aspect (as a second building block) within the governance concept (left panel in Figure 2.4). After the foundation is set in the following section, this is discussed in the Chapter 4, which explores the governance concept through a qualitative study. Based on the outcomes, the research hypotheses (H1 and H2) will need to be adapted, which is the subject of Chapter 5.

2.4 The agile aspect within ITG

2.4.1 Agility definitions

Many researchers have argued that business agility is required to survive the volatility of the market (Cummins, 2009; Sloane *et al.*, 2008; van Roosmalen and Hoppenbrouwers, 2008). Business agility is important to change the direction of a strategy and to respond efficiently

and effectively to such unpredictability (Luftman *et al.*, 1993). In recent years, the term “agile” has gained much attention from practitioners and academics because of its importance in the innovation and competitive performance of corporations in contemporary business environments (Leonhardt *et al.*, 2018). As business agility is a complex, multidimensional and context-specific concept, the literature has proposed several different concepts, frameworks and metrics for defining and explaining it (Sherehiy *et al.*, 2007).

Some of the empirical literature highlight the strategic dimension of agility and argue that business agility is a corporate-wide capability to deal with changes that often arise unexpectedly in business environments via rapid and innovative responses that exploit changes as opportunities to grow and prosper (Goldman *et al.*, 1995; van Oosterhout *et al.*, 2006; Zhang and Sharifi, 2000). This agility emphasizes a dynamic, change embracing and growth-oriented entrepreneurial mind set about strategic direction, decision making, and judgment in uncertain conditions (Sambamurthy *et al.*, 2003; Volberda, 1997) and is concerned with strategic flexibility, nimble and innovative responses to the dynamic competitive landscape (Lewis *et al.*, 2014).

Other researchers see business agility as a kind of dynamic capability that enables a corporation to reconfigure, assemble and integrate resources, information, processes and technologies that are embedded in different activities within a corporation or its subsidiaries – highlighting the operational dimension of the agile concept (Ramasesh *et al.*, 2001; Sambamurthy *et al.*, 2003). Operational agility refers to a corporate’s ability in its internal business processes to physically and rapidly cope with market or demand changes (Dove, 2001). This type of agility mainly underlines flexible and rapidly responding operations as a critical basis for enabling fast and fluid translation of innovative initiatives in the face of changes (Lu and Ramamurthy, 2011).

Using these abilities enables a corporation to create synergies and additional competitive advantages that enhance corporate performance (Yang and Liu, 2012). However, to achieve both dimensions of agility (strategically and operationally) requires timely processing of a large volume and variety of distributed information that can be enhanced by a number of IT-enabled supporting, monitoring or learning systems (Goldman *et al.*, 1995; Lu and Ramamurthy, 2011). Accordingly, researchers agree that the right and agile IT capabilities can improve business performance and business agility (Baskerville *et al.*, 2005; Gallagher and Worrell, 2008; Melarkode *et al.*, 2004). These capabilities allow corporations to configure and reconfigure a corporation’s different resources in a rapid and flexible manner

helping the corporation to sense and respond to changes in its environment (van Oosterhout, 2014). This is referred to as the corporation's IT agility (Yousif *et al.*, 2017). Conceived as an antecedent to business agility, it furthermore encapsulates the ability of the IT function to sense opportunities to innovate and to respond rapidly to competitive actions from a larger repertoire of responses (Leonhardt *et al.*, 2017) and is, therefore, considered to be a main driver of the IT function's ability to support digitization (Haffke *et al.*, 2017b). As such, new ITG and alignment mechanisms need to be developed and established to align a corporations' strategic and operational activities with the digital and the traditional IT in a faster and more agile manner (Horlach *et al.*, 2016). Consequently, corporations' ITG need to consider agility in a broader context capturing the strategic as well as the operational dimension of agility. Based on these considerations the general concept of agility refers to

“the ability to respond operationally and strategically to changes in the external environment. The response has to be quick and effective for the corporation to be considered agile” (Fink and Neumann, 2007, p. 444).

This definition can serve as a proxy representing the established definitions of agility in current research, allowing us to break them down into single agile ITG mechanisms.

2.4.2 Towards agile ITG mechanisms

Few studies have combined agile capabilities with governance frameworks. Qumer (2007) introduces a first definition of agile governance, focusing on agile software development. He presents a summary of exploratory reviews and analysis to identify the related concepts, key aspects and importance of ITG. A second definition is presented by Cheng *et al.* (2009) who introduce a list of measurement and control aspects of agile governance frameworks and validate this view with three case studies. The third definition of agile governance is proposed by Luna *et al.* (2010), who focus specifically on ITG. In another study, Luna *et al.* (2013) present a fourth definition perceiving agile governance as multidisciplinary concept. While the aforementioned studies concentrate on providing a basic definition of agile governance, only a few studies investigate a holistic view of agile mechanisms within the governance framework. A study by Luna *et al.* (2014) offers an overview of the nascent research with respect to agile mechanisms within governance grounded in a systematic literature review. Other studies emphasize single elements that can enhance agility within an organization through governance mechanisms. For example, Power (2011) identifies the establishment of an agile office as an effective way to create a focal point within the organization for the changes brought about by an agile transition. Through a case study, he

shows that such an organizational unit governs an organization's ongoing agile adoption and continuous improvement through agile mechanisms. He further indicates that an agile office should have a steering team comprising the business unit's senior directors and senior managers. Wiedemann's (2018) study provides a starting point for researchers and practitioners on how governance structures, processes and relational mechanisms can be developed in practice with a focus on DevOps cross-functional teams. Through six different case studies, she demonstrates four key governance mechanisms: the ability of teams to take over all tasks of the software delivery life cycle, the autonomy of teams in decision-making processes, the implementation of a product owner for business-IT interactions within the team, and the use of a communication model for knowledge sharing and team learning. Ambler (2009) proposes a governance framework built on the lean principles that enable agility at scale. Wang *et al.* (2012) indicate that lean governance practices, such as aligning the team structure with the architecture, risk-based milestones and staged program delivery, address the inherent complexities in large or distributed teams. Nevertheless, no research has completely described the agile mechanisms within the ITG construct. Research that comes close to agile ITG is that of Luna *et al.* (2010). In their research, the authors present a new concept of agile ITG in which the principles, values and practices of the agile paradigm from software engineering are translated into the context of ITG. This thesis' qualitative study draws on the approach of Luna *et al.* (2010) to the definition of agile mechanisms in ITG because it focuses specifically on ITG and is the most comprehensive framework provided in the literature. These researchers define agile ITG as:

“the process of defining and implementing the IT infrastructure that will provide support to strategic business objectives of the organization, which is jointly owned by IT and the various business units, and [which is] instructed to direct all involved in obtaining competitive differential strategy [by incorporating] the values and principles of the Agile Manifesto” (Luna *et al.*, 2010, p. 327).

Hence, the authors suggest enhancing ITG mechanisms using the values and principles of the agile manifesto of software engineering introduced by Beck *et al.* (2001). They further argue that it is sufficient to adjust the focus of the existing traditional practices, such as COBIT and ITIL, to agree with the principles and values supported by the agile manifesto with the application of best practices adapted from agile software engineering. Madi *et al.* (2011) provide a list of values extracted from the agile manifesto. This list is based on the foundation of agile practices and principles and contains the following values: “1) Collaboration, 2) Communication, 3) Working software, 4) Flexibility, 5) Customer-centric, 6) Incremental, 7) Iterative, 8) Motivation, 9) Respect, 10) Trust, 11) Feedback, 12)

Speed, 13) Technical excellence, 14) Simplicity, 15) Self-organizing, and 16) Learning” (Madi *et al.*, 2011, p. 424). The manifesto and its values and principles represent the philosophy behind agile mechanisms that ideally should be present in all practices based on various agile methods (Fernandes and Almeida, 2010). Several agile mechanisms are available in agile practices and variations, such as Scrum, eXtreme Programming, behaviour-driven development, lean software development, Kanban, design thinking, feature-driven software development and dynamic systems development methods. Such practices focus on various aspects of agile mechanisms. With regard to the concept of Luna *et al.* (2010), implementing agile mechanisms by such agile practices can complement the agile principles within traditional ITG. Thus, agile mechanisms derived from implementing agile principles in the context of ITG can encompass variants of activities that determine lean team structures, short decision-making processes, fast information flows and communication efforts related to projects. In summary, agile ITG mechanisms can be understood as practices where the values of the agile manifesto are key elements to promote agility within an ITG framework. As the aim of ITG is to achieve strategic business/IT alignment, such agile principles within ITG mechanisms might help improve communication and collaboration and lead to both better alignment between business and IT and enhanced responsiveness to business transformation (Moore and Barnett, 2004; Horlach *et al.*, 2018b).

2.4.3 The notion of an ambidextrous ITG

The ability to align governance structures with the existing capabilities and environmental conditions is an important success factor for digital transformation, and the alignment procedures need to be agile. As Gersick (1991), Romanelli and Tushman (1994) and Greiner (1997) show, successful organizations alternate between two states in their organizational development. The first state is characterized by a phase of environmental stability, in which corporations strive for optimization within their existing business logic by focusing on minor incremental adjustments in operational efficiency and benefit from economies of scale (Gersick, 1991; Raisch and Birkinshaw, 2008; Tushman and O'Reilly, 1996). The second state is characterized by fast-changing and highly volatile environmental conditions in which major organizational adjustment is required to successfully manage change (Tushman *et al.*, 1986). This view of organizational development is referred to as the *punctuated equilibrium theory*. Depending on which state the organization is in, it should design adequate governance mechanisms to successfully deal with the specific challenges of each state (Dunphy and Stace, 1988). Thus, the distinction between these two states is important for

the design of an appropriate governance structure and the execution of measures and mechanisms (Gersick, 1991). Adequate governance structures are crucial for corporate success, especially when the economy, society, technology and regulations undergo fundamental and highly complex changes (Higgs and Rowland, 2005). The choice of adequate governance measures is also dependent on the status of the external environment and internal capabilities (Gersick, 1991).

One way for organizations to deal with these two types of states is by becoming *ambidextrous* (Tushman and O'Reilly, 1996), meaning that organizations have the ability “*to both explore and exploit – to compete in mature technologies and markets where efficiency, control, and incremental improvement are prized and to also compete in new technologies and markets where flexibility, autonomy, and experimentation are needed*” (O'Reilly and Tushman, 2013, p. 324). During the exploitation state, the organization focuses on activities to improve efficiency and reduce variance, while in the exploration state, they concentrate on discovery and innovation activities. In particular, incumbent organizations can benefit from taking an ambidextrous approach to organizational development (Markides, 2013). The challenge of becoming ambidextrous lies in an organization's ability to balance the two opposing states in its existing business activities to sufficiently monetize them while exploring new market opportunities to stay competitive in the future (March, 1991). Tushman and O'Reilly (1996) define organizational ambidexterity as a concept of structurally separated business units with distinct organizational responsibilities. However, Markides (2013) and Markides and Charitou (2004) criticize this view for not considering the positive impact of potential benefits from synergies within business units in its assumption of strict separation. Consequently, researchers have introduced ambidexterity models with less strict separation. This contextual dimension of ambidextrous organizations is, for instance, manifested in the dual operating system formulated by Kotter (2012). Mithas and Rust (2016) highlight the importance of the ambidexterity approach to IT by finding significant positive impacts of what they refer to as the “dual focus” of IT, i.e., strategies that involve using IT for both cost cutting and revenue generation. In addition, Markides and Charitou (2004) describe how corporations can develop and execute balanced strategies through dual strategies, pursuing two fundamentally different business models within the same market, and corporations with a hybrid strategy can address differentiation and cost advantages within the same business model. Traditional hierarchical governance structures alone are not able to cope with the increased speed of change (Haffke *et al.*, 2017a). As stated by Magnusson, ITG “*should simultaneously act to support digitalization and*

innovation as well as drive efficiency” (Magnusson *et al.*, 2017, p. 256). In other words, the governance concept for digital transformation needs to follow different management principles. While one mode represents traditional approaches to ITG, with an emphasis on safety and accuracy, the other mode emphasizes agility and speed by operating non-sequentially in multiple iterations (Haffke *et al.*, 2017a). Thus, traditional hierarchical governance structures should be complemented by network-like governance structures that can react quickly to changes in the organization’s environment. Although there are no clear guidelines for governance approaches to digital transformation in the literature, this lack has not inhibited practitioners from developing their own strategies, leading to a situation in which practice is leading research (Haffke *et al.*, 2016). Principally, this has resulted in corporations implementing additional governance mechanisms to foster digital transformation, including the establishment of cross-functional steering committees, digital leadership in individual business units and cross-functional innovation groups (Fitzgerald *et al.*, 2014) to foster agility within the corporation. Thus, agile mechanisms can be understood as the prerequisites for exploration on one side of the balancing act, while traditional ITG mechanisms are important antecedents for exploitation on the other side of the balancing act (Andersen *et al.*, 2017). As such, premised on the punctuated equilibrium theory, the governance of IT could address traditional as well as agile ITG mechanisms without significant disruption. Hence, based on the presented theoretical considerations this researcher argues that an effective ITG could leverage both traditional (as outlined in Table 2.2) and new agile ITG mechanisms, that needs to be examined first. This, however, is discussed in Chapter 4, which qualitatively explores ITG mechanisms that are implemented in corporations.

3 Research Methodology

This chapter discusses in detail the research and methodological approach used for this thesis based on the research objectives and research questions. Specifically, it explains why mixed methods research was considered appropriate for this study and highlights the various stages and steps that were followed within the process of the qualitative research, research model development and quantitative research.

3.1 Methodology rationale and research design

3.1.1 Mixed-methods approach

This thesis followed a mixed-methods approach to answer the stated RQs. Mixed-methods research has become an accepted research approach combining qualitative and quantitative models of research so that evidence may be mixed and knowledge may be increased more meaningfully than either model could achieve alone (Collis and Hussey, 2013; Punch, 2013). The adoption of mixed-methods research was mainly justified by the gaps in the extant literature and to a substantial extent reflected the practical problems in the field of agile ITG research that can be summarized as follows:

As highlighted in Section 1.2, although a considerable amount of empirical research has been conducted in the field of ITG, there is little quantitative evidence on the relationships among the elements of an effective ITG framework for digital transformation integrating agile aspects and how they relate to corporate performance. One factor that limits quantitative empirical research in this context is that there are no widespread accepted models that can measure an effective ITG framework for the digital age and can be used to compare corporations (see Section 1.2). This factor supported the need to conduct a qualitative analysis aimed at integrating the agile aspect within a traditional ITG framework and examining a governance concept suitable for digital transformation. Furthermore, the use of quantitative methods was supported by the need to test and validate governance-performance relationships to identify significant associations that may be useful in generating tools to guide ITG in effective activities within a corporation. Given the above considerations, a mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative and qualitative methods was most suitable for addressing the research objectives of this study and answering the research questions rather than applying a single method.

3.1.2 An exploratory sequential research design

From the various prototypes for mixed-methods designs² presented in the extant literature, the research process builds on the instrument development variant of the *exploratory sequential design* proposed by Creswell and Plano Clark (2007) as shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Exploratory sequential design: Instrument development model adopted from Creswell and Plano Clark, p. 76 (2007)

This approach can be adopted when a study is based on the premise that an exploration is needed for one of several reasons (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007), all of which applied to this project:

- Measures or instruments are not available, the variables are unknown, or there is no guiding framework or theory.
- It is best suited for exploring a phenomenon.
- It is particularly useful when a researcher needs to develop and test an instrument because one is not available or needs to identify important variables to study quantitatively when the variables are unknown.

The exploratory sequential model best suited this thesis' objectives, as explained in the following: With this design, the researcher first qualitatively explores the research topic with a few participants; this phase includes the stages "qualitative data collection", "qualitative data analysis" and "qualitative results" (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). In this research, the qualitative strand corresponded to the exploration of an effective ITG framework for digital transformation integrating agility and referred to research phase 2. The findings from this part then guided the development of the items and scales for the research model ("Develop instrument"), which was congruent with research phase 3. In investigating the presented research, phases 2 and 3 meet the first objective of this thesis. In the second phase of data collection, the research model was tested and validated, thus meeting the second objective of this study (research phase 4). The model included the stages "quantitative data collection", "quantitative data analysis" and "quantitative results". Therefore, in the process presented, the qualitative and quantitative methods is connected through the development of the instrument items and hypotheses formation for the research model.

² For a detailed overview of the various mixed-method designs please refer to Creswell and Plano Clark (2007, pp. 58–88).

There are different data collection methods the researcher can use to collect the required data. In this study, various techniques were used for data collection and analyses based on the mixed-methods approach. Table 3.1 lists the research techniques adopted in this thesis with a brief description of their characteristics. The overview is based on Qu and Dumay (2011), Collis and Hussey (2013) and Vázquez-Ramos *et al.* (2016) as well as Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2007), Arain *et al.* (2010) and Hair *et al.* (2016). The overall research design process of this thesis starting from the systematic literature review as research phase 1 (as already conducted in Chapter 2) is provided in Figure 3.2. It presents the research phases, data collection and data analysis techniques in relation to the RQs. However, the research phases 2 to 4 are based on the process of Creswell and Plano Clark (2007), as highlighted previously (see Figure 3.1). The detailed design of this exploratory sequential approach is presented in the following sections.

Table 3.1: Overview of research methods used

<i>Data collection techniques</i>		<i>Data analysis techniques</i>	
<i>Expert interviews (Semi-structured interviews)</i>	A conversation between the interviewer and another person (an expert) about a topic of interest, following to some degree a predetermined list of questions that can be modified based upon the interviewer's perception of what seems most suitable. It is a flexible data collection method since it allows the interviewer to modify the style, pace and order of the questions to evoke the fullest responses from the interviewees.	<i>Pilot study analysis</i>	It is a small study to help to design a further investigation in a research topic. The analysis can be referred as "proof of concept". It can help test study procedures or validate instruments.
		<i>Content analysis</i>	Provides knowledge and understanding of the phenomenon being studied by investigating the raw data through a systematic classification process of coding.
<i>Delphi method (Scale development)</i>	Used for scale development and is based on several sequential Delphi rounds, which allows judgements on a particular topic through a set of carefully designed sequential questionnaires of opinions derived from earlier responses. It usually contains between three and five rounds in which the development and administration of questionnaires are interconnected. The first and second round most likely use interviews with questions related to a broad problem or issue. During the subsequent rounds, the questionnaire asks the respondents to rank all items identified by the previous Delphi rounds.	<i>Delphi rounds analysis (Content analysis + scale rating)</i>	Delphi round analyses could take several forms, but one or two rounds are likely analysed using content analysis. During the further rounds, the respondents' rank-ordered items or Likert-scale ratings are used to establish priorities among items.
<i>Online surveys</i>	Research data are generated by asking questions through a questionnaire. This method is used to collect primary data from an original source and aims to generalize the results to a population. It provides answers to specific questions that can be analysed through statistical techniques and can often be generalized	<i>Multivariate analysis (PLS-SEM)</i>	Multivariate analysis involves the application of statistical methods that simultaneously analyse multiple variables based on a measurement model. This can be done through the PLS-SEM method, which is used to develop theories in exploratory research by focusing on explaining the variance in the dependent variables within a research model.

Figure 3.2: Research design process

3.2 Research phase 2 – Qualitative research design

3.2.1 Overview

To address the first objective of the thesis, namely, to conceptualize a framework to integrate the concept of agility into the traditional ITG framework, qualitative research was conducted. With this investigation, the second phase of this thesis addressed RQ2. In general, the qualitative investigation involved three main stages: qualitative data collection, qualitative data analysis and qualitative results (see Figure 3.3). However, while stage one contained a six-step approach, stage two contained five steps for data analysis before the results are presented in stage three. These stages and the activity steps are discussed in more detail in the following sections.

Figure 3.3: Qualitative research strategy

3.2.2 Qualitative data collection

Interviews are the most common qualitative research method for data collection in conducting exploratory research (Warren, 2001). In this thesis, interviews with expert practitioners were used as a data collection technique. Such interviews are a well-established method for exploratory research (Saunders *et al.*, 2016) and have become very popular as an efficient data collection technique to explore expert knowledge (Meuser and Nagel, 2009; Pfadenhauer, 2009). An expert can be defined as “*anyone who is responsible for and has privileged access to the knowledge of specific groups of people or decision-making processes*” (Littig, 2009, p. 100). In the context of ITG, executives, boards of directors as well as specialists who do not make high-level decisions at the top of a corporation have expert knowledge in the investigated area, which is the key reason that expert interviews were selected as a qualitative data collection technique.

The qualitative data collection stage followed a six-step process to systematically collect the data, which is outlined below and is based mainly on the approaches of Bortz and Döring (2009), Müller (2016) and Kuckartz *et al.* (2008):

- Step 1: Definition of the target population
- Step 2: Conduction of a pilot study
- Step 3: Identification of the sample
- Step 4: Development of an interview guideline and pre-test
- Step 5: Preparing and conducting the interviews
- Step 6: Transcribing recordings of the interviews

3.2.2.1 Definition of the target population

Any corporation from any industry needs a way to ensure that its IT functions support its business strategies and objectives. While small entities may adopt only essential ITG practices, larger and more regulated corporations need to set up a complete ITG program (Lindros, 2017). Therefore, promoting agility within ITG becomes more challenging with increasing corporate size. Consequently, *the target population of the research was executive management members, senior staff and specialists in governance and digital transformation projects working in corporations with 50 or more full-time employees*. A suitable set of experts with knowledge of ITG who can provide relevant insights about the general agile concept within ITG was expected to be found in corporations of various industries. However, for the sake of simplicity in order to reduce the data effort, a primary qualitative study with a focus on the banking industry in Germany, Switzerland and Austria was conducted. Nevertheless, to check the transferability of the results from an empirical point of view and to show the transferability of the agile aspect within the ITG concept across many industries, an additional small set of cross-industry qualitative interviews was conducted (secondary qualitative study). Regarding the primary qualitative study, the banking industry was appropriate for research on ITG in digital transformation for the following reasons: First, many banks are currently redesigning their governance frameworks and business models, which are not fundamentally different from bank to bank. Therefore, a focus on this industry allowed an investigation of a well-defined context under conditions that are comparable within the whole sample. Second, IT is a key way for banks facing strong competition to achieve both customer intimacy and operational excellence (Tallon, 2010). Third, business processes in banks either are run entirely by IT or rely on the interplay between the implemented IT, manual processes and the technical skills of employees to use all relevant system functionality effectively and efficiently in the business context (Schlosser *et al.*, 2015; Wagner *et al.*, 2014), which makes ITG crucial for banks in relation to IT investment decisions. Therefore, when studying the agile aspect within ITG, one can expect its effects to be detected most clearly in the banking industry sector.

3.2.2.2 Conducting a pilot study

To support the qualitative investigation (primary and secondary qualitative study), a pilot study was carried out first. The main purpose of the pilot study is fourfold: first, to check the practical relevance of the investigated topic; second, to obtain qualitative information that establishes the candidates' suitability and willingness to participate in the qualitative study (Collins *et al.*, 2006; Leech and Onwuegbuzie, 2007); third, to identify participants who best fit the expert status criterion to answer questions in the research area; and fourth, to assist in the development of an appropriate interview guideline for the qualitative research. To do so, a convenience sample of the target population was used to obtain basic data and trends regarding the qualitative investigation. Therefore, a number of executive contacts from the Reutlingen University database who contributed to earlier research projects were invited to participate in an interview session. The interviews were conducted using a semi-structured approach³ and the discussions were recorded. The guideline itself contained a small number of overarching, mainly open questions with the aim of identifying more specific questions that were expected to perform well in the main qualitative investigation. The guideline and the recordings served as a basis for the development of the main interview guideline as well as for the subsequent process of identifying the sample.

3.2.2.3 Identification of the sample

This step concerned identifying a representative sample for the qualitative investigation. Hence, a number of sub-steps were taken to identify an appropriate sample to be interviewed:

Sub-step 1: Construct a database with potential participants

Sub-step 2: Send a letter of solicitation

Sub-step 3: Select sample

Sub-step 1: Construct a database with potential participants: To first construct a database of potential financial institutions with participants who might be interviewed in the primary qualitative study, the websites of the national banks⁴ of Germany, Switzerland and Austria were consulted to obtain a list of bank offices and branch offices on the basis of licences granted. Then, based on these lists, a database of potential participants was created. To retrieve the contact details of bank experts, such as their email address, the corporations'

³ Cf. Appendix A: Interview guideline of the pilot study

⁴ National banks: Germany → www.bundesbank.de; Switzerland → www.snb.ch; Austria → www.oenb.at

websites were searched and social media profiles, such as LinkedIn⁵ and XING⁶, of the potential interviewees were explored to retrieve their professional background. However, in order to design a representative sample of the banking industry, a mix of the corresponding bank categories such as size of the banks, country, and focus of their IT strategy were taken account. Regarding the secondary qualitative study, several executive contacts from the Reutlingen University database who contributed to earlier research projects served as a basis database. To draw a representative sample, corporations from various industries were selected covering a broad range of different number of employees. This led to a mailing list of possible candidates that can be used as a basis to send letters of solicitation.

Sub-step 2: Send a letter of solicitation: A letter of solicitation⁷ was prepared to introduce the research initiative and to invite candidates to participate in the qualitative interviews. The letter comprised (1) an introduction detailing the purpose of the study, (2) an invitation to participate in a 20-minute interview and a description of the expected contribution of the interviewee and (3) an invitation to join a practice conference to discuss the results of the qualitative study. Next, the email addresses were used to contact potential interviewees. The candidates who answered the email and expressed their willingness and availability to participate in the qualitative studies served as the basis for selecting the sample.

Sub-step 3: Sample selection: As the objective of the expert interviews is to gather a thorough understanding of practically applied governance mechanisms for digital transformation, it was important to identify the managers who were mainly responsible for digital transformation for inclusion in the sample population. Therefore, a purposive sampling procedure (also known as judgment or selective sampling) was an appropriate method to identify participants because it concentrates on candidates with particular characteristics who are able to assist with the relevant research (Etikan, 2016). The following four judgment criteria were used to guide the decision for inclusion of email respondents in the sample population (Gläser and Laudel, 2010):

- Participants who have relevant information on the researched topic.
- Participants who are most likely to be able to provide precise information.
- Participants who are most likely ready to provide information.
- Participants who are available to participate in the study.

⁵ www.linkedin.com

⁶ www.xing.com

⁷ Cf. Appendix B: Letter of solicitation.

It is important to note at this stage that because of the exploratory character of this qualitative research, the purpose was to derive broadness rather than generalizability in its findings. For a qualitative investigation, it is preferable to study a few cases thoroughly to increase the explanatory power of the data rather than covering many cases with little depth (Dubois and Gadde, 2002). However, interviews and interpretation activities should continue until the “theoretical saturation” point is reached and the addition of new data can no longer be expected to contribute further themes in the explored categories (Glaser and Strauss, 1977). According to Marshall *et al.* (2013) data saturation in a phenomenological study is reached by completion of the thirtieth interview transcript. Taking this number as a rule of thumb, but to provide sufficient explanatory power in the data analysis, this thesis’ qualitative investigation conducted 41 qualitative interviews (33 interviews in the primary banking study and eight interviews in the secondary cross-industry study). However, during the data analysis the data saturation was reached after the nineteenth interview transcript.

3.2.2.4 Development of an interview guideline and pre-test

The most common type of interview in qualitative research is the semi-structured interview (Qu and Dumay, 2011). It is popular because of its flexibility in asking open-ended questions, which enables the researcher to explore issues that arise spontaneously (Doody and Noonan, 2013). In this thesis, semi-structured interviews were guided by the first guideline used in the pilot study, which was built by this thesis’ author and pre-tested by researchers from Reutlingen University. However, to pre-test the interview guideline for the primary qualitative study, workshops with researchers at Reutlingen University and with scholars at the University of St. Gallen were conducted to check whether the questions work as intended and are understood. In contrast to the first draft in the pilot study, the final version of the interview guideline for the main qualitative investigation contained more specific questions within the context of agile ITG and so a section in the final guideline specifically dealt with agile principles within ITG mechanisms to identify elements in this domain. The final questionnaire contained the four main parts (see Appendix C). The first part comprised of contextual questions that invite the respondents to describe contextual factors for their own organization (Liebold and Trinczek, 2009), which help elicit patterns for effective ITG mechanisms. The second part focused on effective ITG frameworks for digital transformation to uncover agile ITG mechanisms that complement the traditional elements of ITG. Part three specifically focused on agile aspects within governance frameworks to ask the interviewees about the application of agile mechanisms. The final part contained questions about leadership to discover new relational mechanisms.

3.2.2.5 Preparing and conducting the interviews

Interviews can be conducted face-to-face or via telephone. Face-to-face interviews have been the dominant interview technique in qualitative research, but in the last two decades, telephone interviewing has become more prevalent (Bortz and Döring, 2009; Christmann, 2009). While face-to-face interviews enable the interviewer to build a relationship with the expert and to better control the discussion, telephone interviews provide greater flexibility regarding the timing and duration of the call (Gläser and Laudel, 2010). In this thesis, telephone interviews were used because the interviewees are geographically separated. Therefore, the participants had to be contacted to arrange an appointment. As proposed by Arksey and Knight (1999), it is important to conduct the interviews in the interviewees' own language to avoid imposing any restriction through language and to allow the interviewees to communicate freely and confidently. Hence, the discussions were all held in German.

3.2.2.6 Recording and transcribing the interviews

The interviews were recorded after the executives committed to it in order to facilitate the subsequent transcription. Recordings were preferred because they were convenient and less disruptive than taking notes during the interview (Collis and Hussey, 2003). To systematically analyse the collected data, all recorded expert interviews were fully transcribed. Transcription is crucial for converting recorded interviews from the digital audio format to a text format so that the author can analyse the data (Kuckartz *et al.*, 2008).

3.2.3 Qualitative data analysis

To examine the narrative output, qualitative content analysis was performed. Content analysis is a technical tool for examining large amounts of (textual) data systematically and thus understanding the context (Krippendorff, 1980). It compresses text into content categories following rules of coding to examine the data thoroughly (Berelson, 1952). In doing so, coding must follow a structured process to examine the text sources systematically (Basit, 2003; Hickey and Kipping, 1996). For this reason, this thesis followed a process suggested by several authors, such as Hsieh and Shannon (2005), Kuckartz *et al.* (2008) and Mayring (2000). In general, the process to be followed contained the following coding steps:

- Step 1: Preparing and reading the text
- Step 2: Case-by-case evaluation and initial coding
- Step 3: Developing a system of categories and a coding scheme
- Step 4: Testing and extending the coding scheme
- Step 5: Coding the data and checking consistency

To support this coding process, the software MAXQDA (VERBI Software, 2017) was applied. It is a powerful tool for the analysis of text-based qualitative data that makes it possible to search, categorize, classify, code, evaluate and organize without losing the typical complexity of the data (Kuckartz *et al.*, 2008; Ohlbrecht, 2010). In the following sections, the steps are described in more detail.

3.2.3.1 Preparing and reading the text

The data source of the transcribed interviews had to be prepared for use with MAXQDA. This included checking the completeness of the transcripts, uploading the source texts into MAXQDA and preparing a work environment within this tool (Kuckartz *et al.*, 2008).

3.2.3.2 Case-by-case evaluation and initial coding

This step concerned reading the texts and making keynotes, which could represent a single theme or issue of relevance, case by case. In content analysis, this step is fundamental to unitize the texts before they can be coded in detail (Weber, 1990). Basically, a researcher looks primarily for the expressions of an idea by the initial coding of a single word, a phrase, a sentence, a paragraph or an entire document (Minichiello, 1990). Hence, with this step, an overarching category construction is preliminarily examined and may result in the identification of possible content categories into which material can be coded.

3.2.3.3 Developing a system of categories and a coding scheme

A system of categories and a coding scheme can be developed both inductively and deductively (Zhang and Wildemuth, 2009). In studies where no theories are available, coding categories need to be derived directly and inductively from the raw data (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005). By contrast, deductive category development uses existing theory or research to develop a system of categories and a coding scheme (Mayring, 2000). However, a researcher can also (deductively) generate an initial list of coding categories from a preliminary model or theory, which can be modified within the course of the analysis as new categories emerge inductively (Zhang and Wildemuth, 2009). In this thesis an initial list was first created based on existing studies and was then inductively enhanced with new categories that emerged from the data. As a result, at this stage, an initial coding scheme was developed that included categories derived from the literature as well as groupings resulting from the initial coding.

3.2.3.4 Testing and extending the coding scheme

To ensure the validity of the coding scheme early in the process, it was important to provide a definition of each category and to define a set of coding rules to be followed during the

coding process (Kuckartz *et al.*, 2008). The coding scheme then had to be tested in two to three samples to clarify the consistency of the category definitions. Two or more people coded the sample texts and compare the results. A doctoral student at Reutlingen University and another student from the University of St. Gallen supported this thesis' researcher in testing the initial coding scheme. If the level of consistency of the coding rules or the category definition was low, they had to be revised. Inconsistencies, doubts and problems concerning the definitions of the categories, coding rules or categorization of specific cases needed to be discussed and resolved within the research team (Zhang and Wildemuth, 2009). However, coding sample text, checking coding consistency and revising coding rules is an iterative process and should continue until sufficient coding consistency is achieved (Weber, 1990; Zhang and Wildemuth, 2009).

3.2.3.5 Coding the data material and checking consistency

The entire set of data material was coded in a team. Team coding is beneficial since it allows multiple perspectives to establish content validity and coding reliability (Jacoby and Siminoff, 2008). Several researchers advocate collaborative coding in teams to allow shared interpretation and understanding of the phenomenon being studied (Erickson and Stull, 1998; Guest and MacQueen, 2008; Schreier, 2012). In this study, the coding occurred in a group of three. The same two researchers from the previous step supported the primary researcher in coding the data material. This thesis' researcher was assigned the primary responsibility for creating, updating, revising and maintaining the master coding list for the group. The texts were divided among the team members and each member coded the texts individually and independently. As the coding process also included inductive analysis, new codes, categories and sub-categories could be added after the original consistency check. However, in order to avoid inter-coder inconsistencies, the team members met on a regular basis to continually recheck the categories and codes. In doing so, the researchers relied on intensive group discussion, coder adjudication and simple group consensus as an agreement goal instead of using minimal benchmarks calculated through quantitative measures (Harry *et al.*, 2005; Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009; Sandelowski and Barroso, 2007). However, once all transcripts were coded by the researchers and the data were organized in main categories and sub-categories, the data were evaluated in a category-based manner. In doing so, counting the number of times that a particular set of codes per category occurs represents an important measure for assessing the frequency of items or phenomena (Saldaña, 2013). Consequently, the number of codes per category can be quantitatively evaluated and qualitatively interpreted (Kuckartz *et al.*, 2008).

3.2.4 Qualitative results

The results from the content analysis are reported in the qualitative results stage. Evidence for the interpretation of the results is provided by showing codes and related examples and providing appropriate quotations from the interviews (Elo and Kyngäs, 2008; Graneheim and Lundman, 2004). To ensure the trustworthiness and quality of the content analysis, it is paramount to describe the analysis process and results in a comprehensive manner. (Baxter, 2008). As shown in Section 3.2, each stage of the qualitative analysis contained a precisely defined process, including detailed activity steps, to ensure trustworthiness during the content analysis process. However, in order to describe various aspects of trustworthiness, concepts such as credibility, dependability and transferability need to be used in qualitative research tradition (Guba, 1981; Patton, 1987; Zhang and Wildemuth, 2009). These concepts were collectively applied to assess the results as are presented in the following sub-sections.

3.2.4.1 Credibility

Credibility refers mainly to confidence in how well data and analysis address the intended focus (Graneheim and Lundman, 2004). Therefore great importance was taken to ensure that (a) the RQs of the qualitative research are clearly written; (b) the defined research methodology is appropriate for the RQs; (c) purposeful sampling strategies that are appropriate for expert interviews have been applied; (d) the data were collected and managed systematically; and (e) the data were analysed correctly (Baxter, 2008).

3.2.4.2 Dependability

Dependability refers to “*the coherence of the internal process and the way the researcher accounts for changing conditions in the phenomena*” (Bradley, 1993, p. 437). According to Kuckartz *et al.* (2008), the dependability of the data can be promoted by having multiple researchers independently code a set of data and then meet to come to a consensus about the emerging codes and categories. As described in Section 3.2.3, the coding process occurred in a team of three persons to assure the dependability of the data analysis.

3.2.4.3 Transferability

As stated by Shenton: “*In order to assess the extent to which findings may be true of people in other settings, similar projects employing the same methods but conducted in different environments could well be of great value*” (Shenton, 2004, p. 69). Drawing on this idea, this thesis conducted an additional complementary set of eight cross-industry qualitative interviews to check the transferability of the results from the primary banking study to other industries.

3.3 Research phase 3 – Development of the research model

3.3.1 Overview

Following the exploratory sequential design provided by Creswell and Plano Clark (2007), as presented in Figure 3.1, the qualitative and quantitative studies are connected through the development of the instrument items. Within this thesis, this step refers to research phase 3 (see Figure 3.2) and thus to the development of a research model based on the outcomes of the qualitative analysis. The analysis not only established the final model to be tested and validated in the quantitative phase but also developed items and scales that set the basis for the development of the quantitative survey instrument. To do so, a process for designing the research model was introduced in this phase, which is based on Hair *et al.* (2016) and Creswell (2012). The process, comprising three main stages, is presented in Figure 3.4. Each stage included activity steps to develop the constructs and its items. While stage one was concerned with the conceptualization of the research model and hypotheses development and includes a three-step process, stage two aimed to specify the measurement models by searching for items in the literature for existing constructs. Stage three contained a Delphi method approach based on a five-step process to develop new items and scales.

Figure 3.4: Research model development strategy

To set the basis for the quantitative analysis, structural equation modelling (SEM) was chosen as an appropriate approach to model conceptualization and operationalization. The rationale for choosing SEM as a suitable approach is discussed in Section 3.4.3.

3.3.2 Conceptualization and hypotheses development

As shown in Figure 3.4, Stage 1 concerned the conceptualization of the research model in order to provide the general or theoretical meaning of the constructs (Pett *et al.*, 2003). To develop the final research model, the following activity steps were introduced in this stage:

- Step 1: Specification of the structural model
- Step 2: Hypotheses formulation

3.3.2.1 Specification of the structural model

The first step in this stage was to determine the constructs and the relationships among them to specify the structural model (Hair *et al.*, 2016). In this thesis the development of the final structure of the research model follows an incremental development process that builds on Chapters 2 and 4. First, during the literature analysis (Chapter 2), the structure of the basic research model was conceptualized by the integration of the first examined building block within the ITG-corporate performance link. Then, in the same chapter, an initial research model derived from the literature was adopted based on this concept. Subsequently, the specification of the structural model continues with the expansion of the initial research model through the second building block, referring to the integration of the agile aspect into the governance concept examined in the qualitative study (Chapter 4). As a result, the final structure of the research model is determined in the development of the research model chapter (Chapter 5). The abstractions of the constructs and inter-relationships are then used as the basis for setting the hypotheses and specifying the measurement model.

3.3.2.2 Hypotheses formulation

In this step, the research hypotheses introduced in the literature analysis (Chapter 2) were refined based on the outcomes of the qualitative analysis chapter (Chapter 4). With respect to the third RQ, this stage set the basis for the quantitative investigation.

3.3.3 Specifying the measurement models

This step mainly concerned operationalizing the constructs of the research model. It aims to identify initial measurement items that may help to explain and specify the constructs provided in the research model. In this context, Churchill Jr (1979) has recommended a series of techniques for generating measurement items, including literature searches, surveys, focus groups and in-depth interviews. However, since the research model in this thesis partly builds on existing latent variables, this step primarily concentrated on a literature search for measurement items of already developed prevailing constructs. As such, it enables the specification of the measurement models of the constructs with a relatively high degree of content validity (Benson and Clark, 1982; Moore and Benbasat, 1991).

3.3.4 Scale development and analysis – Delphi method

This stage aimed to operationalize the agile aspect within the governance concept explored in the qualitative stage. Since this empirical study is one of the first to investigate the agile aspect in the ITG context, the measurement items of the agile construct had to be developed

from scratch through scale development approaches rather than being borrowed from the literature. Hence, to generate a set of valid and reliable measurement items for the agile ITG construct, a process was introduced in which a combination of steps from the scale development approach of Rauschnabel *et al.* (2016) and phases of Delphi research was used. The Delphi method approach was beneficial for operationalizing the agile governance construct in a manner analogous to that of de Haes and van Grembergen (2009), who identified several traditional ITG practices. As a result, five rounds were divided into an evaluation part and a rating part, setting the item development process (see Table 3.2).

Table 3.2: Item development process

	Rounds
Evaluation part	Round 1: Pilot study of ITG mechanisms – defining an initial list of items
	Round 2: Identifying agile ITG mechanisms – enhancing the list of items
	Round 3: Refining agile ITG mechanisms – completing the list of items
Rating part	Round 4: Quantitative screening – reducing the list of items
	Round 5: Quantitative screening – finalizing the list of items

In contrast to Section 3.3.3, which used a literature search to operationalize existing constructs, in the scale development interviews, focus groups and surveys were adopted to generate measurement items (Churchill Jr, 1979). The evaluation part contained three qualitative expert interview rounds with different pool members to create the item pool.

Round 1: Pilot study of ITG mechanisms – defining an initial list of items: This round reused the discussions from the pilot study from the prior qualitative investigation. In contrast to the qualitative examination, in which the pilot study was used primarily to ensure the suitability of the questions and to pre-test the interview guideline, in the present round of the item development process, the interview outcomes were used to define an initial list of items for the construct of interest. Hence, due to its exploratory character, the same guideline for data analysis that is presented in the qualitative study in Section 3.2 can be followed. Therefore, the responses to the first questionnaire⁸ were prepared for content analysis. Consequently, not only was the pilot study used to adjust the second questionnaire⁹, as presented in the previous section, but the results from the content analysis also led to an initial list of measurement items for the agile governance construct.

⁸ Cf. Appendix A: Interview guideline of the pilot study.

⁹ Cf. Appendix C: Interview guideline of the main qualitative investigation.

Round 2: Identifying agile ITG mechanisms – enhancing the list of items: The results from the exploratory examination (see Section 3.2) were reused as a basis for this round and the identified agile aspects were included in the item pool to enhance the list of items for the agile construct. As noted by Corti and Thompson (2012), the reuse of qualitative data (as intended in rounds 1 and 2) provides an opportunity to study the raw materials of recent research to gain new insights and avoid duplicating efforts in collecting and analysing data. Hence, with respect to the item development process, this round aimed to extend the item pool for the agile construct by reusing parts of the results from this thesis’s qualitative study.

Round 3: Refining agile ITG mechanisms – completing the list of items: In the third questionnaire¹⁰, the questions were adjusted with the analysis output from the previous two phases by focusing on more specific themes in the context of the agile governance construct. Hence, this round conducted an additional qualitative study to refine and complete the list of items. In doing so, it generally followed the same process presented in Section 3.2. Moreover, this round included a focus group session with the participants to discuss the outcomes. In turn, the results of this round led to extensive insight into the measurement items of the construct of interest, which set the basis for the next two rounds.

As proposed by Rossiter (2002), after defining an item pool, the next step is to reduce the number of items. Such a reduction might lead to a core collection of items that can be applied in the following quantitative research. Therefore, the rating part consisted of two rounds of quantitative surveys, which are presented in the following explanations.

Rounds 4 and 5: Quantitative screening – reducing and finalizing the list of items: These two rounds identified potential effective mechanisms by quantitatively screening the previously collected items with a survey (see Appendix E). Hence, based on the item pool and the arguments developed during the previous rounds, the items were presented in the questionnaire for the final two rounds. Then, the quantitative screening rounds were conducted with two different panel members who are considered experts in the research topic investigated. Similar to the research of de Haes and van Grembergen (2009), respondents in both rounds were asked to rate the items on a five-point Likert scale to recognize the preliminary mechanisms among the items. For an item to be considered in the final pool, the average score per item was used. If the average score was above a given threshold, the item was included in the final pool. According to the evaluations, the items were then selected for the quantitative study and represented the final measurement items for the agile construct.

¹⁰ Cf. Appendix D: Interview guideline for refining the agile ITG items.

3.4 Research phase 4 – Quantitative research design

3.4.1 Overview

After defining the measurement instruments of the constructs in the research model, the quantitative investigation concerned the study and validation of the emergent theory resulting from the qualitative investigation. Hence, with respect to this thesis' second research objective, the quantitative research aimed to test a conceptual model for an effective ITG framework for digital transformation and addressed RQ3. The quantitative investigation involved three main stages: quantitative data collection, quantitative data analysis and quantitative results, which were applied as a quantitative research strategy for this thesis (see Figure 3.5). However, each of the presented stages included the following activity steps. While stage one contained a four-step approach, stage two used the partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) method for data analysis before presenting the results in stage three. The stages are discussed in more detail in the following sub-sections.

Figure 3.5: Quantitative research strategy

3.4.2 Quantitative data collection

The objective of the quantitative research for this thesis was to test theories on cause-and-effect relationships derived from theory and the qualitative exploratory study. Standardized written surveys are widely accepted in the social sciences as the most suitable and most applied instrument to achieve this objective (Buckingham and Saunders, 2004; Töpfer, 2010). In this thesis, an online survey was used to collect because it allows responses to be obtained more quickly and at lower cost than with telephone-based or personal surveys, (Bortz and Döring, 2009; Schumann, 2006). Moreover, online surveys offer advantages when the sample is fairly large and geographically widely distributed (Sue and Ritter, 2007). When the target group members have access to the internet, they can easily be reached by email and can connect to the survey since it is available online (Creswell, 2012). For that reason, the quantitative data collection stage followed a four-step process to systematically collect the data and is based mainly on the approach of Bortz and Döring (2009):

Step 1: Development of the online questionnaire

Step 2: Pre-testing and optimization

Step 3: Identification of the sample

Step 4: Survey launch and data collection

3.4.2.1 Development of the online questionnaire

Surveys typically use a questionnaire that may contain structured or unstructured questions (Creswell, 2012). For this thesis, structured (i.e., closed-ended) questions with fixed alternatives were more interesting due to the possibilities for statistical evaluation. However, the questionnaire must be designed carefully to avoid potential biases in the survey method that may result from the sample frame (e.g., non-representativeness, under-coverage), the responses (e.g., non-response, voluntariness, social desirability, cognitive consistency), the context (interpretation of the questions) and the measurement (e.g., leading questions, insensitive measures, ambiguity) (Hartman *et al.*, 2002; Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). To do so, a clearly structured comprehensive questionnaire was established for this thesis' quantitative strand that took account of the aforementioned points. The questionnaire is presented in Appendix F. In general, the design consisted of eight sections. Section 1 was an introduction that present the research topic, provides information about the questions and assures the respondents of anonymity. Section 2 embraced a screen-out procedure. Here, respondents were asked to indicate whether they have personnel responsibility in their current position. If they answer "Yes", they were redirected to the complete questionnaire. If they answer "No", they were thanked for their efforts and were then eliminated from the analysis. In Sections 3 and 4, the demographic information of the participant (job position and country) and of the corporation (number of employees and industry type) was requested. The main part of the questionnaire, however, was represented by Sections 5 to 8. Each section was dedicated to a construct of interest in the research model and contained a number of items operationalized on a 7-point Likert scale from "1=strongly disagree" to "7=strongly agree". In more detail, Section 5 included items about traditional ITG mechanisms derived from the academic literature. Section 6, on the other hand, provided indicators of agile ITG mechanisms that were developed through a scale development process in research phase 3. In Section 7, the construct "Business/IT Alignment" was measured through indicators borrowed from the literature. Finally, "Corporate Performance" was operationalized in Section 8. The corresponding items were also retrieved from research studies. At the end of the survey, the participants were thanked for their participation.

3.4.2.2 Pre-testing and optimization

Survey biases were taken into consideration in this research, both a priori in the survey design and a posteriori by testing the questionnaire. After the questions had been developed, the questionnaire had to be pre-tested to identify potential issues with the wording, question order, visual design and navigation of the survey instrument (Creswell, 2012; Dillman *et al.*, 2009), as it was critical to assess how well a questionnaire performs under actual data collection conditions (Churchill, 1999; Collins, 2003). Based on the feedback of the pre-testers, the survey was modified and optimized to reflect those concerns and re-tested by a second group of pre-testers. (Collins, 2003; Creswell, 2012).

3.4.2.3 Identification of the sample

As pointed out in Section 3.2.2.1, the target population was individuals experienced in ITG for digital transformation working in corporations with 50 or more full-time employees. As a complete list of such corporations cannot be obtained, a nationally representative list of corporations was drawn from the database of Consumerfieldwork GmbH¹¹, an international online market research corporation with over 45,000 potential respondents across Europe. The database provider focuses on online surveys for research purposes and uses established procedures for ensuring data quality, such as identifying careless responders (Sonntag *et al.*, 2018) and for recruiting survey participants. Such online databases can be used with confidence for exploratory studies or experimental tests (Bethlehem and Stoop, 2007; Loosveldt and Sonck, 2008; Taylor, 2005). However, to obtain a representative online sample from the database, the same characteristics for appropriate participants were applied as those stated in Sub-step 3 of Section 3.2.2.3 for the qualitative part. Therefore, several potential executives from the database who met the specified judgment criteria (Section 3.2.2.3) were randomly contacted by email and asked to participate in the quantitative study. However, in contrast to the qualitative study, the quantitative enquiry was contingent on generalizability. Therefore, it was necessary to ensure that the conditions for data gathering was theoretically appropriate and that the sample size provided sufficient statistical power. By following the recommendations Cohen (1992), for this thesis' research model a minimum sample size of 37 observations would be needed to achieve a statistical power of 80% for detecting R^2 values of at least 0.25 (with a 5% probability error), when using PLS-SEM method to analyse the data. Nevertheless, for this thesis' quantitative study, a data set of 400 surveys supported the validity and predictive power of all constructs of the research model.

¹¹ www.consumerfieldwork.de

3.4.2.4 Survey launch and data collection

When conducting surveys, several challenges exist. A general problem is a low response rate. Hence, to obtain a high participation rate, a tailored design was used that follows the social exchange theory. In such an approach, surveys are viewed as a means of social exchange that is facilitated when (1) rewards are perceived as high, (2) costs are perceived as low and (3) trust is established (Dillman *et al.*, 2009). These guidelines were incorporated into this thesis' quantitative study to increase response rates and to avoid non-response error.

3.4.3 Quantitative data analysis

3.4.3.1 Structural equation modelling (SEM)

SEM¹² was chosen as the most appropriate statistical approach to facilitate the analysis of the cause-and-effect relations between the constructs (Hair *et al.*, 2016). SEM methods belong to the class of second-generation multivariate analysis techniques and have been widely established in behavioural social science research for the causal modelling and measurement of multiple measures of proposed data constructs (Hair *et al.*, 2016). The SEM technique has the advantage of supporting latent (unobservable) variables (Urbach and Ahlemann, 2010). One approach to measuring latent variables is to approximate them using multiple manifest variables, called manifests, items or indicators, as proxies (Hair *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, SEM is a class of multivariate techniques that combines aspects of factor analysis and regression, enabling the researcher to simultaneously examine relationships among measured variables and latent variables as well as between latent variables (Hair *et al.*, 2016) and to account for measurement errors in observable variables (Chin, 1998). In this thesis, not all variables in the research model (e.g., the dimensions within the governance construct) can be directly observed, but they can be measured via several manifest variables. In particular, the items explored in the qualitative research and the instrument development process can be simultaneously validated through SEM procedures. Moreover, due to the increasing availability of software packages with user-friendly interfaces to perform SEM, this powerful statistical modelling technique has become “*one of the most popular statistical methodologies available to quantitative social scientists*” (Kaplan, 2000, p. 6). Therefore, based on its power to deal with latent variables and simultaneously provide path modelling and factor analyses, SEM was selected as the most applicable statistical method to investigate this thesis' research model.

¹² For basic SEM concepts and modeling guidelines readers of this thesis are forwarded to the book of Hair *et al.* (2016, pp. 11–14).

3.4.3.2 PLS-SEM approach

There are two different SEM approaches to data analysis: covariance-based SEM (CB-SEM) and partial least square SEM (PLS-SEM) (Jöreskog and Wold, 1982)¹³. However, PLS-SEM was selected as the most appropriate SEM approach for this thesis' quantitative research part. This is based on the following considerations:

- *Research type (exploratory research)*: According Hair *et al.* (2016) the PLS-SEM approach is predominantly used in exploratory research; i.e. in case there is no or little prior knowledge on how the variables are related. In contrast, CB-SEM is primarily applied to test existing theories. Previous studies have operationalized some relevant variables as constructs, mainly focusing on traditional ITG elements. However, in this thesis, the agile aspect represents an extension of the previously empirically validated concepts and thus lacks the empirical evidence and strong theoretical foundations required for CB-SEM. Hence, the need to establish some new constructs (i.e., agile aspects) point to the use of PLS-SEM as an exploratory method.
- *Formative measurement*: The structural equation model and the underlying hypotheses to be tested are developed in Chapter 5, which points towards the necessity of integrating formative measures for the constructs of interest. In formative measurement models the arrows are directed from the indicator variables towards the construct (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001). In other words, the direction of causality is from the indicators to the construct. Such models can be more suitably implemented by PLS-SEM (Hair *et al.*, 2011), and therefore require the use of the PLS-SEM approach.
- *Model complexity*: This thesis requires a large number of indicators for the constructs to be validated. For this reason, the measurement models include both first-order and second-order constructs. Such models are also referred to as higher-order models or hierarchical component models (HCMs). They encompass two layers in which the first-order component (also referred to as a lower-order component (LOC)) might form the more abstract second-order component (also called a higher-order component (HOC)) (Ringle *et al.*, 2012; Wetzels *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, mediation effects needed to be analysed in the structural model. The PLS-SEM approach can handle such complex models better than CB-SEM. Therefore, based on these aspects, PLS-SEM is the technique of choice.

¹³ For a more detailed discussion of the differences between CB-SEM and PLS-SEM, readers of this thesis are forwarded to the works of Hair *et al.* (2016) and Gefen *et al.* (2011) for a more inclusive debate.

3.5 Ethical considerations

To be compliant with ethical principles this thesis' researcher followed the process of Reutlingen University which has adopted rules to ensure good scientific practice and has obliged its scientists to comply with them.¹⁴ Reutlingen University has furthermore committed itself through the collaboration agreement of September 1st, 2014 to design the rules in such a way that they are in line with the regulations with regard to the requirements for research programs at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Contacts within the meaning of these rules are confidants (called Senate Officers) appointed by the Senate at Reutlingen University to provide advice on research ethics.¹⁵ In general, the process at the Reutlingen University for adhering to ethical principles is defined as follows: Initially, the researcher responsible for the project has the duty to assess whether the planned research complies with legal regulations, self-regulation measures and ethical principles. To be aware about ethical principles, this thesis' researcher took part in several courses provided by Reutlingen University where the relevant ethical questions surrounding research were addressed. Second, the respective superior persons are responsible for activities that are subject to their directives. They are also obliged to inform their doctoral students they supervise about any existing research risks and the individual ethical responsibilities involved. During this research, the researcher was in close contact with his supervisory team¹⁶ discussing potential ethical issues. Furthermore, the research plan for this project was formally checked for compliance with the ethical standards of Reutlingen University prior to the interview sessions starting.¹⁷ Third, if there are any potential legal violations or any ethical concerns it should be reported to the responsible persons who need to take the necessary steps. Furthermore, Reutlingen University is responsible for alerting UWS to any concerns regarding the performance quality of research students or ethical issues on the collaborative programme during their study at Reutlingen University as soon as they arise. However, Reutlingen University raised no issues with the research as the ethical principles were strictly followed by the researcher and continuously monitored by the supervisory team. A final review by the research commission of the Herman Hollerith Center at Reutlingen University confirmed that this research meets the requirements of the ethical

¹⁴ See https://www.hhz.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Hermann_Hollerith_Zentrum/Forschung/Ethik_Kodex.pdf

¹⁵ See <https://www.reutlingen-university.de/en/our-profile/committees/senate/senate-officers/>

¹⁶ The supervisory team included experienced academic staff from both UWS and Hochschule Reutlingen.

¹⁷ Cf. Appendix G: Ethical approval

codex for researchers and research projects at Reutlingen University.¹⁸ The process for ethics was discussed at the transfer event and the assessor from the University of the West of Scotland accepted the proposed ethical approach and gave approval for the researcher to transfer from MPhil/PhD to PhD.

In this thesis the ethical considerations were mainly related to the information provided by the corporations in both the qualitative and the quantitative investigation. The confidentiality of the data and the anonymity of the participants were carefully protected in both studies according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as highlighted in the privacy policy¹⁹ of Reutlingen University. First, the participants in the interviews and in the survey voluntarily participated in this research. However, for initial contact, public databases as well as database of Reutlingen University with double opt-in consent was used to contact potential participants for the qualitative research. Then, for the telephone interviews, the participants were contacted in advance and the interviews were performed only after they agreed to participate. Moreover, all participants accepted that the discussions would be recorded. The interviewees were assured that the recorded interviews would be deleted after the end of the research phase. In terms of the quantitative survey, the researcher used the database of the market research corporation based in Germany for identifying the sample. All respondents agreed to the terms and conditions of the market research corporation before participating in the survey. Second, the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were protected in this research. Thus, no corporate names or participant names are revealed. Instead, pseudonyms and general position names are used in the descriptions that to prevent the identification of a participant or a corporation.

¹⁸ Cf. Appendix H: Ethical evaluation

¹⁹ <https://www.reutlingen-university.de/en/footer/data-protection/>

4 Qualitative Research

In this chapter, the findings of the qualitative study are outlined. The investigation primarily intends to answer the second research question and refers to research phase two. In doing so, this chapter develops the second building block for the research model by integrating the agile aspect into the governance construct. The chapter begins with an introduction section to provide the general idea behind the qualitative examination. Then, it proceeds with the data collection and data analysis process, as described in the methodology chapter. Finally, the qualitative results are presented.

4.1 Introduction

As highlighted at the beginning of this thesis, due to significant advancements in digital innovations, corporations find themselves competing in increasingly rapidly changing digital business environments (Henfridsson and Yoo, 2014; Leonhardt *et al.*, 2018). As such, the new enterprise logic of IT business is based on developing the agility and flexibility to identify and respond to existing and emerging demands in an integrated and proactive manner (Haffke *et al.*, 2017b). The challenge for ITG is then “*to simultaneously perform and transform IT in order to meet the present and future demands of the business in a satisfying manner*” (Peterson, 2004b, p. 53). As pointed out by Peterson (2004b), in general, traditional ITG relies on the hierarchy (or vertical coordination) and standardization and provide “command-and-control” structures that are pushed to their limits when innovations are introduced (Haffke *et al.*, 2017a). For this reason, vertical coordination and standardization provide only limited coordination capability in complex and uncertain environments (Daft, 1998; Galbraith, 1994; Peterson, 2004b). For corporations to compete in contemporary hyper-competitive environments, horizontal relationships and lateral coordination as a strategic organizational approach are needed (Galbraith, 1994; Mintzberg, 1979; Peterson, 2004a). Therefore, the emerging ITG paradigm should provide collaborative network structures in which communication is more likely to be lateral and task definitions more fluid and flexible (Yang and Liu, 2012) than in the traditional approach. In summary, the digital transformation era calls for new designs of effective governance collaborative structures and flexible mechanisms to successfully develop and introduce the new digital offerings that are needed (Leonhardt *et al.*, 2018; Nambisan *et al.*, 2017) and to provide “command-and-control” structures to govern IT. In this way, the agile aspect within the

governance concept may become a key element for coping with the challenges of the digital age. Agile governance is one of the latest branches of governance research that has recently emerged. As highlighted in Section 2.4.2, to date the broad scientific community has not analysed the effect of agile mechanisms on ITG (Aguillar *et al.*, 2017; Luna *et al.*, 2010). However, research interest in this topic is growing (Cheng *et al.*, 2009; Zimmer *et al.*, 2012). Current research offers scant insights into proper agile governance mechanics on a holistic level. Hence, a more detailed analysis of agile mechanisms within ITG is required. This thesis' qualitative research aims to investigate the agile aspects of effective ITG in the current dynamic world and this thesis's second RQ is stated as follows:

RQ2: *How is the concept of an effective ITG framework changing with respect to the demand for agility in corporations?*

To answer RQ2, several traditional and agile aspects of governance mechanisms gleaned from qualitative interviews in the banking industry as well as cross-industry interviews were analysed. In doing so, major patterns for ITG mechanisms in the digital world were elicited. The strategies used to implement agile ITG can be grouped under the same general dimensions as in the conventional ITG literature. Many studies, such as those of Ajayi and Hussin (2016), Dahlberg and Helin (2017) and Silva *et al.* (2018) use this type of framework to structure ITG mechanisms. It furthermore may enable the comparison of traditional and agile mechanisms and the derivation of patterns for an effective an agile ITG framework. Such patterns help explain “real-world” problems because they capture and allow the reuse of experiences for best practices in a specific professional domain (Schadewitz and Jachna, 2007). Thus, the contributions of this qualitative investigation are twofold. First, the study reveals agile ITG mechanisms that complement the traditional elements of ITG; second, it elicits patterns for an ITG framework for digital transformation.

4.2 Qualitative data collection

Following the methodology for this thesis' qualitative investigation outlined in sub-Section 3.2.2, the process of the qualitative study starts with the identification of the target population to support this qualitative study in answering RQ2.

4.2.1 Definition of the target population

As mentioned in the methodology chapter, the target population of the research is executive managers, senior staff and specialists in governance and digital transformation projects

working in corporations with 50 or more full-time employees. A suitable set of experts connected with ITG knowledge and digital transformation can be found in the banking sector as well as in cross-industries in Germany, Switzerland and Austria. As also highlighted in Section 3.2.2, a primary investigation in the banking industry was appropriate because financial institutions rely on services and processes driven by IT and ITG is therefore likely to play an important role.

4.2.2 Conducting a pilot study

Before proceeding with the sampling process, a pilot study²⁰ was conducted to identify participants who fit the expert status to answer questions in the context of ITG for digital transformation. Five bank executives in Germany and Switzerland were invited to participate in an interview. However, some of these people forwarded the invitation to employees at the senior manager level who were responsible for digital transformation and had decision-making authority on digital transformation projects and so some staff who were lower in the hierarchy were also included. The pilot study gave the researcher an idea of the feasibility of the process, resources and management in terms of how the full-scale study was planned and assisted the researcher in developing more specific questions for the interview guideline for the main qualitative analysis (see Section 4.2.4). All participants in the pilot study highlighted the relevance of the topic investigated and confirmed the need for further research in integrating the agile aspect into ITG.

4.2.3 Identification of the sample

Sub-step 1: Construct a database with potential participants: To prepare for the sample selection, a contact database was created. Because the interviews would be conducted in German, only German-speaking people who were accessible were of interest.

The email list was created, following the process described in Section 3.2.2 and the final database constructed consisted of contact information for 1805 potential interview participants.

Sub-step 2: Send a letter of solicitation: Next, 1805 emails were sent to the potential candidates to introduce the research project through a letter of solicitation (see Appendix B). The messages were sent by the author's supervisor, as the position of a professor was expected to result in a higher response rate than that of a PhD student. However, not all emails reached the recipients owing to incorrect email addresses or closed accounts. Finally,

²⁰ The detailed findings of the pilot study will furthermore be used in Chapter 5 when the agile items are developed.

this step led to initial contact with 53 bank candidates who were willing to participate in the qualitative study, setting the basis for the purposive sample selection.

Sub-step 3: Sample selection: In this step, experts in ITG for digital transformation were identified following the sample suggestion of Gläser and Laudel (2010) discussed in sub-Section 3.2.2. Hence, the selection of the participants depended largely on their role in the organization in relation to ITG for digital transformation, their ability to provide precise information in this context, and their availability for the interview. This step resulted in a final sample size of 33 executive participants from banks in Germany, Switzerland and Austria. Table 4.1 presents an overview of the corporations, the positions of the interviewees, the countries and the number of employees in the organizations. The names of the banks and the interviewees are anonymous; thus, in this qualitative study, the corporations are referred to as “Bank 1” through “Bank 33”.

All participants in the sample held executive or senior managerial positions with the authority to make decisions and define digital transformation projects. As shown in Table 4.1, the majority of the interviewees were top managers – 23 were C-level personnel, directors or members of executive boards. Ten participants held a senior management position such as head of a department responsible for digital transformation initiatives. One may argue that this sampling method is biased but, from the perspective of the researcher, these were the participants with the relevant roles, skills and knowledge who could contribute rich data to the research.

Table 4.1: Overview of the sample selected

Bank	Position of Interviewee	Country	Empl oyees	Bank	Position of Interviewee	Country	Empl oyees
Bank 1	CIO	Switzerland	1200	Bank 18	COO/CIO	Switzerland	173
Bank 2	Member of the Executive Board	Germany	67	Bank 19	CEO	Germany	293
Bank 3	CEO/CIO	Switzerland	245	Bank 20	CEO	Switzerland	1400
Bank 4	Member of the Executive Board	Germany	256	Bank 21	CDO	Germany	99740
Bank 5	Head of Innovation Lab	Switzerland	892	Bank 22	Head of Digitalization	Austria	2974
Bank 6	CEO	Germany	494	Bank 23	Head of IT	Switzerland	230
Bank 7	Member of the Executive Board	Germany	8395	Bank 24	Head of Digital Banking	Austria	50000
Bank 8	COO	Switzerland	788	Bank 25	CEO	Switzerland	56
Bank 9	Head of Digitalization	Germany	50	Bank 26	COO	Austria	12471
Bank 10	COO	Germany	258	Bank 27	CEO/COO	Austria	352
Bank 11	Member of the Executive Board	Germany	80	Bank 28	CFO	Switzerland	36
Bank 12	CEO	Switzerland	455	Bank 29	Head of Private Banking	Germany	150
Bank 13	Managing Director	Switzerland	6026	Bank 30	Head of IT	Austria	893
Bank 14	Head of General Office	Austria	2380	Bank 31	CEO	Switzerland	1331
Bank 15	CEO	Germany	366	Bank 32	CFO	Switzerland	550
Bank 16	Member of the Executive Board	Switzerland	56	Bank 33	Head of Application Mgmt.	Austria	729
Bank 17	Head of Application Mgmt.	Switzerland	280				

4.2.4 Development of an interview guideline and pre-test

This step entailed the development of a semi-structured questionnaire to provide an interview guideline. The first semi-structured interview guideline²¹ for the pilot study was established and tested in advance and served as a basis for the development of the questionnaire. The discussion of the transcripts obtained during the pilot phase then led to adjustments of the second guideline for the questionnaire used in this qualitative study²². Some questions were rephrased or sequentially realigned and new questions were added. Then, workshops with researchers at Reutlingen University as well as scholars at the University of St. Gallen were conducted to check that the questions worked as intended and were understood and to pre-test the guideline. In contrast to the first draft (in the pilot study), the second interview guideline contained more specific questions within the context of agile ITG. Thus, a section of the final questionnaire specifically dealt with agile principles within ITG mechanisms to identify elements in this domain.

4.2.5 Preparing and conducting the interviews

Following the methodology presented in Section 3.4.2, telephone interviews were chosen as the interview technique. To arrange an appointment for the discussion, the participants were contacted by an email that proposed several appointment dates for the interview session. Before starting the interviews, the two researchers prepared by rehearsing the interviews, briefing each other and ensuring that all the necessary equipment, such as a recorder, microphone, additional batteries, were ready. Furthermore, the interview guideline developed in the previous step was provided to the experts several days before the interview to allow the participants to become familiar with the topic.

The participants were also asked whether they agreed to the recording of the discussions while being assured that the interviews would remain anonymous, and the recordings would be deleted after the research was completed. All interviewees agreed to the digital recording of the discussion. Then, after a short briefing, the core information gathering started according to the guideline mentioned in the previous step. Internal comments on the qualitative interview guideline served as follow-up questions to ask the participants for more details on a mentioned topic if anything was unclear (see Appendix C)²³. Each interview

²¹ Cf. Appendix A: Interview guideline of the pilot study.

²² Cf. Appendix C: Interview guideline of the main qualitative investigation.

²³ The internal comments on the qualitative questionnaire, as presented in Appendix C, were not provided to the interviewees and served as an additional guideline for the interviewers only.

session took approximately 30 minutes. At the end of the discussion, the expert was thanked for his or her time and contribution, the interview documentation process was explained, and the respondent was offered an anonymized summary of all the interviews. Furthermore, the respondent was invited to a practice conference organized by Reutlingen University in which parts of the results would be presented. This allowed the author to maintain the contact for the purpose of future research.

Table 4.2: Interview schedule

Bank	Position of Interviewee	Conducted in	Bank	Position of Interviewee	Conducted in
Bank 1	CIO	April 2017	Bank 18	COO/CIO	April 2017
Bank 2	Member of the Executive Board	April 2017	Bank 19	CEO	May 2017
Bank 3	CEO/CIO	April 2017	Bank 20	CEO	May 2017
Bank 4	Member of the Executive Board	April 2017	Bank 21	CDO	May 2017
Bank 5	Head of Innovation Lab	May 2017	Bank 22	Head of Digitalization	April 2017
Bank 6	CEO	April 2017	Bank 23	Head of IT	May 2017
Bank 7	Member of the Executive Board	April 2017	Bank 24	Head of Digital Banking	April 2017
Bank 8	COO	April 2017	Bank 25	CEO	May 2017
Bank 9	Head of Digitalization	May 2017	Bank 26	COO	May 2017
Bank 10	COO	April 2017	Bank 27	CEO/COO	April 2017
Bank 11	Member of the Executive Board	May 2017	Bank 28	CFO	April 2017
Bank 12	CEO	May 2017	Bank 29	Head of Private Banking	May 2017
Bank 13	Managing Director	April 2017	Bank 30	Head of IT	May 2017
Bank 14	Head of General Office	April 2017	Bank 31	CEO	May 2017
Bank 15	CEO	April 2017	Bank 32	CFO	May 2017
Bank 16	Member of the Executive Board	April 2017	Bank 33	Head of Application Mgmt.	May 2017
Bank 17	Head of Application Mgmt.	May 2017			April 2017

4.2.6 Recording and transcribing the interviews

The interviews were recorded using digital voice recording on the computer. Each interview recording was between 30 and 35 minutes, leading to a total of 990 to 1155 minutes of data to be transcribed and then analysed. After all 33 interviews were conducted, the recorded digital voice files were first labelled “Bank 1” to “Bank 33” and then emailed to a professional transcription service specializing in academic transcription services. Each interview was transcribed by the service using the transcription rules of Kuckartz *et al.* (2008) and the transcripts were then emailed back to the researcher. To ensure accuracy and completeness, each transcription was checked by simultaneously listening to the interviews and reading the transcribed texts. As a consequence, some parts of the transcriptions were adjusted. The transcription process created a broad data set in text format for data analysis.^{24,25}

²⁴ See Appendix I to Appendix M

²⁵ Note: The transcripts were analysed in German. However, 5 interview transcripts translated into English are provided (see Appendix I to Appendix M) in order to provide the readers of this thesis with examples of the interview discussions.

4.3 Qualitative data analysis

The transcribed source texts from the previous step enabled the analysis of the data set. To support the encoding of the data, the analysis software MAXQDA²⁶ was used. However, before starting the actual coding process, it was important to first become familiar with the software and to prepare a work environment within this tool.

4.3.1 Preparation

The transcribed texts were imported into MAXQDA and then checked for completeness. A MAXQDA-PROJECT²⁷ had to be created before the data files could be imported. In doing so, it was important to organize the data in such a manner that each individual interview transcript was imported separately, leading to 33 MAXQDA-DOCUMENTS within the MAXQDA-PROJECT instead of having all the interview transcripts in one MAXQDA-DOCUMENT (Woolf and Silver, 2017). This way of organizing the data allowed the researcher to make comparisons between the interviewed experts by using several DOCUMENT-level tools to derive patterns from each interviewee's bank.

4.3.2 Case-by-case evaluation and initial coding

Once the transcripts were added to a MAXQDA-PROJECT, the DOCUMENTS were explored case by case, as proposed by Kuckartz *et al.* (2008) and Woolf and Silver (2017). In the most general sense, the researcher looked for what was in the data prior to identifying and conceptualizing text segments. Therefore, each text was read and instantaneously coloured to highlight parts that could be important during the coding process. This gave the researcher a case-by-case summary of each bank that allowed him to reflect deeply on the contents of the data and to begin taking ownership of them (Saldaña, 2013). In addition, possible or evolving categories were recognized within the data and text parts were instantaneously coded. As a result, this initial coding step served as an optimal basis for the development of a coding scheme and the discussion of the further evaluation.

4.3.3 Development of a system of categories and a coding scheme

As pointed out in the methodology chapter (see Section 3.2.3.3), one part of the initial list of coding categories was derived from the literature and referred to traditional ITG

²⁶ Detailed information, a demo version and a web tutorial can be found on the website www.maxqda.de.

²⁷ Components of the software tool MAXQDA are specified in capital letters to avoid confusion with data files used or created on the computer. E.g., "DOCUMENT" refers to a component in MAXQDA, while "document" refers to a file saved on the researcher's personal computer.

mechanisms. As such, the traditional ITG elements in Table 2.2 identified in the literature analysis served as basis categories that needed to be examined deductively in the data. For the other categories, referring to agile ITG elements to be developed inductively, a few categories emerged from the previous step during the case-by-case evaluation and initial coding. However, both groups of elements, traditional and agile, were categorized under the same general dimensions provided in the conventional literature – “structures”, “processes”, and “relational mechanisms”. As a result, the following initial coding scheme with the traditional and the first 9 agile mechanisms set the basis for the next step (see Figure 4.1):

Figure 4.1: Initial coding scheme

4.3.4 Testing and extending the coding scheme

The initial coding scheme was tested by the researcher and two additional PhD students who were familiar with the governance topic. An early meeting was organized to define the coding process and to agree the coding rules and category definitions. The process was defined as follows:

To identify traditional ITG mechanisms, the framework presented in Table 2.2 was used. Regarding agile ITG mechanisms, no corresponding template was found in the literature. Therefore, only the overarching definitions for the terms “agile structures”, “agile processes” and “agile relational mechanisms” were agreed upon. However, a section of the questionnaire specifically asked the respondents about agile principles within ITG mechanisms to identify elements in this domain. When a respondent raised a topic that explicitly point to an agile ITG mechanism it must be assigned to an existing category on the initial coding scheme or, if it does not exist, a new category must be created. However, if the respondent does not associate a topic with agility, but appears relevant in the context of this research, then it needs to be checked if the code fits in with a traditional ITG

mechanism. If so, the code must be assigned to the corresponding traditional element in the coding scheme. If not, the code must be checked to see whether it relates to one or more values agile manifesto or to the overarching agile definitions. The code is then either assigned to an existing category of agile ITG mechanisms in the coding scheme or incorporated to a new group until the point of data saturation is achieved. Figure 4.2 depicts this process visually.

Figure 4.2: Coding process for identifying ITG mechanisms

However, a consensus on the emerging categories would be discussed in group meetings to analyse the codes and decided whether each one should be included, excluded, grouped or even sub-grouped as well as to ensure inter-coder reliability. To do so, the researchers agreed to meet every third day. Furthermore, as proposed by Lombard *et al.* (2002) researchers can assess inter-coder reliability formally in a pilot test where each of the coders code a few samples independently and then check if reliability levels are adequate. Hence, each group member started to code three randomly chosen transcripts individually and independently. The coding rules applied were provided by Kuckartz *et al.* (2008) and the coding process as depicted in Figure 4.2. Then, the researchers held a second meeting to share their outcomes of the data coding and to come to a consensus regarding the newly evolving elements. The

three coders revised the initial coding scheme and discussed the definitions, examples, and classification rules for their comprehensibility. The goal was to establish a common understanding of the codes. As a result, seven new categories of agile ITG mechanisms emerged from this step (see Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3: Extended coding scheme

4.3.5 Coding the data and checking consistency

The coding process continued with the same group members because multiple coders are key to establishing the reliability of the coding process, as opposed to the use of a single coder who faces the risk of introducing a degree of bias (Potter and Levine-Donnerstein, 1999). Hence, the remaining 24 interview transcripts were randomly distributed among the three team members and each one was coded individually and independently. Rather than being compelled to adhere strictly to the category structure of the initial coding scheme, each coder had the flexibility to add additional categories if he found comments that were relevant to understanding agile governance but that did not fall under any of the initial categories. In terms of the traditional ITG mechanisms shown in Table 2.2, not all categories were expected to result in codes. Hence, it was possible that some or several of these categories could not be assigned to text parts. However, as in the previous step, the three coders did not try to develop a numerical rating to test inter-coder reliability but to reach a consensus by discussing and clarifying each difference until the group had agreed on an appropriate use

of the code set. Therefore, the three coders met a third time to compare their findings and, if necessary, to reconcile areas of disagreement regarding how a comment should be interpreted or whether additional categories were required beyond the extended list shown in Figure 4.3. As a result, 10 categories for agile ITG mechanisms were added. At this time, a total of 19 interview transcripts had been coded. However, during this consensus session it was recognized that the final coding scheme consolidated a common understanding of the codes between the three coders. Furthermore, all three researchers stated that the last couple of interviews did not provide much more new insights and that all codes emerged so far could be covered by the final coding scheme as outlined in Figure 4.4. Therefore, the three coders agreed that no additional nodes were necessary when coding the remaining 14 interviews.

Figure 4.4: Final coding scheme

After all the transcripts were coded, the coders met for the fourth time. Again, each code was analysed to explore areas of disagreement. At this stage, no categories for agile ITG mechanisms were added or removed highlighting the fact that the coding scheme had reached saturation level after the nineteenth interview transcript. For several categories of

traditional ITG mechanisms, no codes were assigned. As a result, these mechanisms were removed from the list. Then, an additional step was performed by the thesis researcher, who read each of the 33 transcripts to identify potential inconsistencies in the codes and categories. This led to slight modifications, such as grouping some categories into one main category. For instance, in terms of traditional structures, “committees” and “boards” were grouped into one category since each bank had different names for structural mechanisms that had similar functions. As another example, the agile ITG mechanism “Cooperation with corporations” was further divided into 5 sub-categories to offer more details in the analysis. Finally, to provide an overview of the corporations and the referring codes per category, the results were designed in a table that will be presented in the following section on the qualitative results.

4.4 Qualitative results

Data analysis revealed several traditional and agile ITG mechanisms mentioned by the respondents. Table 4.3 provides an overview of the bank characteristics and control variables. Corporate size, degree of agility, duration of strategic focus on digital transformation, and regional differences were included as control variables in the study. Different categories of banks were well distributed on all control variables, with a slight focus on small and medium-sized banks (<500 employees). A differentiation between subsamples and categories per control variable extended the scope of this thesis and opened a fruitful prospect for further analysis.

Table 4.3: Bank characteristics and control variables

Control Variables		Banks																																				
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33				
Corporate size	Small (<500 employees)	x	x	x		x				x	x	x	x																									
	Medium-sized (500–2000 employees)	x				x																													x	x	x	x
	Large (>2000 employees)																																					
Degree of agility in ITG	Very agile	x	x			x																																
	Somewhat agile	x																																				
	Not agile																																					
IT strategy focusing on digitalization for	<3 years	x	x																																			
	3–4 years	x																																				
	>4 years																																					
Regional differences	Germany	x	x																																			
	Switzerland	x	x																																			
	Austria																																					

4.4.1 Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms

Table 4.4 lists all the information gathered from the 33 banks regarding different ITG mechanisms. Overall, 47 ITG mechanisms appear in the sample. As mentioned previously, the ITG mechanisms used by the corporations are grouped into the categories “structures”, “processes” and “relational mechanisms”. Many other studies, such as those of Almeida *et al.*, (2013), de Haes and van Grembergen (2015a) and Symons (2005), use this type of framework to structure ITG mechanisms.

In Table 4.4, if a mechanism does not exist, the cell is empty; when the mechanism is implemented or there is some evidence that it is used, the cell is marked with a capital “X”. If a sub-group exists, the cells of the corresponding sub-categories are marked with lowercase “x”. Furthermore, the last column of Table 4.4, shows the total codes per mechanism.

As a brief explanation of how the text parts were coded and the patterns elicited, consider the following comment by the CEO of Bank 12: “*Decisions of the steering committee will then be [dependent] on the bank and the board, which are mainly responsible for the financial conditions*”. Here, the reference is to the “Boards and committees” mechanism, so the bank was assigned one code on this mechanism.

The interviewees reported on how the goals were inherent in their business strategy and how they strove to manage digital transformation projects. In total, 22 traditional and 25 agile mechanisms were mentioned. While the traditional mechanisms can be retrieved from the literature, the agile mechanisms represent new mechanisms of an agile ITG framework (see Table 4.4).

Table 4.4: Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms

ITG Mechanisms		Banks																																	Codes
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	
Structures	Traditional	1 CIO/COO on executive committee	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	26	
		2 Boards and committees	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	25	
		3 Project steering committee	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	18	
		4 IT organizational structure	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	17	
		5 Business/IT relationship managers	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	5	
		6 CIO on board	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	3	
	Agile	7 Digital transformation units	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	13		
		8 Short and flexible decision paths	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	13		
		9 Interdisciplinary/small project teams	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	13	
		10 Lean (project) structures	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	11	
		11 Delegating decision making	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	6	
		12 Matrix organizational structures	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	3	
Processes	Traditional	13 Portfolio management	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	32		
		14 IT budget control and reporting	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	20		
		15 Project governance	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	20		
		16 Strategic information systems planning	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	16		
		17 Project tracking	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	15		
		18 Benefit management	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	8		
		19 Demand management	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	6		
		Agile	20 Using agile practices (Scrum, DevOps, design thinking, lean start-ups, etc.)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	20	
			21 Taking higher risk (trial and error)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	17	
	22 Fast/agile decision-making processes		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	15		
	23 Using innovative key performance indicators (KPIs)		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	10		
	24 Lessons learned processes		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	10		
	25 Innovation processes		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	10		
	26 Prioritizing processes		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	8		
	27 Evaluation processes for innovation		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7		
	Relational mechanisms	Traditional	30 Regular internal communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	27	
			31 Management sets a good example	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	17	
32 Business/IT co-location			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	16		
33 Shared understanding of business/IT			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	15		
34 IT leadership			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	14		
35 Informal meetings of executives			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	10		
36 Senior management announcements			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	10		
37 Knowledge management			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	8		
Agile		38 Cross-functional business/IT training	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7		
		39 Transformational leadership	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	18		
Agile	40 Open communication and participation	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	18			
	41 Lean communication structures	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	12			
	42 Use of social/digital media	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	12			
	43 Regular training and teamwork	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	9			
	44 Cross-functional training	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7			
	45 Specific innovation rooms/meetings	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	6			
	46 Management dialogues and campaigns	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	6			
	47 Cooperation with	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	25			
	a - Start-ups	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	17			
	b - Business partners	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	14			
	c - Outsourcing partners	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	6			
	d - Research partners	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	5			
e - Internal teams	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7				

4.4.2 Traditional ITG mechanisms

In exploring the traditional ITG mechanisms implemented by the banks, 22 traditional ITG mechanisms (six structural elements, seven processes and nine relational/communication mechanisms; see Table 4.4) were identified. Many of the elements are confirmed in the literature (Almeida *et al.*, 2013; de Haes and van Grembergen, 2015a).

4.4.2.1 Traditional ITG structures

CIO/COO on executive committee: In terms of structure, the most frequently mentioned element was “CIO/COO on executive committee”. Of the 33 interviewees, 26 noted that the CIO or COO is a full member of the executive committee or has reports directly to the CEO. This situation ensures that IT is a regular agenda item and reporting issue for the board of directors.

For example, the COO of Bank 8, a member of the executive committee, indicated that:

“The topic of digitalization is attached to the entire executive management. The first responsible is the CEO, then me as COO, and that’s what the IT is part of. That means the CIO sits in line with me. [...] Therefore, we are very strong on the technical and procedural side”. (COO, Bank 8)

In addition, the COO/CIO of Bank 18, an executive manager, emphasized the close cooperation between the CEO, and the entire executive committee, and the COO when asked who has the main responsibility for digital transformation projects:

“I would say top down in the executive committee. We are very small, and the executive management would probably say that they have the main responsibility, but actually, I do have the main responsibility since I am also part of the executive management”. (COO/CIO, Bank 18)

For banks that have no formal CIO or COO position, it is important for IT to be represented in strategic discussions by reporting directly to the executive committee to decide about IT investment, as is the case in Bank 9. Hence, the Head of Digitalization, who is not part of the executive management, stated:

“We keep it easy. I participate in the management board meetings and therefore work directly with the executives. [...] That’s the way we discuss matters [such as IT decisions], and that’s where we decide. And if we do not come to a decision, then just one person decides”. (Head of Digitalization, Bank 9)

Boards and committees: “Boards and committees” (25 codes) are formed to help align business and IT, make decisions and determine business priorities in IT investments. The

following text highlights the most important aspects of how banks are adopting boards and committees in their organizations:

“For the implementation of the content of a project, we have two committees; on the one hand, there is a technical committee that assesses and approves the technical implementation, and there is a business steering committee, as we call it, which defines the portfolio of individual measures. But the process or the driving [leading the projects] is my responsibility, and that happens to be me. How the budget is used is decided by the steering committee, but I will be responsible for ensuring that it [the budget] will not be exceeded and that it is respected”. (CIO, Bank 1)

Many of the interviewees also pointed out that boards and steering committees are designed to be cross-functional to discuss and agree on the overall priorities for the IT function; to ensure that business, IT and other functions are aligned; and to coordinate among different departments:

“We have set up a few committees and boards at the customer level to facilitate the transfer of know-how. We have also populated these cross-functionally from the business and IT sides. They have responsibility for releasing their road maps and thus for releasing the associated IT budgets. [...]

[In more detail,] we have our own committee that sets the framework first, and then we have an innovation board, which then releases the innovations in detail”. (Head of Digital Banking, Bank 24)

Project steering committees: To prioritize and manage IT projects, “Project steering committees” (18 banks) are primarily used. They are applied mainly to steer a project from start to implementation and therefore play a significant role in project realization. Furthermore, such steering committees serve as a basis for reporting to higher-level boards and committees, as highlighted by the following manager:

“[...] We have a centralized project portfolio where we monitor and track the IT projects that are relevant to digitization and prepare them for these [board] sessions”. (Head of Digitalization, Bank 24)

The main difference from the previously mentioned “Boards and committees” is that project steering committees are hierarchically lower. Hence, only lower-level decisions can be made, as the main objective is helping to achieve project outcomes and providing support, guidance, and oversight of progress. However, the main decisions are made on the hierarchically higher boards and committees mentioned before. The following two interviewees bring this issue to the fore:

“[...] There is a so-called digital board [IT project steering committee] where the concrete work is done and where things are prepared and prioritized. Only if it does not work will it be escalated to the aforementioned board [boards and committees]”. (COO, Bank 26)

“There is a body called Overall Coordination where the results of the projects converge and things [within the projects] that could not be decided. [If no decision is achieved], then it goes directly to the every-four-week Steering Committee”. (Head of Application Mgmt., Bank 33)

IT organizational structures: “IT organizational structures” (17 codes) were identified as important factors behind the adoption and use of ITG practices for digital transformation. In this way, centralization was recognized as the main organizational structure type in how the banks govern IT. For example, Bank 15 switched from a decentralized IT organization to a centralized model by outsourcing the IT department. In the interview, the CEO stated:

“We have a classic banking organization; the IT area is located there. This is ultimately done by our parent corporation. We actually outsourced our entire IT to our parent corporation [together with the units] Process Management and Product Management. These are the three key units in the game [of initiating digital transformation projects]”. (CEO, Bank 15)

A centralized IT organizational structure facilitates interplay among business units with regard to implementation and enables the appropriate governance of digital expenditure, as stated by the following executive:

“Everything that is digital actually falls under IT in this sense. [...] Of course, this is also a distributed responsibility, so to speak. Those of us who talk to the customer also have the responsibility to conduct things accordingly. But ultimately to govern and implement, that is the IT department”. (CEO, Bank 20)

Business/IT relationship managers: In terms of “Business/IT relationship managers”, 5 banks were identified that had implemented such a mechanism to act as an intermediary between business and IT. Bank 14, e.g., has implemented its own unit to coordinate and to help share understanding between the IT and business sides:

“We have reorganized this a few months ago. The organizational unit is called the General Office, which the strategic process is part of. That means I coordinate this. Involved are colleagues from the business units as well as from the IT department”. (Head of General Office, Bank 14)

CIO on board: Surprisingly, only a few institutions had the CIO as a member of the executive board (3 codes).

4.4.2.2 Traditional ITG processes

Portfolio management: Regarding traditional processes, “Portfolio management” was highlighted as the most essential element. Of the 33 interviewees, 32 mentioned that IT investments and projects are prioritized within portfolio management, in which both business and IT are involved. The CEO of Bank 20 provided an example of what such a process looks like within his corporation:

“If we want to initiate a large project in Switzerland, and we do need IT work, then we would have to write a business case for it. That would then be sent to a Priority Grouping Committee, and different people from business and IT will then sit there and look at it. Then, they would put that somewhere in the ranking of the existing projects and the newly proposed projects, and depending on that, the project would be accepted or not. If it gets accepted, we’ll get an estimated delivery time”. (CEO, Bank 20)

IT budget control and reporting: Connected to portfolio management, the process mechanism “IT budget control and reporting” was identified in 20 banks. One CEO described the process as follows:

“On the project side, we have a product board that collects ideas and then prioritizes and channels them [...]. The processes are very structured, of course, with project management, then a steering committee and the decisions of the steering committee. Then, we go to the bank and supervisory board, which are also responsible above all for the financial framework conditions. Also, [we do] monitor the project progress and budget and so on. There is also detailed quarterly reporting, plus certain special projects that we bring separately to the board, each with the progress that is being made”. (CEO, Bank 12)

Project governance: In several banks, numerous projects are governed (20 codes) based on traditional models. However, banks are facing challenges regarding mastering digital transformation projects, as recognized by the following manager:

“I do not know how many projects I’m currently running. Not all follow specific methodologies. In general, [...] they are based on a waterfall [approach] – [hence, the projects follow] normal milestone project governance. But this doesn’t work very well in digital transformation. When I need to do digital transformation of core banking systems, I have to resort to waterfall or waterfall-like models very often”. (Managing Director, Bank 13)

Strategic information systems planning: Such process mechanisms were recognized in 16 interview transcripts. The managers pointed out that they hold formal planning meetings on an annual, semi-annual or quarterly basis to identify opportunities to support the strategic

direction of the corporation and to determine key planning issues and objectives in terms of IT strategy:

“[In our corporation], we have an annual cycle each spring, so the portfolio [of projects] is redesigned each year. We do not have a five-year portfolio; rather, it [the portfolio] is rebuilt each year to take account of the short-term nature of the matter”. (CIO, Bank 1)

In general, the IT strategy is discussed and updated by the executive managers and managers of each department to better align the IT function with business goals:

“At our quarterly meetings, we discuss with all managers and staff units, where we then introduce such topics [of IT strategy]. Then, it is management’s responsibility to bring this to the individual teams afterwards”. (COO, Bank 10)

Project tracking: Fifteen banks used “Project tracking” mechanisms to monitor and manage the overall progress of projects. In general, electronic tools are applied for detailed project tracking, time tracking and overall control, as is the case in Bank 18:

“In operational governance, we use an electronic tool. There the overall control is implemented and also the prioritization/urgency and criteria. So, actually everything is stored there, [such as] how we prioritize projects within the management and decide what we do and what not and also the project reporting and all that. But digital management is also anchored in risk policy. I also have certain ICS [Internal Control System] points that I have to meet and discuss with the management”. (COO/CIO, Bank 18)

Benefits management and reporting: As further highlighted by the same COO/CIO, electronic tools are important for assessing planned business benefits during and after the implementation of the IT investments; these tools are the “Benefits management and reporting” ITG mechanism. However, such a mechanism was identified in only eight corporations:

“At the moment, the electronic tool is actually the strategic tool for management. It is kind of a Kanban board. This is actually the strategic tool for market performance and for senior management to keep things under control and measure success. So, [it provides an overview of] how many projects are being implemented, which ones [project outcomes] do perform well, and which ones do not perform at all”. (COO/CIO, Bank 18)

Demand management: The “Demand management” process mechanism was recognized in six financial institutions. Within this process mechanism, IT demands are centrally

consolidated, periodized and then fulfilled. The following interviewee provided insight into how this process is accomplished in Bank 30:

“With us, the whole [demand management] is organizationally implemented in a program. That means that this is not a project but a program in which many projects are run, and there lies the main responsibility. There are actually two program managers; one of course is IT, and the second is Group Marketing, so to speak.... Multi-channel management means that with us, [...] this is happening in co-working, which means in principle that all the business requirements are controlled [and consolidated] by Group Marketing and the IT requirements by the IT Group”. (Head of IT, Bank 30)

4.4.2.3 Traditional ITG relational mechanisms

Regular internal communication: Communication is crucial in financial institutions. Of the 33 interviewees, 27 highlighted the importance of regular internal communication. As an example, the manager of Bank 4 pointed out:

“For larger topics, we have a staff meeting, or we do what is very successful, a management board call. Here you either explain the quarterly reports, or if there are any essentials, then we invite the employees [to a short meeting] a quarter hour before opening the bank, and here they [the employees] have the chance to get everything. They get the second level of management [middle management], so to speak, or the interpretation that would otherwise come; they are well included and all feel informed right away. This helps”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 4)

Management sets a good example: Executive and senior management set a good example when the IT department is included in the decision-making process and senior business and IT managers therefore act as “partners”. Such relational mechanisms were identified in 17 of 33 corporations. The CEO of Bank 15 described the bank’s approach as follows:

“[Digital transformation] is to be regarded as a joint task. First of all, we do not have classic fractionation [in our corporation]. We are three executives. I do the market side as spokesman; then, I have a colleague who leads the back office, and I have a third colleague who works in between. In the extended management, we then have the general representative who is responsible for the whole IT department [senior IT management]. [...]. So, the strategy is discussed and adopted by the extended management and also with the involvement of the supervisory board. [...]. It is important that things [decisions] are really discussed and communicated very openly and that this [the decision-making process] is not a top-down but rather a bottom-up approach. [...] Acting as a personal role model here [is key]”. (CEO, Bank 15)

IT leadership: Connected to the previous point, leadership aspects play a key role in communication mechanisms. Hence, the “IT leadership” mechanism was discovered in 14 transcripts, which indicated the importance of an executive’s ability to articulate a vision for the IT role in the corporation and to ensure that this vision is clearly understood, as highlighted by the following interviewee:

“In my view, it is particularly relevant that you have clear strategic goals so that the overall framework that you give yourself is as clear as possible. Where do I want to go? What’s the [...] business model, what are the desired changes, or what are the new business models I want to go into? Where do I want to go so that this transformation goal, which one aims for, becomes somehow tangible so that the visions and objectives become clear and transportable? I think that if you look at every technology that is new and exciting, you quickly lose yourself. You can get off track very quickly”. (CEO/COO, Bank 27)

Informal meetings of executives: Linked to the aforementioned mechanism (IT leadership), “Informal meetings of executives” (10 codes) with no agenda may support prioritizing the IT role in the corporation. Furthermore, in such meetings, business and IT senior managers as well as employees may discuss general activities, directions, concerns and ideas. For instance, in Bank 2, such a relational mechanism is implemented as follows:

“We have a large canteen where we have lunch together; that’s the social network. So, we do not have that technically. We are sitting on a level in the bank, actually seeing each other, so everyone knows everyone by name”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 2)

Senior management announcements: Formal communication about IT initiatives, IT decisions, processes and priorities, however, occurs through the mechanism “Senior management announcements”, which were also highlighted by 10 financial institutions during the interviews. The two following managers provided some insights into their corporations:

“There are also information events every year where 80 to 100 employees, which are 10% of the staff population, are informed and updated in two hours on the [IT investment] topic”. (CIO, Bank 1)

“Of course, there are the periodical events, but not all employees are participating there, only some from each department. It is relatively difficult to pick up the whole corporation and communicate something effectively”. (Head of Innovation Lab, Bank 5)

Business/IT co-location: Coupling business and IT resources is important for the co-production of strategic capabilities (Sambamurthy *et al.*, 2003). Sixteen of 33 financial institutions use the “Business/IT co-location” mechanism to combine IT and business resources and consequently to support value-creating innovation processes, as emphasized by the following interviewee:

“Here in Frankfurt, there are more than 400 people, and you will not find a single department name in the whole building [...] because departments are meaningless. It’s all about the topics, and there [in the building] the people of business, of IT, of Legal are sitting. Customers are invited there, and then innovations are built. And that, of course, in the sense of enterprise-wide integration, is just one example”. (CDO, Bank 21)

Shared understanding of business/IT: “Shared understanding of business/IT” (15 codes) is essential for efficient communication in digital transformation projects. Therefore, key stakeholders are involved in developing a shared understanding of the value of IT in terms of introducing new project initiatives and preparing for decision making:

“If we introduce something new, we have a departmental meeting once a week. Everybody updates what the relevant topics are in his area. The persons concerned are involved at specific points in the preparation for the decision. We include the revision, we integrate the IT, we involve the relationship managers and see what the impact is”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 4)

Knowledge management: Eight interviewees mentioned practicing “Knowledge management” (8 codes) in their corporations to share and distribute knowledge about several topics. An example from Bank 25 was provided:

“I think we have a lot [of knowledge management mechanisms], so we have a classic intranet; we have specific screens in all of our organizations around the world that show where we stand with which innovation sprints, so we’re trying to keep this constant change close to our people”. (CEO, Bank 25)

Cross-functional business/IT training: Only seven banks use “Cross-functional business/IT training”. The CEO of Bank 6 presented such a mechanism as follows:

“We make forums again and again. [E.g.,] we had an employee event for a week, which we called Network Week. We brought all the departments together and made market stalls where you could exchange [...]. Then, we made various forums for an hour over the week where we held lectures on various topics and provided discussion places [so that the employees had the opportunity to receive information and training]”. (CEO, Bank 6)

4.4.3 Agile ITG mechanisms

This sub-section presents the analysis of the bank executives' perceptions of agile ITG mechanisms. Based on their answers to the qualitative questionnaire, six structural elements, ten process mechanisms and nine relational/communication mechanisms were identified.

4.4.3.1 Agile ITG structures

Regarding structures, executives from 13 banks mentioned the mechanisms “Digital transformation units”, “Short and flexible decision paths” and “Interdisciplinary/small project teams”. Similarly, important executives from 11 banks mentioned the mechanism “Lean project structures”. Relatively few institutions use “Delegating decision making” (6 codes) and “Matrix organizational structures” (3 codes).

Digital transformation units: The respondents noted that the setup of new dedicated units for digital transformation (13 codes) allows better communication and more intensive collaboration. In general, such units are created from organizational structures and include various positions from other units, as the following interviewee highlighted:

“We have set up a new organizational unit called PAI [Product and Application Innovation] combined from the units AM [Application Management] and PM [Product Management]. This unit cannot be found in the organizational structures because the organizational structures include only linear hierarchical structures shown from top to bottom”. (Head of Application Mgmt., Bank 33)

Such units maintain a top-level structure that is responsible for recognizing the abundant opportunities in terms of digital innovation. This enables quick reactions to business and stakeholder needs. The development of new divisions specific to digital transformation projects was also emphasized by the manager of Bank 7:

“At the beginning of 2016, we founded the Digital Customer Office, which I chair. Hence, I have a dual function, once as a Member of the [bank] Executive Board for [specific] digital topics and once, so to speak, as the Chief Digital Officer of the group for all digital themes. The new unit was created at the beginning of 2016 [...] and bundles all the digital road maps of the individual corporations, so that we also have an entire digital road-map view for the entire corporation”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 7)

Short and flexible decision paths: Rapid decisions are key in the digital area to obtain technological resources quickly and to use technology infrastructure to meet emerging business needs, which in turn foster business agility. Therefore, to make quick and efficient

decisions on digital transformation projects, 13 of 33 banks have implemented short and flexible decision-making paths, as pointed out by the following interview participants:

“[Decisions about digital initiatives] are made in two stages: there’s a Project Steering Committee for the digitization issues, which decides in the first instance what our house is about, and then there’s the board’s decision, which gets incorporated into the board. Well, these are relatively short ways”. (Head of Digitalization, Bank 22)

“The big decisions are all made by the executive committee, partly by the supervisory board, and we are very involved in this, which may also be a special feature. [...] Therefore, we have very short decision paths”. (CEO, Bank 19)

Interdisciplinary/small project teams: To realize agility within digital transformation projects, the 13 interviewees pointed out that they set up agile interdisciplinary and small project teams comprising a mix of different specialists. The team members are responsible for the entire IT delivery process, from planning to operations, as well as for quality assurance. For example, the CIO of Bank 1 responded as follows when asked about the agile aspect of ITG:

“There are these “digital streams” [...]. This is actually the idea of agility, small teams, hierarchically set at the lowest level [and] heterogeneous – comprising product managers, salespeople and IT people who are responsible for a topic. For example, [the topic] credit, or whatever, gets a budget, gets resources, and [the team] can then do something in this context on their own competence. Hence, we attempt to embed some agility in a hierarchical organization, but that’s not so easy”. (CIO, Bank 1)

In addition, the executive of bank 10 highlighted the need for interdisciplinary teams to foster agility within digital transformation projects:

“Here, we are working with either agile project development and/or interdisciplinary teams to improve that [agility]”. (COO, Bank 10)

Lean (project) structures: Implementing flat structures that support faster decision making for digital transformation projects may enhance a corporation’s agility. Hence, the “Lean (project) structures” mechanism was identified in 11 of 33 banks:

“We have very, very broad structures [lean structures]. If someone has a good idea, he or she can launch projects through his or her superior. This has the advantage that [we] are very, very agile or that the ideas come in very agile. We also accept that projects are sometimes launched simultaneously, and you know nothing about each other”. (Head of Innovation Lab, Bank 5)

Lean structures, however, are more realistic in small and medium-sized corporations and allow project achievements to be broken down into smaller pieces, which fosters organizational agility, as pointed out by the following manager from a small bank:

“We are very agile, and we can control it. But overall, it is rather very partially positioned at the end of the day. [...] Yes, very partially oriented to certain points. [Hence,] at the end of the day, these points are not seen in the big vision but rather, so to speak, what do I have to do in the next step to take this bank to the next level”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 11)

Delegating decision making: Few executives mentioned that delegating decision-making authority (6 codes) to individuals or teams is important so that people can interact across the corporation:

“[As a leader,] I have to equip the individual teams with appropriate decision-making authority. As an executive, [I have to concentrate] much more strongly on content and people leadership”. (CDO, Bank 21)

Matrix organizational structures: Only three banks highlighted using the mechanism “Matrix organizational structures” to allow collaboration among employees and foster cross-corporation teamwork. The CIO of Bank 1, for instance, stated:

“The topic of “digital banking” [...] is very strongly networked with the whole bank. [...] The content-related topics are worked out very strongly in a matrix [organization]”. (CIO, Bank 1)

4.4.3.2 Agile ITG processes

Using agile practices: In terms of processes, the respondents noted using agile practices (20 codes). Many bank executives indicated that they used agile practices such as Scrum, design thinking, and lean approaches, as noted by the following CEO:

“[With] Scrum, now that we’re in the newest project, we’re off to sprints, so two, three weeks’ sprints with mock-ups, with customer surveys; we do not project to 12 to 18 months and then see if it flies or not but incrementally evolve it. ... We also use design thinking methods. But [with] Scrum, mock-ups with pilots, we are starting to work with such things now. And it’s amazing what’s possible – amazing”. (CEO, Bank 12)

Taking higher risk (trial and error): The executives further noted that taking higher risk by following trial-and-error processes (17 codes) might enhance corporate agility. Such processes stimulate people to act in self-organized ways and ensure continuous learning. Especially when implementing new business models, such a mechanism is key:

“Actually, to master digitalization, we are working very hard, not just by using the traditional industrial approach of the KPIs, which, so to speak, attracted attention 20 years ago in banks, but by using trial-and-error processes. [...]

Well, if we did not do trial and error, we would not need to tackle the topic at all. With digitization, you will not work without trial-and-error readiness, especially when you try out new business models or new distribution models”. (CEO, Bank 19)

Fast/agile decision-making processes: The respondents highlighted fast and agile decision-making processes (15 codes) as significant for acting in a flexible and rapid manner when making decisions, as pointed out by the following two interviewees:

“It does not take more intense [decision-making] processes to hand over a project proposal or a concept to the management, but if the document exists, then it will be forwarded. Right now, I feel we are really pushing our digital transformation processes. They are working right now”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 16)

“There is no [big] process. If something comes, it is discussed, and then there’s just somewhere the filter of the divisional manager, who says it is worthwhile to present it to the management”. (Head of Private Banking, Bank 29)

Using innovative key performance indicators (KPIs): Ten banks use innovative key performance indicators (KPIs), such as STP (straight-through processing) rates, conversion rates or online client feedback, to improve their processes. The following three executives outlined some examples to provide insight:

“What we do is what everyone probably does: we look at the STP rates in certain areas to check how they develop”. (CFO, Bank 32)

“We look at the total traffic on the home pages when [clients] jump to the leasing calculator. We look at the user numbers on the leasing computer; we look at the likes on Facebook; we look at the conversion rates from the leasing computer, so to speak, how many entrances, offers and bookings there are. We look at where the interested parties jump, so where are the points of departure. We look at how long they linger on our platforms. [We] essentially [do] Google Analytics, if you like”. (CEO/COO, Bank 27)

“One of the most important currencies of the digital world is traffic; [hence,] how much interaction do I have [on the bank platforms] [...]. Then, the second is, of course, very strongly the qualitative feedback of the customers. The most obvious are always the app store ratings”. (CDO, Bank 21)

Lessons learned processes: Equally important were the introduction of lessons learned processes (10 codes). An example is provided by the managing director of Bank 13:

“Yes, we certainly have [processes named] Scrumplings, where we probably learn the know-how [about agile work] slowly and try to get a little broader”.
(Managing Director, Bank 13)

Some banks also mentioned projects for which a profit is not necessarily expected but that are rather implemented to capture lessons learned from mistakes. Such a process is highlighted by Bank 8:

“So now there is, for example, the introduction of an e-mortgage. We have had an e-mortgage for four years ... because we learn a lot, but not in the sense that we make a good deal, but we learn how it does not work. [...]. That means with a digital mortgage, we do not earn money, but we learn how to do digital marketing”. (COO, Bank 8)

Innovation processes: “Innovation processes” were identified in 10 of 33 banks. Encouraging innovation may invite leaders and employees to question their processes, working attitude and use of resources. As such, introducing innovations becomes an important driver for expressing agility within the corporation. The CEO/CIO presented some insights into how such an innovation process occurs within Bank 3:

“We have so-called stage-gate processes. They sum up innovations or thoughts or ideas that can come from different directions. They can come from me, can come from the employees, and can [also] come from other executive committee members. But they can also be carried over to us from outside. It is the awareness that a process should or must exist [...] that summarizes the ideas from different inputs, evaluates them according to a valued principle and then defines the procedure, when it receives a “go”, when a “no-go”, and how do we document that. We have initialized this very stage-gate process, and this is being dealt with within the area of corporate development. But inputs can come from anywhere [...]. You go through four or five different gates, and if you pass them all, it [the project] will be launched”. (CEO/CIO, Bank 3)

Prioritizing processes: In addition to the traditional boards and committees, participants from eight banks emphasized “Prioritizing processes”, to initiate and prioritize digital transformation projects in a flexible manner. For instance, in Bank 17, digital transformation projects are directly prioritized in workshops:

“So, in the middle of this year, we will be conducting a workshop with the executive management, where we actually want to force the management of this multi-option of today’s possibilities of digital transformation to prioritize

[innovative projects] – of course, in coordination with the motherhouse – but actually, we would like to find our way there too. So, decisions are made in workshops. So, as I say, [we prioritize] with the executive management, with the second level of management, and then, as a result, we have to think about it”.
(Head of Application Mgmt., Bank 17)

Evaluation processes for innovation: “Evaluation processes for innovation” were identified in eight transcripts. In general, financial institutions evaluate innovation through their own processes or by working with external corporations. In the following comments, insights from two banks are provided:

“We work together with e-foresight. E-foresight is a part of Swisscom that makes technology and market observations. They do that [evaluation] for us on an ongoing basis. Then, the current trends are presented in the spring. The current developments derived there represent possible thrusts”. (CIO, Bank 1)

“In principle, the needs of the asset manager are identified. This will be evaluated and decided, or we have elaborate processes to determine whether we can automate them”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 2)

Project and budget monitoring/Coordination processes: Few executives mentioned using project and budget monitoring (6 codes) or coordination processes (4 codes). The CEO of Bank 12 highlights the most important aspects in this context:

“Product management actually has the whole setup function: how it’s set up, which documents you need, how the budget has to be made, what the cost keys are – product management is actually responsible for the content, [...] well, not just product management; this can also be another part if it is not about a product development. And then, the Steering Committee is more the correct composition of competence, whether it is the Steering Committee. Then, what must be done by the board of directors? What must be done by the board? What goes on the bank board? [For all that,] we actually have a very clear governance policy, which last year was also looked at very intensively by FINMA [Swiss Financial Market Supervisory Authority] and was also found to be good”.
(CEO, Bank 12)

4.4.3.3 Agile ITG relational mechanisms

Cooperation: One of the most relevant mechanisms, in terms of relational mechanisms, highlighted by the respondents was external cooperation. 67% of the executives agreed that cooperation (25 codes) with external partners (e.g., start-ups, business partners, outsourcing partners and research partners) and internally within their own corporation (e.g.,

subsidiaries) had become increasingly important in achieving their strategic goals. In particular, cooperation with start-ups was highlighted as crucial. For example,

“cooperation is our linchpin ... because most FinTechs [start-ups] just do not take all the value chain but only focus on individual steps on the customer interface; then, we act as the partner in the background. This is something we live and have always lived [by]; that’s why we have no fear of contact there – we do a lot”. (COO, Bank 10)

Cooperation with other partners was also emphasized as important, as underlined by the following executive:

“The software we use is not our software, but we have rented it in an [outsourcing] application-service-providing model, so to speak [...]. This is also used by other clients. That is why it is also much cheaper when using it with other clients. But you also have to agree if certain changes have to be made. [...]

We would never dare to do that [digital transformation projects] ourselves. Of course, we always have the basic idea. However, this is never implemented one to one [by us] because we work with partners. We take professionals who have usually already implemented things They advise us, and then we change things accordingly. These are partly FinTechs; some of them are software corporations that have done so many times, and these are also agencies that help us with the look and feel”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 2)

Transformational leadership: Transformational leadership (18 codes) plays a key role in empowering employees and is seen as an appropriate approach to digital transformation. The comments from the following two interviewees bring this to the fore:

“In terms of transformational leadership, trust is a key factor. But this is not enough. Employees must also be moved. They are still in the old leadership mode, and they must also take this responsibility and be able to carry out these competences. It just needs this transformational leadership in which one involves the employees; promotes, coaches, evolves, [and] not simply [gives] transactional orders”. (COO/CIO, Bank 18)

“As long as the leadership above lives this [the transformational leadership approach] and presents it to the outside, I would say the transformational leadership is actually the better way [for digital transformation]”. (Head of IT, Bank 23)

Open communication and participation: In connection with the previous point, the “Open communication and participation” mechanism was seen as one of the main tasks of the transformational leadership approach and was stressed by 18 respondents. For instance,

“[an important leadership aspect of digital transformation is] transparency, open communication and re-questioning and reviewing things”. (Managing Director, Bank 13)

“[It is important] to report about it [digital transformation initiatives] very often and also to animate subordinates to participate”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 16)

Another respondent provided an example of how employees are involved in digital transformation projects:

“We did a workshop on agility, and the focus was on empowering employees, trusting them, and giving free rein to product owners and project teams”. (COO/CIO, Bank 18)

Lean communication structures: Moreover, executives from 12 banks regarded the setup of lean communication structures (12 codes) in their communication initiatives as a way to engage people. An example of lean communication structures is provided by the following executive:

“We’re doing open space events [...]. At the beginning, when I came here, I got to know a very entrenched hierarchical [communication] structure, and then [I changed it and] did an open space event. What is that, according to my definition? I set up 10 hypotheses, communicated them to the staff, so to speak, and said: We invest a day in an open space event on a voluntary basis [...]. They could register for which thesis they wanted to go to. There is no hierarchy, and the one who moderates must not be a superior, not a leader, but should be an employee. And this day was a real spirit of optimism, where qualities and employees could also come to the fore that one would never have expected. That was great”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 7)

Use of social/digital media: The use of social and digital media (12 codes), such as enterprise social networking, Twitter, Facebook, and WebEx, was highlighted as equally important by the managers in communicating initiatives to shareholders and other stakeholders:

“We’ve built an Innovation Lab, a Video Lab. As a result, we now have a Facebook presence on the Internet. We have our own YouTube channel, and we shoot the videos ourselves”. (CEO/CIO, Bank 3)

“We used to have an internal employee newspaper, which we have now digitized completely. And communication now takes place via electronic media. [We use a tool] in principle, like Yammer – a kind of enterprise Facebook [enterprise social network]. That’s where communication has changed noticeably. We also have started to use Twitter within the executive management”. (COO, Bank 8)

Regular training and teamwork/Cross-functional training: Some bank executives also mentioned mechanisms such as regular training and teamwork (9 codes) and cross-functional training (7 codes). The two following cites highlight the most important facets pointed out by the interviewees:

“We produce new market services, or we try to produce digital market services [...]. There is a problem in using the resources for it because there is an intensive need for training. That means we are currently very busy in conducting training in the entire area”. (Head of Application Mgmt., Bank 33)

“We have 3,000 trading partners who make financial deals for us, that is, data credit businesses, which we now train through seminars and also online training with videos”. (Head of Digitalization, Bank 9)

Specific innovation rooms/meetings: A few participants mentioned having set up specific innovation rooms or meetings (6 codes) where people can meet to talk about innovations. The manager of Bank 16 provided an example in this context:

“A few weeks ago, we started the innovation kitchen. This is really a get-together; these are partly employees, who then really generate ideas and assess and rate them [...]. This is really a room where we say that you can write down every idea, but then do not leave it at that spinning mill, but from this innovation kitchen, you have to create services and products that can be introduced into the market. This is our container where you start brainstorming [...]”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 16)

Management dialogues and campaigns: Six interviewees said they use management dialogues and campaigns (6 codes) to improve communication and transparency within their corporations. For instance, the executive of Bank 7 stated:

“We’ve just launched a new medium here for the bank, “the New Bank in dialogue”, where we keep track of the digital steps at least once every quarter, but usually every 6 weeks. All employees are invited to take a lesson once, a session in the morning or in the afternoon. And the [executive management] and the individual project leaders are there to answer questions and to present what is currently happening, why it is moving, where the project stands, what the next steps are, and then we have a Q&A session with the staff where they can ask questions again”. (Member of the Executive Board, Bank 7)

4.5 Transferability check

As in most studies, the design of the primary qualitative study of this thesis is subject to restrictions. These are highlighted at the end of this thesis in Chapter 8. Nonetheless, a major limitation of the findings that must be mentioned at this stage is that a large part of this thesis' qualitative investigation was conducted in the banking sector, which may limit the generalizability and transferability of the results to other sectors. This issue, however, is addressed in this chapter. To do so, eight supplementary cross-industry interviews were conducted to overcome the restriction of industry-specific generalization and to review transferability in this context. Hence, a purposive sample was used to check transferability. Eight contacts from corporations in different sectors were selected based on the judgment criteria presented in Section 3.2.2.3 and invited to participate in the secondary qualitative study. As in the banking study, the interviews were first conducted using similar interview guidelines (after excluding the bank specific wording) and then recorded and transcribed. In addition, the data analysis followed the same process used for the primary qualitative study described in Section 3.2.3. However, in contrast to the banking study, for the cross-industry study, only brief insights are provided in the following sections.

4.5.1 Background information

Table 4.5 provides background information, such as the corporation name, position of the interviewee, industry, and number of employees.

Table 4.5: Background information of the corporations and interviewees

Corporations	Position of Interviewee	Industry	Employees
Corporation 1	Sales Manager	Mechanical and Plant Engineering	14974
Corporation 2	Team Leader Logistics	Crude Oil and Natural Gas	6500
Corporation 3	Technical Manager	Business Process Outsourcing	8000
Corporation 4	Security Sales Specialist	IT & Services	5253
Corporation 5	IT Specialist	Industrial Technology	450
Corporation 6	Big Data Consultant	Management Consulting	2500
Corporation 7	IT Project Manager	Automotive Industry	35000
Corporation 8	Lead Business Analyst	Business Consulting	5517

The names of the corporations and the interviewees are confidential; thus, in this qualitative cross-industry study, the corporations are referred to as “Corporation 1” through “Corporation 8”. The participants in the cross-industry study were experts in the governance

area. Therefore, the convenience sample included managers, team leaders, analysts, and consultants who were available and voluntarily participated in an interview in relation to the ITG topic of digital transformation.

4.5.2 Qualitative results of the cross-industry study

As mentioned before, the data analysis in general followed the same process as that used in the banking study, with two slight differences. First, the coding was done by the thesis researcher alone and not by a team. Second, the same coding scheme was used that was developed in the principal qualitative study. Hence, the cross-industry study followed a deductive approach.

As in the banking study, the corporate size, degree of agility and duration of strategic focus on digital transformation were included as control variables in the study. However, a transferability check was conducted only for German corporations.

Table 4.6: Corporate characteristics and control variables

Control Variables		Corporations							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Corporate size	Small (<500 employees)					X			
	Large (>2000 employees)	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
Degree of agility in ITG	Very agile								X
	Somewhat agile		X	X	X	X	X	X	
	Not agile	X							
IT strategy focusing on digitalization for	< 3 years	X						X	
	3–4 years				X				
	> 4 years		X	X		X	X		X

4.5.3 Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms

Table 4.7 lists the information gathered from the eight cross-industry corporations regarding traditional and agile ITG mechanisms. The table follows the same design as Table 4.4. Furthermore, in the last column, the percentage of the codes from the banking study were included for comparison. In general, 45 of 47 ITG mechanisms examined in the banking study were also identified in the cross-industry investigation, meaning that 95.7% of the elements are transferable to other sectors. Moreover, no other traditional or new agile ITG mechanisms were identified, highlighting the fact that data saturation was reached in the primary banking study.

Table 4.7: Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms in the cross-industry study

ITG Mechanisms		Corporations								Codes					
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Cross-industry		Banks			
										Frequency	%	%			
Structures	Traditional	1	CIO/COO on executive committee	X	X	X	X				4	50%	79%		
		2	Boards and committees		X	X	X	X	X	X	6	75%	76%		
		3	Project steering committee	X	X	X				X	4	50%	55%		
		4	IT organizational structure		X			X			2	25%	52%		
		5	Business/IT relationship managers			X					1	13%	15%		
		6	CIO on board								0	0%	9%		
	Agile	7	Digital transformation units	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	8	100%	39%		
		8	Short and flexible decision paths	X					X		2	25%	39%		
		9	Interdisciplinary/small project teams	X	X			X			3	38%	39%		
		10	Lean (project) structures	X	X				X		3	38%	33%		
		11	Delegating decision making								0	0%	18%		
		12	Matrix organizational structures								0	0%	9%		
Processes	Traditional	13	Portfolio management	X	X	X			X	X	X	6	75%	97%	
		14	IT budget control and reporting			X						1	13%	61%	
		15	Project governance		X	X	X		X	X		5	63%	61%	
		16	Strategic information systems planning	X	X							2	25%	48%	
		17	Project tracking		X			X		X		3	38%	45%	
		18	Benefit management						X			1	13%	24%	
		19	Demand management					X				1	13%	18%	
		Agile	20	Using agile practices (Scrum, DevOps, etc.)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		7	88%	61%
			21	Taking higher risk (trial and error)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		7	88%	52%
	22		Fast/agile decision-making processes							X		1	13%	45%	
	23		Using innovative key performance indicators (KPIs)	X	X	X	X	X		X		6	75%	30%	
	24		Lessons learned processes		X		X					2	25%	30%	
	25		Innovation processes		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	7	88%	30%	
	26		Prioritizing processes	X							X	2	25%	24%	
	27		Evaluation processes for innovation		X	X						2	25%	21%	
	28		Project and budget monitoring					X				1	13%	18%	
	29		Coordination processes	X		X					X	3	38%	12%	
	Relational mechanisms	Traditional	30	Regular internal communication			X	X	X		X	4	50%	82%	
			31	Management sets a good example				X				1	13%	52%	
32			Business/IT co-location	X				X				2	25%	48%	
33			Shared understanding of business/IT	X	X			X	X			4	50%	45%	
34			IT leadership		X	X	X					3	38%	42%	
35			Informal meetings of executives				X					1	13%	30%	
36			Senior management announcements				X					1	13%	30%	
37			Knowledge management	X	X		X	X	X	X		6	75%	24%	
38			Cross-functional business/IT training							X		1	13%	21%	
Agile		39	Transformational leadership	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	8	100%	55%	
		40	Open communication and participation	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	7	88%	55%	
		41	Lean communication structures	X				X				2	25%	36%	
		42	Use of social/digital media	X	X		X	X	X			5	63%	36%	
		43	Regular training and teamwork			X	X			X	X	4	50%	27%	
		44	Cross-functional training	X			X			X	X	4	50%	21%	
		45	Specific innovation rooms/meetings		X		X		X	X		4	50%	18%	
		46	Management dialogues and campaigns		X	X	X					3	38%	18%	
		47	Cooperation with	X	X		X	X		X	X	6	75%	76%	
		a	- Start-ups	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	7	88%	52%	
b	- Business partners	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	7	88%	42%			
c	- Outsourcing partners	x	x	x	x	x			x	6	75%	18%			
d	- Research partners									0	0%	15%			
e	- Internal teams	x	x		x	x			x	5	63%	21%			

4.5.3.1 Traditional ITG mechanisms

In contrast to the banking study, the most commonly mentioned mechanisms in terms of *traditional structures* were “Boards and committees”. Of the participants, 75% pointed out that they had set up such structural mechanisms to govern business priorities in IT investments. The eight interviewees also noted that the CIO or COO is a full member of the executive committee or reports directly to the CEO. As in the primary qualitative study, cross-industry corporations use project steering committees (50%) and IT organizational structures (25%) to prioritize and manage IT projects. The mechanism “Business/IT relationship managers” (13%) was identified in only one corporation, which is a percentage similar to that in the banking industry (15%). No interviewee explicitly pointed out that the CIO is a member of the board. Overall, in terms of structures, only one mechanism (the last mentioned) could not be confirmed by the cross-industry study in comparison with the banking investigation.

Regarding *traditional processes*, portfolio management was highlighted by 75% of the participants as the most essential element. In terms of controlling, monitoring and reporting projects, most corporations use the process “project governance” (5 codes). Few respondents mentioned using “project tracking” (3 codes) or “IT budget control and reporting” processes (1 code). Formal processes to define and update IT strategy were implemented in 25% of the corporations (strategic information systems planning; 2 codes). The benefit management (1 code) and demand management (1 code) processes were each identified in one corporation. In sum, all process mechanisms applied in the banking industry were found in the cross-industry investigation.

In terms of *traditional relational mechanisms*, the element most frequently indicated by the respondents was “Knowledge management” (75%). The mechanisms “Regular internal communication” and “Shared understanding of business/IT” were each identified in 50% of the corporations, demonstrating that communication plays an important role. In both studies, IT leadership aspects were seen as similarly important (cross-industry, 38%; banking industry, 42%). To ensure that business and IT work together, 25% of the cross-industry corporations locate business and IT close to each other (business/IT collocation; 2 codes). The mechanisms “Management sets a good example”, “Informal meetings of executives”, “Senior management announcements” and “Cross-functional business/IT training” were implemented by 13% of the corporations. In conclusion, all traditional relational ITG mechanisms that occurred in the financial institutions were also identified in the other sectors.

4.5.3.2 Agile ITG mechanisms

Concerning *agile structures*, all respondents (100%) indicated that they have created a digital transformation unit to promote the digital transformation of their corporations. The importance of the mechanisms “Interdisciplinary/small project teams” (38%) and “Lean (project) structures” (38%) was similar to that in the previous examination. These were emphasized as crucial to break down organizational barriers within a corporation and to actively promote teamwork. Furthermore, the experts highlighted short and flexible decision paths (25%) for making the decision-making process more flexible. However, the mechanisms “Delegating decision making” and “Matrix organizational structures” were not mentioned in the cross-industry study. In total, of the six agile structures explored in the banking study, 4 mechanisms also appeared during the transferability check.

Of the *agile processes*, the mechanisms “Using agile practices”, “Taking higher risk (trial and error)” and “Innovation processes” were the most frequently appearing elements in the cross-industry study (each 88%) and were considered relevant to promoting agility. Another element seen as crucial for digital transformation was the use of innovative key performance indicators (KPIs) (75%). While coordination processes were identified in 3 corporations, the process mechanisms “Lessons learned processes”, “Prioritizing processes” and “Evaluation processes for innovation” were each implemented in 2 corporations. Surprisingly, only one interviewee mentioned having implemented specific fast/agile decision-making processes. None explicitly mentioned using project and budget monitoring processes for agile projects; therefore, this mechanism was the only one that did not appear in the cross-industry study.

One of the most relevant mechanisms, in terms of *agile relational mechanisms*, that the respondents highlighted was transformational leadership. 100% of the participants agreed that transformational leadership aspects had become increasingly important in empowering employees. A further relevant mechanism for digital transformation was “Open communication and participation”, which was accordingly highlighted by seven experts. As in the banking study, cooperation with several partners was seen as key to achieving corporate strategic goals and was mentioned by 75% of the interviewees. Of the respondents, 63% indicated that they use social media in their communication and processes. The mechanisms “Regular training and teamwork”, “Cross-functional training” and “Specific innovation rooms/meetings” were each emphasized by 50% of the experts. Furthermore, some used mechanisms such as “Management dialogues and campaigns” (38%) and “Lean communication structures” (25%) to promote agile communication. In conclusion, all the

main agile relational mechanisms found in the banking study were also identified in the cross-industry examination.

4.6 ITG Patterns

4.6.1 Key patterns

When discussing governance models in corporations, the question is what structures, processes and communication mechanisms successfully steer the digital transformation. The previous sections provided deep insights into the interviewees' corporations and revealed agile aspects within the ITG construct. Therefore, several single traditional and agile ITG mechanisms were discovered. Figure 4.5 shows an initial key pattern for the use of ITG mechanisms within the interviewed corporations. While the corporations 1 to 33 corresponds to the banks interviewed in the preliminary study, the organizations 34 to 41 refer to the cross-industry corporations from the secondary study. It groups the revealed ITG mechanisms by traditional and agile ITG structures, processes and relational mechanisms per corporation.

Figure 4.5: Traditional and agile structures, processes and relational mechanisms used

As shown, each corporation (except 4, 6, 17, 30, 31 and 41) uses both traditional and agile ITG structures, processes and relational mechanisms to master digital transformation. For example, Corporation 1 applies five traditional and agile ITG structural mechanisms, six traditional process mechanisms, seven agile process mechanisms, and five traditional and agile mechanisms. Therefore, in general, *Key pattern one* can be stated as follows:

Key pattern one: ITG frameworks for digital transformation are deployed using a combination of various traditional and agile structures, traditional and agile processes, and traditional and agile relational mechanisms in the interviewed corporations.

A second pattern is shown in Figure 4.6, which groups the ITG mechanisms by the traditional and agile mechanisms. As shown in this figure, all the corporations tend to use traditional as well as agile ITG mechanisms simultaneously. Hence, the data analysis of the previous sections indicates the need to strive for a combination of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms in designing ITG frameworks suitable for digital transformation. Therefore, as shown in Figure 4.6, the interviewed financial institutions as well as the cross-industry organizations in general are inclined to use both traditional and agile ITG approaches in balance. For instance, corporation 1 uses 16 traditional and 17 agile ITG mechanisms to govern IT in the digital age. *Key pattern two* is identified as follows:

Key pattern two: The interviewed corporations simultaneously apply governance elements by using traditional ITG mechanisms as one side of the balance and agile ITG mechanisms as the other side of the balance.

Figure 4.6: Traditional and agile ITG mechanisms used

4.6.2 Building block two – Ambidextrous ITG

One major finding out of the coding process is that there are agile mechanisms in ITG besides the traditional ones and that a distinction is made between traditional and agile mechanisms, as shown in Table 4.4. However, the patterns given in the previous section reveal a second key outcome. The two key patterns show that not only do corporations apply well-balanced traditional ITG practices, but they also use agile ITG mechanisms based on the same three dimensions “structures”, “processes” and “relational mechanisms” to drive IT in the digital age. Hence, the key patterns confirm that the concept of ITG for digital transformation not only has to focus on agile ITG mechanisms by replacing the traditional elements, but rather should complement them. As pointed out in Chapter 2, corporations need to handle two states in their organizational development. While in the first state a corporation needs to be concerned with optimizing their existing business logic by focusing on operational efficiency and stability, in the second state it needs to focus on successfully managing innovation and agility (Tushman *et al.*, 1986). As further highlighted, one way to deal with these two types of states is by becoming ambidextrous, meaning that a corporation needs to have the ability to both exploit and explore. This behaviour in implementing a successful ITG for digital transformation was recognized in this thesis’ qualitative investigation. While the revealed traditional ITG mechanisms highlighted by the interviewees focus on exploitation and stability, the agile ITG elements are concerned with exploration and agility. Hence, based on the key patterns uncovered it can be assumed that the implementation of a suitable ITG framework for digital transformation needs to follow an ambidextrous approach in governing IT where ITG enables both exploration encouraged through agile ITG mechanisms as well as exploitation, promoted through the traditional ITG practices. This assumption can be underpinned by theoretical considerations as is now discussed.

For example, Haffke *et al.* (2017b) point out that corporations have focused heavily on IT exploitation in the past and highlight that digital transformation is more about exploring innovative uses of IT rather than optimizing costs and affecting incremental IT improvements. In their study they argue that ITG should operate in two modes which differ structurally and typically follow different management principles, as these are set up to achieve different objectives. Based on the analysis of interviews with 19 executives across different industries they conclude that one mode should represent the traditional approach of ITG with emphasis on safety and accuracy and exploitation, while the other mode should emphasize agility speed and IT exploration by operating non-sequentially in multiple iterations. Yousif *et al.* (2017) see existing ITG as optimized for non-agile delivery, with a

tendency to strive for economies of scale at the cost of economies of scope. They propose that ITG should turn towards an ambidextrous approach with an increased ability of supporting both exploration and exploitation. This shift in ITG is also reflected in the recent promotion of "Bimodal IT" by industry analyst Gartner, which requires CIOs and IT departments to deliver two types of IT: rapid and proactive innovation, and cost-effective maintenance and support (Gartner, 2018).

Through a case study at a global technology corporation, and by drawing on ambidexterity theory, Andersen *et al.* (2017) showed how an IT organization can choose between different types of ITG depending on whether the system supports exploring and developing new innovations (exploration) or whether it exploits current systems to drive the efficiency of the corporation (exploitation). They further noted that "*ambidextrous ITG can help IT managers alleviate many of the top IT management problems such as agility/flexibility, time-to-market, innovation, productivity, IT value, and cost reductions*" (Andersen *et al.*, 2017, p. 144). Based on a literature review, Horlach *et al.* (2016) found that IT operates in two modes: traditional IT and agile IT. They characterize the two modes as follows: the traditional IT mode typically uses waterfall-driven (sequential) approaches to manage IT projects, facilitates a risk averse culture, is IT-centric, focus on stability and is slow in its service delivery. By contrast, the agile IT uses agile (iterative) methodologies (e.g. scrum procedures), concentrates on innovation, is business-centric, focus on agility and speed, and is fast in its deliveries. The researchers noted that traditional as well agile governance mechanisms, processes and organizational structures are needed to respond to this duopoly of speed. However, while the traditional ITG mechanisms that focus on IT exploitation are prominent in literature, the qualitative investigation uncovered agile ITG mechanisms that can be used to counterbalance the traditional elements and to promote IT exploration and agility. As shown during the coding process, the interviewed corporations apply several agile structural mechanisms that are used simultaneously to the traditional ITG elements such as the creation of digital transformation units, lean project structures focusing on innovation and transformation initiatives. Furthermore, the majority of respondents noted that they have already implemented interdisciplinary and self-organized project teams as well as short and flexible decision paths. These aspects might enable them to gain, share, and implement knowledge; speed up decision-making processes significantly; and thus meet business demands in fast-changing environments, which are important aspects to explore innovations and to promote corporation's agility. In terms of agile processes, many firms adopt mechanisms to ensure flexibility, responsiveness, and reliability in their decision making,

such as i.e. using agile practices (Scrum, DevOps), implementing fast/agile decision-making and innovation processes. With respect to agile relational mechanisms, the corporations implement agile ITG mechanisms to foster dynamic knowledge sharing, fast communication, and individual empowerment. Moreover, transformational leadership, collaboration, and cooperation with partners are critical to master digital transformation projects successfully.

Based on this thesis' qualitative investigation, the two patterns identified above and the theoretical underpinning, the concept of an effective ITG framework changing in response to the demand for agility calls for more ambidextrous approaches to governing IT in the digital area. For that reason, the agile ITG mechanisms grouped under the traditional dimensions, structures, processes and relational mechanisms in the qualitative investigation results will be considered a second building block within the governance concept in this thesis' exploration of the ITG-corporate performance link. Consequently, the governance concept presented in Figure 2.1 can be extended with the agile ITG mechanisms representing the counterweight to the traditional mechanisms. Figure 4.7 shows the extended governance concept, which is used in the following chapter to develop the research model.

Figure 4.7: Ambidexterity of ITG

4.7 Summary of the key findings

Two major findings were identified in this thesis' qualitative investigation. The first main outcome is that there are agile mechanisms in ITG beside the traditional ones. This allows assessing the current state of ITG in two distinct dimensions. The second finding refers to the traditional conflict between stability in the context of governance and agility in terms of dynamic adaptation, which calls for an ambidextrous approach in governing IT and might

be resolved through the integration of agile mechanisms within the traditional ITG framework.

4.7.1 ITG structures

The findings of the primary study suggest that corporations are applying traditional as well as agile structural mechanisms to master digital transformation projects. In total, six traditional and six agile structural elements were revealed.

A common view among the interviewees in terms of *traditional structural mechanisms* was that close cooperation between the CIO/COO and executive management is key to assure that IT and business strategies are aligned. Although the CEO has singular responsibility for carrying out strategic plans that are established by the executive committee, most corporations ensured that the CIO or the COO was part of the executive committee or at least reported directly to executive management. The design of boards and committees, such as IT steering committees and IT strategy boards, was also considered an important means of not only making decisions and determining business priorities in IT investments but also assessing technical implementation and defining individual portfolio measures. To efficiently align business and IT policies, such units were composed of business and IT employees as well as executive and non-executive members. Project steering committees, however, were located lower in the hierarchy at the operative level. Such committees were considered key bodies within the governance structure to ensure the attainment of project outcomes. Interviewees further referred to a centralized IT organizational structure to facilitate the interplay with business units and to capture economies of scale in terms of the governance of digital expenditures. Few corporations used business/IT relationship managers to act as intermediaries between business and IT. Additionally, in a minority of the institutions, the CIO was on the board of directors.

In all corporations, innovation was regarded as very important to keep pace with digital transformation. In this context, the interviewees highlighted the need for *agile structural mechanisms* to manage the flexible and fast implementation of digital initiatives. Hence, in terms of agile mechanisms, the majority of the institutions had set up new dedicated digital units to govern innovation projects. A common view among the interviewees was that such a unit was essential to allow better communication and more intensive collaboration between various positions across units as well as executives. This, in turn, would enable quick reactions to business and stakeholder needs. Equally important were “short and flexible decision paths” to make quick and efficient decisions on resources needed and on follow-up

activities for digital transformation projects. Interviewees also reported that they had set up interdisciplinary and small project teams comprising a combination of different experts to foster agility within digital innovation projects. Closely connected to small teams were lean (project) structures to support faster decision making. However, lean and flat structures were seen as more realistic in small and medium-sized institutions. Relatively few corporations mentioned delegating decision making to other members or using matrix organizational structures to enable interacting across business units and to foster cross-corporation teamwork.

4.7.2 ITG processes

A variety of perspectives on ITG process mechanisms were expressed. Corporations highlighted the use of both traditional and agile ITG process mechanisms. In total, seven traditional process mechanisms and ten agile process elements were identified.

In terms of *traditional ITG processes*, the majority of the participants reported having implemented portfolio management mechanisms to identify, select and prioritize projects. However, to monitor the progress of investments, IT budget control and reporting mechanisms are implemented. In addition, electronic tools, as a project tracking mechanism, are applied for detailed project tracking, time tracking and overall control. Many corporations also pointed out that they still use traditional waterfall approaches to govern projects (project governance mechanism) and that they face challenges regarding mastering digital innovations. To identify opportunities to support the strategic direction of the corporation and to determine key planning issues and objectives in terms of IT strategy, the executives mainly hold formal planning meetings on an annual, semi-annual or quarterly basis. In relatively few corporations, benefit and demand management mechanisms were identified.

To foster organizational agility in introducing digital innovations, the interviewed corporations highlighted the implementation of several *agile ITG mechanisms*. One of the most important aspects that the participants noted was the use of agile practices such as Scrum, Design Thinking, and DevOps. Additionally, trial-and-error processes were seen as key mechanisms in digital transformation projects that might enhance corporate agility. Furthermore, respondents highlighted fast and agile decision-making processes as significant for acting flexibly and rapidly when making decisions. To trace the success of the implemented digital innovations and to improve their services and products, some interviewees highlighted having implemented KPIs such as STP rate conversion or online

client feedback. The participants also noted having introduced lessons learned processes in agile work to increase employees' knowledge of future projects. In some interviewees' corporations, innovation processes were identified. These were seen as important for promoting innovation, which in turn may enhance organizational agility. Relatively few executives mentioned using more flexible and faster prioritizing, coordination or project monitoring and evaluation processes.

4.7.3 ITG relational mechanisms

In the realm of ITG relational mechanisms, the qualitative investigation revealed a plethora of activities that corporations have adopted to foster communication, collaboration, and participation within a corporation that are each promoted through nine traditional and agile elements.

With respect to *traditional ITG mechanisms*, the executives of the financial institutions highlighted the importance of regular internal communication to inform employees across the corporation. Additionally, informal meetings of executives with no agenda were emphasized as important by some respondents to ensure that the TMT is discussing general activities, directions, concerns and ideas. The participants were furthermore aware that management should set a good example by acting as IT-business partners when decisions are made. In this way, leadership aspects play a key role in communication mechanisms; therefore, the mechanism "IT leadership" was mentioned by several banks. Almost half of the interview participants noted that a shared understanding of business and IT is essential for efficient communication in digital transformation projects. Seen as similarly important were physically locating business and IT people near each other (Business/IT co-location) to manage the relations between the business and IT departments. As a way to communicate IT decisions and processes as well as to attract attention within the corporation, the mechanism "Senior management announcements" was mentioned by nearly one-third of the financial institutions. In a few banks, knowledge management and cross-functional business/IT training are practiced.

One of the most relevant mechanisms in terms of agile *ITG relational mechanisms* that the respondents highlighted was external cooperation with different partners, such as start-ups, business partners, outsourcing partners, research partners and internal teams across the corporation. Cooperation in general has become increasingly important to achieve a corporation's strategic goals and to support a corporation's agility. Moreover, transformational leadership and open communication and participation were emphasized by

the experts since such mechanisms play key roles in empowering employees and achieving transparency in communication. To facilitate communication, the establishment of lean communication structures was highlighted by some interview participants. The use of social and digital media, such as enterprise social networking, Twitter, Facebook, and WebEx, was considered equally important by managers to communicate initiatives throughout the corporation as well as to the clients. Some bank executives also mentioned mechanisms such as regular training, teamwork and cross-functional training for the staff. These mechanisms not only increase efficiency in employees but also encourage professional development, team performance and overall cohesion. A few executives stated that their institutions had established specific innovation rooms or meetings where people could meet to discuss innovations and that they used management dialogues and campaigns to improve communication and transparency within their corporations.

4.7.4 Transferability check

The main objective of checking transferability was to determine whether the ITG mechanisms revealed in the banking study are relevant in other industries. Hence, a qualitative cross-industry study with participants from eight corporations was conducted following the same analysis steps as those used in the primary qualitative study. The results of the transferability check confirmed that of the 47 ITG mechanisms found in the banking study, 45 were also practiced in other industries.

4.7.5 ITG patterns

Two main key patterns were identified. While the first indicates that corporations use a variety of traditional and agile structures, processes and relational mechanisms, the second pattern shows that corporations try to apply a balance of traditional and agile mechanisms within their ITG framework. This led to the conclusion that the concept of an effective ITG framework changing in response to the demand for agility calls for more ambidextrous approaches to governing IT in the digital area. Consequently, the governance concept was extended with the second building block – a concept of an ITG framework containing both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms grouped under the same general dimensional structure and with the same process and relational mechanisms as in the conventional ITG literature.

4.8 Preliminary discussions

The main objectives of this chapter were to conduct qualitative analyses to identify agile aspects of the governance concept and to elicit major patterns of ITG mechanisms in the digital world. Identifying the traditional and agile mechanisms implemented in the banking industry to master digital innovations allowed the thesis researcher to identify how the concept of an effective ITG framework has changed with regard to the demand for agility (RQ2). As indicated in Section 4.4, the analysis revealed both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms and identified two key ITG patterns. The transferability check confirmed that these ITG elements occur not only in the banking industry but also in other sectors. Therefore, the findings of the qualitative studies allowed the thesis researcher to achieve deep insights into the governance constructs responsible for digital transformation within the interviewed corporations from an empirical point of view.

Innovations enable corporations to make use of these innovations in the form of improved competitiveness. The systematic development and subsequent use of innovations have a significant impact on competitiveness. In this context, ITG plays an important role in governing IT by structuring the future orientation of the corporation's portfolio of offerings. However, existing approaches to ITG usually rely on a linear approach based on stability, predictability and efficiency (Ambler and Lines, 2012; Luna *et al.*, 2014). Implementing only such approaches made sense in the pre-digital world, as that world was characterized by the relative stability of technology and the market environment, and hierarchical business management mechanisms represented an efficient method of governance (Denning, 2015; Kotter, 2014b). However, to meet the demands of the digital age, the agile aspect of governing IT is becoming increasingly important. The qualitative results of this chapter confirm that the integration of agile mechanisms into the governance concept is highly relevant for the design of ITG frameworks in the digital age to ensure the competitiveness of corporations in a dynamic business environment. Therefore, the identified agile mechanisms may help to create a dynamic capability that enables corporations to reconfigure, assemble, and integrate the resources, information, processes, and technologies embedded in the existing activities within an organization.

As Gartner (2018) shows, two separate modes of IT delivery exist, one focusing on stability and one on agility. While mode 1 is traditional and sequential, emphasizing safety and accuracy, mode 2 is exploratory and non-linear, emphasizing agility and speed. However, the mechanisms explored in this qualitative research should be considered one side of the balancing act for the traditional ITG mechanisms and not the desired end state within one

mode. The qualitative analysis shows that corporations have implemented traditional as well as agile ITG mechanisms without separating the two modes in governing digitalization projects. Therefore, effective ITG should consider a combination of traditional and agile mechanisms to master digital transformation by following an ambidextrous approach. The two systems – traditional and agile – should work together, with a constant flow of information and activity between them (Kotter, 2014a). In other words, to be effective, agile ITG governance must work seamlessly and organically with both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms to ensure that tasks are completed efficiently and reliably across the organization and that the organization is constantly and incrementally improving itself and managing the increasing strategic challenges with speed and agility. Therefore, the interaction between the traditional and agile mechanisms should be optimized in management strategies to positively impact the agility of a corporation. In summary, the results of this thesis' qualitative investigations indicate that successful ITG requires mechanisms that, on the one hand, support the existing business with continuous, incremental improvements and, on the other hand, foster the implementation of breakthrough innovation. In the literature, this is known as the ambidexterity approach. Therefore, to further enhance the research model as outlined in Figure 2.4 the idea of the ambidexterity of ITG is applied, which represents the second building block of this thesis' research model.

5 Development of the Research Model

Following the research process design of this thesis, as presented in Figure 3.2, this chapter is concerned with the development of the research model (research phase three). To do so, it combines the building blocks established in the previous chapters by following the steps presented in the methodology in Section 3.3. Hence, it aims to build the final research model based on the outcomes of the literature analysis (Chapter 2) and the qualitative investigation (Chapter 4). SEM²⁸ is used to conceptualize and operationalize the constructs. This chapter starts with the conceptualization of the research model, which includes the specification of the structural model and the formulation of hypotheses. After the specification of the measurement model, it proceeds with the scale development of the agile ITG mechanisms. Finally, the complete research model is presented in detail.

5.1 Conceptualizing

5.1.1 Specification of the structural model

As indicated in the literature analysis in Chapter 2, several researchers have previously investigated the ITG-corporate performance relationship. The results of the literature analysis showed that business/IT alignment is the most frequently explored dimension of the ITG-corporate performance relationship and is considered one of the important necessary mediating factors in the chain of value creation (Building Block One – Mediator Business/IT Alignment). Therefore, based on the results of the systematic literature review, the basic research model was developed by including the first building block within the ITG-corporate performance association. This led to the integration of the general business/IT alignment construct as a mediator of the ITG-corporate performance link and resulted in the basic research model depicted in Figure 2.3. Section 2.3 then provided the theoretical foundation for the mediation aspect of the business/IT alignment concept within the ITG-corporate performance relationship and allowed deeper insights into their interactions. As a result, the initial research model derived from the study of Wu *et al.* (2015) was presented in Figure 2.4. The application of this model is appropriate for this thesis because it represents the most coherent established conceptual model in the literature. Furthermore, as the aforementioned

²⁸ For basic SEM concepts and modeling guidelines readers of this thesis are forwarded to the book of Hair *et al.* (2016, pp. 11–14).

study is one of the latest empirical studies seeking to explain the link between ITG and corporate performance through intellectual business/IT alignment, its results can be used as a benchmark for this thesis’s quantitative analysis. Moreover, comparing the results of this thesis with the findings of Wu *et al.* (2015) makes it possible to illustrate how the agile aspect within the governance concept contributes to business/IT alignment and finally to corporate performance. In their study, the authors show that the impact of ITG mechanisms on corporate performance is fully mediated by the intellectual dimension of IT/business alignment. Their model explains approximately 27% and 30% of the variance in business/IT alignment and corporate performance, respectively. However, they mainly implement traditional ITG mechanisms in the ITG framework. Nevertheless, as indicated in the qualitative examination, the concept of an effective ITG framework changing in response to the demand for agility in corporations calls for more ambidextrous ITG approaches (see Figure 4.7) – explicitly by integrating traditional as well as agile ITG mechanisms into the governance concept (Building Block Two – Ambidexterity of ITG). Thus, to investigate the third research question (RQ3), namely, how the concept of agility affects the ITG–corporate performance relationship, the initial research model was further adapted in Figure 2.4 by extending the governance concept with agile ITG mechanisms that counterbalance the traditional elements. As a result, the following research model in Figure 5.1 was based on SEM.

Figure 5.1: Final research model (extended by the building blocks)

Altogether, the research model contains four constructs. On the left side, the two constructs “agile ITG mechanisms” and “traditional ITG mechanisms” represent the ambidexterity of an effective ITG framework (Building Block Two – Ambidexterity of ITG, examined in the qualitative study in Chapter 4) and are conceptualized as exogenous latent variables (independent variables). The traditional and agile ITG mechanisms embody the social setting and are considered alignment antecedents for the intellectual dimension of business/IT alignment, as described in Section 2.3.3. The target construct “corporate performance”, on the other hand, is modelled as an endogenous latent variable (dependent variable) (right side of the research model) and denotes the alignment outcome. In the centre of the research model, the construct “business/IT alignment” constitutes the mediator variable that interacts between the ITG mechanisms and corporate performance (Building Block One – Mediator Business/IT Alignment). It is considered the alignment state enabled by the traditional and agile ITG mechanisms. Moreover, H1a, H1b and H2 characterize the hypotheses that are based on the research hypotheses H1 and H2 introduced in Section 2.3. They show the expected relationship between the constructs to be tested. However, these must first be refined, which is the subject of the following section.

5.1.2 Hypotheses formulation

Drawing on the theoretical foundation and the results of the literature analysis in Chapter 2 as well as on the qualitative study in Chapter 4, the research hypotheses H1 and H2 must be adapted accordingly. As the governance concept in the research model in Figure 5.1 follows an ambidextrous ITG framework that comprises traditional and agile ITG mechanisms, H1 should be divided into two separate hypotheses, while H2 should be reformulated. As a result, the following hypotheses to be tested through quantitative analysis can be introduced, which establishes the basis for the following quantitative analysis:

H1a: Traditional ITG mechanisms have a positive impact on intellectual business/IT alignment.

H1b: Agile ITG mechanisms have a positive impact on intellectual business/IT alignment.

H2: Intellectual business/IT alignment mediates the positive impact of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms on corporate performance.

5.1.3 Specification of the measurement model

As the research model in Figure 5.1 partly builds on existing constructs, such as the traditional ITG mechanisms, business/IT alignment, and corporate performance, this thesis relies on scales established in the prior literature. Indicators for agile ITG mechanisms are developed in Section 5.2. Furthermore, higher-order models (HCMs) are established in the research model to reduce the relationships and, in doing so, make the path model parsimonious and easier to apprehend (Hair *et al.*, 2016). In detail, indicators are grouped into lower-order components (LOCs), which, in turn, explain the corresponding higher-order component (HOC). In terms of the governance framework, the LOCs represent the agile or traditional structures, processes, and relational mechanisms, which are measured through individual indicators and then mapped onto the corresponding HOC of agile ITG mechanisms or traditional ITG mechanisms, respectively. The same approach is applied to HOC business/IT alignment and corporate performance. While the HOC construct business/IT alignment includes dimensions representing the individual LOCs, such as product strategic alignment, quality strategic alignment, and market strategic alignment measured on single scales, the HOC construct corporate performance items are grouped into three LOC constructs: financial results, operational excellence, and customer perspective (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Table 5.1 provides an overview of the HCMs, showing the relationships between the HOCs and the corresponding LOCs and the item acronyms used in this thesis.

Table 5.1: Overview of the HCMs

HOC constructs	LOC constructs	Items (acronyms)
Traditional ITG mechanisms (see Section 5.1.3.1)	Traditional structures	ITG_TS1–ITG_TS5
	Traditional processes	ITG_TP1–ITG_TP5
	Traditional relational mechanisms	ITG_TM1–ITG_TM5
Agile ITG mechanisms (see Section 5.2)	Agile structures	ITG_AS1–ITG_AS5
	Agile processes	ITG_AP1–ITG_AP5
	Agile relational mechanisms	ITG_AM1–ITG_AM7
Business/IT alignment (see Section 5.1.3.2)	Product strategic alignment	ALIN_P1–ALIN_P6
	Quality strategic alignment	ALIN_Q1–ALIN_Q6
	Market strategic alignment	ALIN_M1–ALIN_M4
Corporate performance (see Section 5.1.3.3)	Financial results	PERF_F1–PERF_F3
	Operational excellence	PERF_O1–PERF_O3
	Customer perspective	PERF_C1–PERF_C3

However, when conceptualizing HCMs, a researcher needs to clarify which type of HCM to include in the path model since such models are dependent on (a) the nature of relations among the LOCs and the HOC and (b) the relationships between the measurement indicators and the corresponding LOCs. Four main types of HCMs can be distinguished (Hair *et al.*, 2017): reflective-reflective (Type I), reflective-formative (Type II), formative-reflective (Type III), and formative-formative (Type IV). In the reflective-reflective HCM (Type I), all relationships are reflective. That means that the HOC is reflectively associated with the corresponding LOCs, and the latter are all measured by reflective indicators. In the reflective-formative model (Type II), the HOC is measured formatively by the LOCs, while the LOC indicators are reflectively measured. The formative-reflective type (Type III) is characterized by a reflective HOC to the corresponding LOCs, while the LOCs are related to formative indicators. Finally, in the formative-formative model (Type IV), all relationships are considered formative. However, researchers predominantly apply the Type II and Type IV styles to model formative links between LOCs and HOCs (Hair *et al.*, 2017).²⁹ In this thesis only formative-formative model (Type IV) emerged. Each construct's measurement models and the HCMs are presented in more detail in the following sections.

5.1.3.1 Traditional ITG mechanisms

The item measures for the latent HOC construct traditional ITG mechanisms were developed by researching the existing literature related to the different dimensions that underlie the construct. As highlighted in Chapter 2, effective ITG requires the implementation of a combination of ITG mechanisms, such as structures, processes and relational mechanisms (each dimension represents an LOC) (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009; Symons, 2005; Weill, 2004). Therefore, items for measuring traditional ITG mechanisms focus on the degree to which a corporation has implemented necessary and well-balanced traditional governance practices based on these three dimensions. Once a corporation has established appropriate decision-making units, such as committees and executive teams, formal processes for monitoring activities related to established IT policies and relational mechanisms to ensure proper communication and the active participation of different stakeholders, the alignment of IT and business strategy can be better ensured (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009; Weill and Ross, 2004; Wu *et al.*, 2015). Thus, as each governance dimension explains a specific aspect of the governance construct, the relations between the

²⁹ For more detailed information HCMs as well as on formative and reflective measures, readers of this thesis are forwarded to the book of Hair *et al.* (2017).

LOCs and the HOC are modelled formatively. Figure 5.2 illustrates the measurement model and the HCM developed to measure the traditional ITG mechanisms.

Figure 5.2: Measurement model and HCM of traditional ITG mechanisms

With respect to the individual ITG mechanisms, the items are based on the research of de Haes and van Grembergen (2009). In their study, the researchers proposed a set of well-defined best ITG practices. By using a Delphi approach to ensure adequate content validity, they interviewed 22 senior IT and business professionals and subsequently provided insights into several ITG mechanisms. Furthermore, the respondents were asked to rate the “perceived effectiveness” (0 = not effective, 5 = very effective) of each ITG mechanism, which resulted in the identification of the most effective elements. This thesis used their study to select the most effective governance elements to measure traditional ITG structures, processes, and relational mechanisms. As in the study of Wu *et al.* (2015), all indicators were designed formatively. Therefore, the conceptualized traditional ITG mechanisms construct is represented by a set of traditional structures, processes, and relational mechanisms that do not necessarily need to be correlated or be similar in their dimensions (e.g., steering committees, portfolio management, leadership). The relationships between the indicators and the LOCs and as those between the LOCs and the corresponding HOC are of a formative nature. Therefore, a formative-formative HCM (Type IV) emerged. The following two tables provide detailed information on the conceptualization of the measurement model of the traditional ITG framework. While Table 5.2 presents the construct definitions and basis references, Table 5.3 shows the individual items in terms of effective ITG mechanisms adopted to measure the ITG dimensions.

Table 5.2: Construct definitions for the traditional ITG framework

Construct	Definition	Type	Reference
Traditional ITG mechanisms	The degree to which the corporation has implemented critical traditional ITG best practices.	Formative HOC	de Haes and van Grembergen (2009); Weill and Ross (2004)
Traditional structures	The degree to which the corporation has established organizational units, such as committees, and roles responsible for making IT decisions.	Formative LOCs	
Traditional processes	The degree to which the organization has established formal processes to monitor IT policies and ensure that they are consistent with business needs.		
Traditional relational mechanisms	The degree to which the corporation has established channels to ensure proper communication and the active participation of, and collaborative relationship among, corporate executives, IT managers, and business managers.		

Table 5.3: Item definitions for traditional ITG mechanisms

Item acronym	Item	Type	Effective traditional ITG mechanism	Reference
Measures for effective traditional structures (LOC)				
ITG_TS1	The corporation has a steering committee at the executive level responsible for determining IT development prioritization.	Formative items	IT steering committee	de Haes and van Grembergen (2009)
ITG_TS2	The corporation has a steering committee comprising business and IT personnel.		IT project steering committee	
ITG_TS3	The CIO reports directly to the CEO and/or COO of the corporation.		CIO reports directly to CEO and/or COO	
ITG_TS4	The CIO is a full member of the executive committee.		CIO on executive committee	
ITG_TS5	IT is a regular agenda item and reporting issue for the board of directors.		IT strategy committee at level of board of directors	

Measures for effective traditional processes (LOC)				
ITG_TP1	The corporation has established a formal prioritization process for IT investment in which business and IT are involved.	Formative items	Portfolio management	de Haes and van Grembergen (2009)
ITG_TP2	The corporation has established formal processes to control and report upon IT budgets.		IT budget control and reporting	
ITG_TP3	The corporation uses various key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure IT performance.		IT performance measurement	
ITG_TP4	The corporation has established formal processes to define and update IT strategies.		Strategic information system planning	
ITG_TP5	The corporation has established formal processes to govern and manage IT and digitalization projects.		Project governance/management methodologies	
Measures for effective traditional relational mechanisms (LOC)				
ITG_TM1	In the corporation, business and IT managers/executives have informal meetings on a regular basis.	Formative items	Informal meetings between business and IT executive/senior managers	de Haes and van Grembergen (2009)
ITG_TM2	Internal corporate communication regularly addresses IT issues.		Internal communication addressing IT on a regular basis	
ITG_TM3	The CIO or similar role is able to clearly articulate a vision for the IT role in the corporation.		IT leadership	
ITG_TM4	The executives/senior managers of the corporation set a good example of acting as “partners”.		Executive/senior managers set a good example	
ITG_TM5	In the corporation, specific communication mechanisms are used to improve communication between business units (e.g., account management, intranet).		Business/IT account management; knowledge management	

5.1.3.2 Business/IT Alignment

As outlined in Section 2.3, business/IT alignment is seen as the fit between business and IT strategic orientation and is concerned with the integration between IT and the business plan to maintain the solutions and strategies aligned with IT strategies and business enterprise (Chan *et al.*, 1997; Lunardi *et al.*, 2017). The term “*fit*” in this context means the degree of coherence between the realized business strategy and realized IT strategy (Chan, 1992). Furthermore, this thesis concentrates on the content of alignment, focusing on how well the business strategy content matches the realized IT strategy content rather than on the process of business/IT alignment itself. In this way, it better captures the argument that business/IT alignment is the *realized alignment state* achieved by implementing effective ITG mechanisms. Therefore, the degree of realized business/IT alignment is influenced by the degree of the implemented ITG mechanisms (Wu *et al.*, 2015). Drawing on the content approach, Hussin *et al.* (2002) propose that business and IT strategies be aligned in three dimensions: (1) product-oriented, (2) market-oriented, and (3) quality-oriented. A product-oriented strategy deals with product differentiation and new product strategy; a market-oriented strategy refers to a new market and intensive marketing strategy; and a quality-oriented strategy is based on service quality, product quality, and production efficiency. The three dimensions (product, market and quality) are also employed in the study of Wu *et al.* (2015). According to them, these dimensions encompass the major business strategies that most corporations employ, and they contribute independently to corporate performance. The same setup was applied to this thesis’s mediator variable. The resulting measurement model and HCM system for the construct business/IT alignment is shown in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.3: Measurement model and HCM of business/IT alignment

Hence, the LOCs represent the three dimensions: product strategic alignment, quality strategic alignment and market strategic alignment, measured by individual indicators to explain the HOC construct business/IT alignment. However, as these three types of strategy do not necessarily covary in the dimensions, their relationship in the HOC construct was modelled formatively. This approach is consistent with the methodological literature on formatively measured constructs (Diamantopoulos, 2006; Jarvis *et al.*, 2003).

The individual measurement items were adopted from Wu *et al.* (2015). In their study, the researchers provide eight formative items for product-oriented, market-oriented and quality-oriented business strategies and eight parallel formative IT strategies to align with each of these eight business strategies. Hence, the HCM of business/IT alignment shown in Figure 5.3 represents a formative-formative HCM (Type IV). The detailed construct and item information is presented in Table 5.4 and Table 5.5.

Table 5.4: Construct definitions of business/IT alignment

Construct	Definition	Type	Reference
Business/IT alignment	The degree of coherence between realized business strategy and realized IT strategy.	Formative HOC	Chan (1992)
Product strategic alignment	The alignment between IT strategy and business strategy in terms of product development.	Formative LOCs	Hussin <i>et al.</i> (2002); Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Quality strategic alignment	The alignment between IT strategy and business strategy in terms of quality and production efficiency		
Market-strategic alignment	The alignment between IT strategy and business strategy in terms of marketing activities.		

Table 5.5: Item definitions of business/IT alignment

Item acronym	Item	Type	Alignment focus	Reference
Product strategic alignment (LOC)				
ALIN_P1	The corporation attempts to be ahead of its competitors in introducing new products.	Formative items	IT strategies supporting new products	Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
ALIN_P2	The corporation's current systems enable it to introduce new products earlier than its competitors.			
ALIN_P3	The corporation attempts to be ahead of its competitors in offering a wide range of products.		Products diversification strategies	
ALIN_P4	The corporation's current systems enable it to diversify its products.		Differentiation strategies	
ALIN_P5	The corporation attempts to be ahead of its competitors in ensuring that its products are distinctively different from those of its competitors.			
ALIN_P6	The corporation's current systems help it distinguish its products from those of its competitors.			
Quality strategic alignment (LOC)				
ALIN_Q1	The corporation attempts to be ahead of its competitors in quality of products rather than price.	Formative items	IT strategies supporting product quality	Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
ALIN_Q2	The corporation's current systems allow the corporation to improve the quality of its products.			
ALIN_Q3	The corporation constantly improves the efficiency of its production processes.		Production efficiency strategies	
ALIN_Q4	The corporation's current systems help improve the efficiency of its production processes.		Service quality strategies	
ALIN_Q5	The corporation attempts to be ahead of its competitors in providing high-quality service to its customers.			
ALIN_Q6	The corporation's current systems enable the corporation to provide high-quality customer service.			

Market strategic alignment (LOC)				
ALIN_M1	The corporation attempts to be ahead of its competitors in intensive marketing of its products.	Formative items	IT strategies supporting marketing strategies	Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
ALIN_M2	The corporation's current systems enable it to intensively market its products.			
ALIN_M3	The corporation attempts to achieve growth by expanding into new markets.		New market strategies	
ALIN_M4	The corporation's current systems assist it in identifying new markets.			

5.1.3.3 Corporate Performance

To measure corporate performance as a dependent variable, three dimensions – financial results, operational excellence, and customer perspective – were considered, as proposed by Rai *et al.* (2006) and Wu *et al.* (2015). The financial results dimension represents growth in revenue from the sales of existing and new products (Rai *et al.*, 2006). Operational excellence refers to responsiveness to customers and improvements in productivity relative to a corporation's competitors. It has been noted that corporations must balance operational costs and service-level performance in terms of lead time to meet customer needs (Fisher, 1997; Gerow *et al.*, 2014). Finally, the customer perspective dimension refers to product leadership, customer satisfaction, and corporate image (Wu *et al.*, 2015). According to Wu *et al.* (2015), combining these different performance perspectives and comparing them to the competition helps managers understand the inter-relationships and trade-offs between different performance dimensions and leads to improved decision making and problem solving. Furthermore, the elements of the mediating variable perspectives on business/IT alignment (see previous section) align well with the proposed dimensions of corporate performance, as these contribute independently to corporate performance. For example, as highlighted by Wu *et al.* (2015), a better alignment of IT to support new market strategies may possibly increase future financial returns but may not increase operational excellence at the same time. Thus, the three performance dimensions are not interchangeable, as they explain corporate performance in different aspects based on formative relationships between the constructs. Therefore, based on the aforementioned arguments, these three dimensions are sufficient and appropriate to explain corporate performance in this thesis research model. However, the three perspectives were measured through individual formative items borrowed from Wu *et al.* (2015). The overall formative-formative HCM (Type IV) was

modelled by considering corporate performance as a HOC, while the three aforementioned performance dimensions represent the LOC constructs that were measured through the individual formative indicators. Therefore, the following measurement model and HCM were established to explain the endogenous variable corporate performance (see Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4: Measurement model and HCM of corporate performance

To measure the financial performance dimension through individual items, financial metrics for the major categories were required. Wu *et al.* (2015) use return on equity (ROE), return on investment (ROI), and return on assets (ROA) as formative elements to capture the different aspects of financial corporate profits. These three aspects are also reflected in the research of Weill and Ross (2004), who identify three dimensions: profit, asset utilization, and growth. Thus, to explain the financial results construct, ROE, ROI, and ROA were borrowed from the study of Wu *et al.* (2015) as the formative items. The individual formative items for measuring the dimensions operational excellence and customer perspectives were also borrowed from the study of Wu *et al.* (2015). While the measures for operational excellence include aspects such as focal corporation responsiveness to customers and improvements in productivity relative to the competition, the customer perspective items contain facets such as the customer view of a corporation's products and services, the overall customer satisfaction level, and how customers perceive the corporate image. Table 5.6 and Table 5.7 summarize the construct and item definitions and references for the HCM and measurement model.

Table 5.6: Construct definitions of corporate performance

Construct	Definition	Type	Reference
Corporate performance	A corporation's aggregate performance relative to its competition.	Formative HOC	Rai <i>et al.</i> (2006); Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Financial Results	The degree to which the corporation's performance is better than that of its competitors in terms of conventional financial measures (ROI, ROE, ROA).	Formative LOC	Weill and Ross (2004); Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Operational Excellence	The degree to which the corporation's performance is better than that of its competitors in terms of responsiveness and generation of productivity improvements.		Kaplan and Norton (2004); Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
Customer Perspective	The degree to which the corporation's performance is better than that of its competitors from the customer perspective.		Rai <i>et al.</i> (2006); Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)

Table 5.7: Item definitions of corporate performance

Item acronym	Item	Type	Points to	Reference
Financial Results (LOC)				
PERF_F1	The corporation's return on investment (ROI) is better than the average in the same industry.	Formative items	ROI	Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
PERF_F2	The corporation's return on equity (ROE) is better than the average in the same industry.		ROE	
PERF_F3	The corporation's return on assets (ROA) is better than the average in the same industry.		ROA	
Operational Excellence (LOC)				
PERF_O1	The corporation has better productivity improvements than other corporations in the same industry.	Formative items	Productivity improvements	Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
PERF_O2	The corporation has a better timeline of customer service than other corporations in the same industry		Timeline of customer service	
PERF_O3	The corporation has a better production cycle time than other corporations in the same industry.		Production cycle time	

Customer Perspective (LOC)				
PERF_C1	Customers perceive the corporation's quality of products and services as better than that of other corporations in the same industry.	Formative items	Quality	Wu <i>et al.</i> (2015)
PERF_C2	The corporation has higher customer satisfaction than other corporations in the same industry.		Customer Satisfaction	
PERF_C3	The corporation has a better corporate image than other corporations in the same industry.		Brand/ Image	

5.1.3.4 Control variable

To account for the differences among corporations, this thesis' quantitative study used three control variables in the research model. These variables relate to corporate size, industry type and country.

To measure *corporate size*, the number of employees was used since it is the measure that is used most often in the literature (Camisón-Zornoza *et al.*, 2004). However, while corporate size is usually treated as one of the antecedents of corporate performance, in this thesis, it is modelled as a control variable directly affecting business/IT alignment in that the main focus of an effective ITG framework is the strategic alignment between business and IT. Chan *et al.* (2006), for example, show that corporate size is associated with strategic alignment between business and IT. Since it is easier for employees in very small corporations to communicate and coordinate with each other, small corporations may tend to have better strategic alignment than medium-sized corporations (Chan and Reich, 2007).

In terms of *industry type*, Wu *et al.* argue that “*IT industry may have higher performance attributed by IT supporting business strategies compared to other industries*” (Wu *et al.*, 2015, p. 508). Maria Morariu (2014) found that IT industries require more IT intensive resources as compared to ordinary businesses which require more input and physical resources. Therefore, in industries driven by IT, corporate performance may be expected to be higher if appropriate ITG practices exist, and as such may vary in corporations across industries. Consequently, the industry type is modelled as a control variable directly affecting corporate performance. To distinguish between the industries in which corporations are operating, the industry sector classification is based on the “statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community” (NACE) (European Commission, 2008).

In order to account for any culture settings in different geographical areas the control variable “country” is modelled. Several studies such as those of Miller *et al.* (2006) and Waarts and van Everdingen (2005) found that national culture influences the way IT is perceived or used. Therefore, it can be expected that culture also influences the way business and IT are aligned. Silvius *et al.* (2009) investigated this topic in their study and empirically showed that national culture influences the alignment of IT and business. Thus, it is important in this study to control for national cultural factors impacting business/IT alignment since the quantitative analyses was conducted across various countries. Therefore, the control variable country is modelled directly affecting business/IT alignment by providing a country list such as “Germany”, “Switzerland”, “Austria” and “Others” within the survey.

However, as the aim in this thesis is to demonstrate generalizable results, these variables are expected not to be associated with the dependent variables of business/IT alignment or corporate performance, i.e. to find them outside of our theoretical framework.

5.2 Scale development of agile ITG mechanisms

Following the methodology of the scale development process outlined in Section 3.3.4, the measurement instruments for the agile ITG mechanisms were established based on a Delphi study containing five exploratory analysis rounds. While the first three rounds were needed to create a list of items (evaluation part), the last two rounds were conducted to rate the items (rating part) and to identify the most effective agile ITG mechanisms.

5.2.1 Evaluation part

The evaluation part contained three qualitative rounds of interviews conducted with bank executives. While for rounds 1 and 2 the sources from the pilot study and the primary qualitative study were reused, for round 3 an additional set of 18 qualitative interviews with bank executives were conducted to refine the agile ITG mechanisms.

Round 1: Pilot study ITG mechanisms – Defining an initial list of items. The first round of the evaluation part reused the pilot study discussions (see Sections 3.2.2.2 and 4.2.2) to define an initial list of items of agile mechanisms. The five interviews with bank executives recorded during the pilot study were fully transcribed during this round, which allowed the thesis researcher to analyse each text manually. Hence, the responses to the first questionnaire were analysed using content analysis in the manner described in the qualitative data analysis section (see Section 3.2.3). This process enabled the researcher to note relevant

statements in terms of agile principles within the governance construct, which led to an initial list of ITG mechanisms. Moreover, the analysis in this phase led to the division of the core aspects of agile ITG mechanisms by magnitude – structures, processes, and relational mechanisms – and set the working definitions for the following rounds.

Round 2: Identifying agile ITG mechanisms – Enhancing the list of items. This round involved incorporating the agile ITG elements presented in the primary qualitative study (see Table 4.4) into the item pool. The results were rechecked in light of the scale development process, meaning that slight modifications, such as renaming or regrouping a few items, occurred at the ends of all the rounds. For example, after the data set was reanalysed, the process mechanism “Evaluation processes for innovation” (identified in the primary qualitative study) was regrouped in the structures dimension and renamed “Innovation Lab”. Furthermore, the agile mechanism “Project and budget monitoring” was included in the new mechanism “Agile project and product management”. Therefore, the integration of the agile ITG mechanisms into the item pool led to an enhanced list of items.

Round 3: Refining agile ITG mechanisms – Completing the list of items. In the third round, the questions in the questionnaire were adjusted based on the analysis output from the previous two rounds and focused on more specific themes in the context of agile ITG mechanisms. Furthermore, in contrast with the previous rounds, which included a random sample of agile and non-agile banks, this stage considered a selected sample of only agile banks. This was done using the analysis of the previous phases. Executives of 18 banks in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria agreed to be interviewed. All the interviews were recorded. To analyse the data collected in this phase, the thesis researcher listened to the tapes and transcribed only the relevant text passages that fit the context of agile governance mechanisms. Such an approach represents a refining process (Strauss and Corbin, 1996). Thus, this procedure allowed the researcher to assign the new coding components to groups in the existing list and to further enhance the dimensions with new ITG mechanisms. Moreover, the respondents were invited to a focus group session to discuss the outcomes. Thirteen executives took part in a closed-door meeting in which the results were evaluated. This led to several modifications of the draft list of items and provided a complete cycle for understanding the respondents’ points of view about agile governance mechanisms. In turn, the outcome of this round led to extensive insight into agile governance mechanisms.

5.2.2 Rating part

To reduce the number of items, the scale development process contained two rounds of quantitative screening in which the effectiveness of agile ITG mechanisms was rated by the respondents. This led to the identification of the most effective agile ITG elements.

Rounds 4 and 5: Quantitative screening – Reducing and finalizing the list of items. Similar to the Delphi research work of de Haes and van Grembergen (2009), the respondents were asked in a questionnaire (see Appendix E) to rate the “perceived effectiveness” (0 = not effective, 5 = very effective) of each of the reviewed agile ITG mechanisms. Round 3 contained the 13 members of the focus group, while the fourth round, contained 16 professors from different universities in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria who are considered experts in the governance domain. The questionnaire was pilot tested for ambiguity and vagueness with professors and doctoral students at Reutlingen University before being provided to the experts. Table 5.8 outlines the position and function area the respondents in each phase.

Table 5.8: Overview of the respondents

All interview partners		Evaluation				Rating		
		Round 1	Round 2	Round 3	Total	Round 4	Round 5	Total
<i>Sample size</i>		5	33	18	56	13	16	29
Position	Board members and executives	1	20	6	27	3		3
	Management level 1	4	13	12	29			
	Middle management					6		6
	Specialists					4		4
	Professors						16	16
Function area	CEO/board		9	2	11	3		3
	IT (CIO/COO/Head of Department)	1	9	3	13	4		4
	Digitalization Unit	2	7	8	17	2		2
	Corporate Development	1	6		7	2		2
	Business Department		2	3	5	1		1
	Sales and Relationship Management	1		2	3	1		1
	School of Economics/Social Science						7	7
	School of Business Informatics						3	3
	School of Business Management						3	3
	School of Computer Science						2	2
School of Applied Psychology						1	1	
Corporate size	Small (<500 employees)	1	18	6	25			
	Medium-sized (500–2000 employees)	1	8	3	12			
	Large (>2000 employees)	3	7	9	19			

5.2.3 Data analysis

The data analysis identified several agile ITG mechanisms. Thus, during the evaluation part, the respondents revealed a total of 46 mechanisms. As shown in Table 5.9, each selected mechanism was obtained from the coding process as well as the percentage of its occurrence per phase. Furthermore, the table shows the total for all three rounds. In the rating part, the respondents in each round rated all the mechanisms on the aforementioned 5-point scale according to their “perceived effectiveness”. Thus, for each mechanism “x”, the score, average, and standard deviation (SD_x) per phase were calculated, providing an overview of how the two groups and the respondents in each group rated the governance mechanisms. To identify the general effective agile ITG mechanisms based on the aforementioned rating scale, rounds 3 and 4 were summed, which resulted in a final sample size of 29. The last column in Table 5.9 provides the final average rating and standard deviation per mechanism. All ITG mechanisms with an average rating equal to or greater than 3.75 were added to the pool of effective mechanisms. The critical value of 3.75 on the 5-point scale represents an ITG mechanism rated as “effective” or “very effective”. Therefore, ratings higher than 3.75 imply greater effectiveness. In Table 5.9, the blue-shaded boxes indicate the final results of effective agile ITG mechanisms. The analysis revealed 21 effective agile mechanisms (six structural elements, seven processes, and eight relational/communication mechanisms). The ITG mechanisms identified as effective are briefly discussed in the following sections.

Table 5.9: Agile ITG mechanisms and their perceived effectiveness

X	Agile ITG mechanisms	Evaluation part								Rating part								
		Round 1 Sample size = 5		Round 2 Sample size = 33		Round 3 Sample size = 18		Total Sample size = 56		Round 4 Sample size = 13			Round 5 Sample size = 16			Final Rating Sample size = 29		
		Mentions	%	Mentions	%	Mentions	%	Mentions	%	Score	Average x	SD _x	Score	Average x	SD _x	Score	Average x	SD _x
Agile Structures	1 Interdisciplinary and self-organized project teams	5	100	13	39.4	8	44.4	26	46.4	51	3.9	0.6	73	4.6	0.5	124	4.3	0.6
	2 Short and flexible decision paths			13	39.4	4	22.2	17	30.4	61	4.7	0.5	72	4.5	0.5	133	4.6	0.5
	3 Lean project organization/Product owner			11	33.3	5	27.8	16	28.6	49	3.8	0.6	60	3.8	0.8	109	3.8	0.7
	4 Digital transformation units			13	39.4	3	16.7	16	28.6	44	3.4	0.7	56	3.5	0.9	100	3.4	0.8
	5 Innovation Lab			7	21.2	5	27.8	12	21.4	46	3.5	0.9	71	4.4	0.6	117	4	0.8
	6 Transformation board/innovation board	5	100			6	33.3	11	19.6	54	4.2	0.9	59	3.7	1	113	3.9	0.9
	7 Multidisciplinary transformation/innovation committee	5	100					5	8.9	49	3.8	0.8	70	4.4	0.7	119	4.1	0.8
	8 Incubators with own agile structures					5	27.8	5	8.9	34	2.6	0.9	50	3.1	0.8	84	2.9	0.9
	9 Matrix organizational structures			3	9.1			3	5.4	26	2	1	44	2.8	1	70	2.4	1
	10 Leadership board					1	5.6	1	1.8	38	2.9	1	45	2.8	0.9	83	2.9	1
Agile Processes	11 Using agile practices			20	60.6	16	88.9	36	64.3	52	4	0.8	69	4.3	0.5	121	4.2	0.7
	12 Trial-and-error processes	2	40	17	51.5	10	55.6	29	51.8	54	4.2	0.9	58	3.6	0.8	112	3.9	0.8
	13 Innovation processes	4	80	10	30.3	15	83.3	29	51.8	43	3.3	0.6	59	3.7	0.8	102	3.5	0.7
	14 Use of key performance indicators (KPIs) for agility/smart analysis processes	2	40	10	30.3	13	72.2	25	44.6	44	3.4	0.5	56	3.5	0.9	100	3.4	0.7
	15 Fast/agile decision-making processes			15	45.5			15	26.8	57	4.4	0.5	73	4.6	0.6	130	4.5	0.6
	16 Agile project and product management	3	60	6	18.2	4	22.2	13	23.2	47	3.6	0.5	66	4.1	0.5	113	3.9	0.5
	17 Lessons learned processes			10	30.3	3	16.7	13	23.2	42	3.2	1.4	64	4	0.8	106	3.6	1.1
	18 Prioritizing processes			8	24.2	5	27.8	13	23.2	41	3.2	1.2	55	3.4	0.5	96	3.3	0.8
	19 Process reengineering (automatization and digitalization)	4	80			7	38.9	11	19.6	45	3.5	1.2	55	3.5	1.2	100	3.5	1.2
	20 Ad hoc meetings/coordination processes			4	12.1	4	22.2	8	14.3	45	3.5	0.7	57	3.6	0.8	102	3.5	0.8
	21 Optimized IT architecture	1	20			7	38.9	8	14.3	48	3.7	0.9	61	3.8	0.9	109	3.7	0.9
	22 Change management processes					7	38.9	7	12.5	46	3.5	0.6	64	4	0.8	110	3.8	0.7
	23 Prototyping	3	60			3	16.7	6	10.7	58	4.5	0.6	67	4.2	0.6	125	4.3	0.6
	24 Decentralized innovation budgets					4	22.2	4	7.1	48	3.7	1	62	3.8	0.9	110	3.7	1
	25 Co-creation workshops with clients					4	22.2	4	7.1	59	4.5	0.6	69	4.3	0.8	128	4.4	0.7
	26 Agile risk management					4	22.2	4	7.1	47	3.6	0.6	56	3.5	0.9	103	3.6	0.8
	27 Flagship projects					3	16.7	3	5.4	38	2.9	1.1	63	3.9	0.9	101	3.4	1
	28 Regular planning cycles					3	16.7	3	5.4	42	3.2	1.2	57	3.6	0.8	99	3.4	1
	29 Regular IT releases					2	11.1	2	3.6	40	3.1	1.1	48	3	0.8	88	3.1	1
Agile Relational Mechanisms	30 Transformational leadership	4	80	18	54.5	17	94.4	39	69.6	50	3.8	0.7	65	4.1	0.6	115	4	0.7
	31 Open communication and participation	5	100	18	54.5	9	50.0	32	57.1	59	4.5	0.5	74	4.6	0.5	133	4.6	0.5
	32 Continuous employee training/cross-functional training in agile work			15	45.5	10	55.6	25	44.6	54	4.2	0.5	71	4.4	0.6	125	4.3	0.6
	33 Use of social/digital media			12	36.4	3	16.7	15	26.8	42	3.2	0.8	54	3.4	0.7	96	3.3	0.7
	34 Lean communication structures			12	36.4	1	5.6	13	23.2	54	4.2	0.8	69	4.3	0.6	123	4.3	0.7
	35 Empowerment of employees			6	18.2	6	33.3	12	21.4	52	4	0.9	70	4.4	0.9	122	4.2	0.9
	36 Regular management dialogues and events (i.e., sounding boards)			6	18.2	3	16.7	9	16.1	41	3.2	0.9	57	3.6	0.8	98	3.4	0.9
	37 Regular cross-divisional communication					8	44.4	8	14.3	48	3.7	1	63	3.8	0.8	111	3.7	0.9
	38 Specific innovation rooms/novel open-plan offices	1	20	6	18.2			7	12.5	42	3.2	0.7	59	3.7	0.8	101	3.5	0.8
	39 Employee recruitment					7	38.9	7	12.5	51	3.9	1	54	3.4	0.9	105	3.7	1
	40 Management attention/management as example					6	33.3	6	10.7	59	4.5	0.6	66	4.1	0.9	125	4.3	0.7
	41 Rewards					1	5.6	1	1.8	45	3.5	1.2	62	3.9	0.8	107	3.7	1
	42 Cooperation and collaboration with	5	100	25	75.8	11	61.1	41	73.2									
	- Start-ups			17	51.5	4	22.2	21	37.5	50	3.8	0.7	61	3.8	0.8	111	3.8	0.7
	- Business partners			14	42.4	7	38.9	21	37.5	47	3.6	0.6	61	3.8	0.6	108	3.7	0.6
	- Outsourcing partners			6	18.2	1	5.6	7	12.5	39	3	0.8	53	3.3	0.9	92	3.2	0.9
	- Internal teams			7	21.2			7	12.5	43	3.3	0.8	58	3.6	1.1	101	3.5	1
- Research partners			5	15.2			5	8.9	43	3.3	0.7	68	4.3	0.7	111	3.8	0.7	

5.2.3.1 Effective agile structures

In terms of agile structures, 10 mechanisms were identified during the evaluation part, six of which were rated as effective. One of the highest average-rated mechanisms is “short and flexible decision paths” (average rating = 4.6). During the interviews, this structural element was mentioned in more than 30% of the cases. Short and flexible decision paths are important for speed and flexibility in several processes. As the respondents highlighted, using fast decision-making paths can help ensure more deliberate, thoughtful decisions by organizing relevant information and defining alternatives. This can lead to greater efficiency because people can reach the same conclusions on similar issues. Such aspects are also reflected in the mechanism “interdisciplinary/small project teams”. Of the 56 interviewees, 26 indicated the importance of having implemented such teams to enhance agility. Accordingly, this mechanism was rated with a final average effectiveness of 4.3 (out of 5). Corporations might use interdisciplinary/small teams to work agilely on a complex project that requires multiple skills to succeed. However, each project has unique characteristics. Therefore, the respondents viewed having implemented a lean project organization as important to facilitate the coordination and implementation of project activities. A project structure can take various forms, with each form having its own advantages and disadvantages. Thus, 28.6% of the respondents highlighted the need for each project to have its own product owner. This agile mechanism received an average effectiveness rating of 3.8 out of 5.

To accelerate innovations, several executives noted that an organization needs to set up specific labs as well as new organizational units. Innovation labs were mentioned by 21.4% of the respondents and received an average rating of 4 on the effectiveness scale. Respondents also noted that such labs can promote creativity, information sharing, and new knowledge building and can support various types of work, such as individual and small group work and large groups of diverse members of an organization. These environments are creative, fast, and flexible in optimizing innovation. Furthermore, the executives mentioned the importance of organizational units such as “Transformation board/innovation board” (19.6%) and/or a multidisciplinary “Transformation/innovation committee” (8.9%), which had an average effectiveness rating of 3.9 and 4.1, respectively. The respondents noted that establishing new dedicated units for digital change allows better communication and more intensive collaboration. Overall, structural elements should be kept simple to allow agile decision making.

5.2.3.2 Effective agile processes

Regarding agile process mechanisms, the respondents identified 19 mechanisms as important for enhancing agility within a governance framework. Of these, seven components were considered effective. One of the highest-rated mechanisms highlighted by 26.8% of the bank executives was “Fast/agile decision-making processes” (average rating = 4.5). These are significant for acting flexibly and rapidly when making decisions. Therefore, many respondents indicated that they use agile practices such as Scrum, design thinking, and lean approaches to promote such processes. The use of agile practices was noted by 64.3% of the respondents and rated 4.2 on the effectiveness scale. The executives further noted that taking higher risks by following trial-and-error processes (51.8%/3.9 average rating) might enhance a corporation’s agility. Such processes stimulate people to act in self-organized ways and ensure continuous learning. Equally effective, with a rating of 3.9, was agile project and product management, which 13 of 56 respondents noted. Therefore, every project should be managed and executed in small parts, as this make it possible to improve decision making and solve issues more effectively, with less waste of time and resources. Few executives regarded change management processes (12.5%/average rating 3.8) as a way to prepare for and support organizational change towards agility.

According to 10.7% of the respondents, agility is critical for accelerating innovation within a corporation. They noted that in an ever-changing business landscape in which technologies and processes are constantly evolving, opportunities are ever present. Therefore, prototyping was highlighted as an effective mechanism for promoting innovations and reacting agilely to new requirements during the development phase (average rating = 4.3). A few executives (7.1%) suggested undertaking co-creation workshops with clients. However, such processes were rated as highly effective (average rating = 4.4) and represented the second-most-effective agile ITG mechanism within the agile governance process.

5.2.3.3 Effective agile relational mechanisms

One of the highest-ranked relevant mechanisms, in terms of agile relational mechanisms, was open communication and participation. Of the 56 executives, 32 agreed that involving employees and communicating transparently have become increasingly important for achieving their strategic goals and enhancing agility within their organizations. Consequently, this mechanism received an average rating of 4.6 from experts during the rating phase. Furthermore, continuous employee training and cross-functional training in agile work received a high effectiveness rating (4.3). Respondents considered this a key element for adopting skills in critical thinking and strategic thinking and building

relationships across organizational silos. New skills would allow them to move with greater speed and agility and to creatively tackle challenges. In the evaluation part, this relational mechanism was emphasized by 44.6% of the interviewees. Moreover, transformational leadership was highlighted as an important way to motivate people. At 69.6%, this mechanism was among the most frequently mentioned during the evaluation part. Furthermore, during the rating part, the experts rated it at an average of 4 on the effectiveness scale. According to the respondents, leaders still rely on the traditional autocratic leadership method; currently, however, they must also take responsibility for and have competence in carrying out new styles of leadership. Thus, transformational leadership needs to involve employees by promoting, coaching, and evolving and not simply giving transactional orders. Consequently, in 10.7% of the cases, management attention was emphasized as another effective mechanism (average rating = 4.3). It is important for managers to pay attention to agility and act as an example for employees. Closely related to the described relational mechanisms was the element “Empowerment of employees”, which was highlighted as imperative by 12 of the 56 respondents to enable employees to make strategic decisions, which in turn allows organizations to react dynamically in a more agile manner in the changing business and IT environment. Accordingly, this mechanism had an average rating of 4.2 and was considered a more-than-effective mechanism.

In general, communication and relational structures should be lean to ensure fast and flexible communication. This mechanism was highlighted by 23.2% of the respondents during the evaluation part and had an average rating of 4.3 in the rating part. An additional important governance mechanism that respondents noted was cooperation and collaboration. Over the entire study, this component was mentioned (73.2%) most often by the executives. In detail, collaboration, and cooperation with start-ups and research partners had an average effectiveness rating of 3.8 out of 5. While assistance from research partners was highlighted by only 8.9% of the respondents, cooperation and collaboration with start-ups was mentioned by 37.5%.

5.2.4 Specification of the measurement model of agile ITG mechanisms

After the results of the scale development were collected, the measurement model of the agile ITG mechanisms construct was established. To do so, several items were selected from the pool of effective ITG mechanisms shown in Table 5.9 to measure the construct of interest. As in the traditional ITG mechanisms construct, the individual agile ITG mechanisms were grouped into the dimensions: agile structures, agile processes and agile

relational mechanisms, which represent the LOCs and aim to formatively explain the HOC construct “Agile ITG Mechanisms”. The resulting measurement model and HCM are presented in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5: Measurement model and HCM of agile ITG mechanisms

To select the final set of effective agile ITG mechanisms for measuring the construct, the measurement nature of the items was discussed with doctoral students and professors. A thorough analysis of the characteristics and dimensions revealed that the identified elements are mainly formative in nature. Finally, five structures, five processes and seven relational mechanisms were selected to formatively measure the agile governance dimensions (see Figure 5.5). Furthermore, to assess the convergent validity of the formative measurement models, a researcher may test whether the formatively measured construct is highly correlated with a reflective measure of the same construct. This kind of analysis is referred to as redundancy analysis (Chin, 1998). To avoid increasing the survey length, a researcher may use a single global item, instead of multiple items, that summarizes the essence of the construct that the formative indicators purport to measure (Hair *et al.*, 2016). For that reason, for each agile governance dimension, a global item reflecting the essence of the dimension was considered in the measurement model, referred to as “ITG_ASG”, “ITG_APG” and “ITG_AMG” for agile structures, agile processes, and agile processes, respectively. Table 5.10 and Table 5.11 present detailed information for the measurement models of the agile governance construct. Furthermore, Section 5.3 illustrates the final research model in detail, summarizing all the constructs discussed in this chapter before proceeding with the quantitative investigation.

Table 5.10: Construct definitions for the agile ITG framework

Construct	Definition	Type
Agile ITG mechanisms	The degree to which the corporation has implemented critical <i>agile</i> ITG best practices.	Formative HOC
Agile structures	The degree to which the corporation has established <i>agile</i> organizational units, such as specific committees for <i>digital transformation</i> , and roles responsible for making IT decisions.	Formative LOC
Agile processes	The degree to which the organization has established <i>agile</i> processes to monitor IT and <i>innovation</i> policies and ensure that they are consistent with business needs.	Formative LOC
Agile relational mechanisms	The degree to which the corporation has established <i>agile</i> channels to ensure proper communication and the active participation of, and collaborative relationship among, corporate executives, IT management, and business management.	Formative LOC

Table 5.11: Item definitions of the agile ITG mechanisms

Item acronym	Item	Type	Effective agile ITG mechanisms
Measures for agile structures (LOC)			
ITG_AS1	In digitization projects, teams are interdisciplinary.	Formative items	Interdisciplinary teams
ITG_AS2	For digitization projects, teams organize themselves largely independently.		Self-organized project teams
ITG_AS3	The responsibility for the development of innovations is bundled in a concentrated unit (e.g., Innovation Lab).		Innovation labs
ITG_AS4	The corporation has a digital transformation steering committee to prioritize innovation initiatives.		Transformation/innovation committee
ITG_AS5	The corporation has a multidisciplinary steering committee consisting of representatives of all management levels.		Multidisciplinary transformation/innovation committee
<i>ITG_ASG</i>	Compared to its competitors, the corporation has short and flexible decision-making paths.	Single Item	Short and flexible decision paths

Measures for effective agile processes (LOC)			
ITG_AP1	In the corporation, agile project and innovation methods (e.g., Scrum, DevOps) are in widespread use.	Formative items	Using agile practices; agile project and product management
ITG_AP2	Employees are encouraged to take reasonable risks (e.g., trying innovative ideas, trial-and-error processes).		Trial-and-error processes
ITG_AP3	The corporation uses change management processes to constantly optimize overall governance.		Change management processes
ITG_AP4	For the development of products and features, the corporation regularly uses the principle of prototyping.		Prototyping
ITG_AP5	The corporation conducts co-creation workshops with customers as an innovation measure.		Co-creation workshops with clients
<i>ITG_APG</i>	Compared to its competitors, the corporation's decision-making processes for digitization initiatives are fast and agile.	Single Item	Fast/agile decision-making processes
Measures for effective agile relational mechanisms (LOC)			
ITG_AM1	Executives in the corporation treat others as individuals rather than just as members of a group.	Formative items	Transformational leadership
ITG_AM2	The corporation attaches great importance to continuous training of employees in the area of digital transformation to promote skills for agility.		Continuous employee training/cross-functional training
ITG_AM3	The corporation's communication structures are organized in a flat structure.		Lean communication structures
ITG_AM4	In digital transformation, the corporation attaches great importance to the empowerment and participation of its employees.		Empowerment of employees
ITG_AM5	In digital transformation, the corporation attaches importance to cooperation with start-ups to promote agility.		Cooperation with start-ups
ITG_AM6	In digital transformation, the corporation attaches importance to cooperation with business partners to promote agility.		Cooperation with business partners
ITG_AM7	In the corporation, there is regular cross-sectoral communication about digitization initiatives.		Open communication
<i>ITG_AMG</i>	The corporation's communication structures allow it to ensure fast communication.	Single Item	Fast communication structures

5.3 Final research model in detail

Figure 5.6: Final research model in detail

6 Quantitative Research

Following the mixed-method design described in the methodology section, this chapter is concerned with a quantitative investigation that constitutes research phase four. It connects to the research model developed in the previous chapter. This chapter provides a detailed overview of the research findings of the quantitative strand as well as the analysis and results of those findings. This phase of the research was guided by the third research question. The three hypotheses introduced in the previous chapter were tested to examine the relationship between an effective ITG governance framework for digital transformation and corporate performance mediated by business/IT alignment. The structure of this chapter is as follows: First, an introduction establishes the basis for the quantitative analysis. Second, the data collection process, including descriptive statistics of the survey participants, is briefly outlined to show the association between the variables. Finally, the results of the multiple regression analyses are presented.

6.1 Introduction

To date, the concept of agility has not been analysed by the broad scientific community in the ITG literature. Therefore, empirical evidence of the role of agility in an effective ITG framework is lacking. In particular, a definition of agility and the specific contribution of agility to business/IT alignment remain vague. To address these gaps in the research, this quantitative study focused on the following research question (RQ3):

RQ3: *How does the concept of agility affect the ITG–corporate performance relationship?*

This quantitative analysis relied on Wu *et al.*'s (2015) study as a theoretical foundation for the ITG–corporate performance relationship. The causal model in the current research was enhanced by the qualitative studies introduced in Chapters 4 and 5 on the notion of agility and the operationalization of items for the measurement of agility. Following this research stream, agility was integrated as a major aspect of governance into the ITG–corporate performance relationship. The devised conceptual framework led to a governance framework containing both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms (see final research model in Section 5.3). This quantitative research aimed to empirically explain the impact of such an enhanced ITG framework on corporate performance. Therefore, the conceptual model

was tested using a quantitative research process with 400 executives responding to a standardized survey. PLS-SEM was used to assess the quality of the measurement models and the relationships formulated in the path model. The results provided evidence that the adoption of agile principles, values, and best practices in the context of ITG leads to meaningful results for governance, business/IT alignment, and corporate performance. Therefore, agility should be treated as a crucial concept for ITG in corporations; that is, corporations should develop a basic governance model powered by traditional ITG mechanisms and simultaneously enhance agility if they want to benefit from the full effect of ITG on business/IT alignment and corporate performance.

6.2 Quantitative data collection

Following the data collection steps outlined in Section 3.4.2, the process of the study started with the development of the online questionnaire.

6.2.1 Development of the online questionnaire

Based on the specifications of the structural and measurement models developed in Chapter 5, a structured questionnaire was developed to gather data. To do so, for all the research model's constructs, the scales were converted to a survey instrument. Particular attention was paid to controlling potential biases in the survey method that may arise from the responses, such as socially desirable answers where respondents may overinflate the rating they provide for the overall performance of their ITG framework (Podsakoff and Organ, 1986). To address this issue, the questionnaire was clearly structured. It was subdivided into eight sections (see questionnaire in Appendix F) and each section was designed identically so as not to hint at a particular section's relevancy. Moreover, the survey included a dummy question in Section 5 to identify non-serious respondents. In general, each section included category headings and sub-headings as well as a brief description to guide the respondent through the questionnaire. Furthermore, the questions were phrased unambiguously and understandably. It was ensured that (1) the language was clear and unambiguous, and standard grammar, punctuation and spelling were used; (2) each question was short and expressed one and only one concept; and (3) sensitive questions that the respondents may not have been willing to answer in a self-administered questionnaire were avoided (Kitchenham and Pfleeger, 2008). After finalizing the design of the questionnaire, the survey

was implemented using the online survey software Unipark³⁰ provided by Questback GmbH, Germany. This tool was chosen to implement the current study's survey instrument because the provider is certified by the German Federal Office for Information Security and therefore meets the data security requirements of the IT-security norm ISO-27001.

6.2.2 Pre-testing and optimization

To improve its validity, the online survey had to be pre-tested to ensure its suitability with professors and doctoral students as well as with 183 employees of a financial institution to identify potential issues with the wording, question order, and navigation (Creswell, 2012). This was done by releasing the survey for a pre-test at <https://ww2.unipark.de/uc/HSRT/>. The participants were asked to review the instrument and to comment on any typos and errors and on the overall layout, structure and design. The comment function activated in the online survey allowed the pre-testers to send feedback quickly and easily. Some of the participants' feedback was also gathered online or via email or telephone. Each pre-test participant's remarks were further validated and implemented during the pre-test phase to ensure that subsequent pre-testers worked with and evaluated the version improved by the previous pre-tester (Collins, 2003). Although most participants reviewed the instrument, only a few improvements on typos or constructive feedback the wording were suggested. These were incorporated into the final version of the online survey.

6.2.3 Identification of the sample

As described in Section 3.4.2.3, the potential participants were randomly selected from the market research corporation database of Consumerfieldwork GmbH. A total of 678 executives from corporations in Germany, Switzerland and Austria were designated to participate in the study. In general, applicants with personnel responsibility and working in a corporation with 50 or more full-time employees were nominated. Smaller corporations typically do not have separate IT departments; hence, no individual in a small corporation would be expected to have specific ITG knowledge. Therefore, the potential respondents represented small, medium, and large corporations in various industries.

6.2.4 Survey launch and data collection

Survey launch. The final survey questionnaire was published online between May 1, 2018 and July 31, 2018. The invitation to participate in the online survey was sent via email.

³⁰ <https://www.unipark.com>

Invitees were asked to participate in the online survey by following a hyperlink provided in the email.

A survey launch requires that survey participants perceive *rewards*, that *participation costs* be kept low and that *trust* be established (Dillman *et al.*, 2009). These requirements were met as follows: *Rewards* for the participants were created by explaining the academic and managerial importance of the topic to the invitees while addressing them personally as subject matter experts. As such, they were asked for help and advice to contribute to an interesting research topic. Moreover, participants were financially compensated by the market research corporation for taking part in the study. *Participation costs* were kept low by limiting the questionnaire to eight pages so that it could be answered within 15 minutes. Furthermore, the questionnaire was structured simply and unambiguously. *Trust* was established by guaranteeing anonymity to the respondents and providing them with the research context. The survey did not require any personal data that would hint at the participants' identity (e.g., number of years worked for the corporation).

Data collection. Survey invitations were emailed to the 678 experts obtained from the previously mentioned market research database. The welcome page of the online questionnaire outlined the purpose of the survey. It also stated that confidentiality and the anonymity of the responses were ensured. Then, the participants indicated whether they had executive responsibility in their current position. If they indicated no, they were eliminated from the analysis. After the respondents were asked to provide demographic information about themselves and their corporation, the actual questions for the constructs of interest started. If the dummy question was not answered correctly, the participants were eliminated due to poor quality; otherwise, they could proceed with the survey. The incoming response data were stored in the database. During the period of data collection, the response status was updated on a daily basis. Because the response rate progressed well during the data collection period, no reminders were sent by the thesis researcher. The final sample size was 400 completed questionnaires (response rate 59%). Figure 6.1 outlines the detailed response rates during the data collection. However, before providing the sample demographics, descriptive statistics and data results of the survey, which are the subject of Section 6.4, the basis for the data analysis is described in Section 6.3.

Figure 6.1: Response rates in detail

6.3 Quantitative data analysis

A key requirement for quantitative analyses when conducting SEM is to assess the internal validity and reliability of the empirical results. Therefore, Table 6.1 provides an overview of the criteria and thresholds used during the evaluation process of the PLS-SEM analysis to assess the quality and consistency of the PLS-SEM findings, which are based on Hair *et al.* (2016) and Hair *et al.* (2017). As a support, SmartPLS software (Ringle *et al.*, 2017) was used to investigate the data as it provides several functionalities as well as a graphical interface and allows the computation of the PLS path model.

Table 6.1: Overview evaluation criteria and thresholds in PLS-SEM

Step/Criterion	Evaluation criteria/rules of thumb
Step 1: Evaluation of the formative measurement models	
Convergent validity (redundancy analysis)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Path coefficient $p > 0.7$ for newly generated items Theoretical validation of existing items
Collinearity among items	Variance inflation factor (VIF) < 5
Significance and relevance of the formative items	<p><i>Significance:</i> Outer weight's p-values are lower than a ($p < a$), where a represents a confidence level of $a = 10\%$, 5%, 1%, or 0.1%.</p> <p><i>Relevance:</i> Outer loadings $l > 0.708$, and their p-values are significant ($p < a$).</p>
Step 2: Evaluation of the hierarchical component models (HCMs)	
Collinearity among the LOCs per HCM	Variance inflation factor (VIF) < 5

Significance of the LOC–HOC relationships	The p-values of the LOC weights to the corresponding HOC are lower than α ($p < \alpha$) at a confidence level of $\alpha = 10\%$, 5% , 1% , or 0.1% .
Step 3: Evaluation of the structural model	
Path coefficients	Values between -1 and +1
Collinearity among constructs	Variance inflation factor (VIF) < 5
Significance of path coefficients	The p-values of the path coefficients are lower than α ($p < \alpha$) at a confidence level of $\alpha = 10\%$, 5% , 1% , or 0.1% .
Coefficient of determination (R^2)	$R^2 = 0.19$ weak, 0.33 moderate, 0.66 substantial
Step 4: Evaluation of mediating effects	
Mediation analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Complementary (partial mediation)</i> ($p_1 \cdot p_2$ and p_3 are significant $\rightarrow p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot p_3$ is positive) • <i>Competitive (partial mediation)</i> ($p_1 \cdot p_2$ and p_3 are significant $\rightarrow p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdot p_3$ is negative) • <i>Indirect-only (full mediation)</i> ($p_1 \cdot p_2$ is significant $\rightarrow p_3$ is not significant) • <i>Direct-only (no mediation)</i> ($p_1 \cdot p_2$ is not significant $\rightarrow p_3$ is significant) • <i>No effect (no mediation)</i> ($p_1 \cdot p_2$ is not significant $\rightarrow p_3$ is not significant)
Step 5: Out-of-sample prediction	
Predictive relevance (PLS Predict)	<p><i>Phase 1: Choosing the number of folds: $k = 10$</i> <i>Phase 2: Choosing the number of repetitions: $r = 10$</i> <i>Phase 3: Assessing Q^2_{predict}</i> Assess the PLS-SEM Q^2_{predict} value for all indicators of a measurement model.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If $Q^2_{\text{predict}} \leq 0$ \rightarrow Predictive relevance not confirmed. • If $Q^2_{\text{predict}} > 0$ \rightarrow Go to Phase 4 <p><i>Phase 4: Assessing PLS-SEM MAE or RMSE:</i> Are prediction errors highly non-symmetrically distributed?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If no, use root mean squared error (RMSE) for comparison with linear regression model (LM) • If yes, use mean absolute error (MAE) for comparison with LM <p>Check if PLS-SEM analysis (RMSE or MAE) $<$ LM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If true for <i>none</i> of the indicators \rightarrow Predictive relevance not confirmed • If true for a <i>minority</i> of indicators \rightarrow Low predictive power • If true for a <i>majority</i> of indicators \rightarrow Medium predictive power • If true for <i>all</i> indicators \rightarrow High predictive power

6.4 Quantitative results

This section reports the results of the data analyses. They include the sample demographics, the calculation of the descriptive statistics of the items and the PLS-SEM evaluation based on the previously mentioned analysis steps.

6.4.1 Sample demographics and descriptive statistics

6.4.1.1 Sample demographics

Table 6.2 outlines the sample demographics. The sample contained corporations in different industry sectors, with a slight focus on banking and insurance (10.25%), IT (11.50%) and healthcare and chemistry (11.50%). The majority of the participating corporations were in Germany (95.25%), with a focus on medium-sized organizations with 251–1,000 (38.25%) and 1,001–5,000 (30.25%) employees.

Table 6.2: Sample demographics

Characteristics	n	%	Characteristics	n	%
<i>Industry type</i>			<i>Corporate size (number of employees)</i>		
Automotive	22	5.50	51–250	10	2.50
Banking, Insurance	41	10.25	251–1,000	153	38.25
Construction	14	3.25	1,001–5,000	121	30.25
Consulting, Services	21	5.25	5,001–10,000	42	10.50
Energy, Electrical	17	4.25	>10,000	74	18.50
Food Trade	31	7.75	<i>Country</i>		
IT	46	11.50	Germany	381	95.25
Healthcare, Chemistry	46	11.50	Austria	13	3.25
Non-profit	28	7.00	Switzerland	4	1.00
Telecom, Media	13	3.25	Italy	1	0.25
Transportation	36	9.00	England	1	0.25
Public, Education	11	2.75	<i>n = 400; no missing data</i>		
Mechanical, Metal	13	3.25			
Other	61	15.25			

6.4.1.2 Descriptive statistics of the construct measures

The breakdown of the respondents' replies regarding their agreement with each statement on traditional and agile ITG mechanisms, business/IT alignment and corporate performance are presented in Tables 6.4, 6.5 and 6.6, which outline the individual item means and standard deviations (SDs). The respondents were asked to score their agreement with each statement on the four themes on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree.

ITG mechanisms (agile as well as traditional) were applied rather frequently in all corporations. Table 6.3 shows the results of the individual ITG practices applied within the surveyed corporations. A higher score for an ITG mechanism indicates stronger agreement of the respondents regarding its application within the corporation, while a lower score indicates lower use of an ITG element. Traditional ITG mechanisms were more frequently applied, with all indicators achieving an average rating above 4.9 on the 7-point Likert scale. These findings were not surprising, as a corporation’s ITG in the digital age is still to some extent related to stability, predictability and efficiency. However, agile ITG mechanisms were practiced, with the majority of indicators rated on average between 4.5 and 4.9 on the 7-point Likert scale, as shown in Table 6.3. These findings indicate that conventional and agile ITG mechanisms were seen as similarly important in mastering digital transformation projects. Therefore, the results were in line with the previous feedback from the qualitative interviews, which showed that a balance of traditional and agile mechanisms was adopted to ensure cost efficiency, on the one hand, and to promote agility, on the other hand.

Table 6.3: Descriptive statistics for ITG mechanisms

Traditional ITG mechanisms								
Traditional structures			Traditional processes			Traditional rel. mechanisms		
Item	Mean	SD	Item	Mean	SD	Item	Mean	SD
ITG_TS1	5.055	1.555	ITG_TP1	5.122	1.415	ITG_TM1	5.230	1.446
ITG_TS2	4.942	1.635	ITG_TP2	5.285	1.373	ITG_TM2	5.220	1.381
ITG_TS3	5.215	1.668	ITG_TP3	4.970	1.526	ITG_TM3	5.165	1.460
ITG_TS4	5.022	1.882	ITG_TP4	5.180	1.341	ITG_TM4	5.075	1.367
ITG_TS5	5.048	1.554	ITG_TP5	5.223	1.333	ITG_TM5	4.963	1.400
Agile ITG mechanisms								
Agile structures			Agile processes			Agile rel. mechanisms		
Item	Mean	SD	Item	Mean	SD	Item	Mean	SD
ITG_AS1	4.980	1.336	ITG_AP1	4.412	1.593	ITG_AM1	4.745	1.384
ITG_AS2	4.845	1.364	ITG_AP2	4.590	1.563	ITG_AM2	4.907	1.466
ITG_AS3	4.772	1.510	ITG_AP3	4.860	1.423	ITG_AM3	4.692	1.542
ITG_AS4	4.920	1.496	ITG_AP4	4.515	1.564	ITG_AM4	4.862	1.415
ITG_AS5	4.758	1.541	ITG_AP5	4.277	1.764	ITG_AM5	4.362	1.647
ITG_AS_G	4.588	1.577	ITG_AP_G	4.560	1.570	ITG_AM6	4.782	1.434
n = 400; no missing data						ITG_AM7	4.867	1.535
						ITG_AM_G	4.970	1.476

Business/IT alignment. The participants were asked to agree on the extent to which the corporation’s IT and business strategies were aligned in the three dimensions of product strategic alignment, quality strategic alignment and market strategic alignment. As shown in Table 6.4, while the observed strategic alignment initiatives in the quality and market dimensions were rated as rather successful (average rate above 4.8 on the 7-point Likert scale), the product strategic alignment dimension was rated as partly successful and received an average rating between 4.5 and 4.7; however, it was still above the midpoint of 4 on the 7-point Likert scale.

Table 6.4: Descriptive statistics for business/IT alignment

Business/IT alignment								
Product strategic alignment			Quality strategic alignment			Market strategic alignment		
Item	Mean	SD	Item	Mean	SD	Item	Mean	SD
ALIN_P1	4.540	1.478	ALIN_Q1	4.97	1.449	ALIN_M1	4.715	1.461
ALIN_P2	4.620	1.523	ALIN_Q2	5.043	1.391	ALIN_M2	4.925	1.452
ALIN_P3	4.680	1.498	ALIN_Q3	5.178	1.430	ALIN_M3	4.925	1.622
ALIN_P4	4.867	1.400	ALIN_Q4	5.067	1.392	ALIN_M4	4.827	1.519
ALIN_P5	4.705	1.476	ALIN_Q5	5.168	1.343	n = 400; no missing data		
ALIN_P6	4.747	1.442	ALIN_Q6	5.145	1.328			

Corporate performance. In terms of corporate performance, the survey respondents were asked to rate their corporate performance compared to that of their competitors in the three dimensions financial results, operational performance, and customer perspective on the aforementioned 7-point Likert scale. The results are provided in Table 6.5. Performance in the customer perspective dimension was seen as better than that of competitors (average rating above 5). The indicators of financial results and operational excellence, however, were rated as partly better than those of the competition and received an average rating of above 4.5 and above 4.6, respectively.

Table 6.5: Descriptive statistics for corporate performance

Corporate performance								
Financial results			Operational excellence			Customer perspective		
Item	Mean	SD	Item	Mean	SD	Item	Mean	SD
PERF_F1	4.572	1.349	PERF_O1	4.780	1.368	PERF_C1	5.125	1.296
PERF_F2	4.685	1.321	PERF_O2	4.777	1.422	PERF_C2	5.027	1.279
PERF_F3	4.652	1.366	PERF_O3	4.607	1.424	PERF_C3	5.053	1.286
n = 400; no missing data								

6.4.2 Evaluation of the measurement models

The assessment of the measurement models contains evaluation criteria to examine the fit of the measurement models. As in the research model for this thesis, only formative measures were considered: *convergent validity*, *collinearity among indicators*, and *significance and relevance of outer weights* were proved (Hair *et al.*, 2016) to assess the single measurement models.

6.4.2.1 Convergent validity

To first assess the *convergent validity* of the formative measurement models, a redundancy analysis was performed (Chin, 1998). For this purpose, the formatively measured constructs were tested to determine whether they correlated to a large extent with a global indicator variable of the same constructs reflecting the essence of the construct that the formative indicators purport to measure (Hair *et al.*, 2016). For this thesis, the redundancy analysis was primarily relevant for the newly generated items in the context of the agile ITG mechanisms identified through the qualitative analysis (see Chapter 4) and further refined through the item development process (see Section 5.2). Therefore, global items for the agile mechanisms were implemented in the questionnaire, with one for each governance dimension in terms of structures, processes, and relational mechanisms – ITG_ASG, ITG_APG and ITG_AMG, respectively. However, for existing measures derived from the prior research, convergent validity between the constructs was assumed to have been established. Figure 6.2 outlines the results of the redundancy analysis of the agile ITG items. According to Hair *et al.* (2016), if the analysis yields a path coefficient greater than 0.7, it supports the formative construct's convergent validity. As shown in Figure 6.2, each path coefficient of the single path coefficient exceeded the threshold of 0.7 (0.704, 0.820 and 0.794), indicating that the agile mechanisms contribute to a sufficient degree to the intended content. Hence, based on the results, convergent validity was established.

Figure 6.2: Redundancy analysis of the agile ITG items

6.4.2.2 Collinearity among items

As a next step, the measurement models were evaluated by analysing the collinearity statistics of the items. To do so, Hair *et al.* (2016) recommend the variance inflation factor (VIF) as a measure of collinearity to determine the degree to which other formative items related to the same construct affect any formative item. Hence, the VIF was computed for every indicator per the formative measurement model by applying the PLS algorithm in the SmartPLS software. A VIF value of 5 and higher indicates a potential collinearity problem. As Table 6.6 shows, all VIFs of the items have a value below the threshold of 5, thus discounting collinearity issues among the indicators.

Table 6.6: Variance inflation factors of formative items

Traditional ITG mechanisms		Agile ITG mechanisms		Business/IT alignment		Corporate performance	
Item	VIF	Item	VIF	Item	VIF	Item	VIF
Traditional structures		Agile structures		Product strategic alignment		Financial results	
ITG_TS1	2.7091	ITG_AS1	1.6818	ALIN_P1	3.0741	PERF_F1	3.4543
ITG_TS2	2.5034	ITG_AS2	1.4365	ALIN_P2	3.8994	PERF_F2	4.2278
ITG_TS3	2.0524	ITG_AS3	2.4032	ALIN_P3	3.5996	PERF_F3	4.5359
ITG_TS4	1.8050	ITG_AS4	2.4884	ALIN_P4	3.1435	Operational excellence	
ITG_TS5	1.9530	ITG_AS5	2.2122	ALIN_P5	2.5934	PERF_O1	2.4094
Traditional processes		Agile processes		ALIN_P6	3.7089	PERF_O2	2.8361
ITG_TP1	2.7379	ITG_AP1	1.9649	Quality strategic alignment		PERF_O3	2.9732
ITG_TP2	3.0841	ITG_AP2	1.9016	ALIN_Q1	2.1784	Customer perspective	
ITG_TP3	2.4888	ITG_AP3	2.2790	ALIN_Q2	3.4358	PERF_C1	3.0585
ITG_TP4	3.2374	ITG_AP4	2.7944	ALIN_Q3	3.3638	PERF_C2	3.1349
ITG_TP5	3.0940	ITG_AP5	2.2753	ALIN_Q4	3.7899	PERF_C3	2.4563
Traditional relational mechanisms		Agile relational mechanisms		ALIN_Q5	3.1372		
ITG_TM1	2.2822	ITG_AM1	1.6488	ALIN_Q6	2.8299		
ITG_TM2	2.4151	ITG_AM2	2.1326	Market strategic alignment			
ITG_TM3	2.6570	ITG_AM3	1.5534	ALIN_M1	2.9872		
ITG_TM4	1.9673	ITG_AM4	2.8428	ALIN_M2	3.8329		
ITG_TM5	3.0020	ITG_AM5	2.0603	ALIN_M3	2.5008		
		ITG_AM6	2.4502	ALIN_M4	3.4822		
		ITG_AM7	2.4734				

6.4.2.3 Significance and relevance of the items

To estimate the indicator weights and loadings, the PLS-SEM algorithm was run by selecting a path-weighting scheme and 5000 maximum iterations. The stop criterion was set to 10^{-7} . To evaluate the significance and relevance of the formative measurement models, the bootstrapping algorithm was run with 5000 subsamples drawn from the sample of 400 valid observations. Table 6.7 presents the results, including the outer weights and outer loadings with the associated p-values.

Table 6.7: Evaluation of the significance and relevance of the items

Construct	Item	Outer Weight	P-value of the Weight	Significance	Loading	Relevance	P-value of the Loading	Significance	
Traditional ITG mechanisms	Traditional structures								
	ITG_TS1	0.2327	0.0028	***	0.8435	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TS2	0.2318	0.0023	***	0.8275	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TS3	0.2084	0.0007	****	0.7909	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TS4	0.2145	0.0004	****	0.7521	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TS5	0.3387	0.0000	****	0.8438	Yes	0.0000	****	
	Traditional processes								
	ITG_TP1	0.3002	0.0000	****	0.8797	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TP2	0.1639	0.0136	***	0.8668	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TP3	0.2563	0.0005	****	0.8634	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TP4	0.2409	0.0007	****	0.8862	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TP5	0.1835	0.0043	***	0.8669	Yes	0.0000	****	
	Traditional relational mechanisms								
	ITG_TM1	0.1812	0.0007	****	0.7996	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TM2	0.1543	0.0074	***	0.7949	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TM3	0.3116	0.0000	****	0.8911	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TM4	0.1555	0.0103	**	0.7507	Yes	0.0000	****	
	ITG_TM5	0.3692	0.0000	****	0.9157	Yes	0.0000	****	
	Agile ITG mechanisms	Agile structures							
		ITG_AS1	0.1836	0.0002	****	0.7343	Yes	0.0000	****
ITG_AS2		0.2270	0.0000	****	0.6791	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_AS3		0.3918	0.0000	****	0.8891	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_AS4		0.2150	0.0000	****	0.8410	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_AS5		0.2217	0.0000	****	0.8199	Yes	0.0000	****	
Agile processes									
ITG_API1		0.2682	0.0000	****	0.8217	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_API2		0.1803	0.0000	****	0.7641	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_API3		0.4312	0.0000	****	0.9059	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_API4		0.2080	0.0001	****	0.8500	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_API5		0.0970	0.0673	*	0.7679	Yes	0.0000	****	
Agile relational mechanisms									
ITG_AM1		0.2035	0.0000	****	0.7387	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_AM2		0.2226	0.0000	****	0.8051	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_AM3		0.1134	0.0136	**	0.6644	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_AM4		0.1169	0.0461	**	0.8346	Yes	0.0000	****	
ITG_AM5	0.1331	0.0084	***	0.7549	Yes	0.0000	****		
ITG_AM6	0.2668	0.0000	****	0.8522	Yes	0.0000	****		
ITG_AM7	0.2019	0.0000	****	0.8402	Yes	0.0000	****		

Business/IT alignment	Product strategic alignment							
	ALIN_P1	0.2045	0.0012	****	0.8600	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_P2	0.1297	0.0786	*	0.8832	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_P3	0.1842	0.0047	**	0.8850	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_P4	0.2667	0.0000	****	0.9004	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_P5	0.0280	0.5798	NS	0.7671	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_P6	0.3142	0.0000	****	0.9066	Yes	0.0000	****
	Quality strategic alignment							
	ALIN_Q1	0.2890	0.0000	****	0.8443	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_Q2	0.2585	0.0005	****	0.8935	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_Q3	0.0449	0.4797	NS	0.8232	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_Q4	0.2259	0.0008	****	0.8696	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_Q5	0.2370	0.0004	****	0.8766	Yes	0.0000	****
	ALIN_Q6	0.1022	0.1276	NS	0.8206	Yes	0.0000	****
	Market strategic alignment							
	ALIN_M1	0.4230	0.0000	****	0.9273	Yes	0.0000	****
ALIN_M2	0.3598	0.0000	****	0.9377	Yes	0.0000	****	
ALIN_M3	0.0846	0.1589	NS	0.7655	Yes	0.0000	****	
ALIN_M4	0.2365	0.0004	****	0.8691	Yes	0.0000	****	
Corporate performance	Financial results							
	PERF_F1	0.4036	0.0000	****	0.9365	Yes	0.0000	****
	PERF_F2	0.1315	0.1260	NS	0.9020	Yes	0.0000	****
	PERF_F3	0.5218	0.0000	****	0.9647	Yes	0.0000	****
	Operational excellence							
	PERF_O1	0.3904	0.0000	****	0.9023	Yes	0.0000	****
	PERF_O2	0.3340	0.0000	****	0.9037	Yes	0.0000	****
	PERF_O3	0.3762	0.0000	****	0.9194	Yes	0.0000	****
	Customer perspective							
	PERF_C1	0.3525	0.0000	****	0.9157	Yes	0.0000	****
	PERF_C2	0.3616	0.0000	****	0.9207	Yes	0.0000	****
PERF_C3	0.3817	0.0000	****	0.9022	Yes	0.0000	****	
Significant at: ****p < 0.001; ***p < 0.01; **p < 0.05; *p < 0.1; NS = not significant								

Of the 57 items, 50 contributed relatively well to the constructs and indicated significant weights at the 5% level. The majority of the item weights (46 of 57) were even significant at the 1% level. For the seven remaining items, 2 were significant at the 10% level, while 5 indicated no significance. However, for the non-significant item weights, the loadings and their significance were considered in order to assess their absolute importance, and hence to evaluate indicators relevance, to the construct. According to Hair *et al.* (2016), significant outer loadings above 0.50 should be retained. This was the case for the five non-significant indicators, all of which provided outer loadings above 0.50 and were significant at the 1%

level. In conclusion, all indicators were retained in the model as they contributed sufficiently to their constructs.

6.4.3 Evaluation of the hierarchical component models (HCMs)

Next, the HCMs³¹ were evaluated. All were of the formative-formative type (Type IV), meaning that only formative relationships between the LOCs and the corresponding HOC are present. Hence, to assess the HCMs, the path coefficients between an HOC and its LOCs must be interpreted as weights in the formative-formative relationship and therefore follow the same evaluation criteria as that used for formative measures (collinearity and significance of relations between HOC and LOCs) (Hair *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, the weights, VIFs and P-values of the HOC-LOC relationships were calculated (see Table 6.8).

Table 6.8: Evaluation of collinearity and significance of HCM relations.

HOC	LOC	VIF	Weight	P-value	Significance
Traditional ITG mechanisms	Traditional structures	2.6274	0.2533	0.0099	***
	Traditional processes	3.6884	0.2827	0.0085	***
	Traditional relational mechanisms	3.2350	0.5407	0.0000	****
Agile ITG mechanisms	Agile structures	3.9493	0.3033	0.0025	***
	Agile processes	4.6109	0.5123	0.0000	****
	Agile relational mechanisms	4.6688	0.2342	0.0191	**
Business/IT alignment	Product strategic alignment	3.8821	0.3840	0.0000	****
	Quality strategic alignment	3.3362	0.2291	0.0001	****
	Market strategic alignment	3.2772	0.4580	0.0000	****
Corporate performance	Financial results	2.6094	0.3562	0.0000	****
	Operational excellence	3.6711	0.5124	0.0000	****
	Customer perspective	2.8683	0.2146	0.0138	**
Significant at: ****p < 0.001; ***p < 0.01; **p < 0.05; *p < 0.1; NS = not significant					

³¹ There are two main approaches to handling HCMs in PLS: a) the *repeated indicators approach* and the *two-stage approach*. In this thesis, the exogenous constructs, such as those for the traditional and agile ITG mechanisms, were modelled by applying the *repeated indicators approach*. The endogenous variables business/IT alignment and corporate performance, however, were developed based on the *two-stage approach*. Readers are forwarded to the book of Hair *et al.* (2016) for more details on these two approaches.

As depicted in Table 6.8, all VIFs between the LOCs per HCM were below the threshold of 5, indicating that collinearity was not an issue. Furthermore, all LOCs contributed to their corresponding HOC, and their weights were significant, at least at the 5% level. Consequently, all HCMs were retained in the model.

6.4.4 Evaluation of the structural model

After analysing the HCMs, the structural model was assessed to test the relationship between the endogenous and exogenous variables. First, the VIF values were calculated to check for collinearity issues in the structural model. It was concluded that no critical collinearity values were present, as the VIFs indicated values lower than 5. Second, the paths and the coefficient of determination (R^2) were examined. Figure 6.3 shows the structural model and the results.

Figure 6.3: Structural model evaluation

Except for all three control variables corporate size, country and industry type that indicated no significance, all other paths in the structural model were significant at least at the 1% level. Therefore, the control variable was excluded before recalculating the model to avoid biasing the other variables and coefficients. Hence, while the path coefficient from agile ITG mechanisms to business/IT alignment was 0.7416, the path from traditional ITG mechanisms to the same construct indicated a value of 0.1218. The path coefficient from business/IT alignment to corporate performance was 0.824. In terms of R^2 values, the model explained 67.9% of the variance in corporate performance and 71.7% of the variance in business/IT alignment, clearly indicating that the effects analysed are substantive. Furthermore, the results provided evidence supporting two of the three hypotheses. However, the outcomes presented the first unexpected finding in the quantitative study. Not only did the data support hypothesis H1a and H1b of the governance construct, as expected, but there was even

evidence that the agile ITG mechanisms that were discovered in the item development process in Chapter 5 showed a far more significant effect on business/IT alignment than the traditional ITG mechanisms. In the next section, the mediating effect is examined to test the proposed hypothesis H2.

6.4.5 Evaluation of mediating effect

To carry out a mediation analysis in PLS-SEM, the first step was to check whether the indirect effect of the exogenous construct via the mediator variable was significant (Hair *et al.*, 2016). In the thesis research model, this referred to the traditional and agile ITG mechanisms via business/IT alignment. In the case of a significant indirect effect, a mediation relationship is likely present in the conceptualized model. In the second step, the direct effect, which represented the direct connection of the traditional and agile ITG mechanisms with the corporate performance construct, was analysed. If this direct effect was non-significant, then an indirect-only effect (also called “full mediation”) occurred, which meant that the mediator fully mediated the relationship between an exogenous and endogenous variable (Hair *et al.*, 2016). Figure 6.4 illustrates the direct and indirect effects within the structural model in more detail. Paths p_3 and p_5 , respectively, relate to the direct effect of traditional or agile ITG mechanisms on corporate performance. The indirect effect, on the other hand, is represented by $p_1 \cdot p_2$ and $p_4 \cdot p_2$, respectively, for the same relationship.

Figure 6.4: Direct and indirect paths in the structural model

Table 6.9 clearly shows that business/IT alignment fully mediated the relationship between the effect of traditional ITG mechanisms and agile ITG mechanisms on corporate performance, as in both paths (mediation paths 1 and 2), the indirect effects were significant at the 5% level, while the direct effects were not. Thus, H2 was supported as well.

Table 6.9: Direct and indirect effects of the paths

Mediation path 1: Traditional ITG mechanisms → Corporate performance					
Direct effect (p_3)	P-value	Significant ($p < 0.05$)?	Indirect effect ($p_1 p_2$)	P-value	Significant ($p < 0.05$)?
0.0986	0.1098	No	0.0843	0.0153	Yes
Mediation path 2: Agile ITG mechanisms → Corporate performance					
Direct effect (p_5)	P-value	Significant ($p < 0.05$)?	Indirect effect ($p_4 p_2$)	P-value	Significant ($p < 0.05$)?
0.0564	0.4690	No	0.5234	0.0000	Yes

6.4.6 Out-of-sample prediction

Finally, an out-of-sample prediction for the collected data was conducted. To do so, the PLS Predict algorithm was used to prove the out-of-sample predictive power of the established model (Shmueli *et al.*, 2019). By following the evaluation guideline introduced in Section 6.4.6, the first two phases were the choosing of the number of folds (k) and repetitions (r). As proposed by Shmueli *et al.* (2019), ten cross-validation splits, $k=10$ (Phase 1), of the sample and ten repetitions, $r=10$ (Phase 2), were used for the calculation with the PLS Predict procedure. In Phase 3, the Q^2_{predict} value for the endogenous HOC construct indicators³² was assessed to check the predictive relevance. As shown in Table 6.10, each indicator's Q^2_{predict} value was positive and therefore suggested that the predictive power of the PLS-SEM analysis for each indicator may outperform the most naïve benchmark, which is the linear regression model (LM).

Table 6.10: PLS-SEM Q^2_{predict} values of the endogenous construct items

Business/IT alignment		Corporate performance	
Indicators	Q^2_{predict}	Indicators	Q^2_{predict}
Product strategic alignment	0.5457	Financial results	0.3419
Quality strategic alignment	0.6187	Operational excellence	0.4718
Market strategic alignment	0.6033	Customer perspective	0.4112

In Phase 4, the prediction errors (residuals) of the indicators (also indicated as manifest variables (MV) in SmartPLS) needed to be checked in terms of whether they were highly

³² Due to the treatment of endogenous HCMs with the *two-stage approach*, the HOC construct indicators relate to the variable LOC scores that serve as indicator variables for the HOC measurement model. Readers are forwarded to the book of Hair *et al.* (2017) for more details on modelling HCMs with the *two-stage approach*.

non-symmetrically distributed. In Figure 6.5, the plots of the business/IT alignment construct indicators in terms of product, quality, and market strategic alignment are outlined. While the left panels represent the residuals of the PLS-SEM calculation, the figures on the right side refer to the LM residuals. The visual inspection of the prediction errors for both the PLS-SEM and the naïve LM benchmark suggest that the distribution was not highly non-symmetric.

Figure 6.5: Residual plots for the business/IT alignment manifest variables

The analysis of the residuals was also promoted for the endogenous construct corporate performance in terms of the manifest variables financial results, operational excellence and customer perspective. Figure 6.6 provides the results of the residual plots. On the left side

of Figure 6.6, the PLS-SEM prediction residuals plots are provided, while on the right side, the LM prediction errors are presented.

Figure 6.6: Residual plots for corporate performance manifest variables

As for the business/IT alignment indicators, the corporate performance manifest variables were all found not to be highly non-symmetrically distributed based on visual inspection. As proposed by Shmueli *et al.* (2019), researchers should primarily use RMSE instead of MAE unless the prediction error distribution is highly non-symmetric to compare PLS-SEM results with the naïve LM benchmark. Therefore, the RMSE values of the endogenous construct indicators from the PLS-SEM analysis with the naïve LM benchmark were used to assess the predictive power. Table 6.11 outlines the results.

Table 6.11: PLS Predict business/IT alignment and corporate performance – RMSE

Business/IT Alignment				Corporate Performance			
Indicators	PLS RMSE	LM RMSE	PLS-SEM<LM?	Indicators	PLS RMSE	LM RMSE	PLS-SEM<LM?
Product strategic alignment	0.6212	0.6372	Yes	Financial results	0.7717	0.7972	Yes
Quality strategic alignment	0.6765	0.6968	Yes	Operational excellence	0.7317	0.7463	Yes
Market strategic alignment	0.6341	0.6529	Yes	Customer perspective	0.8141	0.8246	Yes

Following the guidelines of Shmueli *et al.* (2019), researchers would expect their PLS-SEM-based prediction errors in terms of RMSE to be smaller than those of the naïve benchmarks to confirm the predictive performance of the conceptualized model. The results, provided in Table 6.11, indicated that the PLS RMSEs of all the endogenous construct indicators, including business/IT alignment and corporate performance, were lower than those of the calculated naïve LM benchmark. For example, the indicator “Financial results” had a PLS RMSE value of 0.7717, whereas the LM produced a higher RMSE value of 0.7972 for this (LOC) indicator. Thus, the thesis research model provided high predictive power because all PLS RMSEs were lower than the LM RMSEs. The comparison of the PLS MAEs with the LM MAEs, however, would not have led to different results since all PLS MAEs were below those of the calculated naïve LM benchmark (see Table 6.12) – thus further highlighting the high predictive power of the thesis research model.

Table 6.12: PLS Predict business/IT alignment and corporate performance – MAE

Business/IT Alignment				Corporate Performance			
Indicators	PLS MAE	LM MAE	PLS-SEM<LM?	Indicators	PLS MAE	LM MAE	PLS-SEM<LM?
Product strategic alignment	0.444	0.4535	Yes	Financial results	0.5934	0.6035	Yes
Quality strategic alignment	0.5014	0.5121	Yes	Operational excellence	0.5521	0.5564	Yes
Market strategic alignment	0.4639	0.4872	Yes	Customer perspective	0.6142	0.6364	Yes

6.5 Summary

Overall, the research model suggests that at approximately 72% and 68% explained variance levels and substantive path coefficients, ITG enables business/IT alignment, which itself increases corporate performance, especially operational excellence and financial results. In comparison, the study of Wu *et al.* (2015), which integrated only traditional ITG mechanisms into their model, indicated approximately 27% and 30% explained variance in business/IT alignment and corporate performance, respectively. Hence, the agile ITG mechanisms within an effective ITG framework seem critical in today's digital age. The conceptualized model further indicates a high predictive power as the PLS-SEM prediction errors in terms of RMSE and MAEs were lower than those of the naïve LM benchmark. These findings have substantive implications for corporations implementing ITG practices inasmuch as ITG should be focused and leveraged to create superior business/IT alignment.

According to Cenfetelli and Bassellier (2009), the magnitude of the significant weights can be used to determine the relative importance of indicators in forming a latent construct. Because the PLS evaluates the measurement model and the relationships between constructs simultaneously, the “*item weights of formative constructs display the importance of their impact*” (Chwelos *et al.*, 2001, p. 312) on the dependent variable or the corresponding latent construct. Therefore, as the weights on the subconstructs reveal their relative importance in determining the latent construct, these weights can be interpreted similarly to the estimated beta coefficients from a multiple regression analysis (Chwelos *et al.*, 2001). Consequently, the formative indicator weights can be interpreted as a beta coefficient in a standard regression. Some detailed observations regarding the relationships between ITG mechanisms, business/IT alignment and corporate performance are called for.

First, in terms of traditional ITG mechanisms, the most important ITG dimension referred to the relational mechanisms, with a substantive significant weight of 0.5407. Structure and process mechanisms were slightly less important, but still essential, in ITG frameworks (significant weights of 0.2533 and 0.2827, respectively). These results are slightly different from the studies of Wu *et al.* (2015) and Weill and Ross (2004), who indicated that well-balanced mechanisms lead to effective ITG. Thus, one may argue that the relational dimension of effective ITG has become the key aspect of digital transformation projects.

Second, regarding agile ITG mechanisms, the process dimension in the governance constructs appears to be highly relevant, with a substantive significant weight of 0.5123, while structural and relational mechanisms (significant weights of 0.3033 and 0.2342,

respectively) play a marginally lower role but are still substantive in an effective ITG framework. This could be attributed mainly to the use of agile practices, trial-and-error processes and change management processes, which may be relevant for introducing innovative products or services.

Third, the data generally show that the identified agile ITG mechanisms can complement traditional ITG elements to implement an effective ITG framework for digital transformation. Surprisingly, agile ITG mechanisms show a significant high path coefficient of 0.7416, while traditional mechanisms indicate a significant path coefficient value of only 0.1218. Hence, it can be concluded that an ambidextrous ITG framework containing both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms contributes to the alignment of IT and business strategy, perhaps with an even greater impact of agile mechanisms.

Fourth, market strategic alignment (weight = 0.4580) is more heavily affected by ITG mechanisms than product and quality alignment (0.3840 and 0.2291 weights, respectively). This seems to imply that the more IT strategy aligns with business strategy in terms of supporting alignment in intensive marketing and new market exploration, the better the overall performance. Product strategic alignment, which includes alignment in new product development, product diversification strategies, occupies the second position.

Finally, the strong effect of business/IT alignment on corporate performance suggests that business/IT alignment may also improve corporate performance, especially when it helps corporations to improve their responsiveness in terms of productivity improvements, timeline of customer service and production cycle time, which is a critical success factor in today's competitive marketplace.

Overall, the analysis supported all this thesis' hypotheses. First, the results supported hypothesis H1a, indicating that traditional ITG mechanisms in terms of traditional structures, processes and relational mechanisms affect intellectual business/IT alignment. Second, with respect to hypothesis H1b, the PLS-SEM analysis confirmed that the dimensions of effective agile ITG structures, processes and relational mechanisms have a positive impact on intellectual business/IT alignment. Third, the PLS examination indicated that intellectual business/IT alignment fully mediates the effect of an effective ITG framework on corporate performance, which supported hypothesis H2. In conclusion, the results indicate that the concept of an effective ITG framework suitable for digital transformation should follow an ambidextrous ITG design that allows both exploratory and exploitative tasks. Thus, agility should be treated as a crucial concept for ITG in corporations.

7 Discussion

The purpose of this mixed methods exploratory and confirmatory sequential study was to conceptualize a framework for the integration of the concept of agility into the traditional ITG framework and to test the effects of such extended ITG framework on corporate performance. To do so, the thesis was divided into four research phases and guided by three research questions. This chapter discusses the results obtained during the four research phases. After a brief introduction, for each research phase, the key findings are summarized and the results are discussed.

7.1 Introduction

This thesis researched an effective ITG framework for digital transformation. It is the first study to assess corporate performance through a wide range of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms. It considers a wider scope of the ITG framework than previous studies and thus allows for a more differentiated interpretation and management recommendations tailored to the specific situation of the agile aspect of ITG.

To do so, in research phase 1, the study combined theory – focusing on the ITG-corporate performance relationship – and the existing empirical evidence to develop an initial research model and hypotheses on the relationships between governance mechanisms, business/IT alignment and corporate performance. In the subsequent phases, a mixed methods approach was used to gather empirical data to explore an effective ITG framework for digital transformation. Initially, qualitative and quantitative information from 93 experts was analysed to conceptualize a framework for integrating the concept of agility into the traditional ITG framework and to refine the hypotheses (research phases 2 and 3). Next, quantitative data from 400 professionals tested the impact of the extended ITG framework on corporate performance (research phase 4). Consequently, these phases led to answering the research questions.

7.2 Research phase 1 – Related research

This first phase of the research was guided by this thesis's first research question, which is stated as follows:

RQ1: *How is the current research structured with respect to the link between ITG and corporate performance? What concepts impact the ITG-corporate performance relationship?*

To answer the research question, the researcher of this thesis examined the association between ITG and corporate performance by exploring the related research. To do so, a systematic literature review based on a defined search strategy was conducted to evaluate the available research relevant to RQ1.

7.2.1 Key findings

The systematic literature review identified five main perspectives with respect to the relationship between ITG and corporate performance. The main variables led to perspectives on the concepts of business/IT alignment, IT leadership, IT capability and process performance, resource relatedness and culture. Furthermore, the analysis presented core aspects explored within the identified perspectives that could act as potential mediators or moderators in the relationship between ITG and corporate performance. Figure 7.1 recaps the main findings related to RQ1.

Figure 7.1: Summary of key findings for research question 1

7.2.2 Discussion – Perspectives

The results of the literature review show that the emphasis in the selected literature in terms of the five variables is on business/IT alignment perspective, IT leadership perspective and IT capability perspective, with business/IT perspective playing the most prominent role. The findings are not surprising since these aspects have reached a high level of maturity in the literature. As these perspectives were revealed to be the main objectives of ITG, it is necessary to develop a better understanding of how they impact the ITG-corporate

performance relationship in the digital age. In this era, the rise of mobility and the speed of delivering differentiated business processes is critical to success. Therefore, the interaction between the variables needs to be optimized in managing strategies to positively impact the ITG-corporate performance black box. In particular, the business/IT alignment perspective plays a crucial role in the governance-performance link and is prominently represented in the literature. The reason is that the ultimate goal of ITG is to achieve strategic alignment between business and IT to ensure that IT investments lead to business value (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2005). The results indicate that business/IT alignment, optimized IT capabilities, sophisticated resource relatedness and improved process performance may act as mediators in the ITG-corporate performance link. However, the role of IT leadership and organizational culture may moderate ITG effectiveness and thus its impact corporate performance. In conclusion, the results indicate that there are different pathways in the ITG-corporate performance relationship. Future studies may expand the present literature by adding different levels of analysis and empirically testing the inter-relations of the key variables that impact the ITG-corporate performance association.

Based on the previous suggestion to empirically test the inter-relation of the uncovered variables on the ITG-corporate performance relationship, this test was performed in this thesis with the key variable of business/IT alignment perspective. The basic research model was enhanced with the first building block by including business/IT alignment as a mediator variable within the ITG-corporate performance association, leading to the initial research model. The constellation of a causal model containing the ITG framework as an independent variable, business/IT alignment as an interaction term and corporate performance as a dependent construct is consistent with previous studies, such as those of Buchwald *et al.* (2014), Liang *et al.* (2011) and Wu *et al.* (2015).

7.3 Research phase 2 – Qualitative research

After an initial research model was conceptualized during research phase 1, research phase 2 was concerned with the development of a model of an ITG framework suitable for digital transformation. Through a qualitative investigation, this phase aimed to improve the understanding of the agile aspect within the governance concept and was guided by the second research question:

RQ2: *How is the concept of an effective ITG framework changing with respect to the demand for agility in corporations?*

To answer RQ2, several traditional and agile aspects of governance mechanisms gleaned from 33 qualitative interviews in the banking industry were analysed using content analysis of the interview transcripts. This allowed the researcher to elicit major patterns for an ITG framework for digital transformation. To check the transferability of the patterns, eight cross-industry interviews were conducted.

7.3.1 Key findings

The qualitative study identified 25 agile mechanisms (six structural elements, ten process mechanisms and nine relational/communication mechanisms) and 22 traditional ITG mechanisms (six structural elements, seven processes and nine relational mechanisms) that banks in Germany, Switzerland and Austria use to master digital transformation projects. Furthermore, the research offered two key patterns indicating the use of a mixture of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms and striving to achieve a balance between them. The transferability check confirmed that these results are transferable to other industries. Figure 7.2 summarizes the key findings related to RQ2.

Figure 7.2: Summary of key findings for research question 2

7.3.2 Discussion – Towards ambidextrous ITG

With regards to the understanding of the agile mechanisms within the governance construct, the respondents all believed that implementing agile mechanisms helped improve their agility. The most frequently employed agile mechanisms are the ITG elements of the processes and the relational/communication mechanisms. The results confirm the

assumption that the integration of agile mechanisms into the governance concept is highly relevant for the design of ITG frameworks in the digital age to ensure the competitiveness of corporations in a dynamic business environment. The reason may be that strong and rapidly increasing internal and external pressure to develop digital business solutions, such as ancillary end customer-facing digital services, digital customer communication channels and the digitization of the corporation's offerings, itself demands a level of IT agility and IT exploration that traditional ITG has historically not been designed for (Haffke *et al.*, 2017b). Therefore, the revealed agile mechanisms may help to create a dynamic capability that enables corporations to reconfigure, assemble and integrate resources, information, processes and technologies embedded in their existing activities to promote IT agility and IT exploration. Moreover, the qualitative research also indicates that traditional ITG mechanisms are important for sustaining control. Hence, the traditional ITG mechanisms seem to be central, especially to ensure stability, predictability and efficiency (Ambler and Lines, 2012; Luna *et al.*, 2014) within a corporation. However, in eliciting the major patterns of the results, key pattern one shows that the interviewed corporations use a combination of various traditional and agile structures, processes and relational mechanisms. Key pattern two further indicates that most of the interviewed corporations strive to use traditional ITG elements as one side of the balancing act while applying agile ITG mechanisms as the other side. Thus, one can argue that the concept of an effective ITG framework changing in response to the demand for agility in corporations calls for more ambidextrous approaches. These findings are consistent with the IT ambidexterity literature, which indicates that the IT function should operate in two parallel modes (Bossert, 2016; Leonhardt *et al.*, 2017) and therefore requires an ambidextrous approach to governing IT. The two modes differ structurally and typically follow different management principles, as they are set up to achieve different objectives. As stated by Haffke *et al.*: “*Mode 1 represents a traditional approach to ITG, with an emphasis on safety and accuracy, while Mode 2 emphasizes agility and speed by operating non-sequentially in multiple iterations [...]. Mode 1 typically utilizes waterfall-driven (sequential) approaches to managing IT projects and facilitates a risk averse culture. In Mode 2, customer experience and business outcomes are in the foreground, with teams often applying agile (iterative) project management methodologies (e.g., “Scrum” techniques), targeting short release cycles, and working on endeavours with less certain outcomes*” (Haffke *et al.*, 2017b, p. 1–2). This was confirmed in this thesis's qualitative study by identifying different practices in terms of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms. However, by following the concept of ambidexterity within an ITG framework,

the two systems – traditional and agile – should work together, with a constant flow of information and activity between them, as also proposed by (Kotter, 2014a). In other words, to be effective, agile ITG must work seamlessly and organically with traditional ITG as well as agile ITG mechanisms so that the corporation ensures that tasks are completed efficiently and reliably, constantly and incrementally improves itself and meets today's increasing strategic challenges with speed and agility. Therefore, the interaction between traditional and agile mechanisms should be optimized in management strategies to positively impact the agility of a corporation. The transferability check in research phase 2 confirmed the assumption that the findings may be relevant not only for the banking industry but also for other industries.

The qualitative investigation led to the second building block – a concept of an ITG framework containing both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms grouped under the same general dimensional structure and with the same process and relational mechanisms as in the conventional ITG literature. These findings were used to further enhance the initial research model with the concept of ambidextrous ITG powered by both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms.

7.4 Research phase 3 – Scale development of the agile items

Research phase 3 was concerned with developing the final research model by considering the building blocks in the relationship between an effective ITG framework and corporate performance. This led to a conceptual model comprising traditional and agile mechanisms as exogenous constructs, business/IT alignment as a mediator variable and corporate performance as the endogenous construct. In addition to refining the hypotheses that were introduced in the related research chapter and operationalizing existing constructs, such as traditional ITG mechanisms, business/IT alignment and corporate performance, based on the literature, it included a scale development process for developing the agile items explored in research phase 2. To do so, the scale development process followed a Delphi method approach by partly reusing the qualitative data of the pilot study (5 interview transcripts) and the primary qualitative study (33 interview transcripts), enhancing them with additional qualitative interviews (18 expert interviews) and conducting a quantitative survey (29 quantitative ratings by experts) to develop the final items for the agile ITG mechanisms construct. The outcomes of the scale development are discussed below.

7.4.1 Key findings

The scale development process revealed 46 agile ITG mechanisms, 21 of which were rated as effective (six structural elements, seven process mechanisms and eight relational/communication mechanisms). Figure 7.3 summarizes the main findings related to the scale development for the agile ITG mechanisms.

Figure 7.3: Summary of key findings of the scale development process

7.4.2 Discussion – Agile ITG mechanisms

The agile ITG mechanisms revealed during the scale development process can improve the understanding of agile principles within the governance construct. The respondents to the survey claimed that implementing agile mechanisms within ITG enables the formulation of an IT strategy and the enactment of IT alignment. With regards to an agile ITG structure, corporations might use different approaches to ensure that IT and business objectives are aligned. The findings present several structural mechanisms, such as the creation of new committees, boards, incubators and labs focusing on innovation and transformation initiatives. Furthermore, the majority of the respondents noted that they have already implemented interdisciplinary and self-organized project teams as well as short and flexible decision paths. These aspects might enable them to gain, share and implement knowledge; substantially accelerate decision-making processes; and thus meet business demands in a fast-changing environment (Wiedemann, 2018). In terms of agile ITG processes, the results indicate that many corporations adopt mechanisms to ensure flexibility, responsiveness and reliability in their decision making. The most effective agile ITG process mechanisms used by the interviewees focus on the iterative development of products, learning through trial and error or prototyping, and increasing the speed of decision making by setting up lean processes and agile management procedures. With respect to relational mechanisms, the results show that organizations implement agile ITG mechanisms to foster dynamic knowledge sharing, fast communication and individual empowerment. Moreover,

transformational leadership, collaboration and cooperation with partners are critical to successfully master digital transformation projects. In conclusion, the data used for the scale development process provide relevant perspectives on new agile ITG mechanisms implemented within the German-speaking banking industry. Moreover, the study highlights the most effective mechanisms, as rated by experts, that can serve as measurement items for the agile aspect of the governance concept in future research. Based on these results, the study was able to operationalize the agile side of the ITG construct. Hence, after the constructs of traditional ITG mechanisms, business/IT alignment and corporate performance were operationalized, the uncovered effective agile ITG elements were used to operationalize the agile ITG mechanisms. This was an important prerequisite step to develop the final research model and therefore to investigate the third research question.

7.5 Research phase 4 – Quantitative research

After the final research model was developed and the hypotheses were refined, the third research question attempted to statistically test the relationships of the conceptualized model:

RQ3: How does the concept of agility affect the ITG–corporate performance relationship?

Hence, this thesis's quantitative study aimed to empirically explain the impact of an enhanced ITG framework by including the impact of the explored agile ITG mechanisms on corporate performance. To do so, the conceptualized model was tested using a quantitative research process, with 400 executives responding to a standardized survey. To assess the quality of the measurement models and the relationships formulated in the path model, the PLS-SEM technique was used.

7.5.1 Results of the PLS-SEM evaluation

The PLS-SEM technique was used mainly to assess the measurement model, evaluate the HCMs, estimate the structural model, test the mediation effects and measure the predictive power through the PLS Predict procedure. In terms of the evaluation of the measurement models, first, the convergent validity of the formative agile ITG items was checked through redundancy analysis. Then, collinearity issues among all the formative items were analysed and the significance and relevance of the items were assessed. The same evaluation steps in terms of collinearity and significance were followed for the formative-formative HCM relations between the HOCs and the corresponding LOCs. In the assessment of the structural model, collinearity, path coefficient significance and the coefficient of determination (R^2)

were examined. After analysing the mediating effect of business/IT alignment, the out-of-sample predictive power of the research model was finally calculated in terms of RMSE and MAE. Figure 7.4 outlines the results of the PLS-SEM evaluation.

Figure 7.4: Summary of the PLS-SEM evaluation

7.5.2 Discussion – Effective ITG framework for digital transformation

The statistical tests of the research model developed in this thesis ascertain that governance mechanisms can contribute significantly to explaining corporate performance. In general, the empirical results confirm that effective ITG leads to better intellectual business/IT alignment and significantly affects corporate performance. This is consistent with the conventional ITG literature, which has focused primarily on this effect by using a mixture of traditional ITG mechanisms (Liang *et al.*, 2011; Wu *et al.*, 2015). However, this thesis further integrates the agile aspect into ITG. The results provide evidence that the adoption of agile principles, values and best practices in the context of ITG leads to meaningful results for ITG, business/IT alignment and corporate performance. In more detail, the outcomes imply that corporations should appropriately apply both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms to enjoy the benefits of an effective ITG framework. These findings are

consistent with this thesis’s theoretical arguments, which posit that corporate performance is determined by combining traditional and agile ITG practices and hence following an ambidextrous approach to ITG. This in turn may lead to better alignment and finally to improved corporate performance. The analysis results supported all of the hypotheses, as highlighted in Table 7.1. These are discussed in more detail below.

Table 7.1: Overview of hypotheses results

Hypothesis	Result
H1a: Traditional ITG mechanisms have a positive impact on intellectual business/IT alignment.	Supported
H1b: Agile ITG mechanisms have a positive impact on intellectual business/IT alignment.	Supported
H2: Intellectual business/IT alignment mediates the positive impact of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms on corporate performance.	Supported

First, the results supported H1a, indicating that traditional ITG mechanisms in terms of traditional structures, processes and relational mechanisms affect intellectual business/IT alignment. These findings are supported by the extant literature, such as the studies of Wu *et al.* (2015) and Liang *et al.* (2011). Furthermore, Chapter 2 thoroughly described how such mechanisms may cause better intellectual business/IT alignment. In contrast to the dimensions of the agile ITG mechanisms, the relational mechanisms of the traditional elements play the most prominent role, while the structural and process mechanisms seem to be of equal importance for an effective ITG framework. A potential explanation for this distribution of the dimension weights is that traditional elements are inflexible and cumbersome to implement and thus may require a well-established focus on relational mechanisms. However, once such mechanisms are implemented, they may become less important. This insight is supported by de Haes and van Grembergen, who state that “*relational mechanisms are very important in the beginning stages of an ITG implementation project and become less important when the ITG framework is embedded into day-to-day operations*” (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009, p. 135). However, the path coefficient from the traditional ITG mechanisms construct to intellectual business/IT alignment showed a surprisingly lower significant value of 0.1218 compared to that of the agile ITG mechanisms. Consequently, the impact of the agile ITG mechanisms on intellectual business/IT alignment seems very relevant, while the traditional elements are less appropriate. This shift may be because corporations are focusing on digital transformation and striving to implement agile ITG mechanisms to support them in

developing digital capabilities. This assumption is supported by the literature, which highlights increasing corporate efforts to foster agile and/or digital restructuring because current traditional forms of corporate organization do not always achieve the desired/necessary success in the context of digital change (Bley *et al.*, 2016; Branicki, 2018).

Second, by investigating H1b the PLS-SEM analysis confirmed that the dimensions of effective agile structures, processes and relational mechanisms summarized under the umbrella of agile ITG mechanisms affected intellectual business/IT alignment with a significant path coefficient of 0.7416. This implies that corporations consider it important to implement agile ITG mechanisms by using a combination of effective agile structures, agile processes and agile relational mechanisms to achieve better intellectual business/IT alignment. In particular, within the surveyed corporations, agile processes seemed to be applied to promote agility in governing IT. Effective agile process mechanisms may ensure better alignment between IT strategy and business strategy through promoting adaptive planning, early delivery, and continuous improvement and hence being able to respond rapidly and flexibly to change. This finding is in line with the recent literature, such as the study of Horlach *et al.* (2018a), which points out that introducing effective agile processes, as presented in this thesis, can facilitate rapid response to changing needs by structurally converging the business and IT departments to reduce the communication distance and foster a shared understanding. Furthermore, applying effective agile structure mechanisms, as suggested in this thesis, can enable a higher degree of networking within a corporate organization, which may optimize the exchange of information between stakeholders and shareholders. This finding is also consistent with the existing literature, which highlights that in the course of digital transformation, corporations should be organized in a more networked and project-oriented manner (Arbussa, 2017; Lindner and Leyh, 2018). Consequently, increased agility in corporate organizational structures may enable and enforce intellectual business/IT alignment. However, introducing new process and structural mechanisms requires new forms of relational mechanisms, such as new forms of leadership, participation and empowerment, to achieve better alignment between business and IT, as emphasized by Horlach *et al.* (2018a). This point was confirmed by the PLS-SEM analysis. The results showed that agile relational mechanisms have a weight in the agile ITG mechanisms construct that is significant but is surprisingly lower than the weight of the structural and process mechanisms. The slightly lower impact may be because the effective agile structures and processes intrinsically already include fast and flexible ways of communication as well as empowerment and participation opportunities within the agile

processes. Overall, the results supported the high relevance of the agile ITG mechanisms developed in this thesis, covering the agile aspect of an effective ITG framework, in enabling better intellectual business/IT alignment. However, when discussing the necessity of including the agile aspect in the governance framework, one may risk considering only agile ITG mechanisms as a commensurate solution for designing an ITG framework that is suitable for digital transformation. The thesis results counteract this idea, as explained below.

Third, the PLS analysis indicated that both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms are needed to implement an effective ITG framework for digital transformation to fulfil the goal of better intellectual business/IT alignment. In the thesis research model, the results of the PLS analysis explained approximately 72% of the variance of business/IT alignment, which is a substantive amount. Furthermore, the analysis provided evidence that aligning business and IT initiatives through effective traditional and agile ITG mechanisms leads to better corporate performance. The model explained 68% of the variance in corporate performance and indicated a highly significant path coefficient of 0.824 from intellectual business/IT alignment to corporate performance. According to the analysis, intellectual business/IT alignment even fully mediates the effect of an effective ITG framework on corporate performance, which supports H2. Hence, the results indicate that an extended ITG framework with an ambidextrous application of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms is highly relevant for better business/IT alignment in today's digital age, which might lead to better corporate performance. On the one hand, the agile ITG mechanisms may allow a corporation to rapidly respond to competitive actions with a greater repertoire of responses (Sambamurthy *et al.*, 2003) and, in the context of alignment, enable swift correction of misalignment between business and IT (Tiwana and Konsynski, 2010). On the other hand, the traditional ITG mechanisms may focus on stability and enable the IT function to provide continuous IT services to the business with an emphasis on safety and accuracy (Haffke *et al.*, 2017b).

In conclusion, the results indicate that the concept of an effective ITG framework suitable for digital transformation should follow an ambidextrous ITG design that allows both exploratory and exploitative tasks. Agile ITG mechanisms may support the business side with exploratory digital innovation while maintaining superior traditional IT operational performance through traditional ITG mechanisms. Thus, agility should be treated as a crucial concept for ITG in corporations. Corporations should develop a basic governance model powered by traditional ITG mechanisms and simultaneously enhance agility if they want to achieve a fully beneficial effect of ITG on business/IT alignment and corporate performance.

8 Conclusions

8.1 Revisiting aim, objectives and research questions

The aim of this study was to develop an effective agile ITG framework for digital transformation. To do so, the research set two core objectives and defined three RQs, which were processed in four research phases.

This investigation began with research phase 1 by reviewing related research. Central to this phase was a literature review: it not only identified relevant key perspectives related to the governance-performance association, but it also provided a theoretical foundation of the study. The results of this phase primarily focused on RQ1 and provided the first building block (business/IT alignment as mediating construct within the ITG-performance link) for the research model. In research phase two, 46 qualitative interviews were conducted with experts in Switzerland, Germany and Austria. The outcomes from this qualitative research yielded a broad data set for framing the governance construct, governance effectiveness and agility. The results led to the second building block which indicated a call for an ambidextrous approach in governing IT by applying traditional ITG mechanisms as well as agile ITG practices within the governance construct. The qualitative research addressed primarily the second research question (RQ2) and met the first objective of conceptualizing a framework to integrate the concept of agility into the traditional ITG framework. Research phase 3 was concerned with the development of the research model, which built on the outcomes of the related research phase and the explorative qualitative analysis. As well as operationalizing the constructs, it also included a scale development process for developing agile items explored in research phase 2. This phase concluded with the development of the final research model including the formation of hypotheses. It represented a prerequisite step for the next research phase. Finally, research phase 4 was concerned with answering RQ3. After conceptualizing the empirical model in the previous phase, an online survey was conducted to estimate the impact of effective ITG framework (extended with the concept of agility), business/IT alignment and corporate performance. Hence, this phase finally met the second objective of testing the effects of such an extended ITG framework on corporate performance. The results provide evidence for a strong causal relationship among an expanded ITG concept, business/IT alignment, and corporate performance. Furthermore, the research model provides a high predictive power. Therefore, ITG remains a major discipline for corporations in the process of digital transformation.

In summary, this thesis has achieved the main aim of developing an effective agile ITG framework for digital transformation. The traditional conflict between stability in the context of governance and agility in terms of dynamic adaptation calls for an ambidextrous organization and might be resolved through the integration of agile principles into ITG mechanisms. In such a conceptualization, both traditional and agile mechanisms positively affect business/IT alignment and corporate performance. Moreover, agile mechanisms exert an even stronger effect on business/IT alignment than traditional ITG mechanisms. Therefore, agility must be viewed as a crucial concept for ITG. Corporations need to develop a basic governance framework powered by traditional ITG mechanisms and simultaneously increase agility in their structures, processes and relational mechanisms.

8.2 Originality

Given that industry borders are disappearing and competition is more dynamic than ever, in the age of digital transformation the need for strategic agility – speedy, customer-focused innovation that aims to improve corporate performance – is becoming increasingly obvious. As IT currently plays an essential role in organizational innovation adoption (Acemoglu, 2012), up-to-date and agile ITG is needed due to its significant impact on enabling innovation and enhancing corporate performance.

Through a systematic literature analysis and a mixed-methods design for data collection, this thesis progressively conceptualized a framework for the integration of the concept of agility into ITG frameworks and tested the effect of such an extended ITG framework on corporate performance. Each of the research phases provides an original contribution to the body of knowledge of ITG.

The systematic literature review offers relevant insights into ITG-corporate performance. It presents unique results by providing a consolidated overview of the body of knowledge regarding the relation between ITG and corporate performance. Furthermore, it reduces the blurring of ITG-corporate performance links and clarifies key perspectives that impact the relationship between ITG and corporate performance, including an overview of potential mediating or moderating effects.

As mentioned earlier, researchers have not analysed the effect of agile mechanisms in the context of ITG, although interest in this topic is growing (Sommer *et al.*, 2014; Cheng *et al.*, 2009). The interview data collected during the main qualitative investigation in research phase 2 provide relevant perspectives on traditional and new agile ITG mechanisms

implemented within the corporations and highlight the ambidextrous aspect of the governance concept through identifying key patterns. This research phase can be considered one of only a few studies that emphasize the importance of studying ambidextrous ITG, and it is unique in combining traditional and agile ITG mechanisms in relation to the magnitudes of structures, processes and relational mechanisms.

Based on a scale development process following Delphi steps, research phase 3 refines the agile ITG elements resulting from phase 2 and identifies how corporations implement agile ITG. The extant research has centred primarily on traditional ITG mechanisms (e.g., (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2005; Peterson, 2004b) and few researchers have focused on single agile elements (e.g., (Wiedemann, 2018; Power, 2011). Therefore, this part of the thesis extends the existing knowledge about ITG mechanisms in terms of agile elements within a governance framework. It provides an extensive set of agile ITG mechanisms and highlights the most effective ones. Therefore, the importance of this study is its originality in providing a clear definition and operationalization of agile ITG mechanisms.

In research phase 4, the quantitative research tests the impact of an effective ITG framework, extended through the agile aspect, on business/IT alignment and finally on corporate performance. The PLS analysis supports the high in-sample and out-of-sample predictive power of the conceptualized model. Hence, the results of this research phase contribute to the understanding of the impact of ITG on corporate outcomes.

In summary, this work presents an original analysis of an effective ITG framework for digital transformation by including the agile aspect within the governance construct. The thesis highlights that is not enough to apply only traditional mechanisms to achieve effective business/IT alignment in today's digital age; agile ITG mechanisms are also needed. Therefore, a novel ITG framework following an ambidextrous approach is provided. Such a new framework can help managers and auditors address digital transformation projects. The theoretical and practical contributions are further highlighted in the following sections.

8.3 Theoretical contribution

This research leads to several important implications for ITG theory. First, the research results support the integration of the concept of agility into existing ITG frameworks. To date, the definition of agility has been fuzzy and has been unspecified in an ITG context (Luna *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, this research contributes to ITG theory by providing a clear definition and operationalization of agility in this specific context. Agility in ITG, as

summarized in Chapter 5, consists of precise items such as interdisciplinary teams, self-organized projects, innovation labs, flat communication, and decision processes or constant co-creation with customers. The relevant items for agility might be organized in a mode similar to that of traditional items around structures, processes and relational mechanisms. Future studies on agility and ITG should adopt this operationalization and these items for construct measurement.

Second, the positioning of ITG mechanisms in terms of agile ITG practices directly connects three literatures (ITG, agility, ambidexterity) that previously remained distinct and disconnected save for the occasional reference to governance in relation to the formal aspect of IT agility or IT ambidexterity. The establishment of the agile concept within ITG represents an original level of analysis within the ITG literature and opens the door for the inclusion of agility and the ambidextrous approach in the ITG conceptualization. Therefore, this conceptualization provides researchers with an integrated and connected theoretical platform from which to launch further research.

Third, this research also demonstrates that agile ITG mechanisms can be measured independently of traditional ITG mechanisms within one causal model. This is an important theoretical outcome that allows the current state of ITG to be assessed in two distinct dimensions, offering various pathways for further research initiatives on the different antecedents and effects of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms. This thesis focused on the different effects on business/IT alignment and corporate performance. As a theoretical contribution, the results of this thesis confirm the hypotheses of previous research initiatives on the causal relationship among ITG, business/IT alignment and corporate performance (Haghjoo, 2012; Liang *et al.*, 2011; Wu *et al.*, 2015). The results of the PLS analysis explain a large part of the variance of the two endogenous constructs, with R^2 values of 0.717 (business/IT alignment) and 0.679 (corporate performance). Moreover, all causal paths in the model are strong and highly significant.

This thesis shows that the integration of agile ITG mechanisms contributes significantly to the explanation of business/IT alignment. Furthermore, the direct effect is much stronger ($\beta = 0.7416$) than that of traditional ITG mechanisms ($\beta = 0.1218$). Consequently, agility plays an important but, so far, neglected role in the relationship among ITG, business/IT alignment, and corporate performance. A full consideration of all relevant aspects of ITG might lead to fruitful theoretical developments and further research projects, for example, on the role of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms in different environmental situations or

in different industries. Therefore, this research offers possibilities for a broad range of follow-up streams of research on multiple aspects of the developed model.

Finally, the predictive power of the corresponding model can also be assessed as high, according to PLS Predict. The conceptualized model indicates high out-of-sample predictive capabilities as the PLS-SEM prediction errors in terms of RMSE and MAEs were lower than those of the naïve LM benchmark. As such, it can be confirmed that the developed ITG framework has the capacity to predict the values of both depended variables business/IT alignment and corporate performance. Furthermore, the high predictive validity suggest that the research outcomes are generalizable to other samples. These findings have substantive implications for the theoretical conceptualization of appropriate ITG frameworks for digital transformation inasmuch as ITG should be focused and leveraged by applying both traditional as well as agile ITG practices to create superior business/IT alignment which may lead to a better corporate performance. As a theory building exercise, the output of the research study supports a further investigation into the ambidextrous ITG approach and as such provides academics with a renewed perspective on how best to design IT governance systems.

8.4 Practical contribution

In addition to the theoretical contributions, the findings discussed in this thesis provide rich and relevant recommendations for practitioners. First and foremost, the practical contributions of this research might come from the implementation of the observed strategies for effective ITG. This thesis empirically shows how the notion of agility affects the concept of the governance framework. To be effective in ITG, corporations still need to consider traditional governance mechanisms, such as steering committees, the role of the CIO, clear budget control and reporting and internal communication procedures (de Haes and van Grembergen, 2009). Even more important in the digital age is the parallel implementation of agile mechanisms on the level of governance structures, processes and relational mechanisms. This leads to a call for an ambidextrous organization and a second mode of ITG with operational issues on multiple levels (Magnusson *et al.*, 2017). From a practical perspective, corporations need to implement additional governance strategies that focus on, for example, interdisciplinarity, co-creation with customers, cooperation with start-ups, prototyping or transformational leadership. The results of this study imply that corporations might be even more successful if they include both traditional and agile mechanisms in their

ITG framework. In this way, Table 4.4, resulting from the qualitative investigation, may provide a template for CIOs to derive their own mechanisms in following an ambidextrous approach that is suitable for their corporation. Furthermore, such a template may also be used for initial analysis of status quo.

Second, this study offers practitioners an extensive set of 46 agile ITG practices. Such practices can hopefully guide CIOs and senior business executives in the process of implementing agile ITG mechanisms. Furthermore, this thesis highlights the most effective elements that will enable them to achieve improved business/IT alignment in digital transformation projects. Therefore, IT executives and those responsible for creating an effective ITG framework for digital transformation can utilize the agile ITG mechanisms presented in Table 5.9 as a guide to counterbalance their traditional elements. Moreover, CIOs can observe the interplay between all three types of agile ITG practices. For example, when initially implementing agile ITG mechanisms, attention should be paid to the importance of agile ITG practices instead of focusing on agile ITG structures and relational mechanisms. For this reason, agile process methodologies such as Scrum are already designed to include flat structures and flexible modes of communication. In contrast, implementing traditional ITG mechanisms requires a focus on the relational mechanisms at the start, as highlighted in the discussion chapter.

Third, the findings might be used by IT executives to justify the work and resources required from the organizational budget for IT investment as valid proof that investing in IT will bring returns and business value if the organization opens itself to more extensive ITG practices. This might not only alleviate the pressure on CIOs to justify their expenditures but might also grant them more help and championing of the ITG framework as a whole by the individual business units and at the corporate management level. Therefore, the outcomes can serve as a valuable direction for board members and members of top management teams who are uncertain about how to react to digitization trends in their environment. Moreover, the presented framework may also be used for internal performance measurement reasons.

Finally, the results may also be important for consultants, ITG designers and authorities to recognize and account for the notion of agility within the governance construct. Most practitioner-based literature is still related to the traditional structures, processes and relational mechanisms required to adequately control and guide organizational IT decisions and actions without considering the agile aspect of the governance construct. Therefore, practitioners may wish to improve the success rate of their IT investments for digital

innovations as they are surrounded by a multitude of frameworks and prescriptive anecdotes, all promising a panacea for designing and implementing world-class ITG. By providing a concept of an effective ITG framework, the study directs organisations to follow an ambidextrous ITG approach that incorporates both traditional and agile ITG mechanisms. Therefore, it provides a valuable starting point for exploring how designers of governance frameworks can support corporations by achieving their mandate and engaging in more high-value activities.

8.5 Limitations

In addition to the identified contributions to theory and practice, this thesis has several limitations that should be mentioned. First, the quantitative and qualitative studies that make up the body of this thesis are cross-sectional studies. The economic and environmental conditions at the time of data collection may have led to a bias that limits the generalizability of the results. A longitudinal aspect of the research topics would be helpful, providing opportunities for future research. For example, this research indicates that traditional ITG relational mechanisms are more important, while agile ITG relational mechanisms have lower importance in implementing an effective ITG framework for digital transformation. Hence, monitoring an organization over time could provide valuable data to support or refute this statement.

Second, the data may be culturally biased, as the studies have a geographical focus on Europe (especially German-speaking countries). Thus, additional studies in different cultural settings would improve the validity of the thesis results.

Third, the qualitative study and the qualitative parts of the scale development process focused on the banking industry, which limits the generalizability of the results. To overcome this limitation, a transferability check was conducted with cross-industry corporations. However, the cross-industrial study was constrained by its small sample size of only eight governance experts. Further qualitative research should confirm the results and conclusions of the qualitative parts of this thesis by interviewing a larger sample of corporations from different industries. Nonetheless, the exploratory qualitative studies on the topic of ambidextrous ITG provide impetus for further research in the domain of digital transformation and its implications for an effective ITG framework.

Finally, the data are limited to responses from executives, managers and team leaders. Future research could employ matched-pair survey methods based on business and IT responses at the operational level to improve the objectivity of our results.

8.6 Future research

In addition to future research opportunities to address the limitations, this thesis opens different pathways for further investigations connected to the results. Some main directions can be directly derived from this thesis. First, as pointed out in the originality section, this thesis is the first research in the body of knowledge providing a holistic view of traditional and agile ITG mechanisms used ambidextrously that has shown an impact on corporate performance through the mediating factor of intellectual business/IT alignment. Hence, IS scholars should continue an empirical assessment of the developments to validate these results.

Second, future research can also extend the results of this thesis by identifying additional relevant ITG mechanisms for digital transformation and adding them to the model to further strengthen the understanding of their relative efficacy for an effective ITG framework. Further investigations into possible synergies, complementarities and dependencies between and among ITG mechanisms may take a configurational approach to unravel additional insights into effective combinations of multiple ITG mechanisms. Moreover, it would be useful to connect the thesis results to a framework that provides clarity for the conditions that facilitate the success or failure of implementing each of the identified traditional and agile ITG mechanisms and provides recommendations for any challenges identified.

Third, this thesis's systematic literature review revealed five perspectives within the ITG-corporate performance black box, indicating that business/IT perspective, IT capability and process performance perspective, and resource relatedness perspective potentially act as mediator within the relationship, and IT leadership perspective and cultural perspective potentially moderate the effect of ITG on corporate performance. However, only business/IT alignment was considered in the research model as a mediator variable to test the relationship between an effective ITG framework and corporate performance. Future studies should expand the present research by adding different levels of analysis and empirically testing the interrelationships of the other four perspectives acting either as moderator or mediator variables in the ITG-corporation performance association. A future research agenda might proceed by asking the following questions:

- How is each of the perspectives related to the individual ITG mechanisms?
- How are the four remaining perspectives interrelated in the ITG-corporate performance link?

Last, connections between the aforementioned variables, especially IT leadership, should be highlighted. As stated by the IT Governance Institute (2007), ITG requires leadership to ensure that IT activity is sustained and extended to achieve the organization's goals. This emphasis on leadership is confirmed by Weill and Ross (2004), who found that the factor that most separates top-performing from substandard-performing organizations is the quality of senior leadership in making IT decisions. Hence, IT leadership should be proactive and strategic (Selig, 2008), which requires commitment from the top and supportive behaviour that leads to effective resource allocation with respect to IT (Weill and Ross, 2004). de Haes and van Grembergen (2005) single out IT leadership as the most important condition for implementing effective ITG that leads to successful business/IT alignment. Liang *et al.* (2011) suggest that IT leadership is the most critical element of ITG maturity. It plays a major role in a more mature implementation of ITG practices, which can generate positive impacts on strategic alignment and corporate performance. In today's fast-changing environment, any changes in strategy may encounter employee resistance, placing a premium on good leadership (Liang *et al.*, 2011). Hence, good IT leadership is crucial in the link between ITG, business/IT alignment and corporate performance. With IT currently playing a crucial role in enterprises by driving new business models and enabling new ways of collaboration and mobility, much attention is devoted to the role of leaders, who are “*strongly encouraged to become drivers of business transformation and innovation*” (Peppard, 2010, p. 74). Despite a considerable body of work on ITG, business/IT alignment, IT leadership and corporate performance, solid empirical evidence is needed to demonstrate their interrelationship. This opens the way for further research and the opportunity to build on the results of this thesis. Therefore, including the moderating or mediating effect of IT leadership within the provided research model may provide valuable insights into the ITG-corporate performance relationship.

References

- Aasi, P., Rusu, L. and Han, S. (2016), "The Influence of Organizational Culture on IT Governance Performance: Case of the IT Department in a Large Swedish Company", in *Proceedings of the 49th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2016)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 5157–5166.
- Acemoglu, D. (2012), "Introduction to economic growth", *Journal of Economic Theory*, Vol. 147 No. 2, pp. 545–550.
- Aguillar, D.A.M., Murakami, I., Junior, P.M. and Jr., P.T.A. (2017), "IT Governance Program and Improvements in Brazilian Small Business: Viability and Case Study", in *Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems (FedCSIS 2017)*, *Annals of Computer Science and Information Systems*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 961–964.
- Ajayi, B. and Hussin, H. (2016), "IT governance from practitioners' perspective: Sharing the experience of a Malaysian university", *Journal of Theoretical & Applied Information Technology*, Vol. 88 No. 2, pp. 219–230.
- Alaceva, C. and Rusu, L. (2015), "Barriers in achieving business/IT alignment in a large Swedish company: What we have learned?", *Computers in Human Behavior*, Vol. 51, pp. 715–728.
- Ali, S. and Green, P. (2012), "Effective information technology (IT) governance mechanisms: An IT outsourcing perspective", *Information Systems Frontiers*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 179–193.
- Almeida, R., Pereira, R. and Mira da Silva, M. (2013), "IT Governance Mechanisms: A Literature Review", in Falcão e Cunha, J., Snene, M. and Nóvoa, H. (Eds.), *Exploring Services Science*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 186–199.
- Almeida, R.S. de (2013), *Implementing IT Governance*, Thesis to obtain the Master of Science Degree, Técnico Lisboa, Lisboa.
- Alreemy, Z., Chang, V., Walters, R. and Wills, G. (2016), "Critical success factors (CSFs) for information technology governance (ITG)", *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 36 No. 6, pp. 907–916.
- Altameem, A.A., Aldrees, A.I. and Alsaeed, N. (2014), "Strategic Information Systems Planning (SISP)", in *Proceedings of the World Congress on Engineering and Computer Science (WCECS 2014)*, Vol. 1, San Francisco, USA.
- Ambler, S. and Lines, M. (2012), *Disciplined Agile Delivery: A practitioner's guide to agile software delivery in the enterprise*, IBM Press, Upper Saddle River u.a.
- Ambler, S.W. (2009), "Scaling agile software development through lean governance", in *Proceedings of the ICSE Workshop on Software Development Governance (SDG 2009)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 1–2.
- Andersen, P., Svejvig, P. and Heeager, L. (2017), "Ambidextrous IT Governance: The Art of Balancing Exploration and Exploitation in IT Governance", *Selected Papers of the IRIS*, Issue Nr 8 (2017). No. 2, pp. 134–146.
- Arain, M., Campbell, M.J., Cooper, C.L. and Lancaster, G.A. (2010), "What is a pilot or feasibility study? A review of current practice and editorial policy", *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, Vol. 10 No. 1, p. 67.
- Aral, S. and Weill, P. (2007), "IT Assets, Organizational Capabilities, and Firm Performance: How Resource Allocations and Organizational Differences Explain Performance Variation", *Organization Science*, Vol. 18 No. 5, pp. 763–780.
- Arbussa, A. (2017), "Strategic agility-driven business model renewal: the case of an SME", *Management Decision*, Vol. 55 No. 2, pp. 271–293.
- Arksey, H. and Knight, P. (1999), *Interviewing for Social Scientists*, SAGE Publications, Ltd, London, UK.
- Armstrong, C.P. and Sambamurthy, V. (1999), "Information Technology Assimilation in Firms: The Influence of Senior Leadership and IT Infrastructures", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 304–327.

- Awais, M. and Gill, A. (2016), "Enterprise IT Governance: Back to Basics", in Gołuchowski, Pańkowska, M., Barry, C., Lang, M., Linger, H. and Schneider, C. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Information Systems Development (ISD2016)*, University of Economics in Katowice, Katowice, Poland.
- Baker, E.H. (2004), "Leading Alignment", available at: <https://www.cioinsight.com/c/a/Past-Opinions/Leading-Alignment> (accessed 6 July 2019).
- Banker, R.D., Hu, N., Pavlou, P.A. and Luftman, J. (2011), "CIO reporting structure, strategic positioning, and firm performance", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 35 No. 2, pp. 487–504.
- Barney, J. (1991), "Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 17 No. 1, pp. 99–120.
- Basit, T. (2003), "Manual or electronic? The role of coding in qualitative data analysis", *Educational Research*, Vol. 45 No. 2, pp. 143–154.
- Baskerville, R.L., DeGross, J.I., Mathiassen, L. and Pries-Heje, J. (2005), *Business Agility and Information Technology Diffusion*, *IFIP International Federation for Information Processing*, Vol. 180, International Federation for Information Processing, Boston, MA.
- Baxter (2008), "Qualitative Case Study Methodology: Study Design and Implementation for Novice Researchers", *The Qualitative Report*, Vol. 13 No. 4, pp. 544–559.
- Beck, K., Beedle, M., van Bennekum, A., Cockburn, A., Cunningham, W., Fowler, M., Grenning, J., Highsmith, J., Hunt, A., Jeffries, R. and others (2001), "The agile manifesto", available at: <http://agilemanifesto.org/> (accessed 6 July 2019).
- Benson, J. and Clark, F. (1982), "A guide for instrument development and validation", *The American journal of occupational therapy official publication of the American Occupational Therapy Association*, Vol. 36 No. 12, pp. 789–800.
- Berelson, B. (1952), *Content analysis in communication research*, Free press, Glencoe.
- Bergeron, F., Croteau, A.-M., Uwizeyemungu, S. and Raymond, L. (2015), "IT Governance Theories and the Reality of SMEs: Bridging the Gap", in *Proceedings of the 48th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2015)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 4544–4553.
- Bergeron, F., Raymond, L. and Rivard, S. (2004), "Ideal patterns of strategic alignment and business performance", *Information & Management*, Vol. 41 No. 8, pp. 1003–1020.
- Bethlehem, J. and Stoop, I. (2007), "Online panels. A paradigm theft?", *The challenges of a changing world*, pp. 113–131.
- Bharadwaj, A.S. (2000), "A Resource-Based Perspective on Information Technology Capability and Firm Performance: An Empirical Investigation", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 24 No. 1, pp. 169–196.
- Bianchi, I.S. and Sousa, R.D. (2016), "IT Governance Mechanisms in Higher Education", *Procedia Computer Science*, Vol. 100, pp. 941–946.
- Bley, K., Leyh, C. and Schäffer, T. (2016), "Digitization of German Enterprises in the Production Sector - Do they know how "digitized" they are?", in *Proceedings of the 22nd Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS 2016)*, Association for Information Systems, San Diego, Calif.
- Borgman, H., Heier, H., Bahli, B. and Boekamp, T. (2016), "Dotting the I and Crossing (out) the T in IT Governance: New Challenges for Information Governance", in *Proceedings of the 49th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2016)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 4901–4909.
- Bortz, J. and Döring, N. (2009), *Forschungsmethoden und Evaluation: Für Human- und Sozialwissenschaftler ; mit 87 Tabellen*, Springer-Lehrbuch Bachelor, Master, 4., überarb. Aufl., [Nachdr.], Springer-Medizin-Verl., Heidelberg.
- Bossert, O. (2016), "A Two-Speed Architecture for the Digital Enterprise", in El-Sheikh, E., Zimmermann, A. and Jain, L.C. (Eds.), *Emerging trends in the evolution of service-oriented and enterprise architectures*, *Intelligent Systems Reference Library*, Vol. 111, Springer, Cham, pp. 139–150.

- Bowen, P.L., Cheung, M.-Y.D. and Rohde, F.H. (2007), "Enhancing IT governance practices: A model and case study of an organization's efforts", *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, Vol. 8 No. 3, pp. 191–221.
- Bradley, J. (1993), "Methodological Issues and Practices in Qualitative Research", *The Library Quarterly*, Vol. 63 No. 4, pp. 431–449.
- Bradley, R.V., Byrd, T.A., Pridmore, J.L., Thrasher, E., Pratt, R.M.E. and Mbarika, V.W.A. (2012), "An empirical examination of antecedents and consequences of IT governance in US hospitals", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 27 No. 2, pp. 156–177.
- Branicki, L.J. (2018), "How entrepreneurial resilience generates resilient SMEs", *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, Vol. 24 No. 7, pp. 1244–1263.
- Brown, A.E. (2015), "Exploring IT Governance Effectiveness: Identifying Sources of Divergence through the Adoption of a Behavioural-Based Organizational Routines Perspective", Carleton University Ottawa, 2015.
- Buchwald, A., Urbach, N. and Ahlemann, F. (2014), "Business value through controlled IT. Toward an integrated model of IT governance success and its impact", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 29 No. 2, pp. 128–147.
- Buckingham, A. and Saunders, P. (2004), *The survey methods workbook: From design to analysis*, Polity, Cambridge.
- Burtscher, C., Manwani, S. and Remenyi, D. (2009), "Towards a Conceptual Map of IT Governance: a review of current academic and practitioner thinking", in *Proceedings of the UK Academy for Information Systems Conference (UKAIS 2009)*, Association for Information Systems, p. 15.
- Callahan, J., Bastos, C. and Keyes, D. (2004), "The Evolution of IT Governance at NB Power", in van Grembergen, W. (Ed.), *Strategies for Information Technology Governance*, Igi Global, pp. 343–356.
- Camisón-Zornoza, C., Lapiedra-Alcamí, R., Segarra-Ciprés, M. and Boronat-Navarro, M. (2004), "A Meta-analysis of Innovation and Organizational Size", *Organization Studies*, Vol. 25 No. 3, pp. 331–361.
- Cenfetelli and Bassellier (2009), "Interpretation of Formative Measurement in Information Systems Research", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 33 No. 4, pp. 689–707.
- Chan, Y. (2002), "Why Haven't We Mastered Alignment? The Importance of the Informal Organization Structure", *MIS Quarterly Executive*, Vol. 1 No. 2, pp. 97–112.
- Chan, Y.E. (1992), *Business strategy, information systems strategy, and strategic fit: Measurement and performance impacts*, Digitized Theses. 2143.
- Chan, Y.E., Huff, S.L., Barclay, D.W. and Copeland, D.G. (1997), "Business Strategic Orientation, Information Systems Strategic Orientation, and Strategic Alignment", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 8 No. 2, pp. 125–150.
- Chan, Y.E. and Reich, B.H. (2007), "IT Alignment: What Have We Learned?", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 22 No. 4, pp. 297–315.
- Chan, Y.E., Sabherwal, R. and Thatcher, J.B. (2006), "Antecedents and outcomes of strategic IS alignment: an empirical investigation", *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, Vol. 53 No. 1, pp. 27–47.
- Chatwani, N. (2019), *Organisational Agility: Exploring the Impact of Identity on Knowledge Management*, Springer International Publishing.
- Chen, L. (2010), "Business–IT alignment maturity of companies in China", *Information & Management*, Vol. 47 No. 1, pp. 9–16.
- Cheng, T.-H., Jansen, S. and Remmers, M. (2009), "Controlling and monitoring agile software development in three dutch product software companies", in *Proceedings of the ICSE Workshop on Software Development Governance (SDG 2009)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 29–35.
- Chin, W.W. (1998), "The partial least squares approach to structural equation modeling", *Modern methods for business research*, Vol. 295 No. 2, pp. 295–336.

- Christmann, G.B. (2009), "Expert Interviews on the Telephone. A Difficult Undertaking", in Bogner, A., Littig, B. and Menz, W. (Eds.), *Interviewing experts, Research methods series*, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, pp. 157–183.
- Churchill, G.A. (1999), *Marketing research: Methodological foundations, The Dryden Press series in marketing*, 7th ed., The Dryden Press, Fort Worth, Tex.
- Churchill Jr, G.A. (1979), "A paradigm for developing better measures of marketing constructs", *Journal of marketing research*, pp. 64–73.
- Chwelos, P., Benbasat, I. and Dexter, A.S. (2001), "Research Report: Empirical Test of an EDI Adoption Model", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 304–321.
- Clark, T., Frank, U. and Kulkarni, V. (2016), "Supporting organizational efficiency and agility: Models, languages and software systems (Dagstuhl Seminar 16192)", *Dagstuhl Reports*, Vol. 6, 31-55.
- Cohen, J. (1992), "A power primer", *Psychological bulletin*, Vol. 112 No. 1, pp. 155–159.
- Collin, J., Halén, M., Helenius, M., Hiekkanen, K., Itälä, T. and Korhonen, J.J. (2014), "IT Leadership in Finnish Organizations and Digital Transformation", Aalto University.
- Collin, J., Hiekkanen, K., Korhonen, J.J., Halén, M., Itälä, T. and Helenius, M. (2015), *IT Leadership in Transition: The Impact of Digitalization on Finnish Organizations*, Aalto University publication series Science + Technology, Aalto University, Helsinki, Finland.
- Collins, D. (2003), "Pretesting survey instruments: An overview of cognitive methods", *Quality of Life Research*, Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 229–238.
- Collins, K.M.T., Onwuegbuzie, A.J. and Sutton, I.L. (2006), "A Model Incorporating the Rationale and Purpose for Conducting Mixed-Methods Research in Special Education and beyond", *Learning Disabilities: A Contemporary Journal*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 67–100.
- Collis, J. and Hussey, R. (2003), *Business research: A practical guide for undergraduate and postgraduate students*, 2nd ed., Palgrave/Macmillan, Basingstoke.
- Collis, J. and Hussey, R. (2013), *Business Research: A Practical Guide for Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students*, Palgrave Macmillan.
- Connolly, N., Maccani, G. and Donellan, B. (2017), "IT Governance in Smart Cities: a Conceptual Framework", in *Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2017)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Corti, L. and Thompson, P. (2012), "Secondary analysis of archive data", in Goodwin, J. (Ed.), *SAGE secondary data analysis, SAGE library of research methods*, SAGE, Los Angeles, Calif.
- Creswell, J.W. (2012), *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*, 4th ed., PHI Learning Private Limited, Delhi, India.
- Creswell, J.W. and Plano Clark, V.L. (2007), *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*, SAGE, Thousand Oaks, Calif.
- Cummins, F.A. (2009), *Building the agile enterprise: With SOA, BPM and MBM*, Morgan Kaufmann, Burlington Mass.
- Daft, R.L. (1998), *Organization theory and design*, 6. ed., South Western College Publ, Cincinnati, Ohio.
- Dahlberg, T. and Helin, A. (2017), "Why and How do Municipal areas Govern Interorganizational ICT Cooperation: Indeed "The emperor has no Clothes"", in *Proceedings of the 25th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2017)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Dahlberg, T. and Kivijarvi, H. (2006), "An Integrated Framework for IT Governance and the Development and Validation of an Assessment Instrument", in Sprague, R.H. (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 39th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2006)*, IEEE Computer Society, 194b-194b.
- Davenport, T.H. (1993), *Process innovation: Reengineering work through information technology*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston, Mass.
- de Haes, S. and van Grembergen, W. (2004), "IT governance and its mechanisms", *Information Systems Control Journal*, Vol. 1, pp. 27–33.

- de Haes, S. and van Grembergen, W. (2005), "IT Governance Structures, Processes and Relational Mechanisms: Achieving IT/Business Alignment in a Major Belgian Financial Group", in *Proceedings of the 38th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2005)*, IEEE Computer Society, 237b-237b.
- de Haes, S. and van Grembergen, W. (2009), "An Exploratory Study into IT Governance Implementations and its Impact on Business/IT Alignment", *Information Systems Management*, Vol. 26 No. 2, pp. 123–137.
- de Haes, S. and van Grembergen, W. (2015a), *Enterprise governance of information technology: Achieving alignment and value, featuring COBIT 5, Management for Professionals*, 2. ed., Springer, Cham.
- de Haes, S. and van Grembergen, W. (2015b), "Enterprise Governance of IT", in Haes, S. de and van Grembergen, W. (Eds.), *Enterprise Governance of Information Technology, Management for Professionals*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 11–43.
- Denning, S. (2015), "Agile: it's time to put it to use to manage business complexity", *Strategy & Leadership*, Vol. 43 No. 5, pp. 10–17.
- Diamantopoulos, A. (2006), "The error term in formative measurement models: interpretation and modeling implications", *Journal of Modelling in Management*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 7–17.
- Diamantopoulos, A. and Winklhofer, H.M. (2001), "Index Construction with Formative Indicators. An Alternative to Scale Development", *Journal of marketing research*, Vol. 38 No. 2, pp. 269–277.
- Dillman, D.A., Smyth, J.D. and Christian, L.M. (2009), *Internet, Mail, and Mixed-mode Surveys: The Tailored Design Method*, 3rd ed., Wiley, Hoboken, New Jersey.
- Doody, O. and Noonan, M. (2013), "Preparing and conducting interviews to collect data", *Nurse researcher*, Vol. 20 No. 5, pp. 28–32.
- Dove, R. (2001), *Response Ability: The Language, Structure, and Culture of the Agile Enterprise*, 1st ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- Dubinsky, Y., Kruchten, P., Finkelstein, A., Bass, L., Chulani, S. and Prikladnicki, R. (2010), "Software Development Governance (SDG) Workshop", in *Proceedings of the 32nd ACM/IEEE International Conference on Software Engineering*, ACM, p. 463.
- Dubois, A. and Gadde, L.-E. (2002), "Systematic combining. An abductive approach to case research", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 55 No. 7, pp. 553–560.
- Dunphy, D.C. and Stace, D.A. (1988), "Transformational and Coercive Strategies for Planned Organizational Change. Beyond the O.D. Model", *Organization Studies*, Vol. 9 No. 3, pp. 317–334.
- Earl, M.J. (1993), "Experiences in Strategic Information Systems Planning", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 17 No. 1, pp. 1–24.
- Elo, S. and Kyngäs, H. (2008), "The qualitative content analysis process", *Journal of advanced nursing*, Vol. 62 No. 1, pp. 107–115.
- Erickson, K.C. and Stull, D.D. (1998), *Doing team ethnography: Warnings and advice, Qualitative research methods series*, Vol. 42, SAGE, Thousand Oaks, Calif.
- Etikan, I. (2016), "Comparison of Convenience Sampling and Purposive Sampling", *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, Vol. 5 No. 1, p. 1.
- European Commission (2008), *Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community*, Rev. 2 (NACE Rev.2), European Communities, Luxembourg.
- Fairchild, A.J. and MacKinnon, D.P. (2009), "A general model for testing mediation and moderation effects", *Prevention science the official journal of the Society for Prevention Research*, Vol. 10 No. 2, pp. 87–99.
- Fernandes, J.M. and Almeida, M. (2010), "Classification and Comparison of Agile Methods", in *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on the Quality of Information and Communications Technology (QUATIC 2010)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 391–396.

- Fink, K. and Ploder, C. (2008), "Decision Support Framework for the Implementation of IT-Governance", in *Proceedings of the 41st Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2008)*, IEEE Computer Society, p. 432.
- Fink, L. and Neumann, S. (2007), "Gaining Agility through IT Personnel Capabilities: The Mediating Role of IT Infrastructure Capabilities", *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 8 No. 8, pp. 440–462.
- Fisher, M.L. (1997), "What is the right supply chain for your product?", *Harvard business review*, Vol. 75, pp. 105–117.
- Fitzgerald, M., Kruschwitz, N., Bonnet, D. and Welch, M. (2014), "Embracing digital technology: A new strategic imperative", *MIT Sloan management review*, Vol. 55 No. 2, p. 1.
- Fruhling, A., McDonald, P. and Dunbar, C. (2008), "A Case Study: Introducing eXtreme Programming in a US Government System Development Project", in *Proceedings of the 41st Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2008)*, IEEE Computer Society, p. 464.
- Galbraith, J.R. (1994), *Competing with Flexible Lateral Organizations*, Addison-Wesley, Boston, Mass.
- Gallagher, K.P. and Worrell, J.L. (2008), "Organizing IT to promote agility", *Information Technology and Management*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 71–88.
- Gartner (2018), "IT Glossary - Bimodal IT", available at: <https://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/bimodal> (accessed 6 July 2019).
- Gefen, D., Rigdon, E.E. and Straub, D. (2011), "An Update and Extension to SEM Guidelines for Administrative and Social Science Research", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 35 No. 2, 1-14.
- Gerow, J.E., Grover, V., Thatcher, J. and Roth, P.L. (2014), "Looking Toward the Future of IT-Business Strategic Alignment through the Past. A Meta-Analysis", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 1159–1186.
- Gersick, C.J.G. (1991), "Revolutionary change theories. A multilevel exploration of the punctuated equilibrium paradigm", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 16 No. 1, pp. 10–36.
- Gill, A.Q., Henderson-Sellers, B. and Niazi, M. (2018), "Scaling for agility: A reference model for hybrid traditional-agile software development methodologies", *Information Systems Frontiers*, Vol. 20 No. 2, pp. 315–341.
- Glaser, B.G. and Strauss, A.L. (1977), *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research, Observations*, 1. paperbound ed., 8. print, Aldine, Chicago.
- Gläser, J. and Laudel, G. (2010), *Experteninterviews und Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse*, VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, Wiesbaden.
- Goldman, S.L., Nagel, R.N. and Preiss, K. (1995), *Agile competitors and virtual organizations: Strategies for enriching the customer*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York.
- Graneheim, U.H. and Lundman, B. (2004), "Qualitative content analysis in nursing research. Concepts, procedures and measures to achieve trustworthiness", *Nurse education today*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 105–112.
- Grant, M.J. and Booth, A. (2009), "A typology of reviews. An analysis of 14 review types and associated methodologies", *Health information and libraries journal*, Vol. 26 No. 2, pp. 91–108.
- Grant, R.M. (1991), "The Resource-Based Theory of Competitive Advantage: Implications for Strategy Formulation", *California Management Review*, Vol. 33 No. 3, pp. 114–135.
- Gregory, R.W., Keil, M., Muntermann, J. and Mähring, M. (2015), "Paradoxes and the Nature of Ambidexterity in IT Transformation Programs", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 26 No. 1, pp. 57–80.
- Greiner, L.E. (1997), "Evolution and Revolution as Organizations Grow. A company's past has clues for management that are critical to future success", *Family Business Review*, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 397–409.

- Gu, B., Xue, L. and Ray, G. (2008), "IT Governance and IT Investment Performance. An Empirical Analysis", in *Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2008)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Guba, E.G. (1981), "Criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of naturalistic inquiries", *ECTJ*, Vol. 29 No. 2, p. 75.
- Guest, G. and MacQueen, K.M. (Eds.) (2008), *Handbook for team-based qualitative research*, AltaMira Press, Lanham.
- Haffke, I., Kalgovas, B. and Benlian, A. (2016), "The Role of the CIO and the CDO in an Organization's Digital Transformation", in *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2016)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Haffke, I., Kalgovas, B. and Benlian, A. (2017a), "Options for Transforming the IT Function Using Bimodal IT", *MIS Quarterly Executive*, Vol. 16 No. 2.
- Haffke, I., Kalgovas, B. and Benlian, A. (2017b), "The Transformative Role of Bimodal IT in an Era of Digital Business", in *Proceedings of the 50th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2017)*, Association for Information Systems, pp. 1–10.
- Haghjoo, P. (2012), "Towards a better understanding of how effective IT governance leads to business value: a literature review and future research directions", in *Proceedings of the 23rd Australasian Conference on Information Systems (ACIS 2012)*, pp. 1–11.
- Hair, J.F., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M. and Sarstedt, M. (2016), *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*, 2nd ed., SAGE, Los Angeles, Calif.
- Hair, J.F., Ringle, C.M. and Sarstedt, M. (2011), "PLS-SEM. Indeed a Silver Bullet", *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp. 139–152.
- Hair, J.F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C.M. and Gudergan, S. (2017), *Advanced issues in partial least squares structural equation modeling*, SAGE, Los Angeles, Calif.
- Hall, R. (1992), "The strategic analysis of intangible resources", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 13 No. 2, pp. 135–144.
- Harry, B., Sturges, K.M. and Klingner, J.K. (2005), "Mapping the Process: An Exemplar of Process and Challenge in Grounded Theory Analysis", *Educational Researcher*, Vol. 34 No. 2, pp. 3–13.
- Hartman, J.M., Forsen, J.W., Wallace, M.S. and Neely, J.G. (2002), "Tutorials in clinical research. Part IV: recognizing and controlling bias", *The Laryngoscope*, Vol. 112 No. 1, pp. 23–31.
- Heier, H., Borgman, H.P. and Mileos, C. (2009), "Examining the relationship between IT governance software, processes, and business value: a quantitative research approach", in *Proceedings of the 42nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2009)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 1–11.
- Henderson, J.C. and Venkatraman, N. (1992), "Strategic alignment: a model for organizational transformation through information technology", *Transforming organizations*, pp. 97–117.
- Henfridsson, O. and Yoo, Y. (2014), "The Liminality of Trajectory Shifts in Institutional Entrepreneurship", *Organization Science*, Vol. 25 No. 3, pp. 932–950.
- Hickey, G. and Kipping, C. (1996), "A multi-stage approach to the coding of data from open-ended questions", *Nurse researcher*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 81–91.
- Higgs, M. and Rowland, D. (2005), "All changes great and small. Exploring approaches to change and its leadership", *Journal of Change Management*, Vol. 5 No. 2, pp. 121–151.
- Hirschheim, R. and Sabherwal, R. (2001), "Detours in the Path toward Strategic Information Systems Alignment", *California Management Review*, Vol. 44 No. 1, pp. 87–108.
- Horlach, B., Böhmman, T., Schirmer, I. and Drews, P. (2018a), "IT governance in scaling agile frameworks", *Proceedings of the Multikonferenz Wirtschaftsinformatik, Lüneburg*.
- Horlach, B., Drews, P. and Schirmer, I. (2016), "Bimodal IT: Business-IT alignment in the age of digital transformation", *Multikonferenz Wirtschaftsinformatik (MKWI)*, pp. 1417–1428.
- Horlach, B., Schirmer, I., Böhmman, T. and Drews, P. (2018b), "Agile portfolio management patterns: a research design", in *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Agile Software Development*, ACM.

- Hsieh, H.-F. and Shannon, S.E. (2005), "Three approaches to qualitative content analysis", *Qualitative health research*, Vol. 15 No. 9, pp. 1277–1288.
- Huang, R., Zmud, R.W. and Price, R.L. (2010), "Influencing the effectiveness of IT governance practices through steering committees and communication policies", *European Journal of Information Systems*, Vol. 19 No. 3, pp. 288–302.
- Hussin, H., King, M. and Cragg, P. (2002), "IT alignment in small firms", *European Journal of Information Systems*, Vol. 11 No. 2, pp. 108–127.
- IT Governance Institute (2003), *Board Briefing on IT Governance*, 2nd edition, Rolling Meadows, Illinois.
- IT Governance Institute (2007), *Cobit 4.1: Framework, Control Objectives, Management Guidelines, Maturity Models*, Meadows, IL, USA.
- Jacobson, D.D. (2009), "Revisiting IT Governance in the Light of Institutional Theory", in *Proceedings of the 42nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2009)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 1–9.
- Jacoby, L. and Siminoff, L.A. (2008), *Empirical methods for bioethics: A primer*, *Advances in bioethics*, v. 11, Elsevier JAI, Amsterdam, London.
- Janssen, L.A., Mezzomo Luciano, E. and Gregianin Testa, M. (2013), "The Influence of Organizational Culture on IT Governance: Perception of a Group of IT Managers from Latin American Companies", paper presented at 2013 46th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS).
- Jarvis, C.B., MacKenzie, S.B. and Podsakoff, P.M. (2003), "A Critical Review of Construct Indicators and Measurement Model Misspecification in Marketing and Consumer Research", *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 30 No. 2, pp. 199–218.
- Jewer, J. and McKay, K.N. (2012), "Antecedents and consequences of board IT governance: Institutional and strategic choice perspectives", *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 13 No. 7, p. 581.
- Jöreskog, K.G. and Wold, H. (1982), "The ML and PLS techniques for modeling with latent variables. Historical and comparative aspects", in Jöreskog, K.G. and Wold, H. (Eds.), *Systems Under Indirect Observation, Part 1*, North-Holland, Amsterdam, pp. 263–270.
- Kaplan, D.E. (2000), *Structural equation modeling: Foundations and extensions*, *Advanced quantitative techniques in the social sciences*, Vol. 10, SAGE, Thousand Oaks, Calif.
- Kaplan, R.S. and Norton, D.P. (2004), "Measuring the strategic readiness of intangible assets", *Harvard business review*, Vol. 82 No. 2, pp. 52–63.
- Kappelman, L.A., McLean, E.R., Luftman, J. and Johnson, V. (2013), "Key issues of IT organizations and their leadership the 2013 SIM IT Trends Study", *MIS Quarterly Executive*, Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 47–80.
- Karahanna, E. and Preston, D.S. (2013), "The Effect of Social Capital of the Relationship Between the CIO and Top Management Team on Firm Performance", *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 30 No. 1, pp. 15–56.
- Kaur, J., Mohamed, N. and Ahlan, A.R. (2012), "Modeling the impact of information technology governance effectiveness using partial least square", in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Statistics in Science, Business, and Engineering*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 1–5.
- Kearns, G.S. and Lederer, A.L. (2003), "A Resource-Based View of Strategic IT Alignment: How Knowledge Sharing Creates Competitive Advantage", *Decision Sciences*, Vol. 34 No. 1, pp. 1–29.
- Kearns, G.S. and Sabherwal, R. (2006), "Strategic Alignment Between Business and Information Technology: A Knowledge-Based View of Behaviors, Outcome, and Consequences", *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 23 No. 3, pp. 129–162.
- Kitchenham, B. (2004), *Procedures for Performing Systematic Reviews*, Keele University. Technical Report TR/SE-0401, Department of Computer Science, Keele University, UK.

- Kitchenham, B.A. and Pfleeger, S.L. (2008), "Personal Opinion Surveys", in Shull, F., Singer, J. and Sjøberg, D.I.K. (Eds.), *Guide to Advanced Empirical Software Engineering*, Vol. 52, Springer London, London, pp. 63–92.
- Kohli, R. and Grover, V. (2008), "Business Value of IT: An Essay on Expanding Research Directions to Keep up with the Times", *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 23–39.
- Kotter, J. (2012), "How the most innovative companies capitalize on today's rapid-fire strategic challenges-and still make their numbers", *Harvard business review*, Vol. 90 No. 11, pp. 43–58.
- Kotter, J.P. (2014a), *Accelerate: Building strategic agility for a faster-moving world*, Harvard Business Review Press, Boston, Mass.
- Kotter, J.P. (2014b), "Seizing opportunities and dodging threats with a dual operating system", *Strategy & Leadership*, Vol. 42 No. 6, pp. 10–12.
- Krippendorff, K. (1980), *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology*, *The Sage commtext series*, Vol. 5, 1. print, SAGE, Beverly Hills, Calif.
- Kuckartz, U., Dresing, T., Rädiker, S. and Stefer, C. (2008), *Qualitative Evaluation: Der Einstieg in die Praxis*, 2., aktualisierte Auflage, VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften / GWV Fachverlage GmbH Wiesbaden, Wiesbaden.
- Kvale, S. and Brinkmann, S. (2009), *InterViews: Learning the craft of qualitative research interviewing*, 2. ed., SAGE, Los Angeles, Calif.
- Lainhart IV, J.W. (2000), "Why IT Governance Is a Top Management Issue", *Journal of Corporate Accounting & Finance*, Vol. 11 No. 5, pp. 33–40.
- Lazic, M., Groth, M., Schillinger, C. and Heinzl, A. (2011), "The Impact of IT Governance on Business Performance", in *Proceedings of the 17th Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS 2017)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Lee, C.-H., Lee, J.-H., Park, J.-S. and Jeong, K.-Y. (2008), "A Study of the Causal Relationship between IT Governance Inhibitors and Its Success in Korea Enterprises", in *Proceedings of the 41st Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2008)*, IEEE Computer Society, p. 433.
- Leech, N.L. and Onwuegbuzie, A.J. (2007), "An array of qualitative data analysis tools. A call for data analysis triangulation", *School Psychology Quarterly*, Vol. 22 No. 4, pp. 557–584.
- Leonhardt, D., Haffke, I., Kranz, J.J. and Benlian, A. (2017), "Reinventing the IT function: The Role of IT Agility and IT Ambidexterity in Supporting Digital Business Transformation", in *Proceedings of the 25th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2017)*, Association for Information Systems, pp. 968–984.
- Leonhardt, D., Hanelt, A., Huang, P. and Mithas, S. (2018), "Does One Size Fit All? Theorizing Governance Configurations for Digital Innovation", in *Proceedings of the 39th International Conference On Information Systems (ICIS 2018)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Lewis, M.W., Andriopoulos, C. and Smith, W.K. (2014), "Paradoxical Leadership to Enable Strategic Agility", *California Management Review*, Vol. 56 No. 3, pp. 58–77.
- Liang, T.-P., Chiu, Y.-C., Wu, S.P.J. and Straub, D. (2011), "The Impact of IT Governance on Organizational Performance", in *Proceedings of the 17th Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS 2011)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Lindner, D. and Leyh, C. (2018), "Organizations in Transformation: Agility as Consequence or Prerequisite of Digitization?", in Abramowicz, W. and Paschke, A. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Business Information Systems, Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing*, Vol. 320, Springer, Cham, pp. 86–101.
- Lindros, K. (2017), "What is IT governance? A formal way to align IT & business strategy", available at: <https://www.cio.com/article/2438931/governanceit-governance-definition-and-solutions.html> (accessed 6 July 2019).
- Littig, B. (2009), "Interviewing the Elite – Interviewing Experts: Is There a Difference?", in Bogner, A., Littig, B. and Menz, W. (Eds.), *Interviewing experts, Research methods series*, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, pp. 98–113.

- Lombard, M., Snyder-Duch, J. and Bracken, C.C. (2002), "Content Analysis in Mass Communication: Assessment and Reporting of Intercoder Reliability", *Human Communication Research*, Vol. 28 No. 4, pp. 587–604.
- Loosveldt, G. and Sonck, N. (2008), "An evaluation of the weighting procedures for an online access panel survey", *Survey Research Methods*, Vol 2, No 2, pp. 93–105.
- Lu, Y. and Ramamurthy, K. (2011), "Understanding the Link Between Information Technology Capability and Organizational Agility: An Empirical Examination", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 35 No. 4, p. 931.
- Luftman, J. (2000), "Assessing Business-IT Alignment Maturity", *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 1–50.
- Luftman, J. and Ben-Zvi, T. (2010), "Key Issues for IT Executives 2010: Judicious IT Investments Continue Post-Recession", *MIS Quarterly Executive* No. 9, pp. 263–273.
- Luftman, J. and Ben-Zvi, T. (2011), "Key Issues for IT Executives 2011: Cautious Optimism in Uncertain Economic Times", *MIS Quarterly Executive*, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 203–212.
- Luftman, J. and Brier, T. (1999), "Achieving and Sustaining Business-IT Alignment", *California Management Review*, Vol. 42 No. 1, pp. 109–122.
- Luftman, J.N., Lewis, P.R. and Oldach, S.H. (1993), "Transforming the enterprise. The alignment of business and information technology strategies", *IBM Systems Journal*, Vol. 32 No. 1, pp. 198–221.
- Luna, A.J.H., Costa, C.P., Moura, H.P.d., Novaes, M.A. and do Nascimento, C.A. (2010), "Agile governance in Information and Communication Technologies. Shifting paradigms", *Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management*, Vol. 7 No. 2, pp. 311–334.
- Luna, A.J.H., Kruchten, P., E.Pedrosa, M.L.G.d., Almeida Neto, H.R.d. and Moura, H.P.d.M. (2014), "State of the Art of Agile Governance. A Systematic Review", *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, Vol. 6 No. 5, pp. 121–141.
- Luna, A.J.H., Kruchten, P. and Moura, H.P.d. (2013), "GAME. Governance for Agile Management of Enterprises: A Management Model for Agile Governance", in *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Global Software Engineering workshops (ICGSEW)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 88–90.
- Lunardi, G.L., Maçada, A.C.G., Becker, J.L. and van Grembergen, W. (2017), "Antecedents of IT Governance Effectiveness: An Empirical Examination in Brazilian Firms", *Journal of Information Systems*, Vol. 31 No. 1, pp. 41–57.
- Madi, T., Dahalin, Z. and Baharom, F. (2011), "Content analysis on agile values. A perception from software practitioners", in *Proceedings of the 5th Malaysian Conference in Software Engineering (MySEC)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 423–428.
- Magnusson, J., Torell, J., Polutnik, L. and Ask, U. (2017), "Ambidextrous IT Governance in the Public Sector: A Revelatory Case Study of the Swedish Tax Authorities", in Rusu, L. and Viscusi, G. (Eds.), *Information technology governance in public organizations: Theory and practice, Integrated Series in Information Systems*, Springer, Cham, pp. 253–267.
- March, J.G. (1991), "Exploration and Exploitation in Organizational Learning", *Organization Science*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 71–87.
- Maria Morariu, C. (2014), "Intellectual capital performance in the case of Romanian public companies", *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, Vol. 15 No. 3, pp. 392–410.
- Markides, C. and Charitou, C.D. (2004), "Competing with dual business models. A contingency approach", *Academy of Management Executive*, Vol. 18 No. 3, pp. 22–36.
- Markides, C.C. (2013), "Business Model Innovation. What Can the Ambidexterity Literature Teach US?", *Academy of Management Perspectives*, Vol. 27 No. 4, pp. 313–323.
- Marshall, B., Cardon, P., Poddar, A. and Fontenot, R. (2013), "Does Sample Size Matter in Qualitative Research?: A Review of Qualitative Interviews in is Research", *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, Vol. 54 No. 1, pp. 11–22.
- Mayring, P. (2000), "Qualitative Content Analysis", *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, Vol. 1 No. 2.

- Melarkode, A., From-Poulsen, M. and Warnakulasuriya, S. (2004), “Delivering Agility Through IT”, *Business Strategy Review*, Vol. 15 No. 3, pp. 45–50.
- Meuser, M. and Nagel, U. (2009), “The Expert Interview and Changes in Knowledge Production”, in Bogner, A., Littig, B. and Menz, W. (Eds.), *Interviewing experts, Research methods series*, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, pp. 17–42.
- Mikalef, P., Krogstie, J., van de Wetering, R., Pappas, I. and Giannakos, M. (2018), “Information Governance in the Big Data Era: Aligning Organizational Capabilities”, in *Proceedings of the 51st Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2018)*, Waikoloa Village, Hawaii.
- Miller, S., Batenburg, R. and van de Wijngaert, L. (2006), “National culture influences on European ERP adoption”, in *Proceedings of the 14th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2006)*, Association for Information Systems, pp. 112–123.
- Minichiello, V. (1990), *In-depth interviewing: Researching people*, Longman Cheshire, Melbourne.
- Mintzberg, H. (1979), *The Structuring of Organizations: A Synthesis of the Research*, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey.
- Mithas, S. and Rust, R.T. (2016), “How Information Technology Strategy and Investments Influence Firm Performance: Conjecture and Empirical Evidence”, *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 40 No. 1, pp. 223–245.
- Moore, G.C. and Benbasat, I. (1991), “Development of an Instrument to Measure the Perceptions of Adopting an Information Technology Innovation”, *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 2 No. 3, pp. 192–222.
- Moore, S. and Barnett, L. (2004), “Offshore outsourcing and agile development”, *Forrester Research, Inc.*
- Müller, B.A. (2016), *Managing Global Product Development Teams: A mixed-methods study of (Knowledge) Governance Mechanisms*, UCAM Biblioteca.
- Nambisan, S. (2013), “Information Technology and Product/Service Innovation: A Brief Assessment and Some Suggestions for Future Research”, *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 14 No. 4.
- Nambisan, S., Lyytinen, K., Majchrzak, A. and Song, M. (2017), “Digital Innovation Management: Reinventing Innovation Management Research in a Digital World”, *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 41 No. 1, pp. 223–238.
- Neff, A.A., Hamel, F., Herz, T.P., Uebernickel, F. and Brenner, W. (2013), “IT Governance in Multi-business Organizations: Performance Impacts and Levers from Processes, Structures, and Relational Mechanisms”, in *Proceedings of the 46th Hawaii International Conference on System*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 4466–4475.
- Nfuka, E.N. and Rusu, L. (2010), “Critical Success Factors for Effective IT Governance in the Public Sector Organizations in a Developing Country: The Case of Tanzania”, in *Proceedings of the 18th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2010)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Nyello, R.M., Kalufy, N., Chalu, H., Kitindi, E. and Kingazi, G. (2017), “Analysis of the Use of Mediating and Moderating Variables in Management Accounting System (MAS): Evidence from the Literature Survey”, *The International Journal of Business & Management*, Vol. 5 No. 2, 163-179.
- Ohlbrecht, H. (2010), “Resources for Qualitative Researchers”, in Flick, U., Kardorff, E.v. and Steinke, I. (Eds.), *A companion to qualitative research*, repr, SAGE, London, pp. 373–380.
- O'Reilly, C.A. and Tushman, M.L. (2013), “Organizational Ambidexterity. Past, Present, and Future”, *Academy of Management Perspectives*, Vol. 27 No. 4, pp. 324–338.
- Pang, M.-S. (2014), “IT governance and business value in the public sector organizations — The role of elected representatives in IT governance and its impact on IT value in U.S. state governments”, *Decision Support Systems*, Vol. 59, pp. 274–285.
- Papp, R. (1999), “Business-IT alignment: productivity paradox payoff?”, *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Vol. 99 No. 8, pp. 367–373.

- Paré, G., Trudel, M.-C., Jaana, M. and Kitsiou, S. (2015), "Synthesizing information systems knowledge. A typology of literature reviews", *Information & Management*, Vol. 52 No. 2, pp. 183–199.
- Patton, M.Q. (1987), *How to use qualitative methods in evaluation, Program evaluation kit*, Vol. 4, 2nd ed., SAGE, Newbury Park, Calif.
- Peppard, J. (2010), "Unlocking the Performance of the Chief Information Officer (CIO)", *California Management Review*, Vol. 52 No. 4, pp. 73–99.
- Peterson, R. (2004a), "Crafting Information Technology Governance", *Information Systems Management*, Vol. 21 No. 4, pp. 7–22.
- Peterson, R.R. (2004b), "Integration Strategies and Tactics for Information Technology Governance", in van Grembergen, W. (Ed.), *Strategies for Information Technology Governance*, Igi Global, pp. 37–80.
- Peterson, R.R., O'Callaghan, R. and Ribbers, P. (2000), "Information technology governance by design: investigating hybrid configurations and integration mechanisms", in *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Information systems (ICIS 2000)*, Association for Information Systems, pp. 435–452.
- Pett, M.A., Lackey, N.R. and Sullivan, J.J. (2003), *Making sense of factor analysis: The use of factor analysis for instrument development in health care research*, SAGE, Thousand Oaks, Calif.
- Pfadenhauer, M. (2009), "Das Experteninterview. Ein Gespräch auf gleicher Augenhöhe", in Buber, R. and Holzmüller, H. (Eds.), *Qualitative Marktforschung: Konzepte - Methoden - Analysen*, Gabler Verlag, Wiesbaden, pp. 451–460.
- Podsakoff, P.M., MacKenzie, S.B., Lee, J.-Y. and Podsakoff, N.P. (2003), "Common method biases in behavioral research. A critical review of the literature and recommended remedies", *The Journal of applied psychology*, Vol. 88 No. 5, pp. 879–903.
- Podsakoff, P.M. and Organ, D.W. (1986), "Self-Reports in Organizational Research. Problems and Prospects", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 531–544.
- Posthumus, S., Solms, R.V. and King, M. (2010), "The board and IT governance the what, who and how", *South African Journal of Business Management*, Vol. 41 No. 3, pp. 23–32.
- Potter, W.J. and Levine-Donnerstein, D. (1999), "Rethinking validity and reliability in content analysis", *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, Vol. 27 No. 3, pp. 258–284.
- Power, K. (2011), "The Agile Office. Experience Report from Cisco's Unified Communications Business Unit", in *Proceedings of the Agile Conference (AGILE 2011)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 201–208.
- Prasad, A., Green, P. and Heales, J. (2011), "IT Governance in Collaborative Organizational Structures", in *Proceedings of the 17th Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS 2011)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Prasad, A., Heales, J. and Green, P. (2009), "Towards a deeper understanding of information technology governance effectiveness: A capabilities-based approach", in *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2009)*, Association for Information Systems, p. 122.
- Prasad, A., Heales, J. and Green, P. (2010), "A capabilities-based approach to obtaining a deeper understanding of information technology governance effectiveness: Evidence from IT steering committees", *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, Vol. 11 No. 3, pp. 214–232.
- Preston, D.S., Chen, D. and Leidner, D.E. (2008), "Examining the Antecedents and Consequences of CIO Strategic Decision-Making Authority. An Empirical Study", *Decision Sciences*, Vol. 39 No. 4, pp. 605–642.
- Preston, D.S. and Karahanna, E. (2009), "Antecedents of IS Strategic Alignment: A Nomological Network", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 20 No. 2, pp. 159–179.
- Punch, K. (2013), *Introduction to social research: Quantitative and qualitative approaches*, 3rd ed., SAGE, Los Angeles, Calif.

- Qu, S.Q. and Dumay, J. (2011), "The qualitative research interview", *Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management*, Vol. 8 No. 3, pp. 238–264.
- Qumer, A. (2007), "Defining an integrated agile governance for large agile software development environments", *Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming*, pp. 157–160.
- Rai, Patnayakuni and Seth (2006), "Firm Performance Impacts of Digitally Enabled Supply Chain Integration Capabilities", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 30 No. 2, p. 225.
- Raisch, S. and Birkinshaw, J. (2008), "Organizational Ambidexterity: Antecedents, Outcomes, and Moderators", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 34 No. 3, pp. 375–409.
- Ramasesh, R., Kulkarni, S. and Jayakumar, M. (2001), "Agility in manufacturing systems: an exploratory modeling framework and simulation", *Integrated Manufacturing Systems*, Vol. 12 No. 7, pp. 534–548.
- Rauschnabel, P.A., Krey, N., Babin, B.J. and Ivens, B.S. (2016), "Brand management in higher education. The University Brand Personality Scale", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 69 No. 8, pp. 3077–3086.
- Reich, B.H. and Benbasat, I. (1996), "Measuring the Linkage between Business and Information Technology Objectives", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 55–81.
- Reich, B.H. and Benbasat, I. (2000), "Factors That Influence the Social Dimension of Alignment between Business and Information Technology Objectives", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 24 No. 1, pp. 81–113.
- Ringle, Sarstedt and Straub (2012), "Editor's Comments. A Critical Look at the Use of PLS-SEM in "MIS Quarterly"", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 36 No. 1, iii.
- Ringle, C.M., Wende, S. and Becker, J.-M. (2017), *SmartPLS 3*, SmartPLS GmbH.
- Romanelli, E. and Tushman, M.L. (1994), "Organizational transformation as punctuated equilibrium. An empirical test", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 37 No. 5, pp. 1141–1166.
- Ross, J.W., Beath, C.M. and Goodhue, D.L. (1996), "Develop Long-Term Competitiveness Through IT Assets", *Sloan Management Review*, Vol. 38, pp. 31–42.
- Rosstiter, J.R. (2002), "The C-OAR-SE procedure for scale development in marketing", *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Vol. 19 No. 4, pp. 305–335.
- Sabherwal, R. and Chan, Y.E. (2001), "Alignment Between Business and IS Strategies: A Study of Prospectors, Analyzers, and Defenders", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 11–33.
- Saldaña, J. (2013), *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*, 2. ed., SAGE, Los Angeles, Calif.
- Sambamurthy, V., Bharadwaj, A. and Grover, V. (2003), "Shaping agility through digital options. Reconceptualizing the role of information technology in contemporary firms", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 27 No. 2, pp. 237–263.
- Samuwai, J. and Prasad, A. (2014), "A model of effective IT governance structures for developing economies", in *Proceedings of the 20th Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS 2014)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Sandelowski, M. and Barroso, J. (2007), *Handbook for synthesizing qualitative research*, Springer Publishing Company, New York.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2016), *Research methods for business students*, 7. ed., Pearson, Harlow.
- Schadewitz, N. and Jachna, T. (2007), "Comparing inductive and deductive methodologies for design patterns identification and articulation", in *International Design Research Conference IADSR 2007 Emerging Trends in Design Research*, Hong Kong.
- Schlosser, F. (2012), "Mastering the Social IT/Business Alignment Challenge", in *Proceedings of the 18th Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS 2012)*, Association for Information Systems.

- Schlosser, F., Beimborn, D., Weitzel, T. and Wagner, H.-T. (2015), "Achieving social alignment between business and IT – an empirical evaluation of the efficacy of IT governance mechanisms", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 30 No. 2, pp. 119–135.
- Schlosser, F., Wagner, H.-T., Beimborn, D. and Weitzel, T. (2010), "The Role of Internal Business/IT Alignment and IT Governance for Service Quality in IT Outsourcing Arrangements", in *Proceedings of the 43rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2010)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 1–10.
- Schlosser, F., Wagner, H.-T. and Coltman, T. (2012), "Reconsidering the Dimensions of Business-IT Alignment", in *Proceedings of the 45th Hawaii International Conference on System Science (HICSS 2012)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 5053–5061.
- Schreier, M. (2012), *Qualitative content analysis in practice*, SAGE, Los Angeles, Calif.
- Schumann, S. (2006), *Repräsentative Umfrage: Praxisorientierte Einführung in empirische Methoden und statistische Analyseverfahren, Lehr- und Handbücher der Politikwissenschaft*, 4., überarb. und erw. Aufl., Oldenbourg, München.
- Seethamraju, R. (2006), "Influence of enterprise systems on business process agility".
- Selig, G.J. (2008), *Implementing IT-Governance: A practical guide to global best practices in IT management, Best practice*, 1st ed., Van Haren, Zaltbommel.
- Shenton, A.K. (2004), "Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects", *Education for Information*, Vol. 22 No. 2, pp. 63–75.
- Sherehiy, B., Karwowski, W. and Layer, J.K. (2007), "A review of enterprise agility. Concepts, frameworks, and attributes", *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, Vol. 37 No. 5, pp. 445–460.
- Shmueli, G., Sarstedt, M., Hair, J.F., Cheah, J.-H., Ting, H., Vaithilingam, S. and Ringle, C.M. (2019), "Predictive Model Assessment in PLS-SEM: Guidelines for Using PLSpredict", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 69 No. 2.
- Silva, D., Silva, M.M.d. and Pereira, R. (2018), "Baseline mechanisms for enterprise governance of IT in SMEs", in *Proceedings of the 20th IEEE International Conference on Business Informatics*, IEEE, Piscataway, NJ, pp. 32–41.
- Silvius, A.J.G., de Haes, S. and van Grembergen, W. (2009), "Exploration of Cultural Influences on Business and IT Alignment", in *Proceedings of the 42nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2009)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 1–10.
- Sloane, E., Beck, R. and Metzger, S. (2008), "AGSOA - Agile Governance for Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) Systems. A Methodology to Deliver 21st Century Military Net-Centric Systems of Systems", in *Proceedings of the 2nd Annual IEEE Systems Conference*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 1–4.
- Smith, A.L., Bradley, R.V., Bichescu, B.C. and Tremblay, M.C. (2013), "IT Governance Characteristics, Electronic Medical Records Sophistication, and Financial Performance in U.S. Hospitals. An Empirical Investigation", *Decision Sciences*, Vol. 44 No. 3, pp. 483–516.
- Smits, D. and van Hillegersberg, J. (2015), "IT Governance Maturity: Developing a Maturity Model Using the Delphi Method", in *Proceedings of the 48th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2015)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 4534–4543.
- Sommer, A.F., Dukovska-Popovska, I. and Steger-Jensen, K. (2014), "Agile Product Development Governance – On Governing the Emerging Scrum/Stage-Gate Hybrids", in Grabot, B., Vallespir, B., Samuel, G., Bouras, A. and Kiritsis, D. (Eds.), *Advances in production management systems, Innovative and Knowledge-Based Production Management in a Global-Local World.*, Vol. 438, Springer, Heidelberg, pp. 184–191.
- Sonnentag, S., Reinecke, L., Mata, J. and Vorderer, P. (2018), "Feeling interrupted-Being responsive: How online messages relate to affect at work", *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 39 No. 3, pp. 369–383.
- Strauss, A.L. and Corbin, J.M. (1996), *Grounded theory: Grundlagen qualitativer Sozialforschung*, Beltz Psychologie Verlags Union, Weinheim.
- Sue, V.M. and Ritter, L.A. (2007), *Conducting online surveys*, SAGE, Los Angeles, Calif.

- Symons, C. (2005), "IT governance framework", available at: <http://i.bnet.com/whitepapers/051103656300.pdf>.
- Tallon, P.P. (2008), "A Process-Oriented Perspective on the Alignment of Information Technology and Business Strategy", *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 24 No. 3, pp. 227–268.
- Tallon, P.P. (2010), "A Service Science Perspective on Strategic Choice, IT, and Performance in U.S. Banking", *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 26 No. 4, pp. 219–252.
- Tan, F.B. and Gallupe, R.B. (2006), "Aligning business and information systems thinking: a cognitive approach", *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, Vol. 53 No. 2, pp. 223–237.
- Tanriverdi, H. (2006), "Performance Effects of Information Technology Synergies in Multibusiness Firms", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 30 No. 1, pp. 57–77.
- Taylor, H. (2005), "Does Internet research work? Comparing Online Survey Results with Telephone Surveys.", *International journal of market research*, Vol. 42 No. 1, pp. 51–63.
- Taylor, J., Sahym, A. and Vithayathil, J. (2015), "Do Powerful Technology Leaders Make a Difference in Firm Performance?", in *Proceedings of the 48th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2015)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 4502–4512.
- Teece, D.J., Pisano, G. and Shuen, A. (1997), "Dynamic capabilities and strategic management", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 18 No. 7, pp. 509–533.
- Tiwana, A., Bharadwaj, A. and Sambamurthy, V. (2003), "The antecedents of information systems development capability in firms: a knowledge integration perspective", in *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2003)*, Association for Information Systems, pp. 246–258.
- Tiwana, A. and Kim, S.K. (2015), "Discriminating IT Governance", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 26 No. 4, pp. 656–674.
- Tiwana, A. and Konsynski, B. (2010), "Complementarities Between Organizational IT Architecture and Governance Structure", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 21 No. 2, pp. 288–304.
- Töpfer, A. (2010), *Erfolgreich Forschen*, Vol. 0, Springer, Heidelberg.
- Tsai, W.-H., Chou, Y.-W., Leu, J.-D., Chen, D.C. and Tsaur, T.-S. (2015), "Investigation of the mediating effects of IT governance-value delivery on service quality and ERP performance", *Enterprise Information Systems*, Vol. 9 No. 2, pp. 139–160.
- Turel, O. and Bart, C. (2014), "Board-level IT governance and organizational performance", *European Journal of Information Systems*, Vol. 23 No. 2, pp. 223–239.
- Tushman, M.L., Newman, W.H. and Romanelli, E. (1986), "Convergence and Upheaval. Managing the Unsteady Pace of Organizational Evolution", *California Management Review*, Vol. 29 No. 1, pp. 29–44.
- Tushman, M.L. and O'Reilly, C.A. (1996), "Ambidextrous Organizations. Managing Evolutionary and Revolutionary Change", *California Management Review*, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 8–29.
- Urbach, N. and Ahlemann, F. (2010), "Structural Equation Modeling in Information Systems Research Using Partial Least Squares", *Journal of Information Technology Theory and Application (JITTA)*, Vol. 11 No. 2.
- Urbach, N., Buchwald, A. and Ahlemann, F. (2013), "Understanding IT governance success and its impact: Results from an interview study".
- van Grembergen, W. (2013), "Introduction to the Minitrack "IT Governance and its Mechanisms" - HICSS 2013", in *Proceedings of the 46th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2013)*, IEEE Computer Society, p. 4394.
- van Grembergen, W. and de Haes, S. (2005), "Measuring and improving IT governance through the balanced scorecard", *Information Systems Control Journal*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 35–42.
- van Grembergen, W., de Haes, S. and Guldentops, E. (2004), "Structures, Processes and Relational Mechanisms for IT Governance", in van Grembergen, W. (Ed.), *Strategies for Information Technology Governance*, Igi Global, pp. 1–36.

- van Oosterhout, M. (2014), *Business Agility and Information Technology in Service Organizations*, 1st ed., Scholars' Press, Saarbrücken.
- van Oosterhout, M., Waarts, E. and van Hillegersberg, J. (2006), "Change factors requiring agility and implications for IT", *European Journal of Information Systems*, Vol. 15 No. 2, pp. 132–145.
- van Roosmalen, M.W. and Hoppenbrouwers, S. (2008), "Supporting corporate governance with enterprise architecture and business rule management. A synthesis of stability and agility", in *Proceedings of the International Workshop on Regulations Modelling and Deployment (ReMoD 2008)*, CEUR-WS.org, pp. 13–24.
- Vázquez-Ramos, R., Leahy, M. and Estrada Hernández, N. (2016), "The Delphi Method in Rehabilitation Counseling Research", *Rehabilitation Counseling Bulletin*, Vol. 50 No. 2, pp. 111–118.
- Vejseli, S., Proba, D., Rossmann, A. and Jung, R. (2018), "The agile strategies in IT Governance: Towards a framework of agile IT Governance in the banking industry", in *Proceedings of the 26th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS 2018)*.
- Vejseli, S. and Rossmann, A. (2017), "The Impact of IT Governance on Firm Performance A Literature Review", in *Proceedings of the 21st Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems (PACIS 2017)*.
- Vejseli, S. and Rossmann, A. (2018), "Towards Agility in IT Governance Frameworks", in *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Business Information Systems (BIS 2018)*, Cham, Springer, pp. 71–85.
- Vejseli, S., Rossmann, A. and Connolly, T. (2019), "IT Governance and Its Agile Dimensions", in *Proceedings of the 52nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2019)*.
- Vejseli, S., Rossmann, A. and Connolly, T. (2020), "Agility matters! Agile Mechanisms in IT Governance and their Impact on Firm Performance", in *Proceedings of the 53rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2020)*.
- Venkatraman, N., Henderson, J.C. and Oldach, S. (1993), "Continuous strategic alignment: Exploiting information technology capabilities for competitive success", *European Management Journal*, Vol. 11 No. 2, pp. 139–149.
- VERBI Software (2017), *MAXQDA Standard 2018 [computer software]*, VERBI, Berlin, Germany.
- Volberda, H.W. (1997), "Building flexible organizations for fast-moving markets", *Long Range Planning*, Vol. 30 No. 2, 169-148.
- Waarts, E. and van Everdingen, Y. (2005), "The Influence of National Culture on the Adoption Status of Innovations: An Empirical Study of Firms Across Europe", *European Management Journal*, Vol. 23 No. 6, pp. 601–610.
- Wagner, H.-T., Beimborn, D. and Weitzel, T. (2014), "How Social Capital Among Information Technology and Business Units Drives Operational Alignment and IT Business Value", *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 31 No. 1, pp. 241–272.
- Wang, X., Conboy, K. and Cawley, O. (2012), "'Leagile' software development. An experience report analysis of the application of lean approaches in agile software development", *Journal of Systems and Software*, Vol. 85 No. 6, pp. 1287–1299.
- Warren, C.A.B. (2001), "Qualitative Interviewing", in Gubrium, J. and Holstein, J. (Eds.), *Handbook of Interview Research*, SAGE, pp. 83–102.
- Webb, P., Pollard, C. and Ridley, G. (2006), "Attempting to Define IT Governance: Wisdom or Folly?", in *Proceedings of the 39th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2006)*, IEEE Computer Society.
- Weber, R. (1990), *Basic Content Analysis*, SAGE, Thousand Oaks, Calif., Thousand Oaks, Calif.
- Webster, J. and Watson, R.T. (2002), "Analyzing the Past to Prepare for the Future. Writing a Literature Review", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 26 No. 2, pp. xiii–xxiii.
- Weill, P. (2004), "Don't Just Lead, Govern: How Top-Performing Firms Govern IT", *MIS Quarterly Executive*, Vol. 3 No. 1, pp. 1–17.

- Weill, P. and Broadbent, M. (1998), *Leveraging the new infrastructure: How market leaders capitalize on information technology*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston, Mass.
- Weill, P. and Ross, J. (2005), "A matrixed approach to designing IT governance", *MIT Sloan management review*, Vol. 46 No. 2, p. 26.
- Weill, P. and Ross, J.W. (2004), *IT governance: How top performers manage IT decision rights for superior results*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston, Mass.
- Wernerfelt, B. (1984), "A resource-based view of the firm", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 5 No. 2, pp. 171–180.
- Wetzels, Odekerken-Schröder and van Oppen (2009), "Using PLS Path Modeling for Assessing Hierarchical Construct Models. Guidelines and Empirical Illustration", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 33 No. 1, p. 177.
- Wiedemann, A. (2018), "IT Governance Mechanisms for DevOps Teams-How Incumbent Companies Achieve Competitive Advantages", in *Proceedings of the 51st Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2018)*, Waikoloa Village, Hawaii.
- Wiedenhöft, G.C., Luciano, E.M. and Testa, M.G. (2015), "Definition of a Model for Measuring the Effectiveness of Information Technology Governance: a Study of the Moderator Effect of Organizational Culture Variables", in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Information Resources Management (Conf-IRM 2015)*, Association for Information Systems.
- Woolf, N.H. and Silver, C. (2017), *Qualitative Analysis Using MAXQDA: The Five-Level QDATM Method*, Taylor & Francis.
- Wraikat, M.M. (2010), "Information Technology Governance Role in Enhancing Performance A Case Study on Jordan Public Sector", in *Proceedings of the World Congress on Engineering and Computer Science (WCECS 2010)*, San Francisco, Calif.
- Wu, S.P.-J., Straub, D.W. and Liang, T.-P. (2015), "How Information Technology Governance Mechanisms and Strategic Alignment Influence Organizational Performance: Insights from a Matched Survey of Business and It Managers", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 39 No. 2, pp. 497–518.
- Yang, C. and Liu, H.-M. (2012), "Boosting firm performance via enterprise agility and network structure", *Management Decision*, Vol. 50 No. 6, pp. 1022–1044.
- Yousif, M., Magnusson, J. and Pessi, K. (2017), "IT Agility: Current State, Organizational Contingencies, and Future Research Avenues", in *Proceedings of the 50th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2017)*, IEEE Computer Society.
- Zhang, P., Zhao, K. and Kumar, R.L. (2014), "Impact of IT Governance and IT Capability on Firm Performance", *Information Systems Management*, Vol. 33 No. 4, pp. 357–373.
- Zhang, Y. and Wildemuth, B.M. (2009), "Qualitative analysis of content", *Applications of social research methods to questions in information and library science*, Vol. 318, pp. 1–12.
- Zhang, Z. and Sharifi, H. (2000), "A methodology for achieving agility in manufacturing organisations", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 20 No. 4, pp. 496–513.
- Zhong, X., Vatanasakdakul, S., Aoun, C. and others (2012), "It Governance In China: Cultral Fit And It Governance Capabilities", in *Proceedings of the 16th Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems (PACIS 2012)*, Association for Information Systems, p. 55.
- Zimmer, M., Baars, H. and Kemper, H.-G. (2012), "The Impact of Agility Requirements on Business Intelligence Architectures", in *Proceedings of the 45th Hawaii International Conference on System Science (HICSS 2012)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 4189–4198.
- Zimmermann, K., Petrikina, J. and Schroder, N. (2016), "The CIO Leadership Mosaic -- Results from a Qualitative Survey in the Silicon Valley and San Francisco Bay Area", in *Proceedings of the 49th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS 2016)*, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 4891–4900.

Appendices

Appendix A: Interview guideline of the pilot study

Hochschule Reutlingen
Reutlingen University

BANKEN DIGITAL

Pilot study

Qualitative interview

BANKEN DIGITAL – Pilot study

Welcome!

First of all, we would like to thank you for participating in this interview and for your time doing so. This interview is conducted by the Research Lab for Digital Business at the Reutlingen University.

The focus of the qualitative interviews is on the digital transformation of banks. The following core issues are focused on:

- The status quo of digital transformation in banks.
- The impact on business models in banks.
- Governance, innovation and agility.

In the main, so-called qualitative questions are posed. For this reason, most questions are not accompanied by an answer scale. Please answer the questions as spontaneously as possible on the basis of your personal opinions and experiences.

We find it important to assure you that this interview is strictly confidential, and the data is not disclosed to third parties. Reutlingen University vouches with their name for the confidentiality of the results of the individual interviews.

The aggregated results of the study shall be presented to the Banken digital (Digital Banking) Conference, attended by high-ranking experts, on 26.09.2017 at the Executive Campus of the University of St. Gallen.

The interview takes approx. 20 minutes.

Thank you once again for participating!

The status quo of digital transformation in banks

In theory, the term digital transformation covers the change in business models, customer experiences and internal corporate processes by using digital technologies.

Digital transformation is thus no new phenomenon.

New, however, is the velocity of transformation, which also presupposes an increased innovative capacity in corporations.

- 1) What do you understand by the term "digital transformation of banks"?
- 2) What is the status quo of digital transformation in banking at your bank?

The impact on business models in banks.

- 3) Which strategic approaches do you find relevant in relation to digital transformation and business models typical for banks?
- 4) In relation to Fintech: Which digitally supported business model innovations do you regard as a threat to traditional banking?
- 5) Which digital innovations do you already use for your business model?
Can you state 1 or 2 examples here?

Governance, innovation and agility

- 6) How can digital transformation in banks be coordinated by suitable governance frameworks?
Which governance frameworks does your corporation use?

- 7) Where does the responsibility for digital and IT lie at your bank?
How are IT and business connected?

- 8) How are innovation processes for the application of digital technologies controlled in your business?

How do you rate the agility of these innovation processes?

Which factors, in your opinion, are relevant for a high degree of agility?

- 9) Which future trends, in your opinion, are particularly relevant for the digital transformation of banks in the next 12 months?

Internationality, a hands-on approach and a focus on research are distinguishing of education at Reutlingen University. Today, Reutlingen University teaches and trains almost 6,000 students in five major subjects.

With success: Reutlingen University counts among the leading universities in Germany. For their holistic training at the highest academic level, it was awarded the ASIIN accreditation recognised seal of quality. In countless university rankings (CHE, Wirtschaftswoche), Reutlingen University occupies top positions across the board.

In addition, Reutlingen University offers first-class and comprehensive proposals for business practice. The activities of research into digital transformation are pooled at the Research Lab for Digital Business.

Contact

Reutlingen University
Research Lab for Digital Business
Sulejman Vejseli
Alteburgstr. 150
D 72762 Reutlingen

Mobil
eMail

Appendix B: Letter of solicitation

BANKEN DIGITAL | Request for a qualitative interview

Dear Mr/Ms XY,

Digital transformation poses a great challenge for the banking world. Businesses outside the sector fully understand how to tackle the bank of today in traditional core businesses with innovative business models.

Banks thus need suitable models for agile innovations. With them, new structures of innovation and governance are increasing in significance for the banking of the future.

Reutlingen University has been running the Research Lab for Digital Business for many years and, in this context, established the research and dialogue project:

“BANKEN DIGITAL – The Perspectives of the Digital Transformation for the Bank of the Future”.

In the framework of the research association, we cooperate, among others, with the University of St. Gallen, the University of Leipzig and the Frankfurt School of Finance and Management. Beyond that, we implement intensive collaboration with banks, FinTechs and businesses from various sectors.

The aim of the initiative is to create a well-founded basis of information for the development and optimisation of intra-bank innovation and governance frameworks. It would be our pleasure to include your perspective in the research process in the shape of a **qualitative interview**. We would appreciate your willingness to conduct an approx. 20-minute interview. A brief reply by e-mail shall suffice to participate in the study.

The results of the latest research will be presented at the exclusive **BANKEN DIGITAL Conference on 26 September 2017** at the **Executive Campus of the University of St. Gallen**.

It is our pleasure to invite you to become part of this highly topical research association. You can find further information about the research approach on our websites:

www.bankendigital.de | www.bankendigital.ch | www.bankendigital.at

It would be our pleasure to send you further information in this respect.

We look forward to your interest and your contacting us.

Kind regards

Alexander Rossmann

Prof. Dr Alexander Rossmann
Research Lab for Digital Business
Herman Hollerith Lehr- und Forschungszentrum
Hochschule Reutlingen | Reutlingen University
Alteburgstrasse 150
D 72762 Reutlingen

Appendix C: Interview guideline of the main qualitative study

BANKEN DIGITAL Governance frameworks for digital transformation

Qualitative interview

BANKEN DIGITAL

Governance frameworks for digital transformation

Welcome!

First of all, we would like to thank you for participating in this interview and for your time doing so. This interview is conducted by the Research Lab for Digital Business at the Reutlingen University.

The focus of the qualitative interviews is on the digital transformation of banks. The following core issues are focused on:

- The status quo of digital transformation in banks.
- Governance frameworks for the digital transformation
- Agility of governance frameworks
- Leadership in digital transformation

In the main, so-called qualitative questions are posed. For this reason, most questions are not accompanied by an answer scale. Please answer the questions as spontaneously as possible on the basis of your personal opinions and experiences.

We find it important to assure you that this interview is strictly confidential, and the data is not disclosed to third parties. Reutlingen University vouches with their name for the confidentiality of the results of the individual interviews.

The aggregated results of the study shall be presented to the BANKEN DIGITAL Conference, attended by high-ranking experts, on 26.09.2017 at the Executive Campus of the University of St. Gallen (www.bankendigital.de).

The interview takes approx. 20 minutes.

Thank you once again for participating!

The status quo of digital transformation in banks

In theory, the term digital transformation covers the change in business models, the digitization of the customer interface and the optimization of internal corporate processes by using digital technologies.

Digital transformation is thus no new phenomenon.

New, however, is the velocity of transformation, which also presupposes an increased innovative capacity in corporations.

- 1.) What do you understand by the term "digital transformation of banks"

Internal comment: What is different to the above definition? What can be added in relation to banks?

- 2.) How long has your bank been dealing with digital transformation?

Internal comment: For how many years? In which way? What status have you already reached?

- 3.) Pain barometer: How urgent do you see the implementation of digital initiatives
How digital would you rate your corporation?

Internal comment: What effect does that have on customers?

- 4.) Assessment of digitalisation at your corporation:

How do you rate the effect of digitalisation initiatives at your corporation?

a.) Local support (e.g. introductions of the e-mortgage)	d.) Corporation-wide integration (e.g. Trendwiki)
b.) Reorganisation of core processes (e.g. outsourcing payment processing)	e.) Changes in work division and cooperation (e.g. cooperation with external financial advisers)
c.) Change to the business model (e.g. new customer access via crowdlending)	f.) Other: _____

- 5.) Which digital innovations has your bank already implemented?

Internal comment: New business models? Innovations to the customer interface? Internal processes? Anything else?
Focus on concise examples.

Governance frameworks for the digital transformation

Governance frameworks cover organizational structures, process flows and communication patterns of a bank. With that, it is about the common orientation of own resources on digital transformation.

- 6.) Which organisational unit is mainly responsible for the management of digital transformation at your bank?

Internal comment: One unit? More than one unit? Who else is involved?
Who makes the final decisions?
Has the model changed in recent years?

- 7.) Which governance frameworks do you apply to manage digital transformation?

Internal comment: Which corporate divisions are represented there and how are the powers of decision distributed?
Is there a specific division for digital topics?

- 8.) Do you use KPIs for managing digital transformation? If so, which ones?

- 9.) How are decisions relating to digital innovations made at your bank?

What are the key processes for this?

Internal comment: Are there any specific processes such as innovation processes, prioritisation processes and similar?
Have new processes been introduced in recent years?

- 10.) How strongly do the following statements apply to communication patterns with digital innovations in your bank?

- | | | | | | |
|--|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| a. Ahead of decisions about digital innovations, we attach great importance to intensive horizontal communication between all relevant organisational areas. | Strongly
agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly
disagree | No
response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| b. Ahead of decisions about digital innovations, we attach great importance to intensive, vertical inclusions of all staff members involved. | Strongly
agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly
disagree | No
response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| c. Our communication pattern in digital transformation is particularly distinguished by strong participation. | Strongly
agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly
disagree | No
response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| d. Specific communication measures are applied for managing digital transformation. | Strongly
agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly
disagree | No
response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| e. Our communication structure is organised effectively to ensure fast communication. | Strongly
agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly
disagree | No
response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Agility of governance frameworks

From a theoretical point of view, agility describes the ability of an organisation to act flexibly, actively, adaptably and with initiative where there are insecure and dynamic surrounding conditions. This mainly relates to the fast adaption to change and the dynamic implementation of innovations.

11.) How do you rate the agility of your governance frameworks?

Internal comment: *What has already been done to improve the agility?
When it comes to the factors, please go into detail
of the difference between structures,
processes and communication where necessary.*

12.) Do you apply specific approaches to promote agility
e.g. cooperation with FinTechs, scrum, design thinking, lean start-up, etc.)?

Internal comment: *Ask for individual examples and have them explained
in more detail.*

Leadership in digital transformation

13.) Which of the following management positions is responsible for digital transformation in your corporation?

- a. CEO (Chief Executive Officer)
- b. CIO (Chief Information Officer)
- c. COO (Chief Operating Officer)
- d. CDO (Chief Digital Officer)
- e. CMO (Chief Marketing Officer)
- f. Other, which one

Internal: Is this management position represented within the leadership team?

14.) Which aspects of leadership are particularly relevant for digital transformation in your opinion?

15.) How strongly do you agree with the following statements, based on your experience?

- | | | | | | | |
|----|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| a. | <i>In digital transformation, the control of digital innovations must be placed in one hand.</i> | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| b. | <i>In digital transformation, transformational rather than transactional leadership approach is required.</i> | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| c. | <i>Decisions about digital innovations are a matter for the management</i> | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| d. | <i>In digital transformation, the management must encourage their employees to enter reasonable risks (e.g. trying out new ideas, taking new routes).</i> | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| e. | <i>In digital transformation, the management should value and reward innovation in the corporation.</i> | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Internationality, a hands-on approach and a focus on research are distinguishing of education at Reutlingen University. Today, Reutlingen University teaches and trains almost 6,000 students in five major subjects.

With success: Reutlingen University counts among the leading universities in Germany. For their holistic training at the highest academic level, it was awarded the ASIIN accreditation recognised seal of quality. In countless university rankings (CHE, Wirtschaftswoche), Reutlingen University occupies top positions across the board.

In addition, Reutlingen University offers first-class and comprehensive proposals for business practice. The activities of research into digital transformation are pooled at the Research Lab for Digital Business.

Contact

Hochschule Reutlingen
Research Lab for Digital Business
Alteburgstr. 150
D 72762 Reutlingen

Sulejman Vejseli
Project Director BANKEN DIGITAL

www.bankendigital.de

7

Appendix D: Interview guideline for refining the agile ITG items

Hochschule Reutlingen
Reutlingen University

BANKEN DIGITAL

Governance in the digital world,
Agile models, methods and structures

Qualitative interview

BANKEN DIGITAL

Governance in the digital world, Agile models, methods and structures

Welcome!

First and foremost, we would like to thank you for participating in this interview and for the time doing so.

This interview is a part of the BANKEN DIGITAL (digital banking) research platform. The focus of the current round of research relates to the agile models, methods and structures used in banks. The interview is developed and implemented by Reutlingen University in cooperation with HCM International.

The following key topics are focused on:

- The status quo of the agility in banks
- Agile models, methods and structures in banks
- The measurability of the success of agile models

In the main, so-called qualitative questions are posed. For this reason, most questions are not accompanied by an answer scale. Please answer the questions as spontaneously as possible on the basis of your personal opinions and experiences. We find it important to assure you that this interview is strictly confidential, and the data is not disclosed to third parties. Reutlingen University vouches with their name for the confidentiality of the results of the individual interviews.

The aggregated results of the study shall be presented in the context of the focus group BANKEN DIGITAL, on 01.03.2018 at the Hotel Schweizerhof in Zurich.

It would be our pleasure to send you information about the further process after the interview.

The interview takes approx. 20 minutes.

Thank you once again for participating!!

The status quo of the agility in banks

From a theoretical point of view, agility describes the ability of an organisation to act flexibly, actively, adaptably and with initiative under insecure and dynamic surrounding conditions. This relates, above all, to the fast adaption to changes and the dynamic implementation of innovations.

- 1.) What do you understand by agility in the context of banks?
- 2.) How long has your corporation already been dealing with approaches for promoting agility?
- 3.) How agile is your bank today in your opinion?

Strategies for promoting agility

Approaches for promoting agility refer, for example, to specific project methods (e.g. Scrum), innovative methods (e.g. design thinking, lean start-ups), the cooperation with external partners and start-ups, innovative models of internal communication and collaboration (e.g. internal social networks) down to new structural models for the entire corporation (e.g. dual operating systems).

- 4.) Which strategies, in your opinion, are essential for promoting the agility of banks?
- 5.) Which specific strategies have you already implemented at your bank?
- 6.) What are the essential internal and external challenges, in your opinion, for implementing agile structures in banks?

The agility of banks in digital transformation

Governance frameworks cover organizational structures, process flows and communication patterns of a bank. With that, it is about the common orientation of own resources on digital transformation.

7.) How strongly do you agree with the following statements on the promotion of agility in banks?

- | | | | | | |
|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| a. The use of agile project and innovation methods has a strong influence on the agility of the entire bank. | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| b. The agility of banks is increased by the creation of an organisational unit responsible for digital transformation (e.g. digital office) | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| c. Stability and agility are a contradiction: Both guidelines cannot be integrated in an integrated governance framework. Thus, dual models are imperative. | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| d. In the future, agile governance frameworks will be imperative for the success of banks. | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| e. The digital transformation is a key driver for promoting agility in banks. | Strongly agree | Agree | Disagree | Strongly disagree | No response |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> |

8.) Please put the following drivers for the promotion of agility in digital transformation in order. Which driver is of highest importance in your opinion?

- The behaviour of top management and the transformation to transformational leadership
- The creation of suitable organisational structures
- The introduction and implementation of agile project and innovation methods
- The training of staff and the promotion of competences for agility
- Initiatives for a cultural transformation in banks

Which drivers are important in addition to these?

The measurability of the success of agile models

Measuring success using Key Performance Indicators (KPI) is no new approach. The KPIs that can be used to measure the success of agility is still the subject of discussion.

In particular, the question of the interplay of KPIs for measuring agility and traditional success metrics is posed.

- 9.) What, in your opinion, is success in the context of agility?
- 10.) How can the success of approaches for promoting agility be measured? Do you apply specific KPIs for agility?
- 11.) In what relation are KPIs for agility to traditional success metrics?
(Keyword: Error culture, learning v. reducing costs)

Internationality, a hands-on approach and a focus on research are distinguishing of education at Reutlingen University. Today, Reutlingen University teaches and trains almost 6,000 students in five major subjects.

With success: Reutlingen University counts among the leading universities in Germany. For their holistic training at the highest academic level, it was awarded the ASIIN accreditation recognised seal of quality. In countless university rankings (CHE, Wirtschaftswoche), Reutlingen University occupies top positions across the board.

In addition, Reutlingen University offers first-class and comprehensive proposals for business practice. The activities of research into digital transformation are pooled at the Research Lab for Digital Business.

Contact

Hochschule Reutlingen
Research Lab for Digital Business
Alteburgstr. 150
D 72762 Reutlingen

Sulejman Vejseli
Project Director BANKEN DIGITAL

Appendix E: Questionnaire – Quantitative screening

 Hochschule Reutlingen
Reutlingen University

 DIGITAL BANKING Workshop

Governance in the digital world
Agile models, methods and structures

Zurich | 01 March 2018 #BankenDigital

About you

What is your position within your corporation?

- Director/executive
- Middle management
- Team leader
- Employee
- Other: _____

Which functional area do you work in?

- Specialist department
- IT
- Marketing
- Product management
- Corporation development
- Director/executive
- Other: _____

What is the precise name of your position?

What is your gender?

- Male
- Female

How old are you? _____

Please turn overleaf, more on the back

Agility of the governance models

Governance models comprise the organisational structures, process flows and communication patterns of a bank. In this context, it is about the common alignment of own resources to digital transformation.

Please rate the following strategies according to their effectiveness for the promotion of an agile governance in the corporation.

Agile organisational structures

How effective do you find the following structural adaptations for promoting the agility of governance models within the corporation?

	Not effective	Barely effective	Moderately effective	Fairly effective	Very effective
Small interdisciplinary and self-organised teams.	<input type="radio"/>				
The introduction of short and flexible decision-making processes	<input type="radio"/>				
The creation of a project organisation each with a product owner.	<input type="radio"/>				
The creation of an organisational unit responsible for digital transformation (e.g. digital office).	<input type="radio"/>				
The creation of an innovation lab for exchanging information, knowledge and ideas and for evaluating innovation.	<input type="radio"/>				
The creation of a transformation board/innovation board comprising members of the supervisory board, members of the executive board and experts to discuss and decide on the strategic direction of digitalisation initiatives.	<input type="radio"/>				
The introduction of a multidisciplinary transformation/innovation steering committee comprising members of the management board, middle management and department heads of various areas to prioritise innovation initiatives.	<input type="radio"/>				
The creation of an incubator with its own agile structures (e.g. a subsidiary).	<input type="radio"/>				
The set-up of a matrix organisation in the corporation.	<input type="radio"/>				
The creation of a leadership board and external executives to exchange information about the digital transformation.	<input type="radio"/>				

Agile processes

How effective do you find the following processes for promoting the agility of governance frameworks?

	Not effective	Barely effective	Moderately effective	Fairly effective	Very effective
Use of agile practices (Scrum, DevOps, design thinking, lean start-up etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Assume risks (trial and error)	<input type="radio"/>				
Innovation processes	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of innovative key performance indicators (KPIs) for agility/smart analysis processes	<input type="radio"/>				
Fast and agile decision-making processes	<input type="radio"/>				
Agile project and product management	<input type="radio"/>				
Lessons learned processes	<input type="radio"/>				
Optimised prioritisation processes	<input type="radio"/>				
Process reengineering (automation and digitalisation)	<input type="radio"/>				
Ad hoc meetings / coordination processes	<input type="radio"/>				
Optimisation of IT architecture	<input type="radio"/>				
Change processes (change management processes) (e.g. change agents)	<input type="radio"/>				
Prototyping	<input type="radio"/>				
Decentralised innovation budgets	<input type="radio"/>				
Co-creation workshops with customers	<input type="radio"/>				
Agile risk management (e.g. agility in the implementation of regulations)	<input type="radio"/>				
Lighthouse projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Regular planning cycles	<input type="radio"/>				
Regular IT releases	<input type="radio"/>				

Please turn overleaf, more on the back

Communication patterns/cooperation and collaboration/employees

How effective do you find the following approaches for promoting agility within your corporation?

	Not effective	Barely effective	Moderately effective	Fairly effective	Very effective
Transformational leadership approach	<input type="radio"/>				
Open communication and participation of employees	<input type="radio"/>				
Continuous employee training/regular cross-functional trainings	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of social/digital media (e.g. WhatsApp, Facebook, Enterprise Social Network, blogs)	<input type="radio"/>				
Flat communication structures	<input type="radio"/>				
Employee empowerment	<input type="radio"/>				
Regular management dialogues and events (e.g. sounding boards, panels)	<input type="radio"/>				
Regular cross-department communication	<input type="radio"/>				
Specific innovation rooms/open-space concepts	<input type="radio"/>				
Staff recruiting (e.g. Digital Citizen)	<input type="radio"/>				
Management attention/management as a role model	<input type="radio"/>				
Rewarding employees for innovations	<input type="radio"/>				
Cooperation with start-ups (e.g. with FinTech corporations)	<input type="radio"/>				
Cooperation with business partners	<input type="radio"/>				
Cooperation with outsourcing partners	<input type="radio"/>				
Internal cooperation (e.g. with own subsidiaries)	<input type="radio"/>				
Cooperation with research partners	<input type="radio"/>				

Thank you for your participation!

Appendix F: Questionnaire of the quantitative study

Hochschule Reutlingen
Reutlingen University

Governance Frameworks for Digital Transformation

Dear Sirs or Madams,

First of all, we would like to thank you for participating in this study and for your time. The questionnaire here is conducted by the Research Lab for Digital Business at the University of Reutlingen.

The focus of this quantitative questionnaire relates to the **effectiveness and agility of governance models for the digital transformation of companies**. It would be our pleasure to include **your opinion as an expert** in the development process and we kindly ask for your assistance and feedback. The insights gained in the scope of this study will be drawn on for both purposes of analysis for companies and for gaining scientific insights.

Please answer as spontaneously as possible on the basis of your personal opinions and experiences. We find it important to ensure you that this survey is anonymous and absolutely confidential. Data will not be disclosed to third parties.

It will take about 10 to 15 minutes to fill in the questionnaire.

Please note
To make the questionnaire easier to read, only the male form has been used. It goes without saying that this includes the female form.

Many thanks once again for your support!

Research Lab for Digital Business
Reutlingen University

[Continue](#)

Hochschule Reutlingen
Reutlingen University

10%

Personnel responsibility

Please indicate whether you are responsible for personnel in your current position.

Please choose answer

[Continue](#)

28%

About You

What position do you take within your corporation?

Please choose answer

What is your exact position name?

This field can optionally be filled out. The information is aggregated with other industry data and is in no way used to draw conclusions about individual persons.

In which country is the corporation in which you are employed?

Please choose answer

Back

Continue

39%

About Your Corporation

What industry does your company belong to?

Please choose answer

How many employees does your corporation employ?

Please choose answer

Back

Continue

44%

Governance Frameworks

Governance frameworks cover organizational structures, process flows and communication patterns of a corporation. With that, it is about the common orientation of own resources on digital transformation.

Organizational structures

How strongly do the following statements apply to organizational structures in your corporation?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Our corporation has a steering committee at the executive level responsible for determining IT development prioritization.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has a steering committee comprised of business and IT people.	<input type="radio"/>						
CIO has a direct reporting line to the CEO and/or COO within the corporation.	<input type="radio"/>						
The corporation's CIO is a full member of the executive committee.	<input type="radio"/>						
IT is a regular agenda item and reporting issue for the board of directors of the corporation.	<input type="radio"/>						

Process flows

How strongly do the following statements apply to process flows in your corporation?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Our corporation has established a formal prioritization process for IT investments in which business and IT is involved.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has established formal processes to control for and report upon budgets of IT.	<input type="radio"/>						
In our corporation we use various key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure IT performance.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has established formal processes to define and update IT strategies.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has established formal processes to govern and manage IT and digitalization projects.	<input type="radio"/>						
Please click on the far left on "Strongly disagree" to show that you read the texts.	<input type="radio"/>						

Communication patterns and relational mechanisms

How strongly do the following statements apply to communication patterns and relational mechanisms in your corporation?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
In our corporation, business and IT managers/executives have informal meetings on a regular basis.	<input type="radio"/>						
Internal corporate communication regularly addresses IT issues.	<input type="radio"/>						
The CIO or similar role in our corporation is able to clearly articulate a vision for IT's role in the corporation.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our executives/senior managers set a good example of acting as "partners".	<input type="radio"/>						
In our corporation, specific communication mechanisms are used to improve communication between business units (e.g., account management, intranet).	<input type="radio"/>						

Back

Continue

Agility of Governance Frameworks

Agility describes the ability of an organisation to act flexible, actively, adaptably and with initiative in uncertain and dynamic environments. This mainly relates to the fast adaption to change and the dynamic implementation of innovations.

In this context, it is about complementing, expanding and redesigning organizational structures, processes and communication patterns in terms of agility for digital transformation.

Agility of the organizational structures

How strongly do the following statements apply to the agility of the organizational structures in your corporation?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
In digitization projects, our teams are interdisciplinary.	<input type="radio"/>						
For digitization projects, our teams organize themselves largely independently.	<input type="radio"/>						
Compared to our competitors, our corporation has short and flexible decision-making paths.	<input type="radio"/>						
The responsibility for the development of innovations is bundled in a concentrated unit (e.g. Innovation Lab).	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has a digital transformation steering committee to prioritize innovation initiatives.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has a multidisciplinary steering committee consisting of representatives of all management levels.	<input type="radio"/>						

Agility of the process flows

How strongly do the following statements apply to the agility of the process flows in your corporation?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
In our corporation, agile project and innovation methods (e.g. Scrum, DevOps) are in widespread use.	<input type="radio"/>						
Employees are encouraged to take reasonable risks (e.g., trying innovative ideas, trial and error).	<input type="radio"/>						
Compared to our competitors, our decision-making processes for digitization initiatives are fast and agile.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation uses change management processes to constantly optimize overall governance.	<input type="radio"/>						
For the development of products and features, we regularly use the principle of prototyping.	<input type="radio"/>						
In our corporation, we conduct co-creation workshops with customers as an innovation measure.	<input type="radio"/>						

Agility of the communication patterns and relational mechanisms

How strongly do the following statements apply to the agility of the communication patterns and relational mechanisms in your corporation?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Executives in our corporation treat others as individuals rather than just as a member of a group.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation attaches great importance to continuous training of employees in the area of digital transformation to promote skills for agility.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our communication structures are organized flat.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation's communication structures allow it to ensure fast communication.	<input type="radio"/>						
In the digital transformation, our corporation attaches great importance to the empowerment and participation of its employees.	<input type="radio"/>						
In the digital transformation, our corporation attaches importance to cooperation with start-ups to promote agility.	<input type="radio"/>						
In the digital transformation, our corporation attaches importance to cooperation with business partners to promote agility.	<input type="radio"/>						
In our corporation, there is regular cross-sectoral communication about digitization initiatives.	<input type="radio"/>						

Back

Continue

Strategic Business/IT Alignment

Strategic business/IT alignment encompasses the systematic approach to the comprehensive synchronization of business and IT. It primarily relates to the coordination between business and IT in terms of products, quality and market conditions.

Product-oriented strategic alignment

How strongly do the following statements apply to product-oriented strategic alignment between business and IT in your corporation.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
We attempt to be ahead of our competitors in introducing new products.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our current systems enable us to introduce new products earlier than our competitors.	<input type="radio"/>						
We attempt to be ahead of our competitors by offering a wide range of products.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our current systems enable our corporation to diversify our products.	<input type="radio"/>						
We attempt to be ahead of our competitors by ensuring that our products are distinctively different from our competitors.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our current systems help us to distinguish our products from those of competitors.	<input type="radio"/>						

Quality-oriented strategic alignment

How strongly do the following statements apply to quality-oriented strategic alignment between business and IT in your corporation.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
We attempt to be ahead of our competitors by quality products rather than price.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our current systems allow us to improve the quality of our products.	<input type="radio"/>						
We constantly improve the efficiency of our production process.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our current systems help in improving the efficiency of our production process.	<input type="radio"/>						
We attempt to be ahead of our competitors by providing quality service to our customers.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our current systems enable our corporation to provide quality customer service.	<input type="radio"/>						

Market-oriented strategic alignment

How strongly do the following statements apply to market-oriented strategic alignment between business and IT in your corporation.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
We attempt to be ahead of our competitors by intensive marketing of our products.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our current systems enable us to embark on an intensive marketing of our products.	<input type="radio"/>						
We attempt to achieve growth by expanding into new markets.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our current systems assist us in identifying new markets.	<input type="radio"/>						

Back

Continue

Performance

Financial results

How strongly do the following statements apply to financial results in your corporation?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Our corporation's return on investment (ROI) is better compared to the average in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation's return on equity (ROE) is better compared to the average in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation's return on asset (ROA) is better compared to the average in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						

Operational excellence

How strongly do the following statements apply to operational excellence in your corporation?

Operational excellence is the highest level of capacity in terms of efficiency, effectiveness, value and productivity.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Our corporation has better productivity improvements compared to other corporations in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has better timeline of customer service compared to other corporations in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has better production cycle time compared to other corporations in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						

Customer perspective

How strongly do the following statements apply to customer perspective in your corporation?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	More or less disagree	Undecided	More or less agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Customers perceive our corporation's quality of products and services is better compared to other corporations in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has higher customer satisfaction compared to other corporations in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						
Our corporation has better corporate image compared to other corporations in the same industry.	<input type="radio"/>						

Back

Continue

100%

The data were submitted successfully. You can now close the browser window.

Close window

Appendix G: Ethical approval

Hochschule Reutlingen • Alteburgstraße 150 • 72762 Reutlingen

Ethical Approval

Dear Sulejman

We reviewed your research plan on the project **"IT Governance: Current State of and Future Perspectives on the Concept of Agility in IT Governance"**.

Due to guidelines of ethical research at Reutlingen University compliance with ethical guidelines is assessed continuously by the co-supervisors.

We are pleased to inform you that ethical approval has been granted.

Please keep your supervisors informed should there be any changes to your research plans which may require further ethical consideration.

Yours sincerely

Prof. Dr. Alexander Rossmann

Reutlingen University
School of Informatics

Email: alexander.rossmann@reutlingen-university.de

Prof. Dr. Thomas Connolly

University of the West of Scotland
School of Computing, Engineering
& Physical Sciences

Email: Thomas.Connolly@uws.ac.uk

01. Februar 2017

Seite 1 von 1

Prof. Dr. Alexander Rossmann

alexander.rossmann@reutlingen-university.de

Hochschule Reutlingen
Reutlingen University

Alteburgstraße 150 • 72762 Reutlingen • Deutschland • T. +49 (0)7121 271-0 • F. +49 (0)7121 271-1101 • www.reutlingen-university.de

Appendix H: Ethical evaluation

Hochschule Reutlingen
Reutlingen University

Ethical Evaluation

Mr Sulejman Vejseli
Doctoral Student
Reutlingen University
Herman Hollerith Research Center

20th April 2020

Dear Sulejman,

The research commission of the Herman Hollerith Center at Reutlingen University has reviewed your thesis **"IT Governance: Current State of and Future Perspectives on the Concept of Agility in IT Governance"**. We confirm that your research meets the requirements of the ethical codex for researchers and research projects at Reutlingen University.

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Prof. Dr. Alfred Zimmermann
Head of Research

Reutlingen University
Faculty of Informatics
Herman Hollerith Research Center, Böblingen, Germany

Email: alfred.zimmermann@reutlingen-university.de

Appendix I: Interview transcript of bank 1

A: What do you understand by digital transformation in banks? Do you, for example, agree with the definition or what can, or would you like to add to it? #00:00:11#

B: Exactly. Well, we have defined it internally like your theoretical definition, meaning we simply say that digital transformation has two dimensions. There is an internal bank dimension. In our case, that is in the first instance process automation, and then the second dimension is essentially the use of digital technologies at the customer interface. These are the two dimensions that we see in exactly the same way and we say with regard to the approach: Of top priority is digitalisation at the customer interface and from there, going backwards so to say, the internal bank transformation takes place. However, the process and the definition exactly as you say it. #00:01:11#

A: Good, yes, question number two: How long has your bank been dealing with digital transformation? #00:01:19#

B: You have already said it. It is nothing new. The term we use, “digital banking” not digital transformation, is a project of its own, even now with decided resources on the management’s, supervisory board’s list of items since about 2014. #00:01:41#

A: What status have you already reached when you now look back? #00:01:47#

B: We have now implemented many different solutions at the customer interface. There is one aspect, financial assistance, possibilities of extending mortgages online by way of video identification for example. Then the setup of a specific team for the topic of “digital banking”. Then the setup or ongoing setup of a specific technical infrastructure for these digital solutions. Then the soft factors such as the setup of skills for cultural change within the bank, sensitisation for the topic. We have done such things with the management, dialogues, the presentation of FinTech solutions and discussions for the topic, trainings. How the customer adviser can use TWINT in such a way that the staff also A) know these solutions, B) also know how they are supposed to use them and the fact that I can integrate them on an iPhone or Samsung Smartphone. That kind of thing. #00:03:33#

A: You have probably already listed a few things. Re question 3 for example. Which specific innovations have you put into practice or implemented in your business model? #00:03:47#

B: Well, business model is probably a bit of an exaggeration. but we have implemented financial assistants, the online extension of mortgages, video identification and then, which we also add to the list, that we have fully restructure ebanking to modern technologies in a

modern user interface. These are, from memory, the key elements that went live this past year. #00:04:27#

A: Let's go to the next page which is about governance models, which for the digital transformation here also a short definition in advance, of what we mean by governance models, this covers namely organisational structures, process flows and communications of a bank. With that, the context covers the mutual orientation of own resources to digital transformation. So, what do things look like at your bank? Which organisational unit is mainly responsible for governing digital transformation? Is it one unit, several units? Who is involved in it and so on...? #00:05:14#

B: The responsibility is contained in the organigram. It is in my unit, that is the service centre. Other banks call it logistics. That is the responsibility after all. In my area, there is a unit with five people handling the subject. The topic of "digital banking" and this unit is very strongly networked with the whole bank. That means that the responsibility as per the organigram as well as the fact that the topic is pushed ahead, that resources are provided, control of the budget, all lies with me. The content-related topics are worked out very strongly in a matrix. #00:06:10#

A: That means that at the end, you also make the decision as the party responsible about what should be implemented and what shouldn't be? #00:06:20#

B: For the implementation of the content of a project, we have two committees; on the one hand, there is a technical committee that assesses and approves the technical implementation, and there is a business steering committee, as we call it, which defines the portfolio of individual measures. But the process or the driving is my responsibility, and that happens to be me. How the budget is used is decided by the steering committee, but I will be responsible for ensuring that it will not be exceeded and that it is respected. #00:07:16#

A: So, in this steering committee, there are also many areas included ...#00:07:24#

B: Like I said, in this area, the head of "digital banking", a colleague of mine, is the manager of this steering committee. There are a total of three members of the management board in it, i.e., besides me, the two front management members, that is the retail banking officer, the private banking officer and then the head of product management, the head of multichannel management then the chief of staff of private banking and the head of IT. From memory, that is about 8 people. There is an external representative who monitors the market and technology on our behalf. #00:08:27#

A: If you may, another subsequent question: Has this “digital banking” changed due to digital transformation? Didn’t that used to be like that, or has it been set up completely new in the course of digital transformation? #00:08:47#

B: Exactly, we started sometime in the autumn of 2014 and one of the measures, that was in 2015, we created an organisational concept where this organisation as I described it was created in the course of this organisational concept or where the responsibility lies in my area. We have a specific unit that takes care of this topic, we work on a matrix basis, there are two decision-making committees, a technical and a specialist one and they were set up. #00:09:30#

A: Let’s go to question 5. How are decisions made in your bank relating to digital innovations? Which processes are essential for this? How do things look at your bank? Are there various new innovation processes, prioritisation processes and the likes? #00:09:52#

B: We have an annual cycle each spring, so the portfolio is redesigned each year. We do not have a five-year portfolio; rather, it is rebuilt each year to take account of the short-term nature of the matter. We work together with e-foresight. E-foresight is a part of Swisscom, who conduct technology and market observations. We work together with e-foresight. E-foresight is a part of Swisscom that makes technology and market observations. They do that for us on an ongoing basis. Then, the current trends are presented in the spring. The current developments derived there represent possible thrusts. These are then discussed in the steering committee, prioritised, approved by the management board on this basis; these are relatively rough approaches that are defined. On this basis, project ideas are then specified in the next roughly four to six months, elaborated and the time and effort as well as budget are estimated, then discussed, prioritised by the steering committee and then approved by management in the budget process. After that, the process of implementation begins, and a new portfolio is set up in parallel. #00:11:35#

A: This means that even these processes are quasi re-established. #00:11:40#

B: Re-established and, of course, integrated in existing ones, e.g. in a budget process etc, attuned to the available process. #00:11:53#

A: We can now go on to question six. We make a few statements there. You can fully agree or totally disagree. I will read out to you how strongly the following statements about communications regarding digital innovations hold true in your business. Ahead of decisions about digital innovation, we attach importance to intensive, horizontal communication between all relevant organisational areas? #00:12:26#

B: In that case, I would tend to agree. #00:12:30#

A: Re b) Ahead of decisions about digital innovations, we attach great importance to intensive vertical involvement of all participating staff?

B: Yes, I also agree. #00:12:46#

A: Re c) Our communication patterns in digital transformation are particularly distinguished by a high degree of participation. #00:13:01#

B: That is ... we are trying to change things, i.e. I would rather not agree. We have had too much participation and we have to change that. We are trying to..., because there was a phase... this topic was such a hype, everybody wanted to be involved, everybody wanted to have their say, anybody who was not part felt they would miss out on the future. It was then difficult to make sustainable decisions anywhere. That is why I actually do not agree, but it is also partly still an objective. #00:13:50#

A: Re d) Specific communication measures are applied for governing the digital transformation? #00:13:58#

B: Yes, I would say we are doing that. I fully agree. #00:14:02#

A: And to what extent? So, how are you doing this for example? #00:14:06#

B: What I said earlier or these organisational structures, these process flows, I now understand that as... well, difficult to know what is meant by that. #00:14:22#

A: Yes, by all means. It may also be possible for structures to be interlinked in such a way that communication has a nice flow, or that everybody receives important information from each other about digital transformation, but ok, it is good that ... #00:14:37#

B: There are also information events every year where 80 to 100 employees, which are 10% of the staff population, are informed and updated in two hours on the topic. There are also small circles, communication, information, there are so-called "digital streams", subject-matter-specific, which the topics. There is a lot, this is all counted among communication measures. This is why I would have now agreed. #00:15:21#

A: Perfect. Our communication structure is organised effectively to ensure fast communication. So, here it is the speed factor. #00:15:33#

B: Rather not. We have not achieved that. #00:15:38#

A: Good. That was everything about the governance model. We can now go to the next page about the agility of governance models. Here also a theoretical perspective in advance about

what that means. Namely, that a corporation is able to act flexibly, actively, adaptably and with initiative under insecure and dynamic surrounding conditions. Above all, this relates to fast adaption and changes and the dynamic implementation of innovations. How do you rate the agility of your governance models and which factors are then, for example, relevant for greater agility? #00:16:31#

B: Agility – we have a long journey ahead of us. There is a lot of potential, assessing, or... Which factors are particularly relevant for a higher degree of agility...? I believe it has many cultural topics, it has something to do with the readiness to assume risk, something to do with the perfectionism one has, also has something to do with methodology, the knowledge of methods that one has or doesn't have, experiences one has had or bad experiences that one has possibly partly had. There are many factors and I would say, first and foremost, cultural factors. Of course, there are also structures that are, if anything, stiff or make agility difficult. That is certainly also the case; it is still a hierarchical organisation where agility per se is not that easy. #00:17:48#

A: Obviously. Let's go back to the structures you stated earlier again. The agility there where you said it is still a little rigid or are there means of improvement? #00:18:05#

B: Yes, or the structures we have established are first and foremost targeted at completing the decision-making process in a coordinated and disciplined way, a wider involvement or... there is, of course, a lot of consensus contained in it. Of course, it may have a lot to do with avoiding risks, it also has something to do with the fact that original ideas are maybe polished off in the process. Thus, the structures we have here do not promote agility. At the most, they are neutral. There are these "digital streams", which I briefly mentioned. This is actually the idea of agility, small teams, hierarchically set at the lowest level, heterogeneous – comprising product managers, salespeople and IT people who are responsible for a topic. For example, credit, or whatever, gets a budget, gets resources, and can then do something in this context on their own competence. Hence, we attempt to embed some agility in a hierarchical organization, but that's not so easy. #00:19:48#

A: Yes, exactly. So, taking time into consideration, let's go to question 8. Do you apply specific approaches to promote agility? For example, a cooperation with FinTechs, Scrum, design thinking, lean start-ups, etc. such methods? #00:20:07#

B: We have done or are doing everything you have listed in our own hands and way. We have also cooperated with a FinTech and also introduced a product. Scrum...also a wide term, but we implement these digital projects in Scrum style. Design thinking: We now have

a project that we are proceeding with in design thinking style by the book and the implementation is now taking place with lean start-up methods. #00:20:51#

A: All right. Good, we have also managed agility. We can now go to the next page, which is about leadership in digital transformation. Which of the following management positions is responsible for digital transformation in your bank? I believe you have already partly answered this. #00:21:14#

B: Exactly. I have the ultimate responsibility and my position is called COO. IT also lies with me, but I do not call myself CIO. However, there are committees that make specialist decisions, it's just always a question of what is understood by responsibility. Employing/sacking people is up to me. #00:21:49#

A: Ok, so you are the COO, aren't you? #00:21:52#

B: Precisely.

A: And thus, also part of the management. Good, which aspects of management are of particular relevance for digital transformation in your opinion? #00:22:04#

B: That is a difficult question. I believe it is just like this... So, for our organisation...somehow the interplay between autonomy and control, it is sort of like managing this area of tension. That is what I would regard as the main issue, well even against the background of a hierarchical organisation. How much autonomy can we, do we want to give, how much control does it need. Managing this conflict in objectives. #00:22:58#

A: Let's go to the last point. There are a few statements there again and you can again fully agree here or disagree. To what extent would you agree with the following statements on the basis of your experiences in digital transformation? Must the management of digital innovations lie in one hand? #00:23:32#

B: The question cannot be answered like that. I believe our basic model is good for us. That means the issues to do with content should not lie in one hand unless one describes a committee as one hand. Instead it should be a consensual process when it comes to the implementation, e.g. exclusive control of methods etc. should lie in one hand because I am... When the specialist department says, "we want that", then I can say "we are now doing a lean start-up". That is what I then decide and that makes sense. I can also say "we are now doing design thinking". I also have the budget to call in consultants or experts. I do not believe, however, that the content should lie in one hand. #00:24:28#

A: OK, then you differentiate in your corporation. Well, good let's go to b) In digital transformation, a transformational leadership approach rather than a transactional one is required. #00:24:45#

B: Yes, I do tend to agree but it must be seen in a differentiated way. Right, transformational in principle, but where entire IT infrastructures are to be re-established, then the way may be transactional and one sticks to these standards, even if something else may have been cooler. That is also a mixture, but from the basic philosophy, I think transformational is right, so I tend to agree here. But that alone cannot lead to success.

A:C) Decisions about digital innovations are a matter for the management? #00:25:32#

B: No, I tend not to agree or fully disagree with that. #00:25:39#

A: In digital transformation, the management must encourage their employees to assume justifiable risks. #00:25:47#

B: Yes, I agree. #00:25:51#

A: In digital transformation, the management should appreciate and reward innovations in the corporation. #00:25:59#

B: In my opinion, I used to think that, it is no longer necessary. In the meantime, we have far more ideas for innovation than we can implement. I tend to disagree Thus, it comes naturally. #00:26:20#

Appendix J: Interview transcript of Bank 7

A: What is special about the digital transformation of banks? #00:00:03#

B: Well, I believe that the term itself catered for very much heterogeneity among bankers in the scope of the discussion as I continuously experience it on the basis of how each person defines it for themselves. But when I define it for myself, I always take the process chain from A to Z. What do I mean by that? A is customer behaviour and the speed at which customer behaviour has changed has increased considerably, I would say, and customer behaviour is changing at a speed that was entirely unknown in the banking sector. And, for this reason, I believe digitalisation and new research projects and other issues are something that has always been done meaning digitalisation is actually nothing new. It is by all means an old term, on the one hand, that is experiencing a certain hype, but what I am concerned with really is entirely customer behaviour, products, processes, services and after sales measures and then the customer again. And I believe this process chain is what is decisive when thinking about it. I also experience many competitors even on the market who then say: Yes, then I'll just build an app and then the subject of digitalisation is satisfied again. Well, it isn't. Because I believe that it also strongly intervenes in entire process structures, the handling of tasks in service, in the back office, if I merely say the topic of blockchain, where I believe it will take another 3 to 4 years until there will be any really big breakthroughs, but the signs are already there that we can possibly dream of amazing cost savings, which would, of course, quote unquote create completely different possibilities in the loan administration process, securities, transfer and everything related to that. #00:01:57#

A: That means that the subject of digitalisation covers for you the simplification of processes, perhaps the revision of internal processes and even down to the subject of customer interface. It is thus maybe also local support for individual departments or also the introduction of new possibilities that maybe even make conversation with the customer easier or make it easier for the customer. #00:02:20#

B: Exactly

A: Up to this point, i.e. both the external and the internal. Okay.

B: Exactly. So, if we take it like that, how long have we actually been dealing with, shall we say, digital transformation? I believe for a long time, but not as intensively as this. And that

has been coming up, I believe noticeably in the past 2 to 3 years. Speaking for us. Of course, in our group, we have the unique constellation that we are the only financial conglomerate in Germany. With our bank, insurance business and building society. We thus need all regulatory requirements that the market actually gives us and regulations. On the other hand, of course, we have a unit such as the bank where digitalisation is already more advanced as is the case, for example, in the insurance sector. And that is also the reason why I came here to this group in 2014, to advance the topic of digitalisation of the bank, define test fields there, to try out and then to see how I can translate this to the insurance sector, to the building society. I take the classical subject of video consulting which we have implemented on a very large scale in the investment sector, where customers in the Black Forest go to their field workers, for example. He does not have the expertise now to advise on all possible shares. Instead he says: Gee! I have a specialist located in Ludwigsburg, turns his computer on, sets up the video consulting and the customer receives first-class video advice with an advice protocol with all certifications that are required by the MiFID and required in BPAG terms (?) provided free of charge. And we conducted far more than 2000 video consultations last year, where the customer said: Yep, I am happy to conclude a contract with you. That is sensational. So, such topics like video consulting or video support can be integrated in construction financing at a building society, in more complex products at an insurance corporation and those are the next steps that we will be taking. And the digital innovation if we take it as a whole for our corporation was once the foundation of the [name] Bank by definition, so to say. At the beginning of 2016, we founded the Digital Customer Office, which I chair. Hence, I have a dual function, once as a Member of the [bank] Executive Board for digital topics and once, so to speak, as the Chief Digital Officer of the group for all digital themes. The new unit was created at the beginning of 2016 where we defined and set up a separate unit on the AG level, and bundles all the digital road maps of the individual corporations, so that we also have an entire digital road-map view for the entire corporation. #00:05:25#

A: It is amazing when we search you on Google, it is the only bank where you can see straight away from its appearance that it is somehow digital, it is customer-friendly, it is online. It is totally amazing. I really do have to say, in our opinion, it immediately goes down well with the customer. #00:05:42#

B: Yes, great. All is well then. That's the way it should be. (laughing) #00:05:46#

A: And how urgent do you see the topic of digital transformation in your bank especially or the implementation? #00:05:55#

B: Well, we have come relatively far I must add. Well, if one compares us in terms of benchmarks, I always take an absolute hype such as N26. I have already built the Lego Bank as I call it, I started to build it in 2014. We have divested areas for the [name] bank, transferred the securities business to the IBs so that new frontends can be purchased that are important for the field workers but also for the consumers. The migration took place last October. We have now conducted a migration to the associates' Fiducia IT system, to be able to act according to standards and to concentrate more on the frontend issues and not to see running the bank as the main activity, but change instead, to be able to apply the resources within our organisation in a different way, of course. When I look at all of that, then one has to see that the bank was an essential driver for that, but then again, creating the Chief Digital Officer in the group was an important element because he is directly attached to the CEO, which makes it a clear matter for the management. And the third point is that we also founded a digital GmbH in Berlin, which deals with verifying and testing other business models again to take another look accordingly at how we can position ourselves on the market again. #00:07:32#

A: That was about to be my question as to whether you go as far as to say: Digitalisation means to you a real change or expansion of the business model or whatever. #00:07:40#

B: Definitely. #00:07:42#

A: The 3rd question: Which digital innovations has your bank already implemented? Of course, you have, I believe, already mentioned numerous ones or is there anything else you...#00:07:50#

B: Well, in the meantime, I could write entire books. Well. We have implemented the Robo Adviser in the bank. We are cooperating with Fino GmbH with the automatic account change service with the start-up here. At the end of last year, we bought [name] AG with a majority ownership of 75%. They deal with the topic of financial assistant and CRM usage of customer data and it is one of the apps that with certainty presents the topic of content, insurance, building society contracts, mortgaging, capital investments for customers in a well-arranged way. And that, of course, is a completely different convenience for the customer. We have done various other topics apart from in the normal back office structures, i.e. applied robotics processes to further build certain automations in shadow processing, thus meaning that nobody manually deals with a current account anymore; it passes through

in the background. Then, we will continue to expand the same in various insurance products. So, from there, it can be seen that we clearly want to occupy the customer interface as it is called and do not want to leave it up to the start-up or insure FinTech. #00:09:22#

A: Okay. Good. Let's now go to the next chapter: Governance models for digital transformation. Thus, everything we understand by that is the organisational unit, the process flows, communication, everything that falls under this. Which organisational... #00:09:39#

B: If I act on the assumption of me as a bank, that is a matter for the management. So, I, as the chairman, am the person responsible for digitalisation. Full stop. Well, it really is a matter for the management. I will say this in addition, I operate my organisation and have developed, so to say, a kind of business development if you wish to call it that, which I have transferred to digitalisation and digital transformation and governance, which are, so to say, also active in the group with the job sharing function. This means, the staff have an employment contract with the bank but also work in the BNW_AG (or W&W) via job sharing and this way we control everything from one place. #00:10:22#

A: Okay. I understand. And the model has changed to the extent that this actually never existed, i.e. even now. #00:10:32#

B: It didn't exist. We'll get back to that again later. You had some questions in it such Scrum, design thinking etc. pp., none of that existed in that way previously, yes. #00:10:43#

A: Exactly. Are there any KPIs that you take particularly to control the whole subject of digital transformation? #00:10:52#

B: Yes, well I would say that the bottom line is that I have to be extremely careful. So, when doing F and E processes, you have to have a clear target. You also have to say what you want to invest to arrive at sub-step 1 to 5. And then you have to abort it quickly if you notice you can't manage it. I believe that is the key change process in comparison to the past. In the past, one continued on projects, I believe, until the 12th of never to then ascertain that you had invested a relatively large amount of money and the benefit didn't come across. Today, decisions are made significantly faster, i.e., we undertake something specific and say we want to spend EUR X on ideation, validation and the first NBP. By doing so, we hope for such and such a number of clicks by customers or a leaner process of XY and when we do manage that, it is extended, and if we don't, then it is buried again. #00:11:56#

A: And in the past, it was most probably the case that you were probably on the move significantly more stiffly and as you already said, if something was up and running, it was

kept running for the time being, success was not tracked as much and, accordingly, there was possibly no intervention. #00:12:11#

B: Absolutely, yes. Correct. Absolutely correct. #00:12:14#

A: Now to question 5: How are decisions made in your bank that relate to digital innovations? Which processes are essential for them? #00:12:22#

B: Well, the bottom line is, what processes are for them? Of course, we assess what we want to do digitally, i.e. in the scope of a network matrix where we say: Is it a saving? Is it the occupying of a customer interface? How valuable do we rate the whole thing in its contexts? What costs do we want to save? Question marks. What can additional added values give us and how does the customer see it? And within such a matrix, as I said, it is assessed. And then out comes the famous hashtag as I would put it, where we say: Okay, we will act according to these assessments and would say: For topic XY, the customer and the cost structure are very important to us, as an example. And along the lines of these examples, it is then assessed, and the decision is then made: What do we have to invest to get to that point? And on that basis, my colleague Dr [name] and I on the management board decide together with the team, where we say: Okay, let's try and go the next sub-steps, but according to a classical design thinking pattern. #00:13:43#

A: Okay. Good. Now the question about communication...#00:13:47#

B: Communication. Well, it has to be clearly said: How do we communicate? I wouldn't want to be as blatant and divide it into horizontal and vertical. We've just launched a new medium here for the bank, "the New Bank in dialogue", where we keep track of the digital steps at least once every quarter, but usually every 6 weeks. All employees are invited to take a lesson once, a session in the morning or in the afternoon. And the executive management and the individual project leaders are there to answer questions and to present what is currently happening, why it is moving, where the project stands, what the next steps are, and then we have a Q&A session with the staff where they can ask questions again. In this respect, we have a very wide vertical AND horizontal integration. And that is actually partly a secret of success as well. Thus, the fewer newsletters that nobody reads anyway, thus everything is loving and cumbersome, but it is not effective enough. That is why we said: We, as the management, will take the time, like a lighthouse is the way you can envisage it, and we will both stand at the front and each of those responsible for their respective subarea, and gives inside information and explains: Where are we standing, what

is our intention with it all and then everything goes its known normal way until the project has been completed. #00:15:26#

A: Great, of course. That is very advanced, I think and for the staff it is also, they feel, I think, involved, as if they every couple of months... #00:15:37#

B: Absolutely. Well, we're doing open space events where we have said: At the beginning, when I came here, I got to know a very entrenched hierarchical structure, and then did an open space event. What is that, according to my definition? I set up 10 hypotheses, communicated them to the staff, so to speak, and said: We invest a day in an open space event on a voluntary basis. Whoever wants to can come to these hypotheses to discuss matters. They could register for which thesis they wanted to go to. There is no hierarchy, and the one who moderates must not be a superior, not a leader, but should be an employee. And this day was a real spirit of optimism, where qualities and employees could also come to the fore that one would never have expected. That was great. #00:16:32#

A: That means, however, that there is also an innovation in the scope of digitalisation, so you said to yourself: You have to change the entire means of communication. #00:16:45#

B: Definitely.

A: Okay. Sub-question C. Participation, i.e. how strongly employees, departments or maybe even customer are involved when it comes to decisions about digital innovations? #00:16:54#

B: Generally speaking, the customer is always involved. Thus, in the scope of design thinking in any case. When we are talking about the service process, it is the staff per se of course. Only, you always have to have your wits about you, of course. If you have, for example, a unit and I'll just say that's about 50 employees, and you wish to shadow process the entire process, then you know that there will be a loss of 50 jobs afterwards if push comes to shove. And that is where it is absolutely advisable to not handle the topic quite so openly but to then consider where I can put the employees afterwards. Don't communicate until you also have solutions or a clear idea about how many employees will really lose their jobs. But in that case, you are, of course, bound by certain processes in the scope of the Works Constitution Act and on the workers' council. #00:17:46#

A: Sub-question E. Are we already there? Specific communication measures are applied for the governance of the digital transformation. You have already addressed sub-question D. #00:17:58#

B: That is the employee dialogue. It is the most effective. When we noticed that the staff at the beginning didn't really know what to do with it, my colleague and I, we had, I believe, 20 sessions each always with a small group of employees, where they could always ask us how we imagine the new strategy of the digital bank. But it was extremely time-consuming. We always took about 1 to 2 hours of our time and there was always a small group of employees, sometimes only 3, sometimes 5, sometimes 10 employees. So, we didn't go in there with a presentation. Instead, the employees fired questions at us, it was sort of like a duty to inform the employees, ask questions and, depending on how many questions there were, it took one hour or sometimes even two. And if there were only a few questions, then it only took half an hour, but this was not down to our management. #00:18:51#

A: Impressive. Great. What is the prevailing mood? Rather positive and a sense of hope or rather... #00:18:56#

B: Well, at the beginning, it was like this: My God, what are they actually doing there? We are now meant to even ask questions. Can't they answer them themselves? Until they understood that we were actually coming from a completely different corner, that of participation and to also to maintain a totally different kind of open communication. That took another six months. That is why we also divided it down into small groups, because we had noticed that the open space event was not everybody's piece of cake to also produce or to utter a statement when a superior is sitting there. And one says: There are no stupid questions or stupid answers in general, rather it an exchange of information among each other. #00:19:40#

A: That means, sub-question E, our communication structure is effectively organised to ensure fast communication. #00:19:47#

B: Yes. Definitely. #00:19:49#

A: Okay. Good. Then let's move on to the next chapter. Agility of the governance models. Thus, the whole thing: How fast, how flexible is your organisation, how fast can you adapt, how can you respond to changed environmental conditions with initiatives? #00:20:05#

B: Well, I believe at the moment, where the bank is concerned, we are sometimes too fast for the one or other in the group, because in the meantime, we have some employees for the last 3 years we can say, 14, 15, 16, who have all now understood that the customer acts faster and, for that reason, we also have to be faster or have become faster. It is frequently the case that if someone from the insurance side of business says to us: Well, that now took 6 months to implement, the bank staff laugh then and say: We can manage that in 3 weeks. So and you

have thus stated a level of demand in the group, of course, where everybody in the A group pulls along but naturally also causes a certain amount of frustration true to the motto: Then in the bank, they manage it. Now we have to catch up or run but that is also the raison d'être of the matter for us all to become faster. #00:21:06#

A: And what are you now doing being responsible that right now, i.e. now as a bank, I would say when I hear bank and digitalisation or bank and agility, I would now say: Ah well, rather not that way, yes? When I hear what you are doing and see it, then I am really impressed and think: Okay, I got it wrong, but what is the leading cause that can you really act in such an agile way, that you actually, as the pioneer advance the bank...#00:21:33#

B: I'll put that simply. It depends on the people. #00:21:36#

A: Really depends on that.

B: Really depends on people.

A: Okay. So, that means that you really do actually hold the reins, set an example. The things... #00:21:43#

B: I'll really put it this way. In the meantime, even the workers' council itself said to me: Mr [name], you always said at the beginning when you came here in 2014 that you are completely off your rocker. I have fought many fights with my workers' council here at the beginning, where I said: Do they really understand what I actually want? I don't really think so, but I have to pervade nevertheless so that customer orientation becomes different and, of course, one can still continue to consider regarding the costs. And that is why I say; it really depends on the people. #00:22:18#

A: Question number 8. Do you apply specific approaches to promote agility? You did mention design thinking a couple of times. Exactly. #00:22:29#

B: Exactly. We do Scrum, design thinking, we are in the meantime, we have umpteen experts in the corporation alone who are qualified. We cooperate with FinTechs, like in the account change service, we have bought a FinTech corporation in Munich, [name] AG. We send employees there to see how the guys work there. The employees we send there, they don't actually want to come back. That is the other side of things (laughing). They say: It is so great; we like it there. We actually want to stay there. I actually have difficulties deploying them here. In this respect, I would say that this organisation has to change so that the people who have learnt from a FinTech then have an incentive again to come back because, in principle, one can say: People who have learnt in Berlin or in Munich are really difficult to

deploy again. Because they say: I no longer want this traditional stuff. I can see how inefficient, how little customer-oriented it is, how product-driven it is from the corporation's point of view, the processes are somehow no longer state-of-the-art, I would like to provide other services. The people come back with different expectations. And that is a point where I repeatedly say: We have always succeeded in getting people back but only in the long term for us to reimplement in the long run if the organisation changes itself. If the organisation does not change itself, at some point, the people are lost and leave frustrated. #00:24:01#

A: Is that a generation thing or do you say: No, it doesn't matter. #00:24:07#

B: No. It is a question of interest. Otherwise, I wouldn't be able to do the job myself. There is always a bit of a light bulb moment when I am standing on a stage somewhere. I was recently together with some Bosch colleagues. One of them said: How old are you now? I said: Well, ok, I happen to be 56. Then he says: But you are not a digital native? I say: That's not what I would call myself. I would merely say one thing to you: I believe I can explain a few things to you that no digital native would be able to explain. And then we are then, which is why I say it that way that it is a question of interest, enthusiasm, customer orientation, of engaging in a game, own change management that one has somehow maybe learnt over the decades. If you have maybe followed my career a little bit, you will see that I have certainly seen a lot in my life. And that distinguishes me in part as a person. Sounds stupid, but that's the way it is. #00:25:10#

A: No. Absolutely and is surely an advantage over any 30-year old, who appears to be a digital native or believes he embodies one and these experiences are simply lacking. #00:25:22#

B: I'll put it this way: Sometimes you have to take on the competition with younger people. Well, that sounds stupid but I do say: It really does sound stupid but, when I look at my children when WhatsApp came out, we all competed to see who understood all of the functionalities the earliest and quickest to see what the thing was capable of. That is a point where I say: Where can digitalisation actually help me? #00:25:54#

A: Let's move on to the last chapter: Leadership. #00:26:01#

B: Yes, there, well, it lies with the new ones. I said for myself. It is clearly with Dr [name] or now with Mr Junker as successor. It is a matter for the management for me. Why? Because if you wish to go along with certain innovations, then you must also reckon with producing losses and that definitely doesn't work without the CEO. In this respect, I would say, it is like a triad at our corporation. This means, if you take the CEO above and the CIO, the boss,

below, not the Information Officer, rather the CIO here is the IT Officer, probably covered by you as the Chief Operator Officer, then ultimately, you would have A and C and D below that. And D is my position in the group and of Mr Wieland as the COO, the IT colleague and we both say in general: A sheet of paper must not fit between us two and if it does, we will first have to have an argument. I always come from the customer side of things, he always comes from the IT and technical side of things. When he comes with IT: I saw something at the XY exhibition, then I always ask what benefit does it have for customers? He then says: That's your job, Mr Marold. Then I say: But to be honest, I cannot imagine it. #00:27:24#

A: Well, it is good that you are able to challenge things. But decisions are made by the CEO simply because they are probably investments. #00:27:33#

B: Exactly. We both usually present it straight away, always and say: We can both imagine this here both from the IT and customer side of things. And then, of course, it is easier for the CEO to make a decision, because if I say from the customer side of things: I need this or that, he then says: Yes, that's okay, but on the other hand, the IT colleague fails. And nobody wins. And for this reason, I believe that the viewpoint in many corporations nowadays is too one-sided. #00:28:08#

A: Then question 10. Which aspects in your opinion are relevant for the digital transformation of banks? #00:28:19#

B: Well, change management ad infinitum. That is the core discipline. Taking the worries from people that change means everything will turn bad. I don't know how often I have stood on the stage at the beginning and said: Digitalisation is an opportunity. I was booed out. I really was booed out in 2014 until I kept on presenting examples where I then said, for goodness sake: Dear colleagues, you all like to go skiing. Three quarters of them raised their hand. Then I said: Now just imagine you are at the base station. You now want to ski the black piste. You think: Oops, if I now need rescue ambulance, that will be really really bad. Now, you can scan your accident insurance there with your smartphone and conclude it for the day. Or another route is suggested to you in the skiing area where you are. Automatically with GPS tracking. Whatever. And I say: A is first labelled a nutcase as per the motto: He's gone completely bonkers. But the more frequently and sustainably one tells the story and the first topics of digitalisation come, then the whole thing works. And that is why I am glad to take control and especially leadership, for me, that is actually one term, so I always use quarterly results and say: There is one significant topic of digitalisation per quarter. If so to say that in media, in interviews, the breakfast discussions with employees, or whatever,

brutally ahead and I explain it until no-one can or wants to hear it anymore. And that way, I repeatedly told the story and everyone noticed: My God, this is not just a project that is over after 3 months, rather this project goes on and on and doesn't finish with him, he will come up with yet another project and that is digitalisation yet again. And that is what drives it, actually partially connected to the Open Space stories, to the direct dialogues with employees as stated earlier. It is a management and governance topic to me and also, of course, a great deal of change management. #00:30:48#

A: Yes, I think every employee always finds digitalisation great in their private life and as a simplification for them, but to then implement it at work and to accept it there certainly requires a certain degree of sustainability and effort. #00:30:58#

B: Those are two completely different things and that is definitely underestimated by management figures. #00:31:02#

A: The last question. How strongly would you agree with the following statements on the basis of your experiences: in digital transformation, leadership must be concentrated in one hand. #00:31:14#

B: Well, that's not how I would see it. I believe it is a great interplay at our corporation among the staff. Here, together with Dr [name]. I can say what digitalisation topics I currently have. She then creates the seminars for them or books the seminars via design thinking, etc. It works out really, really well hand in hand. So, I don't believe it has to be concentrated in one hand. Instead, I believe one can combine different elements with each other nicely. #00:31:44#

A: Sub-question B. In digital transformation, not a transactional leadership approach is sought after but a transformational one. So, are you preferably for the cooperative leadership style where you implement visions together, or do you say: It is okay simply do what that are told to do and ...#00:32:03#

B: Well, I am rather on the corporative side of things, but also, because it is frequently said, according to the motto: Now we'll do Scrum or something, laissez faire. E.e. Scrum is a classic means of synchronising a project structure with sprints, with classic results protocols. It also has something to with classic, shall I say, statement. That is why, I believe one should be able to convey the vision, one must be able to get there in a cooperative way but on the way, it is a matter of simply implementing things as well. #00:32:37#

A: Okay. And you do not see that in the area of tension to other...#00:32:44#

B: I do not see them as being competitive. #00:32:46#

A: Sub-question C. Decisions about digital innovations are a matter for the management. #00:32:50#

B: Yes. That is right.

A: Okay. D. In digital transformation, must the management encourage their employees to assume feasible risks? #00:32:59#

B: That is true. Yes. Error culture – something you just leave aside. That is part and parcel #00:33:06#

A: Okay. And the last question. Should the management appreciate and reward in digital transformation. #00:33:12#

B: Yes. Very important, but also extremely important that not only digitalisation is rewarded but also root economy is rewarded. So, because this hype digitalisation actually makes people somehow only think about digitalisation and no longer think about the existence of the original business models. But I believe that in some corporations, it is considered too hype-like, which is why I believe that a balance is very important at this stage. I have to reward them. So, I would say: Yes, always, I fully agree. But also, so to say, the analogue models must be rewarded accordingly and appreciated, because it is frequently the case. I know a few of my colleagues that have somehow become Digital Officers, they got there and have said: Everything else is rubbish and they survived 3 months. That is what I mean. #00:34:13#

Appendix K: Interview transcript of Bank 13

A: To the first question, what do you understand by the digital transformation of banks. So, would you agree with the definition or would you like to add anything? #00:00:11#

B: Above all, I would say that it is not an IT thing but a very distinguished change mindset, change behaviour issue, i.e. it is the interplay of new processes and ways of thinking with the digital possibilities that are available today. This means, it does not only have to change technology but must prepare people for it and take them on this path. It is not merely about the technical training of processes but also implementing the new ways of thinking and the new possibilities in the bank. #00:00:52#

A: Are you probably speaking of cultural change within the corporation? #00:00:57#

B: Exactly, and that is almost an even greater challenge.

A: I see.

B: The fact that the behavioural patterns themselves/one had in the past will no longer function in the future or the fact that one has to adapt and adjust oneself. #00:01:10#

A: Okay, good. Yes. Let's go to question 2. How long has your corporation been dealing with digital transformation? For how many years, for example, and how? #00:01:24#

B: In principle, I always say that presumably every bank set up a website for the first time about 15 to 20 years ago and that is where it actually began. It has now been dealing with it intensively for three or three and a half years. #00:01:41#

A: Okay. Good and which digital innovation has your bank already implemented? Can you name a few examples? Is it in the customer interface, for example, are there new...#00:01:55#

B: There are many... i.e. we are on two levels. I am responsible for all the channels and for the entire client lifecycle, but also for everything that is operational efficiency. We finance our digital innovations by revenues, i.e. we have gone beyond an increase in capital and said that we now need a billion of 500 million and then conduct a digital transformation, instead I have to find a balance between operational efficiency and client experience. Thus, we have both innovative e-banking solutions and when it comes to the client touch point, i.e. from a login process, i.e. of scanning, pay-in slips and the likes, like other banks have also done, we are smart followers, we are not innovators. Right down to where we are considering the documents flows on the efficiency side of things, how do we receive customer documents,

how can the letters, for example,... you send me a letter with a change of address and, at the same time, you want the power of attorney for this woman deleted and also effect a payment. That is always a huge pain in paper form. In digital form, I can now, of course, parallelise, I can see where the document is right now, who is working where, I can answer that. If my efficiency increases in the bank the transparency towards customers and thus also the client experience, i.e. nowadays in paper form always the client experience... he phones, have you received my letter and the clerks frequently have to shrug their shoulders because they have no idea where the letter is at that moment and, of course, there, we can make a mixture of operational efficiency and client touch point. #00:03:49#

A: Okay. So, the innovation is directed more towards internal processes so to say? #00:03:56#

B: Not only, no. Of course, it is also possible that the client can go onboard themselves, can activate new services with the digital signature directly in the e-banking software Can say, hey, I no longer want any post, then he presses a button and the corresponding legal document is generated. It converts the CRM systems for me, it converts the printer queue and then he no longer is sent post. So, it is then already through ... end-to-end. So, it is on both sides ... i.e. I am coming from the back I shall say, where the operational efficiency really is an internal process, but also from the client touch point to the back. #00:04:40#

A: Okay. Good. Yes, that is actually the status of digital transformation. Let's carry on to the next page. Here, we are addressing governance models for digital transformation and here also a brief definition of what is meant by that in advance. Governance models cover the organisational structures, process flows and communication patterns of a bank. In this context, it is about the mutual alignment of own resources to digital transformation, And now to question 4: Which organisational unit has the main responsibility for the governance of the digital transformation at your bank? It is on unit or several units? Who is involved in it, etc. #00:05:31#

B: The largest part is and the main responsibility is in the COO department. We have a 20/20 vision that is attached to the CEO. Of course, from that, the core competences are derived, the responsibility for the implementation via the channels, via the client lifecycle to operational efficiency rest with me or even inside the COO unit. We also have made a second area of elements out of that, but not necessarily the touch points. The touch points all lie with me, but in the area of advisory solutions, i.e. the investment process, we also have a

specialised unit there, because we say we have the USP. We see ourselves as a private bank and are not an authority, we have pooled separately in a special unit our research, our analysis of depots, our risk parameters as core competence and these algorithms and this know-how.#00:06:41#

A: Okay, okay. Who makes the decisions now, for example, in your unit? Is that then you as the COO#00:06:49#

B: No, somehow ... well, it is all lies with the COO and in the COO structure, I am responsible for digitalisation and am the Head of Digitalisation, for the channels and for the partners. The decisions paths are surely, there are similar committees... we develop a road map, we define, we discuss them in... we try them firstly in the room and before the COO, then also in IXP respectively, then to sound them out in the management board where the long-term issues are involved. Where, let me say, medium-term strategic issues are involved, i.e. the next six or eighteen months, I am actually free. Logically, I have obtained the strategy, which is defined by the management board by the 2020 vision, we know where we want to get the bank to. Where I, however, set the priorities and which steps are best for me to take one after the other is up to me.#00:07:53#

A: Okay. Good. Now maybe an additional question that isn't in the questionnaire. For example, how urgent do you find the implementation of digital innovations is at your bank or how do you estimate... how digital would you rate your corporation? #00:08:09#

B: No longer an absolute beginner, but not very much further either, thus...#00:08:17#

A: Okay.

B: We try to be market followers as far as possible. This means from the late follower we used to be two years ago or three, we are now beginning to become the smart follower and analyse topics faster, at least have an opinion about them. And I am not talking about sales either. #00:08:39#

A: Okay, okay. Good. Let's continue. Let's maybe go to question 5. That is about processes, the decision-making processes. How are decisions made at your bank? #00:09:15#

B: Point A... i.e. stakeholder management, horizontal, communication, including all regions. We sound it out, we include all regions, but are totally convinced that with the complexity we have... 8 booking centres, 49 cross-board constellations and 1,500 lived cross-board regulations, it is not possible to create the consensus. That means, what I do, I present an idea, I listen to the regions, the other organisational areas, see whether a majority finds it

useful and feasible when we take the next step. For example, e-identity or digital signature or prospect or pipeline management or whatever it is. And then the decision is made. Thus, it is not the basis of a democratic decision.

But it has been widely sounded out. #00:10:22#

A: Okay, so there is ...#00:10:25#

B: I would say this is horizontal communication, I can strongly agree with that. #00:10:31#

A: Okay, but maybe as well ... I think we have jumped a question. At no. 5, I...

B: Okay, I have now jumped to no. 6.

A: No problem. So, actually with question 5 so...#00:10:43#

B: Yes, the statement in no. 5 is correct, of course.

A: Yes, exactly, that has now... fit in. #00:10:51#

B: Exactly.

A: Exactly

B. Exactly, you are right.

A: However, as was just said, the decisions or there are these ports that you now mentioned. How it actually works, that is then specific innovation processes that have to be gone through until a decision is made, is that right? Is that the way it is in your corporation now? #00:11:15#

B: Yes, of course it also depends on the budget. There are possibly three levels.

A: Okay.

B: The first level, digitalisation, is do we as a bank want to invest anywhere? In a start-up, in a FinTech, in a digitalisation corporation. #00:11:30#

A: Okay.

B: In the second level, we want to look at start-ups or incubators and include these concepts in the proof of concept; that is a different level. And the third level is which instruments, tools or processes do we precisely want to implement now? #00:11:52#

A: Okay.

B: In three different levels. After we have completed the budget process, then I am in charge of the budget. I have certain amount of flexibility in this budget power unless we have the flexibility to vary the scope ourselves in the triangle of time, scope and money. #00:12:16#

A: Okay, I see. Okay, were such processes that have just been named, are they new processes that have been introduced due to digitalisation or have they always existed? #00:12:31#

B: No, they have ... I'll put it this way, they change due to the new way we implement projects, so that we lean in the direction of Scrum and away from the waterfall. We have not finished the implementation and we still have mixed forms and thus, I do not have a culture. #00:12:51#

A: Okay.

B: Thus, I have, I do not know how many projects I'm currently running, but there are several hands' full. #00:12:59#

A: Okay.

B: Not all follow specific methodologies. In general, it is fundamentally based on the old story of Julius Bar. They are based on a waterfall – normal milestone project governance. But this doesn't work very well in digital transformation. When I need to do digital transformation of core banking systems, I have to resort to waterfall or waterfall-like models very often. When I look at the client touch point or the front channel or the upstream channels, I am moving rather agilely and also try to decide these processes and structures “on call”. In the long run, we have... we are then very, very fast. #00:13:54#

A: Okay, okay. Good. Yes. Let's go to question 6. It is about communication. We have a few statements here. Here, you can fully agree or down to fully disagree. TO what extent do the following statements hold true about communication patterns with digital innovations for your bank? We attach importance to an intensive horizontal communication between all organisation units ahead of decisions about digital innovations. #00:14:33#

B: Yes, I agree with that.

A: Okay, do you fully agree? #00:14:39#

B: Fully I'll say.

A: Okay, gut.

B: As I said, I... we really do listen. We sound it out, we present what we are planning and obtain their opinion.

A: Okay.

B: And then, it is not a democratic decision, rather it is a gut feeling, a feeling for a trend. So, I have a huge amount of freedom to decide about it afterwards. #00:15:00#

A: Okay.

B: But, first of all, I obtain the ...

A: That then takes place from information on the horizontal level.

B: Exactly.

A: Okay, good. B is about the vertical direction. In advance of decisions about digital innovations, we attach great value to an intensive involvement of all employees concerned. #00:15:21#

B: I would only agree if I say all of those involved in the project or topic. I thus mean project staff that push a topic, in that case, I really sound out over all levels. #00:15:36#

A: Okay.

B: But not over the bank.

A: Okay, okay, then here, in this case, with all affected. That therefore means everyone involved in the project. #00:15:47#

B: Yes, I absolutely firmly believe, rock-solidly believe that, especially when it comes to digital transformation, it depends on the juniors, the graduates, the... even the staff who have maybe only temporarily worked for me for 6 months, that make a stage because they are now working from Asia to Europe and they have fresh ways of thinking, they have a fresh spirit, fresh ideas and that really makes sense for them also to be able to give their input. #00:16:13#

A: Okay, good. Now to question C. Our communication pattern in digital transformation is distinguished particularly by strong participation. #00:16:21#

B: What do you mean by that?

A: Yes, it is like the... well the first two statements actually solely relate to communication and now you have actually already answered statement C. That is about also involving the people; that means the decision-making process is based on input from employees, on...#00:16:50#

B: Absolutely, yes.

A: So, you fully agree?

B: Yes.

A: Okay, good. Re D – specific communication measures are applied for the governance of digital transformation. #00:17:02#

B: Yes, but I am not saying that it is specific. We do use them, of course, but whether that is now a Webex session or a video; we have also used that before. Well, that is nothing. Nothing I would say now would, has now... #00:17:18#

A: Changed specifically. Okay.

B: No.

A: Now, would you in the middle here...#00:17:22#

B: I do not agree. I totally disagree. #00:17:24#

A: Okay. Good. Our communication structure is organised effectively to ensure fast communication. #00:17:31#

B: ...for a fast.... I tend to agree. #00:17:44#

A: Okay. Good. So, we have now actually also covered the governance models. #00:17:51#

B: What is the communication structure? Is it what goes into the project or into the organisation that can be expected? #00:17:59#

A: Well, seen as a whole, it means the organisation if, for example, a new innovation is to be introduced into a business model so that fast communication really is ensured, if it is an Intranet, if it is an Enterprise Social Network, it is the fact that all relevant players communicate targeted and quickly and that they are all informed quickly. That was actually what was meant by that. #00:18:30#

B: Yes, I ... we could do it even better. #00:18:32#

A: Okay. Good. There are always means of optimisation, that is...#00:18:37#

B: Precisely.

A: Exactly. Well, good. Let's go now to the next page, keeping time in mind. That is the agility of governance models, okay? In the case, too, we have provided a definition from a theoretical viewpoint as to what agility means. Namely, the ability of an organisation to act flexibly under insecure and dynamic environmental conditions and keep up with the initiatives actively and adaptably. This relates, above all, to the fast adaption to changes and

the dynamic implementation of innovations. Now question 7: How do you rate the agility of your governance models that you described earlier. And which...#00:19:24#

B: The models themselves are very inert. #00:19:26#

A: Okay.

B: The organisational structures or units, the relevant persons down to the management board or executives, however, are very, very agile. #00:19:36#

A: Okay.

B: And when help is needed somewhere and I need something or have a fast decision, then they are available even on a Wednesday morning at half past six for a telephone call and we have a decision, that happens really, really quickly. But, adapting the models now and completely adapting the governance and then to incorporate and penetrate them to the organisation, we're finding that difficult. #00:20:00#

A: Okay, okay. Are there also any structures that have been made agile, for example, due to digitalisation? #00:20:10#

B: "Yes, we certainly have Scrumplings, where we probably learn the know-how slowly and try to get a little broader".

A: Okay.

B: But I wouldn't see it as a success story yet, they are the first attempts at walking. #00:20:25#

A: Okay, okay. And now, from your experience, which factors are particularly relevant for a higher degree of agility, for example, to make my governance model more agile? #00:20:37#

B: The buy-in of management.

A: Excuse me, I didn't understand you.

B: The buy-in of management.

A: Okay, okay.

B: Well, it is certainly an important point and the confidence of the next lower level afterwards that it can work because it is always a risk. The old structures are always tried and tested and secure and new things are unsettling and then one prefers not to try it out and finds 100 reasons why it is not possible at the moment. #00:21:02#

A: Okay, that has already been done at your bank, hasn't it? #00:21:06#

B: Absolutely, yes, yes. #00:21:08#

A: Okay. Good, and question 8, you have already given a few answers to it. Do you apply specific approaches to promote agility? #00:21:18#

B: Yes, certainly, the FinTech where we are in the incubator, accelerator ourselves.

A: Okay.

B: Also supporting us there. We have Scrum teams; we have design and lean thinking. We also do the entire business architecture and we are trying to trim process excellence in this direction, well there... Also not professional but somewhat more than just a start. #00:21:50#

A: Okay. Good. Well, a start is always good and if you, as I can now make out, you are actually advanced, aren't you? #00:21:57#

B: Well, most definitely with the FinTech. With Scrum, I would say part of the team is, but I always have to say we are a CEO business where the employees, there are maybe 1500 of them, and possibly 10% or 20% of them have already worked with it. So 80% of us are not yet. #00:22:21#

A: Okay.

B: Maybe we won't even be 100%.

A: Yes, step by step, it works out then.

B: Exactly.

A: Okay. Well, good. Let's go to the next page, bearing the time in mind maybe. It is... it is about the subject ...#00:22:37#

B: Ok, let's go there.

A: Precisely. Mostly there are only a few statements, for example

B: C – at nine.

A: At 9, it is rather the COO. That is you. Are you then also...

B: No, I am not the COO.

A: Oh, excuse me.

B: The COO is my immediate superior.

A: I see. Okay.

B: But the main responsibility and that is the reporting line, the allocated topic in our corporation is always an EXP member. #00:22:59#

A: Okay.

B: Thus, each ... core topic of the ten-point strategy Vision 20/20 is allocated to a management member. #00:23:08#

A: Okay.

B: In our corporation, that is the COO.

A: Okay

B: The COO is my immediate superior.

A: Okay, and the COO is also part of the management?

B: Yes, yes.

A: Okay, good. Then let's go to question 10: Which aspects of leadership are particularly relevant for digital transformation in your opinion? #00:23:29#

B: Transparency, open communication and re-questioning and reviewing things. #00:23:37#

A: Okay. Good, so let's go to question 11. This is the final question i.e. the statements again from A to E from fully agree to absolutely disagree. On the basis of your experience, to what extent would you agree with the following statements? In digital transformation, the management of digital innovation must be focused in one hand. #00:24:06#

B: As I already said, we are not innovators, thus digital transformation... if you had written that, I would have tended to agree. But not innovation. I would not answer that. #00:24:22#

A: None, okay. In digital transformation, a transformational leadership approach rather than a transactional one is sought after. #00:24:31#

B: Yes, absolutely.

A: Okay, Decisions about digital innovations are a matter for the management. #00:24:38#

B: No, I don't agree.

A: Okay.

B: But that if a team thought, we will have to bust a gut, yes. #00:24:50#

A: Okay. In digital transformation, the management must encourage their employees to assume feasible risks. #00:24:58#

B: Yes.

A: Do you fully agree ...

B: Absolutely, yes.

A: Okay, good. In digital transformation, the management should appreciate and reward innovations within the corporation. #00:25:09#

B: Encourage. What is reward? That sounds far too much like a bonus... I believe the error culture must above all be allowed allowing us to try something to then dispose of it again and to do something else. That should be rewarded. #00:25:32#

A: Okay, yes, it is also targeted at that.

B: Well, if that is what is meant, then I agree. If it is about appreciating and rewarding in the sense of a bonus or the likes, then I tend not to. #00:25:43#

O, in general, appreciating so to say.

B: Yes

A: Precisely.

Appendix L: Interview transcript of Bank 15

A: The first question. What do you now understand by the digital transformation of banks at your bank? #00:00:07#

B: Yes, you actually described it quite well, I would thus share your assessment. We read quite a lot about the digitalisation of the customer interface, that is the shall I say shop window area that, well becomes relatively clear very, very quickly, so that the whole FinTech area and so on that takes place all around the topic of digitalisation, I would say very intensively for 18 months now, even played up in the media of course, by many issues that then came up, now even many start-ups that are out and about with a loud rattle. At least as equally important as the digitalisation of the customer interface is, in my opinion even more important, is the optimisation of internal processes because, of course, I first have to, shall I say, look at my processes before I digitalise at all, I have to absorb them, give thought to whether the process is actually good and then I can give thought to how I can automate them in a sensible way and then if I do a good job of automating them and have digitalised processes in my corporation, it is, of course, very easy for me to transport them to the outside in the digital customer interface. So, the topic is, I would say, a bit more complex than putting any old app in any old shop and in this respect, it is, of course, a huge challenge for us first of all because, how did we always put it in our corporation: If you then digitalise a very bad process, then you simply have a very bad digitalised process, but that changes nothing about your basic problem. And, of course, shall I say, of this whole thing, to give much thought to the processes and the digitalisation of them, I quickly come to the topic of business models and then new possibilities simply turn up, also due to the new technological possibilities that are around, especially due to the devices that are suddenly available to the customer and what, of course, has simply happened at a crazy speed. Whether the Smartphone now, the entire mobilisation of the Internet or even the degree of distribution, of course, and it is actually now continuing at full speed ahead. When simply looking at the latest things, you simply have to pose the question as to how the world will be tomorrow or the day after tomorrow. I used to have one of those Alexa devices at home myself. #00:02:55#

A: Ah, really cool #00:02:56#

B: Obviously, when I talk to it, then, of course, I have to ask myself whether the Smartphone is now it. Yes, it is not the last level of evolution, rather I can assume the next step will be here very soon. And, of course, that doesn't make things any simpler because, in the end, I have a bank that will soon be 55 years old, which has its established structures, which has

quite a complex business model. I have my processes here that are steeped in history in part. I have to deal with them one after the other and I have to do that in an environment under mega regulatory pressure with a high level of insecurity for investment decisions. Can we, for example, turn to the video ID process, which in itself is a drama when I first have a framework condition in Germany and then I prepare myself for it and then it is encashed, and temporarily tolerated and then yesterday or so, I receive a newsletter from the BaFin saying the whole thing is being rethought. It's okay to do all of that, but we do not have endless resources, neither in money nor in brains. When I have to implement MiFID, where I am still not even sure how my target market definition looks in the end. Then, everything has become relatively complex and now getting this topic of digitalisation neatly under control is, of course, a huge challenge. #00:04:42#

A: And you have the feeling that time-wise, at some point you said 18 months, where you say you have been dealing really intensively with it, do you say that is a timeframe where you were on time, or do you say it was well. #00:04:59#

B: No, I wouldn't say that. We have had a nice name for it for 18 months. We have been occupying ourselves with it actually for a very long time. It is an evolutionary process when looking at banking over the past decades. We then have continuous development which is now simply accelerating even more. After all, it all started at some point in time with self-service cash machines and then telephone banking was implemented, then came Internet banking. Then suddenly the mobile phone came along, and the next will certainly be Alexa or Siri or whoever. #00:05:35#

A: Whatever their names are...

B: Yes, exactly.

A: You also bought NetBank last year...

B: Yes, that is an additional challenge, because we are currently consolidating the two banks. We did conclude the legal merger in the middle of last year, but let's say putting the IT side of things together will occupy us until the end of this year. #00:06:07#

A: I can imagine, mainly because two worlds are colliding. #00:06:12#

B: Yes. And by the way, that is one, shall I say, one of the really big challenges when we speak of consolidating the sector. Now, of course, a really difficult framework condition from the earnings side of things of the possibilities one has. And keyword low interest and the likes. Well, the pressure of consolidation is there. To be frank, from my own experience,

the greatest hurdle that is stopping this consolidation is again the IT, not the business side of things, the IT. That also applies with regard to each of the three columns. When looking at the cooperatives, the fact is that a Fiduzia can only handle a certain number of transactions and more is not possible. And then one has to say for us with [name]Bank, it comes from the realms of the [name]-Bank. Here, we have a completely different world on the IT side of things and are now consolidating this to make something out of it in the first place, something that is really sensible and including synergy effects at some point in time really is a real challenge. #00:07:35#

A: Yes, I can imagine that. So, in principle, we are arriving at the third question, because you have actually covered the timeframe in question two. Which digital innovations has your bank already implemented? You have already mentioned some examples or is there anything else you would like to add? #00:07:56#

B: Yes. It goes without saying that we have already implemented various things in the past. We have, shall I say, in the account opening process, for example, implemented a complete opening process, including video ID in the securities business, which is no trivial matter I must add. There is a difference in whether I'm opening a savings account with video ID or doing it completely in the securities business and to then be empowered at the end of the process. That is an example of what we have implemented. We also did establish a start-up but it didn't work out in the end, i.e. before we entered the market, the topic was filed ad acta again, but that is all part of it, the fact that we at least try even if the business model was not feasible in the end. #00:08:56#

A: Yes, I see. Is something like that initiated by customer behaviour? Or customer requirements have changed massively. Would you that is the starting point? #00:09:07#

B: It was pure innovation, i.e. we really only wanted to, shall we say, give the customer an understanding of the securities business in a different way, in a very specific model, where then simply saw in the preparations, that it wouldn't take off. We then took it out. But we learnt a lot. #00:09:27#

A: That is part and parcel of it. Failing also advances you. #00:09:34#

B: Yes, absolutely. #00:09:36#

A: So, we would now arrive at the chapter on governance models where we simply wrote down the theoretical definition once again. Governance models comprise organisational structures and communication patterns of a bank. Of course, it is a matter of aligning own

resources to the digital transformation and question four: Which organisational unit is mainly responsible for the governance of digital transformation at your bank? #00:10:02#

B: Firstly, this is how it is: We have programme management where the coordination of all open projects, which is not a low number, takes place. It is displayed for real via our own, we call it project committee, where all the respective necessary decisions are also made. Otherwise, it is such that I would name as the most important departments involved here in our bank: We have a classic banking organization; the IT area is located there. This is ultimately done by our parent corporation. We actually outsourced our entire IT to our parent corporation, Process Management and Product Management. These are the three key units in the game. #00:11:05#

A: Now to question 5: How are bank decisions made with regard to digital transformation and which processes are essential for this? #00:11:14#

B: Of course, that does always depend somewhat on what consequences the decision is actually connected to. So, if it is only an automation step in an existing process, then, I would say, it would be done during ongoing operations. And if we enter the strategic area, then also the strategic process, which is run through here every year, i.e. we then have an existing business strategy that we review every year, we have an IT strategy that belongs to that, a sales strategy, etc. So, in this entire construct, if a fundamental decision is required, it is discussed there and ultimately displayed accordingly in the strategy. And from that we actually derive all of the measures. And then there is the topic of new processes and new product processes there, where the onus is on all the other units: Risk control, revision, compliance, etc, who then of course have to submit their vote. And finally, we need a budget in the scope of planning and then it is all about the implementation. #00:12:26#

A: Then question 6 deals with the issue of communication: TO what extent do the following statements about communication patterns hold true for digital innovations at your bank? You can say you fully agree down to fully disagree respectively.

The first sub-question is about horizontal communication:

We attach importance to an intensive horizontal communication between all relevant organisational units ahead of decisions about digital innovation, i.e. the head of IT, of marketing or whoever is informed in advance and involved. #00:13:02#

B: I agree. I would actually say I fully agree. That is a discussion that is simply imperative. With regard to regulatory law, it is in part institutionalised via the new processes process or

the new products process depending on where all affected units give their opinion in advance, because the decision is made on the basis of that. #00:13:35#

A: And the vertical objection, i.e. the second sub-question? #00:13:40#

B: I would tend to agree but maybe take one step down. It is also important, but one does have to be careful if I were to handle it very excessively, then the question is, when do I actually arrive at a decision? Of course, if I involve everybody down to the last clerk and ask them: Well, what do you say? Should we automate your workplace? Then of course it would be difficult. You can't ask the frogs when you want to empty the pond. #00:14:12#

A: So, the answer to that is probably clear enough. When it comes to communication, for example, you would simply communicate that such and such an appointment is pending, probably involve staff at the given point in time as well, but when it is really a matter of letting them participate in decisions, you say there is a boundary, of course. #00:14:36#

B: Yes. This is the way it is. One has to fundamentally anchor and accommodate the subject in the corporation. It is a question of the overall corporate structure that also has to be created, because it is actually a change management process that we have here, and we do not have very minor effects on the subject of staff. Now, thank goodness this is not an affiliated bank and not the huge numbers of staff who will then maybe become obsolete. To be honest, I do not envy the colleagues at the Commerzbank at all, but there are effects. We have been telling our staff for a long time that they don't need to worry about their jobs, but they must realise that they cannot assume that they will be doing what they are doing now until they retire. So, that means that a readiness for change is sought and we all know that it also has its limitations. After all, not everybody can go from being a loan clerk to being a compliance officer, that just doesn't work. But I believe it is actually important to handle it openly. The worst thing I can imagine is if such a digitalisation project were made a secret matter, true to the motto: We'll do it now and tell you later that we no longer need you. #00:16:14#

A: No, that is important to try and change this culture a little and if you set an example, it is certainly easier. #00:16:21#

B: The necessity is also seen, even by our staff. If you make the effort and get into it a bit deeper, also enter discussion, you will not experience that they say no, we don't need that, we've already done it. That might be the case here and there, but not really. #00:17:03#

A: The third sub-question related to this participation, i.e. our communication pattern in digital transformation is formed especially by strong participation. Would say that that here, it would depend who we are speaking about?

B: Yes. In principle, I can say that we communicate a lot in our corporation. Also particularly in the scope of the staff, there are many platforms such as the general meeting, open question and answer sessions, the management newsletter, employee magazine, appointment discussions, so all kinds of stuff that we have in our corporation and I find it imperative. In the times we find ourselves in, especially since the financial crisis, it is actually vital. #00:17:36#

A: And do you use something like an enterprise social network. Well, I presume you probably have intranet. Is there something like a social platform where they can exchange ideas/information? #00:17:50#

B: No, we don't have that.

A: Still the good old corridor chitchat probably.

B: Yes, we are not that large a corporation after all with 400, so we still manage that. And we do have a great advantage that we are central. We are located in Augsburg, have a small office in Hamburg via NetBank, but we manage that well. #00:18:13#

A: Good, now the next sub-question: For the governance of the digital transformation, specific communication measures are used. You have already just listed a few means or measures of communication. #00:18:27#

B: Yes, we do not have a communication measure specifically only for the topic of digitalisation. We don't have that. But we do have a very wide range and that is where we map it.

A: Now, the last sub-question: Our communication structure is organised effectively to ensure fast communication. #00:18:47#

B: Yes. That is 100% true.

A: Next chapter: The agility of governance models. It is about how agile, how fast, how flexible your governance models, your structures, are. So, question number 7: How do you rate the agility of your governance models and which factors, i.e. which factors out of the structure and out of the processes and out of communication are particularly relevant for a greater degree of agility? #00:19:17#

B: Well, I believe our agility is very good, but there are limits. I already mentioned it in the introduction. Well, due to the wide variety of topics that arrive there, there is simply a total limit to what we can still do. I then had at some point in time a limited number of people who have a limited number of working hours and it is the same with the budget. And when I have years where three quarters of my resources are stolen by regulations, then not much remains. In this respect, that does, of course, slow me down, and to be quite honest, that is the way it is, and I know that many colleagues see it that way, i.e. also at other banks. We all would wish there were a break. The fact that we sometimes maybe say, let's have a look at what we have and what we have done makes sense and the fact that one tends to tidy up before setting off in the next round, so that we have a chance to be able to do something for the customer again. Well, that is the issue. And then we have another obstacle and that is the really crass complexity in the IT systems in the meantime. Almost all banks are blessed with backends that are not that young. This means it is a constant fight so that we actually have to look to capsule the backend a little. I always say that making ship's diesel out of the backend doesn't make it boom, but it only runs back there and everything else has to be mapped. But they are extremely complex structures with a large number of interfaces and yes, with far-reaching effects. As soon as one screw is turned, one has 17 other systems that are also affected and that makes it difficult. You have also listed a couple of methods here. Well Scrum is certainly such an issue. We have also collected our experiences with it, yes, let's say I still find cooperation really exciting. That is, of course, a point in time where one has to say okay, I also need to remember what my core task actually is. The [bank] in essence is actually a relatively boring settling bank. So, we do the book-keeping, securities management, administer accounts, i.e. all of it is quite boring. We have by way of tradition an affiliate corporation outside, i.e. external cooperation partners which, in turn, work with some kind of front ends, partially developed themselves, partially by third parties on the market. For this reason, we need two topics totally essentially. One is a good interface architecture to be able to quasi connect external front ends to our middleware Thank goodness we have that, and, on the other hand, a stable data supply. And we do actually have that too. That is, I believe, an important requirement and then we can leave innovation up to those out there a little, I would say. #00:22:53#

A: Yes, I understand what you mean. Good, with that you have answered the eighth question. Let's go to the last point, that of leadership in digital transformation. Question 9: In which management position is this topic anchored at your bank? #00:23:11#

B: It is to be regarded as a joint task. First of all, we do not have classic fractionation. We are three executives. I do the market side as spokesman; then, I have a colleague who leads the back office, and I have a third colleague who works in between. In the extended management, we then have the general representative who is responsible for the whole IT department. Now, it depends a little bit on what we are discussing. So the strategy is discussed and adopted by the extended management and also with the involvement of the supervisory board. So, my back office and process control colleague is rather in the implementation, because he is responsible for the organisation IT side of things and operatively with the person who is really responsible for the organisation IT area. #00:24:11#

A: Ok, I understand. Question 10: Which aspects of leadership are particularly relevant for the digital transformation in your opinion? #00:24:19#

B: Well, I have already addressed a few topics. It is important that things are really discussed and communicated very openly and that this is not a top-down but rather a bottom-up approach. Then, the other aspect is, however, that things don't work out without the management level. That thus means, if you have someone sitting there who is trying to block themselves against it because he is saying we have needed it before, then it will also be difficult. I do believe it can be borne by a wide consensus., and then also combined with very open and efficient communication. And then also by the readiness to bear such decisions together and implement them with all consequences – and acting as a personal role model here. #00:25:28#

A: Then we have a few more sub-questions where you can say you fully disagree How strongly would you weight the following statements: In digital transformation, the management of digital innovations must be focused in one hand. #00:25:46#

B: I tend not to agree with this. To be honest, I would find that too dangerous because the danger could arise of going down the wrong track. #00:25:58#

A: In digital transformation, a transformational rather than a transactional leadership approach is sought after. This means, we don't only want staff who follow their rules, who are happy when they get their salary for their work and only do what their superior expects of them. Rather. We would prefer to see a cooperative leadership style where we can include the employees to possibly pursue this version that we have together. How do you see it? #00:26:29#

B: It is not surprising that I agree with this, i.e. what I did actually say earlier, but not looking at the next question that you have here: Decisions about digital innovation are a matter for

the management. So, what is not alright is something that I can delegate elsewhere somehow. I mean, in the end, I have to say that I am now ready to simply say we are doing this now.

A: With that, you are saying that the decision is a matter for the management? #00:27:02#

B: Yes, exactly.

A: The last question but one: In digital transformation, the management must encourage their employees to assume feasible risks, i.e. try out ideas. #00:27:13#

B: Well, yes, of course it is. However, no hara-kiri stories of any type. You cannot say now that we are totally into innovation and we are not interested in what is the working guidelines at the moment and we are now going to try out something completely different. It doesn't work that way, of course, especially not in such a regulated sector as we are in. But feasible is in the question. In that respect, it is correct. #00:27:44#

A: And in digital transformation, should the management appreciate and reward within the corporation? Probably yes, do you think? #00:27:51#

B: Yes, absolutely.

Appendix M: Interview transcript of Bank 33

A: What do you understand by the digital transformation of banks? #00:00:02#

B: Well, I have deduced a certain definition from the intro. The thing for me for a bank – and even for a very successful bank, for the [bank name] is extremely successful, it has always had record results in profit in recent years, but what mostly puts the ball in our court in digital transformation is the change in customer behaviour. Well, I know that how you describe in the intro, digitalisation is always the core in business models and in optimisation and in finding new market performance. But, in fact, the greatest problem by far for most banks is the change in customer behaviour caused by digitalisation. #00:00:52#

A: Ok, this cause the pressure to probably get to grips with digital innovations? #00:00:59#

B: Exactly, quasi in customer contact. The digitalisation of customer contact. Due to the fact that the customer no longer goes to the bank, well, we have measured the figures, they are alarming. From this point of view, the bank is quasi forced to act because the customer is no longer content with a simple online banking system So now, a bit more has to be done. #00:01:25#

A: Question number two: How long has your bank been dealing with the topic of digitalisation? #00:01:29#

B: For four years. Since I was recruited here. #00:01:31#

A: Ok. So, you were recruited especially for it, for this position to take the reins of the topic? #00:01:38#

B: Exactly. I was at the Commerzbank for eleven years, I did all the frontends at the Commerzbank, was head of the software department and then I quasi came here to the Hypo, to take over the topic. #00:01:48#

A: Ok, and how would you rate the status quo that you have achieved? Would you say you are good in comparison to the market if you benchmark yourself with your competitors? Do you have a good position or are you rather at the top? #00:02:06#

B: That depends. That cannot really be said. We are located right on the border in [location]. We have defined a per group in Austria. And we are a universal bank, which means I am responsible for private customers, business customers and wealth and they are extremely different. When I think in comparison to the peer group, then we are certainly private customers now ... i.e. I am speaking of customer frontend, with private customers, we are

on the same level as our peer group. Compared to our German colleagues, who are also competitors of ours, of course, here as a border bank, we are still close to bringing up the rear. Business customers have drawn level with Germany, but we are, of course, the leading bank in Austria. At present, we are introducing the most modern business client application Austria has to the market because our core business (business clients) includes the south German area and we had already lost customers and that was, among others, priority no. 1 reason why I was brought to the bank. When I think about wealth management, we are still far away from the peer group. So, as I said, it cannot just be simplified. #00:03:26#

A: Ok. If you were to classify the topic, how urgently is the whole thing treated in your business? #00:03:37#

B: (Laughs) In theory, that is a simple question, but only in theory. Officially, there has been a change of strategy. Digitalisation has been adopted in the core strategy of the [bank name]. I have a regular steering committee comprising the entire management plus the two sales directors. It is officially a priority number 1 topic, the absolute top priority right after statutory regulations. None of that becomes reality, a fact that is easily explainable. The topic is difficult. It has nothing to do with traditional banking. It is much more laborious to talk to me like with, let me say, someone who talks about the credit business. I use words that are strange, boring. It is much more exciting to talk about a logo than whether we now actually need a modular architecture in the new private banking system. And which widgets are to be included in the ecosystem. I think, and this is an issue that I also have later on the questionnaire, the most important thing by far is a mind change and if starts... Such a mind change, certainly with a background from the Commerzbank, I wouldn't have thought that people would find it so difficult, I would say in general. People who are fully digitalised in their private life but are convinced that it does not affect their own bank. #00:05:44#

A: Yes, that difference, private and work life. But how do you explain the lack of acceptance or even this resistance to want to take this step. Is it a fear of rationalisation? #00:05:56#

B: No. primarily not. Well, not at the [bank name]. We now have... we are carrying on with a branch strategy and are only incorporating quasi in private banking only what is necessary, are now only offering all standard products online, are introducing video legitimation. That took quite a while because we did our own development. For this new banking system, it is on a par with GEORGE in Austria, which is the leading banking application, if that means anything to you. No, no, it is not fear of rationalisation. It is a question of mentality in a way, no desire for change, fear of change, that is then no more... So, things I have been doing for

20 years that I can do, I don't need to give them much thought. Wonderful. I already know today what I will be doing at 4.23 p.m. tomorrow. Of course, this is no longer given by this movement. And that is the point. It is not fun or desire for something new, but rather a fundamental, dismissive stance. #00:07:17#

A: Yes, maybe that is also the way bank employees think. I mean, you do operate a very regulated environment and I can then well imagine that people move about in a very secure manner within these sets of rules. As you also say, they always know that B comes after A and C comes after B and it is then possibly even more difficult in such an environment to somehow change the attitude, isn't it? #00:07:39#

B: Whereby, there is a great difference between the branches, i.e. the branch staff they want and need it, they are extremely in favour of it – across the board. The problem lies in the head office, i.e. the people who have nothing to do with the customers. #00:07:54#

A: That is quite interesting. #00:07:56#

B: I can clearly say that, and I have already experienced this at two or three banks where I was responsible for the frontends, whereby I have not experienced it anywhere else as extremely as here. And we have, you would not know this, we have the project management for currently 13 Austrian banks. That means, almost all Austrian banks that you know, i.e. all private banks and Hypobanks including the Volksbanken in some parts, and one does notice it is a refusal to evolve is how I would put it. Thus, on a wide front, we notice that we also have the lead for the online banking function or generally for digitalisation in the private banking sector for so many banks. #00:08:49#

A: So, that means you are saying that you discuss this subject rather on a management level because you say it does not become reality or it is very difficult for it to become reality, i.e. on the management levels or even, as you say, across the board where the people really do see what the customer demands are; it becomes reality there but is otherwise very difficult, yes? #00:09:14#

B: I will give you an example. We have decided on an omnichannel strategy and the revenues from the online products go to the branches. The branches say – and these really are our figures – 70% of our customers have online banking and these customers come into the bank on average less than once a year. The branches say: We must have online products so that our customers, our regular customers and also new customers continue to conclude contracts for products because that is what we live off. Some customers wait two years until they finally find time again to go to the bank to order a credit card, for example. The head office

says: What do you mean, online products, only the antisocial do that, we don't need them. Because they do not perceive the change in customer behaviour. And that is precisely the area of tension. And the branches, in turn, cannot understand why head office is blocking and the head office says: Only the antisocial are on the Internet to exaggerate it somewhat. But we also asked whether they order their medication and everything they need in life themselves from the Internet (laughs). #00:10:36#

A: Exquisite. But, can you see an effect on the customer yet? You probably do, don't you? So, you have even won back ... #00:10:46#

B: Well, we went live on 18.10. with the private banking application, very successfully, with the first release and have already added two releases since then. On 18.10., we also went live with a sales portal, with a portal architecture so there are no websites anymore, just a portal where an ecosystem will be built in. One thing that has been well known all the time is that we will be one of the first to implement it in Austria. The feedback in the app stores has increased from 2.3 with the old app to a current average in all stores of 4.8 to 4.9. The customers are very happy, the majority of them already use it, yet increasingly more of them now only use the new banking system. They also use the new features, i.e. the most-used functions are all actually new features, starting with PFM over smart transfers over gimmicks, and soon, target saving will be coming, whereby a virtual account is opened in the background and the customer can then save for as many targets as they wish, where they can upload images and the entire system manages it quasi like budget management, so that they can afford these targets in one year. But, as I already said, this is not seen internally. Going live is not perceived. The customers are really happy. And the business customers who also use it are also happy to get the first proper banking system in Austria, i.e. online banking for business customers. They are a mega resonance, clearly. #00:12:26#

A: Ok, good. Then let's go on to question number 4: If you were to rate how digitalisation is reflected in your corporation, in what depth, in what width, is it a local support, i.e. for individual departments, is the way I understood you? #00:12:52#

B: In principle, there is a department, my department, I have joint leadership with an expert leader. So, I manage the "technical" part where there are only hybrids, IT specialists and bankers at the same time. I am also an IT specialist and banker. And I have a team of project managers that quasi implement the digitalisation projects in the bank. That is my area. And then there is a specialist area, which specifies to me, makes demands of me or formulates requirements with me and that is joint leadership. I think that comes up later as a question

but, in order to be able to explain this, there is in fact only one department or rather an organisational unit to be precise that answers to both sales directors private banking and business banking. And then there is basically the support by the sales directors and the management and that was it. #00:13:55#

A: So very prioritised, ok. What else does digitalisation mean to you in your corporation when you look at subitems A, B and C, D, E of question four? This is the way I understood you: In all events, B is the reorganisation of core processes, D is a bit wobbly, or the cross-corporation integration you say is not entirely in place? #00:14:23#

B: Well, I find crowdfunding cute (laughs). Right, what we do on the side is to try to generate new market performance, however, not the kind that is in competition with our bank products. It is always cute when it comes from us, it is clearly noticeable. We produce new market services, or we try to produce digital market services of which there is well enough and what can be easily done. There is a problem in using the resources for it because there is an intensive need for training. That means we are currently very busy in conducting training in the entire area. But the back office and processing control, i.e. the entire head office, the entire back office is still missing. Our priority currently lies on the whole corporation. I think what is very important is that digitalisation actually means the optimisation of processes in the whole bank, but we are not consciously thinking that far because many fears will be triggered. Because the branches out there are affected more directly, because they see: The customers are no longer there, they are no longer there, full stop. Now we have to some way to deal with that. But the head office, which has been filling in the same Excel sheet for 25 years and moans when Excel 1998 is upgraded to 2002, if one were to say there you either manage the Excel sheets or you get rid of them, then there would probably be significantly more fears. And I think we should first of all clean up the customer corner, i.e. the corner that continues to generate revenues and then we can happily optimise the back office and process controlling. But I believe there is a significant priority there. So one can do it either this way: I keep the revenues, I remain just as successful without entering the valley of trends and then having to respond, in matters regarding revenues, or I optimise and economise with jobs, but that won't help me in the revenue corner. #00:16:41#

A: So, that means you clearly prioritise this topic of customer interface, what the customer wants and how customer behaviour changes and that is where we first have to take things up? #00:16:52#

B: Yes. But that is in fact due to the bank's situation. We don't have any financial problems and what is fully clear is in the fact we can only keep ourselves in as good a situation as we are if we implement digitalisation at the customer interface. And as long as we can quasi continue the revenue, we can afford the head office in the way it is set up. Of course, that is a luxury, that must be said. If things were different, we would have to, of course, work on both corners with the same level of priority. #00:17:27#

A: Good. Question number five. Concrete digital innovations. You have already addressed a lot. Is there anything else you would specifically like to mention? #00:17:38#

B: We apply the ecosystem as already said. You wrote that down earlier on. We also apply a BI layer, a rule engine in the omnichannel, i.e. to the branch and to the customers with personified cross-selling. The next large programme, in Austria we call it a programme and not a large project, a programme with four projects is pending, namely a completely new adviser interface, which also has a small degree of artificial intelligence. It is not self-learning but at least it does have it. This rule engine is hung in the background with a completely modular app server, which we programme ourselves, from where we run campaigns automatically via all channels, all customer touchpoints; this means all self-service areas, the branches, all monitors, the banking for private and business customers, wealth, mobile devices, everywhere where a customer could come across us. There will also be a reorganisation. #00:18:51#

A: Ok, thus, to also implement the entire topic of customer interface better? #00:18:58#

B: Uh-huh (in the affirmative). So, digitalisation, it goes even further. The management fully realises that what we are doing at the moment is only quasi the external effect first of all, changing the external effect. It won't help us at all if we offer an HSK – that is a consumer credit – fully automated online for new customers, existing customers and non-resident persons and we receive it and it is processed manually, that serves the purpose... (laughing). #00:19:23#

A: I understand. It's clear. Good, now let's go on to the next chapter, governance models for digital transformation. Question number six: Which organisational unit at your bank is mainly responsible for the governance of the digital transformation? #00:19:42#

B: We have set up a new organizational unit called PAI (stands for Product and Application Innovation) combined from the units AM (stand for Application Management) and PM (stands Product Management) This unit cannot be found in the organizational structures

because the organizational structures include only linear hierarchical structures shown from top to bottom. #00:20:03#

A: Ok. And that was introduced specifically for digitalisation? #00:20:08#

B: Yes. #00:20:07#

A: So, it didn't exist before? #00:20:10#

B: No. It was initiated six to nine months after I came here, that it would be formed, otherwise we wouldn't have been able to implement any project. There was no structure to do it. #00:20:22#

A: Obviously. Question number seven: Which governance models do you use to govern the digital transformation? Are there special organisational things, process flows, regulations, other things that are around to govern or support this implementation or initiatives for digital transformation? #00:20:45#

B: There is a body called Overall Coordination where the results of the projects converge and things that could not be decided. Then it goes directly to the every-four-week Steering Committee. Thus, the heads have regular meetings with the respective management boards. To be frank, it is stubbornness, blood and tears. (laughing) #00:21:13#

A: Oh, the sounds really tough. Ok. Question number eight: Are there any KPIs that are somehow used specifically for governing the digital transformation? #00:21:28#

B: No. None in actual fact. AT beginning, we considered using KPIs for the online products but then said: No targets have be stated in terms of figures on purpose, because we said: We'll wait and see, we will take and set targets for next year because currently, well, we are running a brand project at the end of the year and this brand project overrules digitalisation somewhat. #00:21:58#

A: Obviously. You can't have everything else tipping off the back. I understand. #00:22:05#

B: Exactly. #00:22:03#

A: Question number nine: How are decisions made at your bank relating to digital innovations and which processes are responsible for them? I believe you already answered this a bit. #00:22:18#

B: Precisely. There are currently actually two boards. The first one is the joint board with the two sales directors and me and head of PM, which is that steering committee. Otherwise things are still run quite unregulated. #00:22:37#

A: Question number ten: How do communication patterns work at your bank on the topic of digital innovations? You can answer each question with fully agree to fully disagree. On A: We attach great importance to intensive horizontal communication between all... in advance of decisions about digital innovations. #00:22:55#

B: Rather not. Well, not in the head office. #00:23:02#

A: We attach importance to an intensive inclusion of all employees ahead of decisions.? #00:23:06#

B: I fully agree because, of course, we have the problem that before we want to come out, we want everybody here down to every clerk to be in the know to avoid our customers coming and knowing more than our staff in the branches. #00:23:20#

A: Ok. C: Our communication pattern in the digital transformation is distinguished by strong participation? So, do you involve your employees or maybe even your customers ahead of decisions? #00:23:34#

B: Well, not the customers. You can't do innovation with customers, that's not possible. We regularly go to events such as the Management Circle in Frankfurt or the like. I have a lot of friends in banking who are dealing with digitalisation, that is an immense help. What we are permanently doing – because we have no deadline and we are actually not first follower – apart from business customers. What I quasi do is to break down how the market is developing to the demands of the [bank name]. So, because you have to see clearly what the role of a bank is. So, if I were now the Commerzbank or if I were UBS or the Züricher Kantonalbank, then I would be first, whereby UBS is rather a first follower. So, let's take the PostFinance. We quasi have a defined peer group and we try to catch up with this peer group, which is neither first nor a first follower. So, the target is simply fully clear. That means, that when I now say, I don't know, the UBS has payment, then I say: I don't need that, we are a regional bank, we are a very successful regional bank but we are a regional bank, I don't need payment. I may need per-to-peer payment in an app at some time, where it is only a small function. Exactly. It is always really important because there are some people in my job, who have the same role as me, who don't break down the requirements to their bank. That is one of my experiences in my job that I have been doing somehow for 15 years. You always have to look: Which bank do you stand for? #00:25:38#

A: Under question D: Specific communication measures are applied for the governance of the digital transformation. #00:25:47#

B: Yes. #00:25:51#

A: Internal? Or to customer or both? #00:25:55#

B: Both. We have an external communication concept and an internal communication concept that crosses several levels. And we have a separate communication concept for the management because we have learnt that communication is a very difficult thing (laughing) and we have, by the way, failed on a grand scale there. (laughing) But, we don't give up. #00:26:23#

A: Ok. E: Our communication structure is organised effectively, in order to... #00:26:29#

B: (Laughing) I fully disagree. #00:26:32#

A: Ok, good. So, there is room for improvement in your opinion? #00:26:37#

B: There is a lot of room. That is the problem that so many people at head office are simply worried that people outside could get frightened if we advertise something. This is why it may be the case that such an announcement by a project manager "we are now live with so and so" passes through different hands four or five weeks for a vote (laughing) until no word after the other is left over and it is no longer comprehensible. But, before it is finally sent out, has quasi gone through three heart attacks and seven images have gone through the newsletter, well I can tell you as an example: A newsletter that actually says that digitalisation is of high priority has been going through the voting system since the beginning of February. #00:27:28#

A: A newsletter, ok. Wow. #00:27:32#

B: Yes, but that comes from what I explained at the beginning, namely the fear of change, i.e. how do employees respond to change? How much dare we expose them to? What could trigger something? And that is why there is a large number of policemen making sure that no fears are triggered. Whether they would be triggered or no, I don't even believe that, but... #00:28:00#

A: I get the picture. Well, it doesn't make things easier, of course. Ok. Let's go on to the next chapter, probably an exciting one accordingly, the agility of governance models. #00:28:11#

B: By the way, that is where I had to laugh the loudest. #00:28:14#

A: (Laughing) I can believe that looking at your explanations. Yes, how agile, i.e. how flexible and adaptable are your governance models, or which factors, in your opinion, are particularly relevant? #00:28:27#

B: To be frank, I am friends with the managing director of Crealogix in Germany and in Austria. In the scope of Management Circle, they held a speech about agility in front of sales directors and sales manager of all banks of this world, FK, i.e. corporate. Afterwards, I went up to him and said, well Thomas, what rubbish are you telling here actually? Not one single bank, none, look me in the eyes, is agile. No-one. Never. And he looked at me and said: Yes, but it is trendy at the moment. Yes, ok. Actually, in software development, the projects that are part software can be made agile up front in the development. I can do that with Scrum by the way. But as soon as the process and the product enter the bank, agility is not possible, it is not possible, no bank can do that, unless it has a small pseudo-bank somewhere to play along with this somehow. It really does not work at all. It is a fashionable term, it is quaint, it is really nice. It can be done in software development, we do it there, too. The private customer application is made agile in part in Scrum. The portal was actually made in Scrum. But, the moment I have to plan a white box test, a black box test, a performance test, a compliance test, a legal department process, a pre-live phase in a traditional waterfall-like way, where I have to book the tests for a week's testing phase four months in advance, it is fully impossible to apply agile software in a bank. That is why I always have to laugh. That is totally cute. If this is only done with the customer and a mega high risks is taken like the UBS did with payment and has loads of wrong entries, then it can be done. But if your bank is a half-decent, reputable bank, as is the UBS, it only happened in the case of an acquaintance of mine, it was a small side blow, but normally, if you are more or less responsible in my job, then you conduct tests and going live without agility. And that way, only the specification and development remain for agility. #00:30:47#

A: Good, the bank environment is also such that from a customer's point of view... Well, there are few areas where you are dependent on reliability as a customer and also on trust, so therefore... #00:30:55#

B: Well, it is a trendy term that you follow, as I already said... I nearly exploded in Frankfurt. Thomas do you actually realise they will be going back to the bank as managing director, as corporate director and will be saying: We are going agile and they all puke up because they can't. And then he says: Yes, but we have to speak about it because it is simply in. (Laughing) Ok I see. That's up to you. #00:31:19#

A: SO that means, you are saying there are actually no levers, no factors that you could change to increase agility or become agile because you say: It is simply the way things are. #00:31:32#

B: I have a product application process in a bank to keep the quality of software at a high level. Of course, there are, as I would say, really small gimmicks that mean nothing serious for the customer. I can introduce something agile there, I can maybe do some agile things internally, i.e. the Excel sheet will be changed and will become database access, but nothing that has anything to do with the customer and transactions. That is totally impossible. That doesn't work at all. People can't really take a joke where their money is involved. It will probably be the same with you. #00:32:18#

A: It would be. Absolutely, i.e. my opinion, I can only agree from my point of view, of course. Clear. #00:32:23#

B: And what my job involves it still craftsmanship. That means I have to test such a baby a lot of times, I have to test iteratively, etc. The wrong exchange rate shown once – no customer will forgive you of that so quickly if they sell at a wrong exchange rate. #00:32:39#

A: I can imagine that. It's clearly about the money. #00:32:43#

B: Exactly. #00:32:44#

A: Question number twelve: Do you apply specific approaches to increase agility. You already mentioned Scrum, but really then only in relation to the specific field of application, correct? #00:32:53#

B: They are all fashionable terms. I find it hard, maybe I am too old. I'm 43. Of course, you have to use Scrum, whereby Scrum is nothing other than the performance of a specification and a development phase via sprints with a different role allocation such as the traditional project manager in the past. We use Scrum in the frontend and in the backend, we use the traditional waterfall. We also do that with the external corporations who, by the way, are all currently saying: You cannot use Scrum throughout as a bank, that does not work at all. And that is true. I also find Design Thinking so cute. Lean start-up, to be honest, we do brainstorming, which is actually the former version of design thinking. What we do is apply new methods, i.e. what we did with the hackathon; it was a specialist hackathon, i.e. teams started off on a specification marathon and in a competition, who makes the best specification for an ecosystem. I find that approach much more exciting. So, I would get rid

of the in terms. Rather the methodology a bit and there are much more exciting things.
#00:34:15#

A: Good. Let's move on to the last chapter about leadership in digital transformation.
Question number 13: Which of the following leadership positions is responsible for digital transformation at your bank? #00:34:28#

B: Well, we only have the CEO, three of them. #00:34:35#

A: An below that, what you previously explained. #00:34:37#

B: The (Head?)-PAI, i.e. PAI, precisely. #00:34:41#

A: Question number 14: Which aspects of leadership are particularly relevant for digital transformation in your opinion? #00:34:48#

B: I quickly scribbled won: Stubbornness, self-awareness, courage and protective instinct. Right, it is not my job to be better than my staff, I'm not either, rather to shovel away more dirt so that they can work better. That's the way it really is. They are the pioneer, the fighter in a bank. They have that in a software business. I was the head of a software business for many years, there are, of course, the drivers, the innovators, they are the highly appreciated people in large trust banks, by the way also in the IT department, they are the highest appreciated people in a bank. In our size of bank, it is rather those who disturb and that is conveyed to my staff everywhere, of course. And that is why a large amount of protective instinct is part of the parcel and broad shoulders like a snow plough at the front to make work possible. Otherwise, if we did actually stop fighting, everything would come to a standstill and everybody would quasi say; Thank God it's over. We have averted digitalisation. #00:35:56#

A: Mad. #00:35:59#

B: That's the way it is, yes. #00:36:01#

A: Ok, last question: On the basis of your experiences, to what extent do you agree with the following statements? I fully agree to a fully disagree respectively. A: IN digital transformation, the management of digital innovations must be concentrated in one hand.
#00:36:14#

B: That depends on the size of the bank. At our bank, for example, it is taken care of in one hand, due to the fact that I am a bit of a multi-talent guy, In a large bank, let's take the Commerzbank again, it is the management board there. Underneath that, while I was there,

there were the regional managers and then there was the position I had; I was responsible for all of the digital frontends for all divisions. Of course, you have to delegate in that case, because you are working much further. And that takes us back to the issue with the first and first follower. It always depends on the bank. If it is a bank with a size of a medium-sized corporation like the Hypo is, with about 700 or 800 employees, then it is enough to be in one hand if that person has basic knowledge and a half-decent understanding of all areas within a bank. That would be this traditional Change the Bank, CTB, like many banks are structured; it would be quasi the head of CTB. #00:37:23#

A: Ok, question number B: In digital transformation, transformational leadership approach rather than a transactional one is sought after. #00:37:32#

B: You can explain that to me again because it was the only thing in this questionnaire that I didn't understand. #00:37:36#

A: What is meant by that in principle is actually... Well, transactional would be: You operate a rather authoritative leadership style where your employees have totally clear targets, rules and only come to work because they are paid for it. #00:37:48#

B: Ok, then I agree. Well, I rely on total self-responsibility. Each employee, each of my guys, is my colleague and has more knowledge than me. The only benefit I have is that I understand three-quarters of everything and can put that together so that everything goes together at the end. But I am also convinced that everyone has at least as much know-how as I do. Somewhere else, but that is totally ok and it goes together then. #00:38:28#

A: So, you are saying that employees can contribute their ideas, visions and you pursue them together and that works well despite regulations in which you act?? #00:38:37#

B: Yes. I back every idea from my employees unless there is something that speaks against it because it doesn't fit in with something else, I try in all conscience to fully back them. Sometimes they escape my attention, sometimes I'm too stressed out and sometimes I am touchy, but otherwise, yes. #00:38:57#

A: Ok, C: Decisions about digital innovations are a matter for the management. #00:39:02#

B: Not at all. Rubbish. #00:39:06#

A: D: In digital transformation, the management must encourage employees to assume feasible risks. #00:39:12#

B: No. What I do is that I actually take on the risk myself. That means when something goes wrong then I assume it myself, otherwise they wouldn't dare to do as much. #00:39:25#

A: Absolutely, but probably not many managers have this approach, nevertheless. Ok, And E... #00:39:32#

B: No. For me, it is absolutely clear. There was a time where every mail, the smallest of decisions was sent back this way: Please reply. Then I say: Yes, I'll call... You're speaking to me in this way, you are sitting across from me. Well, I find that kind of thing an absolute nightmare. Preferably make a decision yourself, it can be a wrong one, and normally, I will take the fall for it#00:39:56#

A: Good, and the last sub-question: In digital transformation, management should appreciate and reward innovations within the corporation. #00:40:02#

B: Theoretically... #00:40:09#

A: The implementation is difficult? #00:40:10#

A: Yes, the Hypo still have certain problems, for example (inaudible #00:40:21#) builds up on the branch structure. That position is no longer in a branch structure, but it has to be regulated across all Hypos, so yes, theoretically, yes. To this effect, however, one has to understand enough to be able to appreciate performance if one has people in upper positions that think... excuse me, one moment. #00:40:50#

(Break) #00:40:58#

B: If one means by absolutely high positions the programming of a portal is the same as creating a photoshop image, if one doesn't understand that printing is completely different to online, then of course it is difficult to appreciate when it is a portal with a three-layer architecture, different areas, all websites on one portal, if it is easy to do because one thinks it was as much work as printing a brochure. That is the problem in my opinion. That is no meant badly per se, but if one understands what is behind it, then one gives more recognition. #00:41:55#

A: Super, then we've managed it.